

**ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENT, CONTENT, AND FORM OF
WRITTEN IGBO POETRY**

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DEDICATION

With love

to God Almighty (Oduputa m O kpere azu), whose support made this work a reality;

and to,

Chief, Sir, Francis Peter Ezeoba Nwakanma (Uduakomili 1 of Achalla), thank you for

being a fantastic human being and for all you did for my late mother.

also,

In loving memory of the womb that bore me, my mother, a woman of honour, Late

Mrs. Agnes I. Mboyi, Oraegbunam, whom Maazi Death prevented from seeing this

piece.

**SCHOOL OF POSTGRADUATE STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS
CERTIFICATION**

This is to certify that the Thesis:
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OF WRITTEN IGBO POETRY**

Submitted to the
School of Postgraduate Studies
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For the award of the degree of
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY (Ph.D.)
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ABSTRACT

The appreciation of poetic works lies in the knowledge of their nature, content, and form. Written Igbo poetry began with the publication of *Akpa Uche* in 1975, 42 years after the first Igbo novel, *Omenụkọ* by Pita Nwana, debuted in 1933. Earlier studies on written Igbo poetry primarily examine the social and thematic interpretation of a few extant poetic works, with little attention to the developmental trends of written Igbo poetry, its content, and form. This study aims to survey the historical development of written Igbo poetry in terms of periods and extant works, and to examine the nature, subject matter, and formal elements that characterised the Igbo poetic scene over the past four decades (1975-2015). The Mirror image perspective of Taine's Sociology of Literature theory and Shklovsky's 'defamiliarisation' of Formalism were adopted for the content and form analysis. The exploratory and ethnographic research designs were used. The triangulation research method was deployed. Findings revealed that written Igbo poetry has grown tremendously in both quantity and quality from its inception in 1934 as religious hymns, through its debut in 1975, and has continued to grow through 2015 and beyond. In terms of content, the study finds two types of poems in Igbo poetry: pseudo-poetic verses and standard poetic verses. During the periods under study, Igbo poets wrote more on political, cultural, and economic issues. Furthermore, the study finds that modern Igbo poets defamiliarise language in their poetry through stylistic cohesion, stylistic deviation, and stylistic devices. The study recommends developing more straightforward and more engaging ways to teach written Igbo poetry in schools.

Key Words: Defamiliarisation, Poetry, Form, History, Igbo.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

The main aim of this study is to provide students and society with the opportunity to understand the history and form of written Igbo poetry, as well as Igbo society through the lens of written Igbo poetry. To achieve this goal, it is imperative to understand the developmental trends of written Igbo poetry, with a view to unmasking the true path Igbo poetry has travelled from its oral state to its present state of contemporariness.

1.1 Background to the Study

The motivation of this study stems from the contributions of two Igbo scholars to the study of Igbo poetry. First, from a paper written by Nnabuenyi Ugonna in 1982 titled “The Growth of Igbo Poetry, where he appraised the state of written Igbo poetry. In this study, Ugonna raised salient and fundamental questions which have, hitherto, defied satisfactory and holistic answer(s), particularly in Igbo scholarship, even after four decades. Ugonna asked: “What is poetry? Is there Igbo poetry? If there is Igbo poetry, to what extent has it grown? What characteristically is Igbo poetry?” (Ugonna, 1982, p. 20). Perhaps, the reason these questions appear not to have been given serious attention in Igbo scholarship is born out of the general assumption that written Igbo poetry is not as developed as poetry in English language, which is patronised by many nations today, given the position of the English language as being widely spoken and serving as the lingua franca in most African countries (Nigeria inclusive). Second, from another paper by one of Ugonna’s students, Iwu Ikwubuzo, who took it a step further in 2007, by appraising the growth of Igbo poetry in three

decades of its existence, in terms of the number of extant texts and how its study has fared at the University of Lagos. The need to provide empirical answers to the loaded questions posed by Ugonna in 1982 and to account for areas not addressed by Ikwubuzo is pertinent and motivates this study.

It is expedient to state that the phrasal expression ‘written Igbo poetry’ connotes every form of Igbo poetry written down in a text, as opposed to the ‘oral Igbo poetry’ which is orally transmitted. In light of this operational understanding, the present study assesses all the factors that marred or facilitated the growth of written Igbo poetry, before its emergence in 1975 and from 1975 to 2015. Since the year 2015 marked the fourth decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry, there is no better time to assess the level of progress that written Igbo poetry has made over the years than now.

The basis of the assessment of written Igbo poetry done in this study is not limited only to the quantity of Igbo poetic works published so far, but also the quality of those works in terms of the thematic issues addressed in them, as well as their formalistic features. Thus, our assessment of the development of written Igbo poetry in the present study is based on both the quantity or number of existing Igbo poetic works published from the time written Igbo poetry made its debut in 1975 to 2015 and the intrinsic quality of those published poetic works in terms of topical thematic issues that are prominent in the periods under study. This is because literature mirrors the life of the society that produces it; hence, its role as a lens for viewing the socio-political, socio-economic, and socio-cultural life of any tribe, race, state, or nation. The Igbo society, like other societies, has undergone political and socio-economic changes of far-reaching proportions, which are also reflected in Igbo poetry and prose

fiction. The main changes are manifested in areas of governance, the economy, and the social life of the Igbo.

The Igbo political structure is built around the Igbo *enwe eze* (the Igbo do not have a king) ideology, as evidenced by the egalitarian nature of Igbo society. It is such that can be said to be of true democracy, one in which no one can claim a monopoly on the law (Ibenekwu, 2012). Again, the Igbo society is patriarchal and egalitarian, one that is seriously supported by strong pillars of family, tradition, social justice, religion, and power. The Igbo poet, being a member of the Igbo society, documents the political, cultural, and socioeconomic life of the Igbo in a creative way and in a coded language (poetic language), hence the importance of also exploring the content and form of written Igbo poetry.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Earlier studies on Igbo written literature have focused more on the development of Igbo prose fiction and drama, with little attention paid to poetry. For instance, two eminent Igbo scholars have conducted an in-depth historical study of the Igbo novel. These scholars were Emenyonu (1978) and Onyekaonwu (1986). Also, Nnabuihe (2010) chronicled the historical development of written Igbo drama, but the historical trajectory of written Igbo poetry is still unclear. As a result, many Igbo scholars, teachers, and students cannot trace the historical development of written Igbo poetry because historical documents are unavailable. This gap clearly indicates the need to survey the historical development of written Igbo poetry to assess its growth.

It should be noted that earlier doctoral studies on written Igbo poetry have focused mainly on the thematic interpretation of Igbo poetic works. These studies

have not paid adequate attention to the significant issues that have preoccupied poets over the past four decades of Igbo written poetry. This lacuna has left the rich resources in written Igbo poetry untapped and poets unappreciated for their literary contributions to the Igbo society and to Nigeria as a country.

Furthermore, Igbo literary scholars have all laid out the structure of oral Igbo poetry, detailing its thematic and social interpretation. However, earlier works on written Igbo poetry have glossed over such important issues as its classification, nature, structure, and other formal features. In light of the above, this study aims to offer a better approach to the study of written Igbo poetry by exploring its content and form.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to survey and assess the historical development of written Igbo poetry in terms of periods and extant works, and to examine the nature, subject matter, and formal elements that characterised the Igbo poetic scene over the past four decades (1975-2015). To this end, the study hopes to achieve the following objectives:

- i. Survey the historical development of written Igbo poetry from its rise to its present state of contemporariness and ascertain its present state after four decades of existence.
- ii. Investigate the factors that both marred and accelerated the growth of written Igbo poetry;
- iii. Classify written Igbo poetry in the decades under study based on their titles;
- iv. Examine in selected poetic texts the types of poems that dominated the written Igbo poetic scene in the decades under study;

- v. Examine in selected poetic texts societal issues and other human concerns addressed by modern Igbo poets within the decades under study;
- vi. Analyse the form of some selected poems with a view to highlighting the artistic skills of modern Igbo poets.

1.4 Research Questions

In order to adequately address these objectives, this study is guided by the following research questions:

- i. How has Igbo poetry developed from its rise to its present state of contemporariness, and what is the state of its growth after four decades of existence?
- ii. What factors both marred and accelerated the growth of written Igbo poetry?
- iii. How can written Igbo poetry in the decades under study be classified based on their titles?
- iv. What kind of poem dominated the written Igbo poetic scene in the decades under study?
- v. What societal issues and other human concerns are addressed by modern Igbo poets within the four decades under study?
- vi. How does the form of some selected poems within the period under study reveal the artistic skills of modern Igbo poets?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The present study will be of immense benefit to scholars, historians, teachers, students of Igbo poetry, examination bodies, editors of books, state governments in the South-East zone, Delta state in the South-South zone, and anyone who wishes to

investigate the Igbo society through the lenses of written Igbo poetry. The study, therefore, is designed to bridge the critical gap in understanding the developmental trends of written Igbo poetry. Igbo poetry teachers and lecturers in secondary and tertiary institutions will also find this helpful study, as it provides a guide to facilitate the teaching and learning of poetry in our secondary schools, colleges of education, and universities.

1.6 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

When examining Igbo poetry, there are many aspects to consider. This study, however, is focused on the investigation of the historical development, form, and content (thematic) analysis of written Igbo poetry from 1975-2015. The study shows how written Igbo poetry has grown in the decades under study in terms of quantity and quality of published texts, as well as its study in institutions of learning. The institutions of learning chosen for this study are only federal universities in Southern Nigeria where the Igbo language and literature are taught at the postgraduate level. The institutions include the University of Ibadan, the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, the Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, and the University of Lagos. The textual analysis done in this study is limited to sixteen Igbo poetic texts, with four texts representing each decade. These sixteen poetic texts are taken to represent the decades under study. The texts include *Akpa Uche* (1975) edited by R. M. Ekechukwu, *Nkà Okwu* (1979) by J. C. Maduekwe, *Utara Ntị* (1979) by N. Emenanjo and *Akpaala Okwu* (1983) by J. Onwuchekwa, *Ekpe Nna* (1986) by A. Obierozie, *Akọ bu ndu* (1988) by A. B. Chukuezi, *Uche bu Afa* (1989) by G. Onyekaonwu, *Omenkà* (1992) by Ikwubuzo, Ogbulogo and Okoro. *E Chezọla* (2001) by C. Ofomata, *Ije Uwa* (2003) by N. Okediadi, *Uwa Onye na Chi Ya* (2004) by R. N. Ekegbo, *Uche bu Akpa*

(2005) by C. C. Anozie. *Akọnauche* (2006) by I. U. Nwadike, *Ọ Natara Chi* (2009) by O. Ifeka, *Uche bụ Ahịa* (2009) by Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, and *Abụ Ụtọ* (2015) by N. R. Ezejesi.

The quantitative analysis in this study is conducted to determine the number of published texts visually.

1.7 Definition of Operational Terms

Given the nature of this study, it is important to define the key terms that are essential to understanding it. This is to make the study more transparent to readers. The following key terms are hereby defined according to their contextual usage in the study:

1.7.1 The Igbo

The Igbo, one of the three major ethnic groups in Nigeria and one of the largest single ethnic groups in Africa, occupy an area of some 15,800 square miles in lower Eastern Niger basin, which falls approximately within latitude 5-7 North of the equator and longitude 6-7 east of the Greenwich Meridian which are areas designated as 'Igboland' (Nwadike, 2012, p. 7). The word 'Igbo' is used in this study to refer to the people, their language, and their culture. This means that the Igbo speak a language known as Igbo. Igboanusi (2006) asserts that the Igbo language is spoken as a first language by 20 million Nigerians in states such as Anambra, Enugu, Imo, Abia, and Ebonyi. The Igbo language is also a national language, which serves as a regional lingua franca for the above-listed South East states in Nigeria. The Igbo can also be found in large numbers in parts of states such as Delta, Rivers, and Edo, as well as in all nations of the world. The Igbo belong to the Negro race in Africa (Nwala, 1985, p. 15) and speak a language that is said to belong to the 'new Benue-Congo' (Bendor-

Samuel, 1989) or the West Benue-Congo group of language families (Williamson & Blench, 2000). The Igbo language is also a tone language (Emenanjo, 2015).

Before the arrival of the colonial masters, Igbo literature was orally transmitted. That is why Onuegbu (2008, p. 132) asserts that before the British colonial government's westernisation of Africa, Igboland was one of the places with a culture of oral literature, and such oral performances were carried out in Igbo. Nwadike (2012, p. 11) also affirms that long before the Igbo had contact with Western civilisation, through whose influence they had their language reduced into writing, their language, as well as their rich corpus of literature, were orally transmitted. Now, Igbo literature has long evolved and developed further, including written forms.

The Igbo have been making a marked impression on other ethnic groups in Nigeria, where, due to their willingness to travel and involvement in community development projects, they have established large Igbo communities in those host communities (Onunwa, 1990, p. 3). The closeness of the Igbo to their natural environment is reflected in their philosophical, political, and religious ideas and organisations (Nwala, 1985, p. 15). These philosophies and worldview of the Igbo are not only showcased in prose narratives but also in their poetry (oral or written).

1.7.2 Written Igbo poetry

Before we delve fully into this study of written Igbo poetry, it is important first to understand what this study considers written Igbo poetry. In this study, written Igbo poetry refers to poems by Igbo poets in Igbo, reflecting the traditional and modern sociocultural life of the Igbo. In this study, written Igbo poetry is defined as poems that are opposed to transcribed oral texts. They are the creations of the poets that wrote them, as opposed to some transcribed oral texts that are not the creation of their collectors. At this point, it is important to state that transcribed poetic texts like *Abu*

na Egwuregwu Oḍinala by Ugonna, *Mbem Akwamozu*, and *Abụ Akwamozu* by Uzochukwu, and many other texts in this form are not written Igbo poetry but transcribed oral texts whose originality cannot be credited to their collectors. This is because oral transcribed texts are collected from the pool of oral Igbo poetry, which is communally owned and, as such, not the creations of their collectors (Ikwubuzo & Oraegbunam, 2016). However, written Igbo poetry is purely the creation of their writers, who can also be called poets. In other words, written Igbo poetry shows the creative use of the poets' imagination about their milieu, written in the Igbo language.

1.7.3 Thematic Issues

In this study, thematic issues are topical concerns affecting the lives of the Igbo, identified and commented on by contemporary Igbo poets in their poems. These thematic issues, as used in this study, are broadly categorised into three: political, cultural, economic, and ecological.

1.7.4 Igbo Poetic Origin

The term 'Igbo poetic origin' is used in this study to refer to a narrative that provides the Igbo with accurate information about the journey of Igbo poetry from its early beginnings to its present state of contemporariness. By this, we consider all efforts made by individuals and groups towards the birth and growth of what we now know as written Igbo poetry, which has its roots in oral Igbo poetry.

1.7.5 Ibo

In this study, Ibo refers to the Anglicised version of the word "Igbo". It is used in this study only when reference is made to the way the C.M.S. wrote it.

1.7.6 Decades under Study

This refers to the four decades of Igbo written poetry, 1975-2015.

1.8 Theoretical Framework

To properly carry out this research, this study adopts the theoretical frameworks of the Sociology of Literature and Formalism.

1.8.1 Sociology of Literature

Initially pioneered by the French critic H. A. Taine, the sociology of literature examines the relationship between literature and the society in which it was created. Taine regards literature as the collective expression of society, embodying the spirit of the age in which it was written, and the formative factors behind its emergence are race, milieu, and moment (Jadhav, 2014, p. 659). Wellek and Warren (1949) believe that the essence of literature is to imitate life, and life in its entirety is a social reality. The poet, as a member of a given society, is influenced mainly by a specific social status. Through his art, he addresses an audience, and in return, he receives some degree of social recognition (Wellek & Warren, 1949).

The need to submit literature to the same research methods as those employed in the sciences led to the founding of this field of literary studies. Even though the sociological study of literature has long historical trace from Taine in the nineteenth century, it however gained its special place in history as a critical theory in the late twentieth century in the hands of scholars like Lucien Goldmann, Alan Swingwood, Leo Lowenthal, Robert Escarpit, Diana Laurenson John Hall and the several social thinkers and critics (Jadhav, 2014; Franssen & Kuipers, 2015).

The term ‘Sociology of Literature’ combines two broad disciplines: ‘Sociology’ and ‘Literature’. ‘Sociology’ is an academic discipline in the social sciences (including economics, psychology, and human geography) that is concerned with human society and human interactions in society. Sociology is thus defined as

the scientific study of social behaviour, its origins, development, organisation, and institutions (AHSD, 2007). Sociology, as an academic field, endeavours to clarify, provide details, and understand human actions in society (Abumere, 2014). 'Literature', on the other hand, is expressive in nature and points to various creative ways in which members of society express their feelings. Vatsa (2016) views literature as written to refresh and inspire the mind, recording the thoughts and feelings of great minds. The literary expressions of members of a society can take the form of prose, drama, or poetry. As part of a culture in a milieu, literature occurs only in a social context (Wellek & Warren, 1949).

In sociology, concepts such as 'culture' and 'society' are key to many sociological studies (Doda, 2005). For this reason, Doda's idea of 'society' is adopted in this study to refer to a group of people who live within a bounded territory and share a common way of life. By extension, it also points to a group of people related to one another through continuous, uninterrupted relations (Vasta, 2016, p. 120). These relations can be linguistic, cultural, economic, or religious relations. 'Culture', on the other hand, refers to a group's shared beliefs, values, and practices (OpenStax, 2013), which can be called their ways of life. A society is a group of people who share the same culture. The Igbo society shares common cultural, religious, and economic relations.

Although Igbo dialects vary, the Igbo share a common official lingua franca (Standard Igbo) that is understood throughout Igboland. Poets write in the standard Igbo language for a broader readership. However, they also employ little dialect in their writing, which confirms that the poets are not only members of the larger society but also of their local community, and that, through their poems, they mirror societal issues. An attempt to study the sociological interaction and social structures in a given

society is considered a sociological study. 'Structure' here refers to the social, political, religious, and economic institutions in the society (Ogunsina, 1987, p. 18).

Wellek and Warren (1949, p. 90) propose that the descriptive relation between the society and literature admits to three main classifications of problems, which in one way or the other justify how far literature is dependent or determined by its social setting. These divisions of problems, which literature is supposed to solve, form the basis of our sociological study of Igbo poetry. Those classifications include: the sociology of the writer, the social contents of the works themselves, and the influence of literature on society.

By the sociology of the writer, Wellek and Warren (1949) explain that what must be considered is the generality of the whole economic foundation of literary production, the writer's social ideology and status, which find expression in the writer's literary pronouncements. They believe that the primary source of information about the writer is his biography, which, a study of it will widen into the milieu from which he came and lived. Such a study will also reveal background information about the poets' family, economic position, social provenance, and religious attachment. With that, we can distinguish among writers based on their degree of integration into the social process. This information will aid in the better interpretation of poetic works. The social content of the works refers to what the text says about the social structures in the culture in which it was situated. In discussing the influence of literature on society, Wellek and Warren (1949) argue that, since it cannot be denied that literature projects some social picture, it can be made to yield the outlines of social history. Quoting the historian of English poetry, Thomas Warton, Wellek and Warren (1949, p. 98) opine that literature has the full merit of faithfully recording the features of the times, and it also preserves the expressive and picturesque representation of manners.

Scholars differ on what the sociology of literature should do. For instance, Ferguson, Desan, and Griswold (1988, p. 423) think that sociology of literature should focus on decentralised and centralised publishing, organisations and markets, networks of editors and book sellers, copyright laws and censorship norms, strategies of diffusion, and the reading habits of a particular social group. Some other scholars believe that the sociology of literature should focus on addressing social issues, hence the need to use it to understand various issues mirrored in works of literature. This latter view is shared in this study, which uses the social theories to interpret Igbo poetry. There are different approaches to the sociology of literature, as identified by Folorunso (1998) in his study of Yoruba written poetry. These are the Marxist approach, publisher-author-audience and the mirror image approach. For this study, we will draw on the tenets of the Mirror Image approach.

1.8.1.1 The Mirror Image Approach

Championed by the French philosopher Louis de Bonald (1754 – 1840), who argues that through a careful reading of any nation’s literature, one could tell the type of life the people lived (Ogunsina, 2006). The mirror-image approach to the sociology of literature views literature as a reflection of society (Lowenthal, 1957). The mirror image approach also conceives literary works as a conscious attempt by the poet to depict events and happenings in his society (Ogunsina, 2006, p. 10). The mirror-image approach performs its mirroring function in poetry by identifying the social structures that a poet, as a participant in the sociological process, mirrors.

The term ‘mirror’ is a significant concept in the sociology of literature, as literature is often considered a mirror of society. In one way or another, the reflection model supports practically all work in the sociology of literature. Muda (2011, p. 10)

believes that the concept of “mirror image” is the best phrase that describes the social function of a work of art. Muda (2011) further breaks the concept of “mirror image” down by explaining that when one talks about the mirror image of anything (literature in the case of this study), it refers to the reflection of the thing, which may likely be in respect of how it reflects the thing directly as the same or shows a distorted view of that thing. When discussing the mirror image, there is always a connection to a larger or different context. Therefore, when using the mirror image approach, it is necessary to understand the social structure being mirrored. In essence, the ‘mirror’ refers to the various reflections and mis-reflections of society in the literature. It can also be used to represent an observer who assesses the image (society), evaluates the reflection (what is reflected), and places both in perspective (Muda, 2011).

The mirror image approach bears witness to the inseparable relation between art and society. To this end, the approach views literature as a tool that provides a comprehensive picture of the nature of society, its defined social facts, and specific historical periods in all their facets (Folorunso, 1998). In literature, characters are used to mirror real-life events as they unfold in society. Vatsa (2016, p. 121) opines that every good and bad ordeal that society is facing is somehow reflected in its literature. Hence, literature is simply a mirror of life, a reproduction (reflection), and obviously a social document. Therefore, the concept of the ‘mirror image’ in this study refers to how different social structures or social realities are represented, or rather, portrayed in poetry texts.

Instead of narrating the nature of the native or contemporary social context of the Igbo to the reader, he/she (the poet) decides to let the reader fill the gap with his mind’s eye with the images he portrayed in his poem. In Igbo poetry, the poet achieves this by utilising the instrumentality of imagery (metaphors, simile,

personification, and euphemisms) as a central poetic device. The work of the sociologist of literature in this guise is to transpose all the imaginary characters in a literary work into social situations, since literature, as it is known, reflects the culture and norms of the society that produced it (Folorunso, 1998).

From the angle of the Igbo literary critic who is viewing literary works with the mirror image approach, the literary piece becomes a hub of information about the society that produced it, as seen in written Igbo poetry. This is because events and situations depicted in a poetic text are not just figments of the poet's imaginary prowess; instead, they point to the historical evolution of society. This is shown in the form of various social objects or facts that the poets discuss in their works to effect some level of social change. In the words of Ogunsina (2006), with reference to the novel, which is also true of poetry:

The themes of a literary work have to be interpreted in relation to definite social facts of the society where the artefact takes its root. The narrative technique and stylistic devices employed by an artist are not just end in themselves, they all have social implications (p.10).

The poetic license enjoyed by poets avails them the privilege to break the rules of language and thus create a stylistic effect. In poetry, poets try as much as possible to economise words, hence the need to go the extra mile, more than the novelist and the dramatist, to make their message understood by the reading public. Poets stylistically address social issues in a few lines of poetry, employing devices that give the reader (who is also a member of the same society) an accurate picture of the social object or structure mirrored. Their linguistic choice and the underlying motif of their works say a lot about the time and age the poetic work was written. The poem, '*Dibia Adugburuja*' (Fake doctor) by Ikwubuzo in Omenkà, for instance, mirrors the incursion of the military into Nigerian political history, the series of failed leadership,

and its effects on Nigerians. Anyone who reads the poem will want to understand Nigerian political history and, in doing so, investigate the role of Nigerian leaders in the country's present political realities.

Through the works of various contemporary Igbo poets, we can examine the social objects of the Igbo as regards the time these poets produced their works. This is because literature changes with time. These changes are seen in the varying themes that underscore the works of Igbo poets. In the words of Vatsa (2016, p. 119):

Literature as a whole grows and changes from generation to generation. It is not static but dynamic. It means that each age has its own particular point of interest and its own particular way of thinking and feeling about things. So, the literature that it produces is governed by certain prevailing tastes. These tastes last for a time only. The tastes of one age are sure to differ and often are found to differ enormously from those of another.

This goes on to suggest that, though some contemporary Igbo poets who pioneered Igbo poetry in 1975 are still active contributors to the genre of written Igbo poetry. They have continued to use the messages in their poems to address various societal issues.

The limitation of the mirror image approach, on the other hand, is hinged on the fact that the writer's (the poet, novelist, or playwright) account of the society may be a distortion of the historical facts and as such may not be a reliable representation of the society (Fororunso, 1998). The approach also limits the evaluation of a literary work to a single person's (either the writer's or the reader's) understanding of societal structures (Ogunsina, 2006).

A thorough examination of the Igbo society from the Stone Age down to this contemporary period of technological advancement reveals that the life of the Igbo, as reflected in their belief system, lifestyle, standards, religion, and other aspects, has

shown severe signs of change. Our interest in this study is to identify these social changes as reflected in the various decades of written Igbo poetry, with a view to eliciting the views of various Igbo poets in that regard. To this end, this theory of sociology of literature shall be a compass through which we navigate the terrain of Igbo society to investigate various societal issues addressed by Igbo poets.

Since one of the aims of this study is to examine in selected Igbo poetic texts, societal issues and other human concerns addressed by modern Igbo poets in the decades under study, this aspect of the sociology of literature (the mirror image approach) is considered appropriate. It shall be used to handle the content analysis of the selected Igbo poems. This is with a view to investigating the various themes reflected in contemporary Igbo poets' works to understand Igbo society better. The themes mirrored in the selected texts that this theory will handle in this study include political, economic, and cultural issues.

1.8.2 Formalism

Two schools of language developed formalism as a theoretical framework. The Moscow Linguistic Cycle first developed this mode of literary study in 1915, and in 1916, the Society for the Study of Poetic Language started the second formalist movement (Selden, 1985). Before the literary revolution of 1917, formalist studies had already been well established. According to Selden (1985), the leading figure of the Moscow Linguistic Cycle who championed this formalist movement was Roman Jakobson, who later assisted in founding the Prague Linguistic Circle (PLC) in 1926. On the other hand, the leading figures of the Society for the Study of Poetic Language (SSPL) were Boris Eikenbaum and Viktor Shklovsky.

To the formalist literary critics, literature is considered primarily as a specialised use of language by the writer (prose, drama, or poetry). Formalist critics proposed a fundamental distinction between the artistic (poetical) use of language and the everyday (practical) use of language (Selden, 1985; Abrams & Harpham, 2012). Since the ordinary use of language performs basically communicative functions, formalist proposes that literary language is self-focused in the sense that as Abrams and Harpham (2012, p. 139) put it, formalism provides the reader a special mode of experience by drawing attention to the works qualities and international relations of the linguistic signs that make up the work or simply put to the poems own formal features. This is why Selden (1985) opines that formalists treat poetry as a quintessential literary use of language.

The formalists believe that the literary work and, in this case, poetry, contains everything in itself to facilitate the comprehension and understanding of the poem. This is to say that the significant interest of formalist critics is in the form of the poem and not the content. Formalists focus on identifying the literary composition and artistic style that shaped the poem's aesthetics, focusing on rhythm, structure, rhyme, imagery, tone/mood, etc. This freshness in the reader's experience is achieved through a central concept developed by the formalist school, known as 'defamiliarisation' or 'estrangement'. (Selden, 1985; Eagleton, 2007; Abrams & Harpham, 2012; Pourjafari, 2012).

1.8.2.1 Defamiliarisation

In his article in 1917, which he titled "Art as Technique," Viktor Shklovsky introduced the term 'defamiliarisation', which he used to refer to how poets draw readers to see language which they are familiar with in an unfamiliar or rather in a

strange way (Pourjafari, 2012). Poets do this by deviating from the linguistic norm in a language, thereby creating a fresh awareness about the phenomena or objects they are writing about. It is in doing this that poets create art in itself. These deviations must be in tandem with the original idea of poetic license, which empowers the poet with the skill to twist language in a way that creates new forms and thus elevates the language from its everyday use (general) to a more sophisticated use of the language (figurative or poetic), thereby creating images that make the poem poetic. This is why formalists see the end product of this act of defamiliarising a language as ‘Estrangement’ (making strange).

The whole idea of defamiliarisation, as developed by Viktor Shklovsky, is anchored in the need for poets (through language) to create new images from what people are familiar with and to make people appreciate language in new ways. For this reason, Viktor Shklovsky believed strongly in the philosophy that art means thinking in images and that the key purpose of every work of art is to present the unknown (usually in abstract form) in place of the known (Shklovsky, 1965). This idea becomes necessary when we recall that the more we hear an expression, be it a proverb, metaphor, simile or any figure of speech (trope), or even a narrative, the more we tend to get used to such expression in the sense that when we hear them again, they no longer give a sense of newness because we are already used to the images created in them. This is because our perception of those expressions is already generalised and automatised through repeated use. Hence, for poets to create art, they must defamiliarise or instead make strange these expressions that people are familiar with by de-automatising them and rearranging the images to give them a new sense of meaning. Let us consider the words of Viktor Shklovsky (1965, p. 7):

The works of poets are classified or grouped according to the new techniques that poets discover and share, and

according to their arrangements and developments of the resources of language; poets are much more concerned with arranging images than with creating them. Images are given to poets; the ability to remember them is far more important than the ability to create them.

These images are peculiar to the individual societies in which they are used. A reader can better understand Igbo poetic works through the means of defamiliarisation, as it is only when the reader approaches the Igbo poetic work from another level of understanding that the poem can truly reveal itself to the reader. The primary aim of defamiliarisation is to help to deepen our knowledge about a particular object or phenomenon, which the poet(s) draw our attention to, in the images projected in the poem (Pourjafari, 2012).

To see the defamiliarised in poetry, the onus lies on the literary analyst, who is expected to first understand the norm (the familiar form) in the language (or culture) to notice the deviation. This means that the reader who intends to understand Igbo poetry, for instance, must bring the associative meaning of the images painted in the poem to bear on it.

Since the significant difference between poetry and other genres of literature is that poetry is a special way of thinking in images (Shklovsky, 1965), it is essential to study how Igbo poets familiarize the everyday use of language through imagery to produce their art. First, as a poetic technique, Igbo poets often employ poetic defamiliarisation to foreground the everyday use of language and, by creating images in readers' minds, open their poems to many sociological interpretations. However, the question here is how Igbo poetry defamiliarises the everyday use of language to create an art. Bertens (2007) asserts that by employing devices like various forms of repetition, such as rhyme, that are not found in other genres of literature, metaphors, and other symbols, poetry defamiliarises the familiar language and by employing

these devices, poetry draws on the potential of ambiguity which is originally in the language. This view is also accurate for written Igbo poetry, which employs various tropes in its bid to create something new from the everyday language people are already used to.

An extensive examination of written Igbo poetry reveals that Igbo poets employ a metaphorical form of poetic defamiliarisation in their compositions. This is done with a view to creating images that people can relate to and, through them, address more complex issues in the Igbo sociological world. Through repetition and parallelism, which promote Igbo poetic features such as rhyme, rhythm, and other tropes, the poem's language draws attention to itself, prompting readers to rethink what they know about it. The use of various figurative devices in Igbo poetry creates metaphorical images in readers' minds, thereby giving Igbo poetic works an extended meaning (associative meaning) and evoking various emotive responses.

In analysing a poetic work, there are two significant things to consider: the content (what is said in the poem) and the form (how the poet presented his message – language). While the mirror-image approach of the sociology of literature will be used for the content analysis in this study, formalistic defamiliarisation will be employed to examine how Igbo poets deploy their mastery of language in creating works of art. This aspect (defamiliarisation) of formalism shall be used to determine how the poets' appropriate use of language (which is manifested in the formal elements in the poem) achieves the poets' intention in addressing social realities.

1.9 Justification for the Adoption of Sociology of Literature and Formalist Theories

Many literary theories can be used in appraising literary works; some include, but are not limited to, Reader-response, Feminism, Marxism, Structuralism, and Deconstructive criticism. We cannot dispute that these approaches can also be used in the appraisal of Igbo poetic texts, but, in line with our aims and objectives in the present study, the sociology of literature and formalism as theories appear to be more appropriate for the content and formal analyses conducted in this study. This is because, since one of our objectives in this study is to examine, in selected poetic texts, societal issues and other human concerns addressed by modern Igbo poets, the mirror image approach of the sociology of literature, on one hand, provides the proper framework for seeing various Igbo societal structures mirrored by modern poets and how each of the poets has portrayed them in their works.

On the other hand, in analysing the form of written Igbo poems with a view to highlighting the artistic skills of modern Igbo poets, there is no better approach than formalism. This is because formalism focuses on the specialised use of language in literary works, especially poetry. The approach is used in this study to examine the structure and form of written Igbo poetry, with greater emphasis on the artistic skills adopted by modern Igbo poets to defamiliarise language in Igbo poetry.

1.10 Research Methodology

In view of the objectives of this study, the present study adopts triangulation, combining quantitative and qualitative research approaches to obtain reliable findings. Hussein (2009) defines triangulation as the process of combining qualitative and

quantitative methods to study phenomena. The study also adopts an exploratory and ethnographic research design in interpreting historical data.

1.10.1 Method of Data Collection

The data used in this study emanated from both primary and secondary sources. Seven Igbo poets and scholars in Igbo studies were interviewed in an unstructured manner to elicit information about the history of Igbo poetry, their works, and Igbo society. This was done using a tape recorder that recorded the interview sessions, which were later transcribed and used in this study. Eleven publishing houses that publish Igbo texts were also visited to get information about their contribution to the growth of written Igbo poetry. Again, the researcher visited four popular markets where Igbo books are sold to obtain up-to-date data on Igbo poetic texts available there.

Furthermore, the data used to assess the level of study of Igbo written poetry in institutions of learning were collected from four Federal Universities in southern Nigeria. The institutions include: University of Nigeria, Nsukka, University of Ibadan, University of Lagos, and Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The choice of these institutions follows from the fact that Igbo is studied up to the Postgraduate level in these institutions. This enabled the researcher to compile a list of B.A. projects, M.A. dissertations, and Ph.D. theses exclusively on written Igbo poetry from the decades under study and due to the problem of lack of data base and poor documentation for B.A. and M.A. projects on written Igbo poetry noticed in the course of the study, the study limits the number of B.A. and M.A. projects recognised in this study only to studies carried out at the Department of Linguistics, African and Asian Studies, University of Lagos and the Department of Linguistics and African Languages,

University of Ibadan. The only data obtained regarding the study of written Igbo poetry at the other institutions visited in this study were PhD theses on written Igbo poetry conducted at these institutions so far.

Several journal articles on Igbo literature, politics, religion, stylistics, newspapers, textbooks, and poetry texts were also consulted as secondary sources in this study. Other online sources of data were also used in this study.

1.10.2 Sampling Method

This study adopts a purposive sampling method. From the pool of existing poetic texts, sixteen that are representative of the four decades and share similar sociological topicality were purposively drawn. The researcher read these texts before focusing on key societal issues and human concerns that drew the attention of modern Igbo poets in the decades under study (1975-2015). These societal issues are then grouped into three categories: political, cultural, and economic. Again, these sixteen texts are critically examined to expose the artistic skills of modern Igbo poets in conveying their thoughts.

Table 1. A breakdown of the number of poems selected from each of the above-listed texts includes:

S/n	Name of Poetic Text	Year of Pub.	No. of Poems Selected
1	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975	30
2	<i>Nkà Okwu</i>	1979	8
3	<i>Utara Ntị</i>	N.D	8
4	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983	7
5	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986	11
6	<i>Akọ bụ ndụ</i>	1988	14
7	<i>Uche bụ Afa</i>	1989	7
8	<i>Omenkà</i>	1992	11
9	<i>E Chezọla</i>	2001	1
10	<i>Ije Ụwa</i>	2003	12
11	<i>Ụwa Onye na Chi Ya</i>	2004	3
12	<i>Uche bụ Akpa</i>	2005	10

13	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006	25
14	<i>Ọ Natara Chi</i>	2009	2
15	<i>Uche bụ Ahịa</i>	2009	6
16	<i>Abụ Ụtọ</i>	2015	7
	Total =		162

These texts were selected due to their sociological connections in topics and themes.

1.10.3 Justification of Data Selection

As previously stated, the present study adopts triangulation as its research method. Triangulation entails combining two research methods – quantitative and qualitative- to obtain reliable findings. The quantitative method is used in this study to measure the number of existing Igbo poetic works and to assess the current state of written Igbo poetry. A descriptive analysis is conducted in this study, using bar charts to present the frequency and percentage weight of written Igbo poetry texts published from the first to the fourth decade. This design is considered appropriate because the interest is to examine, visually, the trend of written Igbo poetry published within the four decades of the existence of written Igbo poetry. Since this study, on the one hand, focuses on examining the developmental pattern (progression) of Igbo poetic texts over four decades, the bar chart is most appropriate. Again, exploratory and ethnographic research designs were used to organise and present data for the development of written Igbo poetry. An exploratory research design was used to gather background information and identify gaps in the developmental trajectory of written Igbo poetry. An ethnographic design was used to elicit and interpret primary data, drawing on the background information gathered.

On the other hand, the study is also based on critical textual analysis of data elicited from both primary and secondary sources. To this end, a qualitative method is adopted to interpret poetic verses and understand the various societal issues discussed

by poets. Furthermore, the case study design is used to examine and describe the form of written Igbo poetry and various social phenomena in Igbo society.

1.10.4 Sources of Data Collection

The primary data used in this study were gathered through oral interviews with seven Igbo poets and scholars in Igbo studies. Again, as stated earlier, the primary data used in the study of the development of written Igbo poetry were obtained from eleven publishing houses. The publishing houses that were visited for data collection include: Evans Brothers (Ibadan), University Press Limited (Ibadan), Format Publishers (Enugu), Cowries and Mandillas (Onitsha), University Publishing Co. (Onitsha), Learn Africa Plc (formerly Longman Nigeria; Lagos), Pacific Publishers (Obosi), Macmillan Nigeria (Lagos), Fulladu Publishing company (Enugu), Elite Publishers (Onitsha) and Nelson Publishers (Lagos) were purposively selected for consultation. The selection was based on the fact that the majority of Igbo poets published their works through these publishing companies. Again, four markets where Igbo poetic texts are sold in large quantities were also visited for data collection. The markets include: Main Market (Onitsha), Relief Market (Onitsha), Eke-Awka Market (Awka), and Yaba Market (Lagos). Information obtained from booksellers in these markets was used to determine the number of Igbo poetic works in the public domain.

On the other hand, the study also draws on critical textual analysis, using data from both primary and secondary sources. To this end, the qualitative method is adopted to interpret poetic verses, with a view to understanding the various societal issues discussed by poets and to examining and describing the form of Igbo poetry and the social phenomena in Igbo society. Sixteen Igbo poetic texts that represent the four decades and share similar sociological topicality were purposively selected from

the pool of existing texts. The texts, according to the decades they represent in this study, include:

Table 2. Number of poetic texts selected from each of the decades:

First Decade Samples		
	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
	<i>Nkà Okwu</i>	1979
	<i>Utara Ntị</i>	N.D
	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983
Second Decade Samples		
	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
	<i>Akọ bụ ndu</i>	1988
	<i>Uche bụ Afa</i>	1989
	<i>Omenkà</i>	1992
Third Decade Samples		
	<i>E Chezọla</i>	2001
	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
	<i>Uwa Onye na Chi Ya</i>	2004
	<i>Uche bụ Akpa</i>	2005
Fourth Decade Samples		
	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
	<i>Ọ Natara Chi</i>	2009
	<i>Uche bụ Ahịa</i>	2009
	<i>Abụ Uto</i>	2015

The secondary data used in this study consist of materials obtained from peer-reviewed journals and texts. Some of these materials were consulted, quoted, and paraphrased to arrive at the findings made in this study.

1.10.5 Validation of Data

The present study affirms that the data it has employed to reach its findings are from trustworthy and bona fide sources. Some of the primary data used in the historical study were collected directly from the researcher's interviews with poets and scholars, publishing houses, higher institutions of learning visited, open markets where Igbo poetic texts are sold, and extant texts from which various poems used in

the content analysis were drawn. Other secondary data used in the historical survey and other parts of this study were obtained from the works of outstanding Igbo scholars who have made considerable contributions to the study of Igbo poetry as an academic field and other areas relevant to this study.

1.11 Limitation of the Study

One of the significant challenges encountered in this study is the discrepancies in some Igbo spellings by poets. It was observed that, upon translating the excerpts into English, they tend to lose the rich flavour of the language and the touch of the core image painted by the poet. Again, most of the publishing houses visited to elicit comprehensive data on the number of Igbo poetic texts published in the decades under study do not keep a proper record of all the poetic texts they publish. Some of the institutions visited also lack a database to maintain an up-to-date record of research conducted in their departments of Igbo studies. This posed many challenges for the researcher throughout this study.

1.12 Conclusion

This chapter has provided all the preliminary information that guides this study. Based on the preliminary information, it has become imperative that this study investigate the growth and study of written Igbo poetry, and the chosen theoretical frameworks are thought to be best suited for this study.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

To understand the gap this study is designed to fill, it is necessary to review earlier studies on poetry and related literature. The review of literature in this study aligns with the review of the conceptual framework and earlier studies on written Igbo poetry. The four doctoral works done so far on written Igbo poetry shall also be reviewed in this chapter in order to identify their areas of emphasis and the gaps that need to be filled by the present study. However, first, it is important to look at what has been written about poetry as a concept.

2.1 Definition of Poetry

To begin our discussion on the nature of written Igbo poetry, it is essential to ask, what indeed is poetry? An attempt to define poetry as a term may likely be difficult, as the word 'poetry' in itself is relative in its nature, given that it also imports something which may also be found in prose (Mill, 1999) and even in drama (Ugonna, 1982). Thus, the term, poetry, defies precise definition and appears to be inexplicable. 'Poetry' is a term derived from the Greek word 'poiein', which means 'to make' (Okediadi, 2004). The Greek term referred to writings that give concentrated imaginative utterance to experience, with words chosen and carefully arranged to create an intense emotional response (Okediadi, 2004). This means that poetry deals with emotions, and, as a result, a poem can influence people both positively and negatively. Poetry can be regarded as the earliest and oldest form of literature. Poetry began with man's attempt to communicate his inceptive visions,

thoughts, joy, fears, and grief through songs, words, and drums (Akporobaro, 2008, p. 601).

In their definition of poetry, Ollila and Jantas (2006, p. 33) view it as an expression of an idea, emotion, or state of being conveyed through rhythmic language. The rhythmic nature of poetry is also recognised by Akporobaro (2008, p. 12), who maintains that poetry encompasses many forms in which man gives rhythmic expression to his imaginative and intense perception of the world, which he lives in. Furthermore, Onwumere (2010) offers a more encompassing definition of poetry, asserting that it is an imaginative awareness of experience, expressed through meaning, sound, and rhythmic language choices, to evoke an emotional response. This definition of poetry seems to align with Okediadi's (2004, p. 249) earlier view, which maintained that poetry combines both the intellectual (cognitive) and the physical forms. According to Okediadi (2004, p. 249):

The physical form of poetry may include the sound we hear when the poem is read to us, or the sound we hear mentally when we read the poem to ourselves. Such sounds include: rhythm, rhyme, various kinds of echo, and repetition. On the other hand, the intellectual form of poetry relates to the content, which includes logical sequences, grammatical structure, the pattern of associations, the use of dominant image, and the pattern of image and emotion. It is by the convergence of all these features that the aesthetic of a poem is felt or seen.

Okediadi's assertion has revealed the significant difference between poetry and other genres of literature, such as prose and drama, which do not have the power to leave a lasting effect on the reader as poetry does.

In all the features of poetry identified in various definitions of poetry by scholars, language is the major driver. This is because the realisation of all other features is predicated on the poet's creative use of language. Gillespie, Fonseca, and Sanger (1996, p. 989) assert that poets use language in poetry to create images that

appeal to the four human senses (taste, touch, smell, and sight). Gillespie, Fonseca, and Sanger (1996) further state that they (poets) achieve this through the use of figurative language in their poems, and as such, appeal to the reader's imagination. This is why poetry is believed to use a condensed form of language. DiYanni (2002, p. 670) concurs with this by asserting that poetry condenses language and concentrates meaning with a view to distilling feelings. Kirsznner, Mandell, and Fertile (2003, p. 505) also believe that in poetry, language is used as a tool by poets to condense experience into an intensely concentrated package, making each word, sound, line, and image carry significant weight. That is to say that the poets use language for aesthetic effects, and it (the language) adds special meaning to the poem. The language we are referring to, here, which is used in poetry, is figurative (tropes).

The poet uses his art (poetry) to convey his insights and perceptions of the people in his milieu through a meticulous, deliberate, and conscious use of figurative language (Onuigbo, 2006, p. 141). Poetry tends to reveal the poet's sense of organisation of life experiences. Due to the poet's choice of language, his work impinges on the hearts and minds of the readers who emotionally and intellectually respond to the poem (the poet's life experiences) and thus, the poet avails the readers a chance to have a feel of his personality, mood, feelings, and experiences (Onuigbo, 2006, p. 141). However, it is well known that to achieve stylistic and aesthetic effects, poets foreground language by creating new words in their poems. They do so through the power of poetic license they enjoy and through a process known as neologism.

'Neologism' is the process by which poets create new words and exceed the normal usage and resources of the language (Nofal, 2011, p. 47). This can be regarded as poets using their style as a form of deviance (deviating from the regular usage of language). Jeffries (1993) explains that the reason poets tend to deviate from the

standard use of language in their works is that, sometimes, some lexical items in the standard usage of the language is seen as oppressive, so they desire to escape from it and tend to use the spoken style of the language for certain characters in the poems. By so doing, they (the poets) aim to surprise the readers by using vocabulary that is not commonly found in print.

To this end, we define poetry as a well-structured verse that rhythmically expresses the creative use of imagination, characterised by figurative language, intending to stir emotions and drive home deep thoughts. In this, our working definition of poetry, the functions and features of poetry are made apparent.

Having defined and described what poetry is, it will not be out of place to understand the benefit of poetry. One paramount importance of poetry to mankind, unlike prose and drama, is that poetry sharpens one's reading skills (Beaty, Booth, Hunter & Mays, 2002). The reason for this, according to Beaty et al (2002, p. 811), is that poetry is entirely dependent on aphoristic expressions of feelings, which means that in poetry a lot of ideas are expressed in a few lines, which makes the reader think deeply in an attempt to decode the message and, by so doing, increase learning.

The impact of poetry on civilisation has been immeasurable. Poetry exercises a controlled violence upon practical language, which by so doing compels the reader's attention to its constructed nature (Selden, 1985). Poetry has helped men achieve artistic and creative expression since its creation. However, poetry has not only helped its composers but also contributed immensely to its readers and fans. It also serves as a means of therapy for the people it entertains in several ways, and through the way a person interprets and relates the work to his or her own experiences in order to feel better or less alone about a situation in his or her life (Ollia & Jantas, 2006, p. 2).

Furthermore, the relevance of poetry to the Igbo society has also been recorded by Igbo scholars, who believe that the role of poetry in the African and Igbo society is huge. Uche (2009) posits that poetry, just like the other genres of literature, is used by African (Igbo inclusive) poets to showcase the beauty of African continent by complimenting the native, social and philosophical life of Africans. This simply means that through the works of Igbo poets, the world has been able to see the beauty of Igbo ways of life, more especially, Igbo political, religious, cultural, and economic ways of life. Onukwube (2011) confirms that, like other societies worldwide, Igbo society attributes religious, social, and political functions to poetry. Poetry has been a means by which Igbo poets speak to leaders and contribute their ideas towards the development of the society. Igbo poets have also used poetry to foster unity and promote development in the society (Nnyigide & Egenti, 2014). Through poetry, various Igbo poets have contributed positively towards the economic, political, cultural, and religious advancement of the Igbo society.

2.2 Nature of Written Igbo Poetry

Having considered the views of scholars as to what poetry truly means, it is now expedient to understand the nature of written Igbo poetry. We must also not lose sight of fact that before the advent of what we now know as written Igbo poetry, the nature of Igbo poetry was purely traditional or oral (and it was part of the genres of Igbo literature that formed the identity of the Igbo). Igbo poetry, which started in its oral form, metamorphosed into the written form. Today, both forms of Igbo poetry exist side by side, and both serve their purpose among the Igbo. This means that, though written Igbo poetry seems to be in vogue, the oral Igbo poetry still has its place in the hearts and minds of the Igbo, as its performance has now been improved

to accommodate the written form of storage and transmission. However, the written forms of poetry, according to Senanu and Vincent (1976, p. 13), represent developments in the medium of language communication in response to the complexity and growth of human societies.

What then is written Igbo poetry? As easy as this question seems, it is riddled with meaning and, as such, capable of generating arguments among Igbo scholars. Since poetry is a primary genre of literature (oral or written), the semantic extension of the question is what can be regarded as written Igbo literature. This study is not ignorant of the earlier debate among Igbo literary scholars as to what can be accepted as written Igbo literature.

The debate, which was triggered by Obi Wali's assertion about what can be regarded as African literature, had Igbo scholars divided into two camps. With scholars, such as Emenyonu (1978) Ebeogu (1980) Acholonu (1985) Igboanus (2017) on one side of the divide, arguing that in talking about what is to be accepted as Igbo literature, premium should not be put on the language of Igbo literature in determining if a literary work qualifies as Igbo literature, instead the ethnicity of the author, ethnicity of the setting in text (place and time), characters and themes should be considered.

On the other side of the divide are scholars, such as Ugonna (1978), Anabogu (1983), Emenanjo (1985), Onyekaonwu (1986), Maduka (1989), Ikwubuzo (2007), all arguing that language of the text is a sine qua non to the determination of what is to be accepted as Igbo literature, since it is expected that the study of those texts should advance the study of Igbo in various tertiary institutions and not be confined to English studies (Onyekonwu, 1986). These arguments have led to two major classifications of African literature: African Literature in non-African languages and

African literature in indigenous African languages, under which Igbo Literature falls (Ikwubuzo, 2012; 2015).

At this juncture, it has become expedient to clearly define our concept of written Igbo poetry with a view to explaining its nature. This study, however, is not a contribution to the discourse on whether the Igbo language should be the vehicle for any Igbo literary text; instead, it limits its scope to Igbo poetry (literature) written in the Igbo language. This is why, in this study, Igbo poetry refers to poetry written in the Igbo language that projects Igbo worldviews and ideologies (Ugonna, 1980; Uzochukwu, 1981; Ikwubuzo, 2007; Akaeze, 2018). This study believes that indigenous language still remains the best channel of expressing the culture, ideology, and worldview of the people who use the language (Ugonna, 1978, p. 3), which in this case, is the Igbo language. This means that, for a poem to be referred to as Igbo poetry, the said poem must be written in the Igbo language. By this assertion, it does not matter if the poet is an Igbo person or not; all that matters is that the language of his or her poem must be Igbo, and the poem must project the Igbo worldview. It has earlier been stated in this study that, when speaking of the Igbo, the language and the people are one; hence, the term Igbo refers to both the people and their language.

To buttress the above view and further explicate our concept of written Igbo poetry, let us consider the definition of contemporary (written) Igbo poetry as given by Onyekaonwu (2010). Onyekaonwu sees written Igbo poetry as a composition in verse, characterised by the imaginative treatment of experience, creative and figurative use of language that is more intense than ordinary speech, which in turn creates beauty and a pleasurable effect. Onyekaonwu seems to have played down the power of rhythm (though implied in his definition) as a veritable ingredient of written Igbo poetry, just as poetry in other languages of the world. However, his definition

hallows creative imagination, figurative language and the use of the Igbo language as the key features that underscore written Igbo poetry, which is a position this study upholds. It does not mean that our evaluation of Igbo poetry (oral or written) is dependent on rhythm alone. It just means that rhythm plays a vital role in whatever that must be accepted as poetry in Igbo. Uzochukwu (2001, p. 2) admits that all forms of Igbo poetry are rhythmical. However, just as we have earlier stated, rhythm should not be the only basis for judging the quality of Igbo poetry (Uzochukwu, 2001). For any verse to qualify as written Igbo poetry, such a verse must possess the following features; rhythm, language, thought, and emotion (Uba-Mgbemena, 1990). Uba-Mgbemena further makes it clear that any verse that is short of any of these four features cannot be considered as written Igbo poetry. Furthermore, Akaeze (2018) defines written Igbo poetry as a literary work with minimum characteristics of poetry, written in Igbo language, which reflects Igbo world view and is understood by the Igbo when read or heard in their language. Akaeze's definition of Igbo poetry focuses more on the content of Igbo poetry and the language of transmission.

Based on the above information and other knowledge that would be gained in this study as regards the meaning of poetry, we then offer our working definition of written Igbo poetry in this study as the process of putting into image, through the use of Igbo language, various conceptions of the mind in a rhythmic format with a view to steering up emotions. In this working definition of poetry, there are four major features of poetry that are underscored, namely, imagery, language, rhythm and emotion. Written Igbo poetry can further be said to be the creative use of imagination, which is characterised by figurative language and written in the Igbo language to expose the reader to the Igbo world view, with a view to evoking emotional responses. This definition captures all that Igbo poetry stands for and the aim it is

designed to achieve. Again, the major features of Igbo poetry that are meticulously considered in our definition of written Igbo poetry support the fact that an Igbo poem may sound pleasing to our ears due to its rhythmic ambiance and rhyming structure, yet promote deep thoughts. It can, at the same time, express deep thoughts about the Igbo sociological paradise. The beauty of the poem may even be promoted by assonance or alliteration, which enforces sound effect and in turn promotes the feeling it evokes.

It is also important to note that when discussing the nature of written Igbo poetry, one of the primary considerations is its forms and types. This is why it is important to note at this juncture that, for Uzochukwu (1982; 2001), Igbo traditional or oral poetry can take the form of chants, recitations, or songs. These three classifications are based on modes of delivery and provide insight into the nature of oral Igbo poetry. In Igbo written poetry, classification may be based on the mode of delivery, since the poems are in written form; instead, it is based on the content (theme) and form of such poems. Nnyigide (2015), for instance, has classified written Igbo poetry by content, including philosophical, satirical, natural phenomena, political, lamentation, prophetic, and praise poems. All these types of Igbo poems can be observed in extant texts if the reader can decode the meaning of the Igbo poem, which is why it has become important to look at the meaning in written Igbo poetry.

2.3 Meaning in Written Igbo Poetry

Meaning is highly germane in Igbo written poetry. This is because meaning is quite important in the appreciation of poetry. Nsolibe (2013, p. 86) maintains that for a poem to be a poem, it must be meaningful. Nevertheless, oftentimes, the meaning of a poem is coded in the language at play in the text. In order for a reader to truly

understand the meaning of the poem, he must first decode the language of the poet, which will then open the poem to various interpretations that even the poet did not imagine. This was why Peskin (1998) believes that the intractable language of poetry primarily causes reticence among scholars in studying how readers understand poetry.

In written Igbo poetry, meaning is compressed into a few poetic lines. This is because, unlike prose and drama genres, where the writers are at liberty to explain their points, poetry summarises a whole account in just a few lines, making the few lines pregnant with meaning. This is what gives poetry its mystic nature. On this note, we can classify meaning in written Igbo poetry into two: general meaning and associative meaning.

Eagleton (2007) explains that a poem was never written to have just one meaning; it can mean anything we interpret it to mean, since the experiences that poetry portrays are purely imaginary. This means that there is no direct interpretation of a poetic work because the reader's life experiences provide the lenses through which their understanding of the poetic image painted by the poet will be predicated. This unique feature of poetry opens poems to various interpretations and can be read in many contexts. Eagleton (2007, p. 32) further explains that this is possible because a poem does not, in a complete sense, come with a ready-made context for making sense of its words. Instead, we have to bring such a context to it. The meaning Eagleton refers to here is associative. For one to truly understand Igbo poetry, one must be able to separate the general meaning from the associative meaning. While the general meaning can be said to refer to the peripheral meaning of lines of poetry, the associative meaning can be taken to refer to the pragmatic denotation of lines of poetry.

Writing on meaning in poetry, Suppes (2009) argues that meaning can be understood in relation to three senses, namely, formal, dictionary, and associative meaning. The formal sense refers to general definitions of topics in Mathematics, Biology, and other disciplines. The dictionary meaning is most familiar in schools, as it refers to the standard, conventional concept of dictionary definitions. The dictionary meaning can also be regarded as the general meaning since it relates to the established meaning of a thing in a folk group. However, associative meaning is the sense that applies to poetry and many other subjects as well. According to Suppes (2009), associative meaning refers to the natural part of the mental life of everybody in the society vis-à-vis an ordinary meaning upheld by members of the society about a particular subject or item – even if it is not so named in ordinary conversation, it is domiciled in the silent private thought of individuals. Associative meanings have no limitations as they flow seamlessly from the cognitive thinking of the poet to something mainly affective and rhythmic.

Associative meaning makes imagery possible, as everybody understands the item represented in the image projected by the poem. Most of these images are manifested in figures of created imagery employed by the poet (Oraegbunam, 2015). To illustrate this, let us consider Madubuike’s Igbo poem ‘Abali’ (Night) in *Utara Nti* (Emenanjo (Ed.), Nd.) (Poem 1), where the poet says:

Ìsì kpùrù ebe dum	(Everywhere is blind
Ànyasì nà-èji kà unyi...	Night is dark as charcoal...
Eluigwē anāghì achì ọchì mà ì	Heaven is not smiling at all
Kpakpando – anya abali – alakpuola	Stars – eyes of the night – have gone to sleep
Ọnwa na anyanwụ na-ehikwa ụra	The sun and moon are also sleeping.
Egwu dị ebe dum	There is fear everywhere.

(Madubuike in Emenanjo (ed.), Nd., p. 32)

For one to fully understand the meaning of any good Igbo poem, like the above poem, one must bring the associative meaning to it. Bringing the associative meaning to bear on the interpretation of the above poem will reveal the intricacy of its language play and thus unveil the profound message embedded in it. This is why the student of Igbo poetry must first understand the associative meaning of various images employed in a poem before he or she can appreciate the poem.

For instance, the semantic sense in the second line of Poem 1 is predicated on the comparison between two key words, ‘*Anyasi*’ (Night) and ‘*unyi*’ (charcoal). The associative sense of colour (nature) associated with charcoal in the Igbo community is deep black, such that nothing is darker than it. The choice of the lexical item ‘*unyi*’ by the poet evokes in the reader an image of a very dark and fearful night. Any student of poetry who reads Igbo poetry with the formal or general (dictionary) sense of meaning will see most Igbo written poems as shallow since the titles of most of them are based on places, things, and natural phenomena, with only a few on politics and other social, economic, cultural, and religious issues. However, they are still largely philosophical, irrespective of the title the poet chooses to write. It is only by reading Igbo poetry from its associative meaning that one can appreciate the uniqueness of Igbo poets. The student of Igbo poetry will also discover that the associative meaning attached to the mental images depicted in the poems and the way language was manipulated, promotes the sociological, historical, philosophical qualities of the poem, bearing in mind that the association the words in the poem excites in the reader is often significant and vivid but equally idiosyncratic and private (Suppes, p. 2009).

Decoding the meaning of another poem in Igbo, ‘*Ugbo*’ (Vehicle) by Akoma in *Akpa Uche* (1975), it will reveal that, although the poem seems to be on means of transportation when one talks about the general meaning of the poem, however, in

talking about the associative meaning of the poem, it will be observed that the poet uses the image of transportation that is known to man to mirror the role of death as a means of moving from one plane of existence to another. The general image of a vehicle to the Igbo is an equipment that moves people from place to place; therefore, in writing on the title 'Ugbo', the way it appeared in the text, the reader is expected to bring associative meaning to the meaning of the poem before the meaning of the poem can be decoded.

Another point we must consider in line with the meaning of Igbo written poetry is its themes. Igbo poetry addresses a wide range of themes related to human society (Nsolibe, 2013). In written Igbo poetry, themes like love, politics, death, natural phenomena, belief in the supernatural, and many more find their full expression in the works of many written Igbo poets. Emenanjo (1983) explains that some of the topics and themes in Igbo poetry include love, wealth, and examinations, to name a few. Emenanjo further explains that an Igbo poem may address a particular subject, but the theme may run contrary to the subject or title the poet has given it. Citing a poem 'Onyemelukwe' written by Ezuma in *Nkemakolam*, Emenanjo asserts that although the poet appears to be praising the name 'Onyemelukwe', the meaning of the poem, which is also the thought it expresses, focuses on the nature of mankind who no matter how well one tries to please them, will never agree that one has done anything for them.

2.4 The Written Igbo Poet

The Igbo poet in writing is no ordinary person. He or she lives in society and is affected by events around him or her, like everyone else. This means that he or she feels the pain, joy, sadness, and other effects of daily events in society. However,

while other members of society choose other means of responding to those events, the Igbo poet responds differently, using the instrumentality of his or her creative work. This is why Ezejideaku (2003, p. 426) sees a poet as a man of many parts who is not only a reformer, a satirist, a political watchdog, a praise singer, a chronicler of events, or a teacher, but also a spokesman for the people. These qualities that the Igbo poet possesses are what enable him to respond to events around him differently from everyone else. For this reason, what others see and turn a blind eye to, the Igbo poet sees through it. This explains why Nnyigide (2014) asserts that what other people cannot visualise with their ordinary eyes is what the poet sees. In the same vein, he feels things differently from the way other members of society do and, by doing so, creates his own words and presents his feelings and experiences in a way that stirs readers' emotions.

Many societal problems could engage the poet's creative mind and prompt him to consider how to address them. In Igbo poetry, the totality of man's environment – human, natural, and cosmic – is brought into the fore, for the sole purpose of understanding the human situation (Okediadi, 2004, p. 250). For this reason, Igbo poets share a vision of life as a struggle against physical, spiritual, and intellectual forces, and this vision has naturally resulted in powerful and charming poetry, whether oral or written (Okediadi, 2004). To achieve his ultimate aim, a good Igbo poet avoids the use of overused language or expressions and clichés. He or she must use language creatively. To this end, the poet can draw on any of the linguistic resources available to him. He must painstakingly choose the appropriate expression to present his ideas or experiences in a way that gives the reader new meaning (Nsolibe, 2013). By doing this, the poet creates art from happenings that members of society overlook because of their overfamiliarity with them.

2.5 Previous Studies on Written Igbo Poetry

At this juncture, we shall examine earlier studies that have so far been carried out on written Igbo poetry. Here, our focus is on articles published in learned journals that exclusively address various issues in written Igbo poetry, as well as all doctoral studies carried out so far on written Igbo poetry. This is done with a view to understanding the areas that have been covered and the gaps that remain in Igbo poetry scholarship.

Ugonna (1982) sparked off the discussion on the need to assess the development of Igbo poetry. His study briefly examines the growth of Igbo poetry from its oral form to its written state, revealing the level of progress Igbo poetry has made up to 1982. Ugonna's study distinguished oral poetry from the written form. He (Ugonna) opines that serious study of Igbo oral poetry began after the Nigerian civil war with the establishment of Igbo Language Departments in various Colleges of Education and Universities in Nigeria. Ugonna (1982) maintains that "a thorough examination of Igbo poetical works reveals that Igbo poetry has grown both in quantity and in quality." Ugonna concludes that Igbo poetry is rooted in Igbo civilisation, which has developed from Igbo antiquity and is now fast developing.

Uzochukwu (2003) wrote on Emenanjo's contributions towards the development of written Igbo poetry. Uzochukwu identifies the qualities of a good poet according to Emenanjo in *Utara Nti*— they include profundity of thought, a keener sense of seeing, hearing, and smelling, a more profound knowledge of language usage, and a deeper sense of sound than the average person. Uzochukwu also identifies lineation as one distinguishing mark of written Igbo poetry, and the implication of lineation in poetry is the incidence of rhyme as one of the artistic

devices employed in poetry. While there are incidences of syllabic rhyme in English poetry, for Uzochukwu (2003), there is no incidence of syllabic rhyme in Igbo poetry; instead, there are occasional instances of tonal rhyme as illustrated in *Nkemakọlam* (p. 235). Uzochukwu (2003), however, submits that Emenanjo's contribution towards the development and appreciation of written Igbo poetry, an area outside his discipline, is an explicit confirmation of his virtuosity.

Ezejideaku (2003) examines the language of satiric poetry in selected written Igbo poetry. Ezejideaku perceives satire as one of the literary arts, which the Igbo poet employs to achieve his goal of exposing folly, vices, and other social misdemeanours to ridicule. In light of this revelation, Ezejideaku's (2003) paper examines how Igbo poets use language in their poems to achieve satiric goals. The data used in his study were derived from eight satiric poems purposively selected from two Igbo poetic texts, namely, *Omenka* and *Utara Nti*. The study, which uses a semiotic framework, argues that the Igbo satiric poet achieves his literary goals by exploiting the rhetorical devices already present in the language, by exploiting his own creative use of the imagination, and by making use of the various signifiers in the extra-text. Ezejideaku (2003) concludes that among the Igbo, satire is used by poets to sensitize and correct society by exposing society in general or offenders to ridicule through contempt, ridicule, mockery, indignation, humour, parody, and other signifiers in the extra-text. He also submits that the studied poems reveal that the Igbo satiric poets have lived up to their social responsibilities by charting, in words, a new course for Nigerian and Igbo society.

Ikwubuzo (2004) investigates the myth of 'Iyi Une' and Obike's creative inputs in *Eke Une*. His study aimed to appraise Obike's exploitation of local myths in his epic poem, to explore how the poet (Obike) has gone beyond the ambit of his

traditional background to create new myths, and to examine different themes that address issues characteristic of contemporary Igbo society. The study finds that traditional myth is the chief ingredient of Obike's narrative epic poem in *Eke Une*. The study also finds that, apart from the import of oral myth by Obike in his work, all other conceptions of the myth, such as its themes, characterisations, symbolism, and narrative techniques, are the poet's (Obike's) creation. The study also identified and discussed some themes that Ikwubuzo believes could be interpreted as realities of human attitudes in society. The themes identified by Ikwubuzo (2014) include: conflict and reconciliation, the deity's invincibility, suppression, appropriation, and foolishness, love and disaffection, pride and extravagance, and praise and rejection. The study concludes that Obike does not just lift oral material for the fun of it but also brings in his own imagination, resulting in the extension of the story.

Okediadi (2004) thematically studied the poems of six Igbo poets from five Igbo anthologies: *Utara Nti*, *Nri Uche*, *Akpa Uche*, *Nkemakolam*, and *Echiche Miri Emi*. The poets studied are Tony Ubesie, I.U. Nwadike, J.U.T. Nzeako, J.C. Obienyem, N. Emenanjo, and N. Olebara. Okediadi (2004), after studying the works of these poets, classified them into various groups based on their themes. Her classification of the six poets is as follows: Nnamdi Olebara – a weeping poet, J.C. Obienyem – a philosophical poet, I.U. Nwadike – a historical poet, Nolie Emenanjo – a satirist, T.U. Ubesie – a moralist, and J.U.T. Nzeako – a traditionalist. After a critical study of the works of these six poets and an identification of the literary features in their works, Okediadi (2004) concludes that Igbo poets have always been committed to addressing the social and other problems of their societies.

Ikwubuzo (2006) again studies the myth of 'a black god' in Chukuezi's poetry. The paper focuses on A.B. Chukuezi's poem, 'Chukwu Ndi Isi Ojii' in *Utara*

Nti, in which the poet invents a myth of a black God with a view to revaluing and scolding blacks for being ignorant of the value of their African personality. The study aims to explore Chukuezi's literary contribution towards the development of the African continent. After a critical analysis of Chukuezi's poem, Ikwubuzo finds that indeed Chukuezi's literary (poetry) efforts are geared towards redeeming the image of Africa. In doing so, the study also found that Chukuezi is very blunt in pointing out the evils that afflict the African continent, and he condemns Africans and holds them responsible for their many misdeeds. Ikwubuzo concludes by suggesting that even if efforts are made through the arts and sports to project a positive image of Africa, the perpetuation of evil deeds such as political assassinations, economic sabotage, and many more in Africa will continue to negate those efforts, hence the need for Africa to be proud of its cultural identity.

Ikwubuzo (2007) consolidated Ugonna's (1982) study, focusing mainly on written Igbo poetry. Ikwubuzo (2007), however, appraised the growth rate of written Igbo poetry over its first three decades. In his study, Ikwubuzo examined factors that contributed to the growth of Igbo written poetry, which, according to him, include author-financed publishing, renewed interest in writing Igbo among lovers of the language, and the end of the orthography controversy. Ikwubuzo, in his study, having assessed the present state of written Igbo poetry, thinks that despite the poor quality of some published Igbo poetic texts and the fact that they were author-financed, there has been progressive, steady growth in extant works since 1982, when Ugonna wrote his work. Ikwubuzo (2007) concluded with recommendations for the growth of written Igbo poetry.

Ikwubuzo (2009) examines Nnamdi Olebara's poem "Iwe dị m n'obi" and Oguguo's poem "Ihe gara agaala" as protest poems. The study posits that Nnamdi

Olebara and Oguguo's protest poems criticise racism and colonialism in Africa, and the two poems also show allegiance to justice, equity, and freedom in Africa. Ikwubuzo argues that these two poets are revolutionists who used their poems as a weapon to canvass for social and political change in Africa. Ikwubuzo concludes that the two poems studied exemplify how modern Igbo poets respond to societal problems by moving beyond the sphere of their artistic creation into the socio-political reality of their time.

The first systematic study of written Igbo poetry was conducted by Ogbuagu (2010), who, at the doctoral level, analysed the poems of Nnamdi Olebara, whom she views as a poet, prophet, and social critic. Ogbuagu (2010, p. 6) argued that the first Igbo poem published was Obienyem's *Mbem Igbo*, followed by Akpa Uche, in which Olebara contributed seven poems. Ogbuagu's study, which adopts a survey method, examined only the seven poems of Nnamdi Olebara in Akpa Uche in relation to how the poet criticises various misdemeanours in Igbo society, and thus concludes that Nnamdi Olebara expresses his views of life through laments, prophecy, and criticism. Ogbuagu's work focuses on the poems written by a single poet without taking into consideration any other poem, not even in passing. Again, Ogbuagu's position that Obienyem's *Mbem Igbo* was the first published Igbo poetic verse is not proper, since *Mbem Igbo* was published in 1979, according to Nwadike (2002), while *Akpa Uche* was published in 1975. The analysis in Ogbuagu's study can be said to be cursory, as it is geared toward justifying the claim that Olebara is a prophet, a social critic, and a weeping poet who frowns on the ills in society. Ogbuagu's work is primarily limited in scope. It cannot be used to understand Igbo social life, as it borders only on the views of a single poet, who never wrote another poem except for his initial contributions in *Akpa Uche*.

Nnyigide and Egenti (2013) adopt a Marxist theoretical approach to study written Igbo poems that address contemporary issues related to African unity, identity, and development. The aim of adopting the Marxist approach as a social theory in their study was to determine the level at which the poets addressed these issues in their poems. After a careful examination of the five selected poems by five Igbo poets, namely, Olebara, Onyekaonwu, Nwadike, Okediadi, and Emenanjo in their work, Nnyigide and Egenti (2013) reveal that Africans are still suffering the effects of colonialism. However, the study also submits that Igbo poets address issues relating to African unity, development, and identity by criticising the activities of African leaders through satire and admonition.

Nsolibe (2013) critically analyses four Igbo written poems. She based her study on two Igbo poetic texts, each written by Uba-Mgbemena and I.U Nwadike – two philosophical and two satirical poems. Nsolibe’s study aims to expose the extent to which the poets, through their activities, have gone on to x-ray the varieties of human experiences in the Igbo community, which could help reshape our contemporary society at large. Nsolibe (2013, p. 88) highlights eight traditional stylistic techniques that a satirist has at his disposal when writing or performing poetry. Those techniques include invective, caricature, burlesque, mock-heroic, irony, lampoon, parody, and *Reductio ad Absurdum*. Having analysed the poems of these two poets, Nsolibe (2013) submits that Nwadike and Uba-Mgbemena are versatile in their language style and creativity as displayed in their poems.

Nnyigide (2014) analyses some philosophical and satiric poems in *Uche bu Afa* and *Akpa Uche*. In her study, Nnyigide offers a formalist interpretation of the selected philosophical and satiric poems by examining their forms. The poems she examines are Obienyem’s ‘Akwwkwọ Ọrụ Ego’, Akoma’s ‘Ụgbọ’, and Ogunjiofor’s

‘O dī m nnọọ ka m buru Nnunu’, all from *Akpa Uche*, and Onyekaonwu’s ‘Osisinwere uji’, ‘Ohi ero’, and ‘Obodo m’ from *Uche bu Afa*. In her formalistic analysis of these six poems, Nnyidige also considers the diction and unity of the formal features in promoting the overall aesthetic of the poems. However, Nnyidige (2014) does not identify the formal features in each poem and how they contribute to the overall meaning; the study only acknowledges their presence.

Agwuna (2014) also examines visionary echoes in Onyekaonwu’s ‘Najjiria Bu Enyimba’ in *Uche bu Afa* and Ogunjiofor’s ‘Zere Ohi’ in *Akpa Uche*. The study aims to use the lenses of poetry to identify visionary echoes in current trends and governing behaviours in Nigeria today. Agwuna (2014) believes that remarkable benefits and wisdom are rooted in Igbo poetry through the visions of poets as prophets, as it appears in the poems. After the interpretative analysis of the two poems concerning the content and the language use in them, Agwuna (2014) submits that in the poem, ‘Najjiria Bu Enyimba’, the social ills of the country are ironically predicated, while Ogunjiofor in ‘Zere Ohi’ showcases the neglected traditional folktales today. Agwuna (2014) finally submits that Igbo studies are consistently progressing in leaps and bounds, as the visions of Igbo poets would bring about tremendous improvements and reformations towards a positive change in the society we live in today.

Epuchie and Ezechukwunyere (2014) study poets as social mobilisers and the conscience of society, using Emenanjo’s “Aririọ” and Olebara’s “Afrika enwerela onwe ya”, with *Akpa Uche* (1975) as a case study. Their study, which adopts a survey research method, aims to establish that Igbo poets usually serve as the society’s consciousness and also act as repositories of the people’s cultural heritage. After a thematic analysis of the two poems, the study finds that Igbo poets are always sensitive to the sociopolitical realities of their environment. The study also

recommends that the Igbo rekindle their interest in the study of Igbo poetry, which has suffered from widespread apathy among Igbo language speakers.

Nnyigide (2015), the second Ph.D. study of written Igbo poetry, analyses selected poems on natural phenomena in seven Igbo poetic texts through the theoretical lens of Ecocriticism. The poetic texts Nnyigide analysed include *Akpa Uche*, *Utara Nti*, *Nkà Okwu*, *Akọ Bụ Ndu*, *Echiche Miri Emi*, *Ije Uwa*, and *Akonuche*. Nnyigide (2015) adopts a survey research design in her qualitative study, focusing on the thematic analysis of selected Igbo poems. Her study was anchored solely in poems that border on natural phenomena in the written Igbo texts chosen for the study. However, she does not provide reasons for choosing those poetic texts from the pool of other available poetic texts. The thrust of Nnyigide's (2015) study is to investigate the relationship between natural phenomena such as water, air, wind, and sun, and man in society. The study also examines how the Igbo perceive these natural phenomena, or rather, the significance of these phenomena to the Igbo. Nnyigide (2015), having examined various poems on these natural phenomena as projected by Igbo poets, who are members of the Igbo society, finds synergy among Igbo poetry, natural phenomena, and the Igbo society. Nnyigide suggests that Igbo poets, through their works of art, portray the importance of these natural phenomena to the Igbo society.

In her doctoral thesis, Agwuna (2016) investigates Igbo poets as social critics, focusing on selected Igbo poems. Her descriptive survey study stemmed from the need to identify various ills in Igbo society that Igbo poets selected and criticised in their poems. Agwuna (2016) adopts a purposive sampling technique in her thematic examination of selected Igbo poems to highlight various criticisms of society by Igbo poets. This is with a view to creating awareness and enhancing people's

understanding of the sociopolitical, socioeconomic, and agricultural issues of life. Agwuna (2016), using the social theory of Marxism, limits her study to eighteen Igbo poems selected purposefully from six Igbo poetic texts, namely: *Echiche* (1989) by Ezeuko and Anowai, *Uche bụ Akpa* (2006) by Anozie, *Akpa Uche* (1975) by Ekechukwu (ed.), *Akọnuche* (2006) by Ugwunkwo, *Utara Ntị* (1979) by Emenanjo (ed.), and *Akọ Na Uche* (2001) by Echebima. In her study, like Nnyigide (2015), Agwuna (2016) briefly explains the categories of Igbo poems, which, according to her, include: philosophical, satirical, natural, political, lamentative, prophetic, and praise poems. Agwuna (2016) also examines the style used by Igbo poets in presenting these critical issues in the selected poems she studied. In this, she considers the exposition, diction, tone, and figurative language used in the poems by poets. She concludes her study by summarising the themes in each of the eighteen poems studied.

More recently, Akaeze (2018) studied creative dissidence and revolutionary temper in selected Igbo poems, employing the Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) framework. Akaeze (2018) explains creative dissidence as the artistic or imaginative approach to struggle or resistance. Her study, which adopts a qualitative research design, used data elicited from 12 Igbo poems from five Igbo anthologies: *Nkemakolam* (1983), *Echiche Miri Emi* (1990), *Ekenegwurugwu* (1996), *Nka dị N'ụburu* (2007), and *Akị na Ụkwa* (2015). Akaeze's consideration of the poems focused mainly on their functions, themes, and the language devices used to express creative dissidence and revolutionary temper. According to Akaeze (2018), the themes of creative dissidence and revolutionary temper identified in Igbo poems include corruption, violence, sycophancy, tribalism, nepotism, and bad leadership. Akaeze further investigates the functions of creative dissidence and revolutionary

temper as reflected in Igbo poems and finds that they serve political, historical, educational, aesthetic, and ethical functions. Furthermore, Akaeze examines the language of creative dissidence and revolutionary temper in written Igbo poetry to reveal how Igbo poets use aspects of everyday language to create special effects related to dissidence and revolutionary temper. Akaeze (2018) concludes her study by asserting that creative dissidence and revolutionary temper are honest emotional responses to the many sociopolitical problems in society. She further states that all the selected Igbo poems studied show evidence of creative dissidence and revolutionary temper in addressing the numerous problems in Nigeria. Akaeze's study could be said to have contributed positively to the appreciation of Igbo poetic texts through her use of sociolinguistic theory in the study of Igbo poetry. Her study has shown a new dimension towards the appreciation and study of Igbo poetry in general. However, her study does not account for the historical development and general form of Igbo written poetry, which are among the gaps the present study aims to address.

Agwuna and Osinomumu (2018) analyse G. I. Nwaozuzu's poem "Chara m ka m kpara ego" (Get out of my way, let me make money) in *Akōnauche*. The study adopts a descriptive survey research method to determine the cause of the desperate desire among the youths to make money. However, the study does not adopt any critical lens (theory) in its inquiry and instead reviews all the poems and contributions by Nwaozuzu in the anthology *Akōnauche*. Having examined the poem's thematic implications and its language, the study submits that the Igbo youths' burning desire for quick money is not peculiar to them. However, it is a challenge associated with modern youth around the world.

Having reviewed some earlier studies on written Igbo poetry, especially the four doctoral works, the gaps the present study intends to fill become more apparent.

Ogbuagu (2010), for instance, provides background information on written Igbo poetry. However, the information she provided cannot in any way be considered historical, because the study does not investigate the factors that gave rise to the birth of written Igbo poetry, which is one of the major emphases of this study. Nnyigide's (2015) classification of Igbo poetry, on the other hand, is mainly based on the thematic study of selected Igbo poems. It does not account for the social issues addressed by Igbo poets in writing, which is one of the gaps the present study intends to address.

Agwuna's (2016) study is sociological; it differs from the present study in several ways. First, the poetic samples used in the present study are more numerous than the samples used by Agwuna in her study. Agwuna's study focuses only on 18 poems selected from 6 Igbo poetic texts. In comparison, the present study draws excerpts from 162 written Igbo poems, purposively selected from 16 poetic texts, as representatives of Igbo poetry published over the four decades of its existence. Again, Agwuna's study does not account for the historical development of written Igbo poetry, whereas the present study offers a historical exegesis of that development. Furthermore, Agwuna's study played down, in a significant way, the form of written Igbo poetry. In contrast, the present study focuses on establishing the general form and nature of Igbo poetry in writing. To this end, this study provides a detailed account of the developmental trajectory of written Igbo poetry, discusses some societal issues and other human concerns addressed by modern Igbo poets in the decades under study, and also describes the form of written Igbo poetry.

2.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, earlier studies on poetry and written Igbo poetry, as our primary focus in the study, have been reviewed in relation to their significance to the present study. The review in this chapter focuses on the concept of written Igbo poetry and previous studies on various issues related to it. In the next chapter, we shall examine the historical development of Igbo poetry from orature to its present state of contemporariness.

CHAPTER THREE

THE DEVELOPMENT OF WRITTEN IGBO POETRY

3.0 Introduction

In this chapter, we will investigate the developmental progression of written Igbo poetry, with an emphasis on the factors that both gave rise to it and marred its growth. This chapter shall also examine the state of written Igbo poetry in terms of the number of extant works published and research works carried out on written Igbo poetry in the decades under study (1975-2015).

3.1 Igbo Poetry, Its Origin and Forms

Oral poetry, as we know it, has its origin in man's belief in the supernatural, as it was conceived in the invocation of gods by the early Igbo, whose primary occupation was hunting (Okediadi, 2004, p. 250). To survive, the early Igbo regularly hunted and depended on the gods for their daily kill. With oral poetry (incantations, chants, and songs), the early Igbo engaged the gods regularly and were always assured of their (the gods') continued support. The early Igbo employed songs and chants of praise to gain the gods' favour, and when they faced more serious challenges or danger, incantations were used to invoke the gods' power to come to their aid quickly, and the gods always came to their rescue. Through this chain of connections, the Igbo, like every other African tribe, developed its own religion, which is traditional in nature. This goes on to justify Emenyonu's (1978) claim, in which he asserts that oral Igbo tradition is the foundation of all Igbo literature.

Igbo traditional religion served as a point of convergence between oral Igbo poetry and drama. This is because the masquerade (*mm̄onwu* - the Igbo traditional

drama) performers employ a wider range of Igbo chants in their performance. The *Ndi dibia* (Medicine men) also employed a wide range of chants and recitations to commune with the spirits. The early Igbo, having discovered traditional religion as a communicative link between them and the gods, employed chants, songs, and incantations which they dramatically performed at the shrines, village squares, and the king's palace, or at any other place designated for such performance to interact with the gods and seek their favor. This cordial relationship that exists between the Igbo and poetry thus metamorphosed into what can be termed 'Igbo poetic life circle'.

'Igbo poetic life circle' refers to the poetic chain that underscores the Igbo way of life from birth to death. This circle is rightly captured in the phrase '*si na ndu rue n'onwu*' (from life to death). Ojukwu, Onuora-Ogunno, and Esimone (2014) opine that the rhythmic nature of the Igbo life cuts across many facets of Igbo traditional life and thus follows the Igbo child from womb to tomb. This poetic life circle of the Igbo is confirmed by the fact that in the traditional Igbo society, the birth of a child is marked by shouts of joy, which is accompanied by birth songs that are used to thank God for the gift of the newborn baby and also appreciate the new parents for a job well done. As the child is being nurtured, when the child cries, lullabies are used to calm or put the child to sleep, but more importantly, the songs introduce the child to the rhythmic nature of Igbo life. Ojukwu, Onuora-Ogunno, and Esimone (2014) confirm that the basic rhythmic training given to a child in Igbo society is mainly channeled through folksongs to enhance easy assimilation and comprehension. As the child grows, he or she is introduced to different play songs, satire, and other pedagogical poems or songs used to teach the child the native sense and the Igbo way of life. These songs are sometimes employed to mould the psychological, moral, spiritual, and social life of the child who is expected to become

a full-grown man or woman. Ohuche (1991) opines that in precolonial Africa (Igbo land inclusive), children are taught through a traditional system of education, which they receive through observation, imitation, and participation in social activities, and, in doing so, they learn how to cope with their environment. In the words of Ohuche (1991:3) about children in Igbo society, Ohuche states:

Through observation, imitation and participation, they learnt to farm, hunt, cook, fish, play, wrestle, deliver messages, run homes and build houses. Teachers included all members of the extended family as well as secret societies for those who benefited from the traditional form of higher education. Clearly, this type of education was, for the most part, practical, utilitarian, non-formal and non verbal.

To reinforce retention and ease learning of the skills mentioned above, poetry (songs and recitation) was usually employed. The child, in the process of transitioning into adulthood, continues to enjoy oral poetry and uses it appropriately. When the child becomes an adult and gets married, marriage songs are used for such ceremonies. In the case of a lady, marriage songs are also used by other women to escort the lady to her husband's home. When the individual dies, funeral songs or poems are employed to bid him or her farewell. In other words, the Igbo people's rite of passage is characterised by poetic rendition.

The early forms of Igbo poetry were orally transmitted from person to person and from one generation to another. In every generation, there are poets who, through their creative imaginations and artistic skills, add to the existing poetic repertoire of the Igbo. However, because the early Igbo poets did not have a clear orthographic system for documenting their poetic works, the names of the original composers of the early oral poetic works, or what we now know as oral poetry, have long since fallen into oblivion. Funk and Wagnalls (1972) provide a justifiable reason for this by asserting that, because the number of songs (oral poetry) that were newly composed

during a given generation is usually small within a folk group, by the time the songs spread over an area and having moved through a generation or two, the name of the originator or composer is usually forgotten. This, which is true of Igbo oral poetry, also means that, as these early Igbo poets performed their art, people learnt it over time as they watched and listened. Since these early oral poetic works were not documented until a few decades or a generation after the demise of the original composer, the songs became popular among the people and were stored in their memory; the composers' names are usually forgotten over time, making the poems communally owned.

The nature of Igbo oral poetry is such that it depends partly on performance for realisation of its effects, for it is only in such a situation that its aesthetic satisfaction is heightened, as both the visual and acoustic effects are realised (Uzochukwu, 1982). Furthermore, oral Igbo poetry, like other genres of Igbo oral literature, permeates the cultural, political, religious, social and informal occasions of the Igbo (Ikwubuzo, 2008, p. 39), which is why, two things considered in the composition of oral poetic verses include, first, the social needs of the communities, where they are performed and secondly, the traditional form of the poetry, which derives from and is indigenous to the community (Egudu & Nwoga, 1971).

The messages encoded in oral Igbo poetry distinguished one form of oral Igbo poetry from another, thereby allowing for major classifications. Scholars have identified some of these classifications to include lullabies, festival songs, marriage songs, birth songs, folk ballads, incantations, love songs, elegies, and work songs, to mention but a few (Egudu & Nwoga, 1971; Ogbalu, 1974; Nwadike, 2002; Ikwubuzo & Oraegbunam, 2016). Uzochukwu (2001) categorised all these forms of oral Igbo poetry into three major branches: songs (*uri/egwu*), chant (*mbem*), and recitation

(ngugo) - all these forms of Igbo oral poetry project the life and philosophies of the Igbo.

The above classification of oral Igbo poetry attests that before the Igbo had contact with Western civilisation, education, and writing, they had a fully developed poetry. These poetic presentations were delivered orally at moonlight plays, marriage and burial ceremonies, wrestling matches, and other social activities among the Igbo (Ogbuagu, 2010). These forms of Igbo poetry serve the sociological and religious needs of the Igbo. This background is given to establish the fact that oral poetry forms the foundation upon which written Igbo poetry was built. However, the rise of written poetry can be traced to the activities of the Christian missionaries in Igboland.

3.1.1 The Contribution/Influence of the Christian Missionary to the Development of Written Igbo Poetry

The abolition of the slave trade brought the Igbo and other African peoples into contact with the white man, who came for different reasons, including, but not limited to, colonisation, evangelisation, and commerce (Emenyonu, 1978). Nwadike (2002) upholds the view that the only thing the Igbo and some other African peoples gained from the slave trade era was the development of some African languages as written languages. This season was described by Emenyonu (1978) as the era of Christian Missionaries in Africa, and the missionary group that took this first leap of faith in reducing Igbo language and literature (poetry inclusive) to writing was the Church Missionary Society (C.M.S.). The CMS laid this foundation with their publication of *Akwukwo Ukwé n'Asusu Ibo* in 1934. This will be thoroughly discussed in this chapter.

Before this era of Christian Missionaries in Africa, and, by extension, in Igboland, various individuals had earlier, on different occasions, made efforts to put the Igbo language into writing. We recall that after the abolition of the slave trade, slaves from Africa were repatriated to Africa. The Igbo and other ex-slaves from other African countries were kept at slave camps in Freetown, Sierra Leone. It was at these slave camps that the effort by a few individuals to reduce African languages (Igbo language inclusive) to writing began (Nwadike, 2002). Igboanusi (2006) believes it should be termed as incomplete, any historical study of Igbo language that forgets the name of the German pastor of the Moravian Brethren, G. A. C. Oldendorp who, in 1777, published his work which was a collection of 28 brief vocabulary of African languages, which two of them were in the Igbo language titled 'Ibo' and 'Kalabari'. With this publication, Oldendorp became the first person to write anything in Igbo. Efforts of other individuals like Hannah Kilham, J.F. Schon, Ajayi Crowther, J. C. Taylor, and T.D. Dennis provided a springboard for the study of the Igbo language, which, by extension, led to the birth of the written Igbo language and literature. The efforts of these individuals, both at the West Indies and the slave camps at Freetown, Sierra Leone, and Nigeria, established a precedent for studies in the Igbo language and literature. Accounts of how the Igbo language evolved from its oral nature to a written language have been well chronicled and documented by various Igbo scholars, such as Emenyonu (1978), Onyekaonwu (1986), Nwadike (2002), Igboanusi (2006), and Anizoba (2013). Based on the data provided by these scholars and other sources, it is clear that the contact the Igbo had with Western civilisation played a significant role in the development of Igbo poetry from its oral to its present written form.

The earliest attempt at writing Igbo poetry was the effort of the Church Mission Society (C.M.S), which arrived in Onitsha in 1848. On its arrival, the C.M.S.

played a vital role in Christianising the Igbo cultural area. Christianity was one of the things the Igbo were quick to accept from the missionaries. Ekwueme (1973) opines that the Igbo are known to have embraced Christianity more than any other ethnic group in Africa. Ekwueme provided two reasons for this. The first point is that the Christian principles were not far from Igbo principles as observed in their traditional religion, and secondly, Christian ethics, on the other hand, is, in many ways, synonymous with Igbo ethics. Apart from the traditional religion, which is indigenous to the Igbo, the Igbo cultural area is divided mainly into two Christian denominations, the Anglicans (C.M.S.) and the Roman Catholic Movement (R.C.M.), with a small fraction as Methodists and Pentecostals.

Having come in contact with Western civilisation, occasioned by the British government, after embracing Christianity, the Igbo set out to become experts in whatever they learnt from the British. This is why Afigbo (1981) holds that the Igbo's eagerness to become experts like the British in changing their physical world ensnared them in Christianity rather than converting them to Christianity. This is why the earliest attempt at writing Igbo poetry was more of a religious move, championed by the C.M.S. The C.M.S., having discovered how important poetry is to the Igbo, knew that the fastest way to penetrate the Igbo cultural area was through religious poetry. For this reason, the C.M.S. did not delay in translating their English hymns into the Igbo language and used same at their various worship centres. This made their Christian religious gatherings more attractive for the natives who enjoyed the melody of those translated hymns. This point will be fully discussed in due course later in this chapter.

It would be recalled that when the C.M.S. team, which included Samuel Jonas (who served as an interpreter), J. C. Taylor (who was familiar with the Isuama Igbo

dialect), and Ajayi Crowther, arrived in Onitsha on 26 July 1857, they set up the first C.M.S. headquarters in Onitsha. Shortly after the CMS headquarters was established, Crowther left J.C. Taylor, who had been ordained explicitly for the Onitsha mission, to manage the Onitsha headquarters as he continued his missionary work up the Niger (Igboanusi, 2006). However, Crowther left Taylor with a detailed eleven-point written advice, which is presented in Ferguson (1971, p. 27) as cited in Ogunewu (2010), to include:

One, cultivate friendships with all the people as much as possible. Two, a private conversation will be of more importance than public worship. Three, be patient and forbearing. Four, develop the study of Ibo vocabulary and grammar, and its best reduction to writing, and make as many translations as possible...

With this advice, Taylor was encouraged to achieve great things in Igbo. However, his shallow knowledge of the Igbo language stood as a challenge against him, since he was born to both freed Igbo slaves, who spoke different dialects of Igbo. Due to his language limitations, Taylor requested to meet with Schon, who had earlier abandoned the study of the Igbo language because of his bitter experience at Abo, to learn Igbo from him. After Taylor met with Schon in London and studied Igbo for a while, he returned to Onitsha in 1860, after publishing his journal in 1859, which contained a small collection of Igbo proverbs (Igboanusi, 2006). Upon his return to Nigeria, Taylor became instrumental in the development of the Igbo language and literature through the C.M.S. mission, as he began translating and publishing in Igbo, using the Isuama dialect he had learnt from Schon. By 1866, Taylor had already finished translating the New Testament of the English Bible into Igbo. In 1871-1872, Taylor and his team of translators published a few Igbo hymns and other prayer materials (Igboanusi, 2006). It is unclear whether the songs in Taylor's works were translated from Christian hymnals in Ancient and Modern (A & M), used by the

C.M.S. in London. Efforts to see a copy of this hymn translated into Igbo by Taylor, in the course of this study, proved abortive. Ab initio, nothing was said about written Igbo poetry. It never emerged. However, Igbo oral poetry continued to serve the social and religious needs of the Igbo.

As expected, the C.M.S. remained the major advocate of Igbo language study during this period (1901-1929). With the Isuama dialect fading away, Dennis at a conference, which was held at Asaba in 1905 imposed a dialect, which was an amalgam of five dialects of Igbo (Onitsha, Bonny, Owerri, Arochukwu and Uwani) known as 'Union Igbo' (Nwadike, 2002; Igboanusi, 2006) with the hope of solving the dialect problem that has posed a challenge to translating religious texts into the Igbo language. It was with this Union Igbo that Rev. T. Dennis, together with other Igbo natives, who worked and assisted him in translation (Mr Alphonsus Onyeabo and Anyaegbunam), translated the Bible and other English religious and literary texts into the Igbo language, some of which include the *Pilgrim Progress*, some catechisms, Igbo folklore, *Union Hymnal* and *Union Reader* (Nwadike, 2002, p. 58).

After these earlier attempts, nothing serious was heard about written Igbo poetry until 1934, when the Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge (S.P.C.K.) published the C.M.S.'s translated *Book of Common Prayer* into the Igbo language and titled *Akwukwo Ẹkpelu nke Anẹkpelu Cuku n'Ọgbo* (Ibo Holy Prayer Book, 1934). This text was divided into two parts: one part of it contained the C.M.S.'s prayers, catechisms, collects, and other church proceedings, the second part of this book were hymns (poems) translated from the Church of England's *Hymns Ancient and Modern* (1924) into the Igbo language and titled, *Akwukwo Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo* (Hymns in Ibo Language). In this *Akwukwo Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo*, the Igbo composed a few hymns, which were added to the translated hymns from the English language. To distinguish

the creation of the Igbo from the hymns translated from Hymns *Ancient and Modern*, the hymns written by the Igbo were all branded ‘Original’. The reason for branding them ‘Original’ was to give the creative right to the Igbo and to distinguish them from the translated hymns clearly. This was why, when *Akwukwo Ekpelu Anekpelu Cuku n’Ogbọ* (which had *Akwukwo Ukwę, n’Asusu Ibo* as its second part) was revised in 1977, as *Ekpere na Abụ*, which is today used in the Anglican Communion, all the hymns written by the Igbo were grouped alongside other new hymns written by the Igbo and titled: ‘ABU NKE NDI-IGBO CHEPỤTARA’ (Hymns created by the Igbo). Let us instantiate this claim with one of the hymns (poems) written by the Igbo Christian adherents, which was published initially in *Akwukwo Ukwę n’Asusu Ibo* (1934, p. 65) as hymn 70, which was later revised and can now be found in hymn 373 of the *Ekpere na Abụ* (1977, p. 288) (Hymn 1), which is used today in the Anglican Communion. The hymn is in eight stanzas, all written in couplets; the writer is anonymous.

**Hymn 70 (*Akwukwo Ukwę n’Asusu Ibo*)
(ORIGINAL)**

1. Oyim, bia k’inu akuko
Nke nuku ifu-n’anya

Koros – Jesu nwulu, Onwulu
Maka ifim na ngi azi

2. Madu nine bu ndi njo,
N’anya Cuku nke di nsọ:

3. Jesu, Okpala nke Nna,
Ful’ayi n’anya kali aka.

4. Jesu bialu n’uwa nka,
K’Owezoputa ndi njo...

(*A.U.A.I*, 1934, p. 65)

(1. My friend, come and listen to a tale
Of a great love

Hymn 373 (*Ekpere na Abụ*)

1. Eyim, bia, nu akuko
Nke ihu-n’anya uku

Koros – Jisus nwuru, O nwuru,
N’ihim, gi, na madu dum.

2. Madu nile bu ndi-njo
N’anya Chineke di nsọ.

3. Jisus, Okpara nke Nna,
Huru anyi n’anya ri-nne.

4. Jisus biara n’uwa nka
K’O we zoputa ndi njo...

(*E.A*, 1977, p. 228)

Chorus – Jesus died, He died
Because of me, you, and everybody

2. Everybody is all sinners
In the sight of holy God
3. Jesus, firstborn of the Father,
Love us so much
4. Jesus came to this earth
To save us from sin...)

The above (Hymn 1), continues like this till the eighth stanza. Taking a look at the above hymn 1, one will readily notice that the only difference in the two hymns is in the orthography that was used in it. While the first one was written in Union Igbo, the latter was written with Ọnwụ's orthography, though the spellings are not very correct. The table below is a list of some of the hymns, which were earlier written by Igbo persons and published in the C.M.S.'s *Akwukwọ Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo* and later revised in the now *Ekpere na Abụ* under the group title 'Abụ Nke Ndi-Igbo Cheputara';

Table 3. List of hymns that were earlier written in *Akwukwo Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo* (A.U.A.I.) and their numbers in the revised *Ekpere n'Abụ* (E.A.)

S/N	Hymn number in <i>Akwukwọ Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo</i> (1934)	Page number In A.U.A.I	Same Hymn in <i>Ekpere na Abụ</i> , number (1978)	Page Number in E.A
1	50	51	391	304
2	21	23	376	291
3	170	142	385	299
4	171	143	386	300
5	273	227	390	304
6	274	227	399	310
7	70	65	373	288
8	7	259	374	289
9	10	261	378	292
10	18	268	388	302

This *Akwukwọ Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo* contains three hundred and four (304) hymns, among which twenty-eight (28) of the hymns are poetic creations of the Igbo

Christian adherents. These poetic creations of the Igbo, as expected, were influenced by the Western poetic writing tradition. Thus, just like many other hymns in *Akwukwọ Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo*, which were translated from the English language (*Ancient and Modern*), these 28 Igbo hymns were written in couplets, triplets, quatrains, and some in octaves. Two among the 28 Igbo hymns were written in couplets (like in the case of the above Hymn 1). Another hymn was written in triplets; two of the Igbo hymns were octaves, while the remaining twenty-four Igbo hymns were written in quatrains. Since these early Igbo hymns were all lyric poems, tunes were assigned to them to help singers. To substantiate this claim that these were the original compositions of the Igbo Christian believers. Let us look at one other hymn, which is among these 28 hymns written by the Igbo and published in the C.M.S.'s *Akwukwọ Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo*, Hymn 278 (p. 230), (Hymn 2):

Hymn 278 Lacrymax. 7.7.7.
(Tune only, H. C. No. 259)
Original

- | | | |
|----|---|---|
| 1. | Onye gwalui goba mọ?
Ayi mel'ife nna-ayi melu.
Nna-i gbue ọcu, igegbu? | (Who told you to practice heathen religion?
We did what our forefathers did.
If your father commits murder, will you kill?) |
| 2. | Ndi dibia nalafu ngi,
Si ngi nyebe ndi-mo nni,
Gwam, ma ozu neli nni? | Medicine men are deceiving you,
Telling you to continue giving food to the spirits,
Tell me, does corpse eat? |
| 3. | So Nwa Cuku bu Dibia
Nke newepu njo n'obi:
Gbo nkpa-i nine m'iyọ Ya.
(<i>Akwukwọ Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo</i> , 1934, p. 230) | God's son is the only medicine man
That purges sin from the heart
Solve all your problems. Amen.) |

The above verse is a clear evidence that all the hymns that were labelled 'Original' in *Akwukwọ Ukwẹ n'Asusu Ibo* were indeed the poetic creation of the early Igbo Christian converts, who were already influenced by the classical religious culture. The above hymn 2 reminds us of the silent but brutal battle the missionaries

fought with traditional religion believers shortly after arriving in the Igbo cultural area.

It would be recalled that the missionaries encountered fierce resistance from the Igbo in their early attempts to Christianise the Igbo cultural area. Ugonna (1984) reports that the mm̄nwū cult was one of the most challenging opponents the missionaries faced upon their arrival in Igboland. Ugonna (1984, p. 25) further confirms that the missionaries described mm̄ū as an obstacle to their missionary endeavours in the central Igbo area. It is important to recall what we stated earlier, that the Igbo, just like other ethnic groups in Africa, believe strongly in the relationship between man and spirits. These beliefs are all embedded in Igbo traditional philosophies and religion. The Igbo understanding of the spirit world has been well documented by various Igbo scholars, including Ugonna (1984) and Nwala (1985). This background is provided to explain that the above hymn 2 portrays a direct attack by the missionaries on Igbo ways of life, using the Igbo brothers against their own brothers.

Hymn 2 above, no doubt, is a satirical hymn (poem) written by early Igbo Christian converts. At the time the hymn was written, the early Igbo Christians were already influenced by Western religion and, as such, believed in the supremacy of Christianity over Igbo traditional religion. Hymn 2 was written to be used as a satirical tool to lure the unbelievers into embracing Christianity as the right religion. Again, hymn two was designed to prime new Igbo Christian converts (who might be contemplating returning to their traditional religion) to see their newfound faith as superior to, or better than, their previous faith in Igbo traditional religion. The thought and emotion that the above hymn 2 evokes prove that the poem was not

translated from English but was indeed the poetic creation of Igbo Christian adherents.

Another key reason the C.M.S. allowed the Igbo's poetic contributions to appear in the translated hymns from Hymn Ancient and Modern in Akwukwo Ukwè n'Asusu Ibo was the Education Ordinance of 1926. It will be recalled that, due to the controversy that greeted the 1882 Education Ordinance, which the C.M.S. and the Wesleyan played no small role in, the British government enacted the Education Ordinance Code of 1926. The Ordinance became operative on 27 May 1926. One of the immediate effects of the 1926 education code was that it led to the inauguration of the International Institute of African Languages and Cultures (I.I.A.L.C.), which some of its objectives include: "to advise and aid in the publication of studies on African languages, folklore and native art and to promote an understanding of African languages and social institutions, and to study the possibilities of their use as an instrument of education" (Lugard, 1928).

Nwadike (2002) opines that this Institute (I.I.A.L.C.) influenced most policy decisions on indigenous education in Africa. The Institute also assisted in establishing a Translation Bureau in Nigeria, solely for translating available literature from English into Igbo, Hausa, Efik, and Yoruba, respectively. The C.M.S. quickly keyed into the native language revolution being promoted by the I.I.A.L.C. It is believed that the reason the C.M.S. keyed into this language revolution was to increase the number of converts they have, because the C.M.S. thought that if the Igbo could see their own hymns written by their own as part of what the church uses, they would be more willing to accept Christianity over their traditional religion, which *Mmọnwu* (masquerade) cult, at this time, was the church's greatest rival.

The names of the Igbo poets who composed the Igbo hymns added to the translated hymns from Hymns Ancient and Modern are unclear, but Nwadike (2002) explains that Archdeacon Dennis had a team of Igbo indigenes who worked with him on the translations. At the top of these people were Mr Alponus Onyeabo, who was the Catchiest as at that time, and Mr Anyaegbunam. In an oral interview in 2018, Maduekwe explains that Mr Anyaegbunam, who hails from Obosi, in Anambra State, headed a team that wrote most of the Igbo hymns in *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo*. Just like *Omenuko*, the original orthography that was used in the writing of this *Akwukwo Ekpelu nke Anekpelu Cuku n'Ogbo* was the Union orthography, which Igboanusi (2006) believes Archdeacon T.J. Dennis imposed at a conference, which was held in Asaba on August 14, 1905. The Union orthography that was used in the writing of this text (*Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo*) favoured more of the Onitsha dialect, which was why the majority of the Igbo nicknamed the *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo* as 'Ukwe ndi Onitsha' (songs of the Onitsha people) (Maduekwe, 2018).

This *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo* by the C.M.S. is thus considered the most visible attempt towards the birth of written Igbo poetry, though purely hymns for religious purposes. Since it could be said to have formed the foundation of written Igbo poetry, any discussion on the development of written Igbo poetry that does not mention or acknowledge it can be deemed incomplete. These C.M.S. Igbo hymns can be seen as a part of what Ruth Finnegan, in her popular *Oral Literature in Africa* (1970), termed 'Religious poetry'. Finnegan (1970, p. 165) opines that there is a pool of religious poetry in Africa, some of which includes praises, hymns, possession songs, oracular poetry, and prayers. According to Finnegan, these forms of African religious poetry vary in their functions and contents across cultures. Finnegan strongly believes that the missionaries played a vital role in the birth and development of

African literature, and Igbo poetry is no exception. According to Finnegan (1970), it was not just the Christian missionaries that influenced African literature, but also the Islamic missionaries. Hence, Finnegan further opines that the Islamised people, such as the Fulani or Hausa in the northern portions of West Africa and the Swahili in East Africa, have their Arabic-influenced poetry. The *Dabteras* people of Ethiopia have their ecclesiastical poetry, which is linked with the Coptic Church. At the same time, some hymns and lyrics stem from the impact of Christianity (Christian missions) in many parts of the African continent.

Going by Ruth Finnegan's view, one can argue that these early Igbo contributions to translating religious hymns from English into Igbo could be said to have inspired the emergence of Igbo poetry. However, an examination of the content of these hymns reveals that they do not project the philosophies or worldviews of the Igbo; instead, they are hymns influenced by missionaries and written mainly for Christian religious edification, hence the restriction of their use to the church. For this reason, even though these hymns may be considered to be the foundation of written Igbo poetry, they could not be accepted as the first written Igbo poetry. It can be assumed that these hymns might have influenced the early Igbo writers, who at this stage began composing poetry in the corners of their homes and waiting for an opportunity to showcase their compositions, which were modelled on the western poetic writing tradition, as exemplified in *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo*.

3.2 Literary Climate Prior to the Rise of Written Igbo Poetry

After the publication of *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo*, one would have expected that it should have encouraged the writing and publication of secular Igbo poetic works or stirred up the desire in the Igbo to produce poetic works that would, at

that time, mirror the life and society of the Igbo, but just like in the case of *Omenụkọ* after its publication, no serious Igbo poem was written for a couple of decades. The Igbo continued with their oral poetry. Emenyonu (1978, p. 57) provides the reason for this by asserting that at this time, the Nigerian government placed more emphasis on the study of the English language to the detriment of the Nigerian languages after the publication of the first Igbo novel, *Omenụkọ*. This was why the attention of the people shifted from Igbo written literature, which was still in its infancy, to the English language and literature. This premium the government placed on learning English made knowledge of English the key to all privileged positions in government and in key businesses.

Written Igbo literature began with the publication of the first Igbo prose, *Omenụkọ*, by Pita Nwana, and *Ala Bingo* by D. N. Achara, both in 1933. Upon the publication of these great texts, they were received by the Igbo with much enthusiasm (Onyekaonwu, 1986, p. 33). Onyekaonwu, however, expresses disappointment at the inability of the other Igbo writers to build on the existing foundation laid by Pita Nwana and D. N. Achara when he states that:

After the publication of *Omenụkọ* and *Ala Bingo* in 1933 and considering the enthusiasm with which these works were received, one expected that subsequent works by other writers would emerge. But for a couple of decades, no other serious work was forthcoming.

Although Onyekaonwu's (1986) observation was in relation to the Igbo prose fiction, he did not foresee the role that the enthusiasm that greeted the debut of these two texts (*Omenụkọ* and *Ala Bingo*) played in the development of written Igbo poetry. It is possible that, due to the way the Igbo accepted *Omenụkọ* and *Ala Bingo*, the C.M.S. saw the inner yearning of the Igbo to have their literature written down, even though the government, at this time, placed more premium on the study of the English

language in schools, as opined by Nwadike (2002). The C.M.S. moved to satisfy this yearning of the Igbo to have their literature in print by allowing the Igbo to contribute a few hymns to the hymns translated from *Hymns Ancient and Modern*, which are contained in *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo*.

There is no gainsaying that the orthography controversy, which hit the Igbo language, dealt a devastating blow to the development of written Igbo poetry. During this controversy, emerging poets (writers), who were putting their thoughts together for onward publication at this time, fell into a state of confusion as to the correct orthography to follow. For this reason, many years passed without any Igbo poetic work appearing. When the orthography controversy ended in 1961, its ripple effect set in, as people did not want to publish for fear of not knowing whether it had truly ended. In the height of this confusion, in 1967, the Nigerian civil war broke out, and all preparations to publish Igbo poetic works were again put on hold.

During the Nigerian civil war (1967-1970), Igbo writers were too preoccupied with saving their lives to write poetry. Most of them hid themselves, while some of them joined the war. Writers such as Tony Ubesie, J.C. Maduekwe, and many others (who also pioneered Igbo poetry) were known to have played active roles in the war. For instance, T. Ubesie joined the Eastern Command of the Biafran Army in Enugu as a recruit and later rose to the rank of Captain (Nnabuihe, 2005, p. 58). J.C. Maduekwe, on the other hand, worked with the Radio Biafra station (mobile station). He performed chants on air, alongside Okookon Ndem, who read the 'News Talk' on the radio. While Okookon Ndem presented 'News Talk' on the radio, Maduekwe presented Onyekulum (Night Masquerade), a chant in the name of the Igbo masquerade known as *Ayaka*. Maduekwe's aim in performing this chant on the radio was to encourage the Biafran soldiers fighting on the front lines, demoralise the

fighting spirit of the Nigerian soldiers, and also encourage non-fighting Biafrans, who were demoralised during the heat of the war. This could have been said to be another attempt at writing Igbo poetry, but since the script Maduekwe used at this time was not published, the content of the poem was purely oral text, and as such, it could not be accepted as the first written Igbo poetry.

When the Nigerian civil war ended in 1970, there was a new wave of love for the Igbo language, and many Igbo writers began to publish their literary works in Igbo. However, prose fiction received more attention during this period, until Igbo poetry made its debut with the publication of *Akpa Uche*, an anthology of Igbo poems. According to Onyekaonwu (1986), three reasons were responsible for this literary explosion. The first one is that the three-year interval (1967-1970) created by the Nigerian civil war helped to convince people that the orthography dispute had truly ended. Secondly, the war reawakened the Igbo sense of ethnic identity and cultural awareness. Lastly, the war period provided writers with the opportunity to write, since movement was restricted and their experiences formed the theme of their works. Writers like Tony Ubesie, J.C. Maduekwe, J.U.T. Nzeako, and a few others had already made their presence felt in the Igbo literary scene, with their prose texts traversing many Igbo states and beyond. Many of these Igbo writers, who emerged at this time, had begun writing poetry but published more novels because there was yet to be a market for written Igbo poetry. The civil war and other global incidents provided emerging contemporary Igbo poets with enough experience and messages that formed the basis of their poetic writing. This was why the theme of most of the poems written in the first decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry (1975-1985) was centred on the consequences of war, the need for unity, colonialism, the quest for freedom, natural phenomena, philosophy, politics, death, places, and things. The

themes of war, its effects, and death were common in some of the poems written in the first decade. Let us exemplify this claim with a few excerpts from some poems written in the first decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry. The poem ‘Ugbo Elu Ogu’ (Poem 2), written by Tony Ubesie, in Ekechukwu (Ed.)’s *Akpa Uche* (1975), first and second stanza, the poet says:

Egbe b̄iawa ib̄uru ōkuk̄o	(When the kite comes to carry the chicken
A n̄a-àkp̄o egb̄e naān̄i aj̄o ah̄a	It will be called only bad names.
M̄a ñmad̄u turu ñk̄u b̄ia ōḡu	But when a man comes for a fight wearing feathers
Ib̄ia ḡbuf̄u um̄u ñmad̄u	Coming to kill people
N̄di nk̄e ya à na-an̄u on̄u	His people will be rejoicing
N̄di ō biàrà igb̄u à na-az̄u	The people he has come to kill will be moaning
Ùz̄u ya b̄u ñke Āmadīoh̄a	Its sound is like that of the god of thunder.
Osō yā n̄a-èyi um̄u ùw̄a egw̄u	Its speed scares the world
O fewe w̄e feb̄a n’igw̄e	When it flies, it flies into the sky
Ucha yā n̄a-àd̄i k̄a ñk̄e igw̄e	Its colour is like the clouds
Ihe e j̄i na-àma n̄a ō d̄i egw̄u	What will be used to know that it is wondrous
B̄u ñgb̄e ō gh̄ap̄ur̄u igw̄e ōk̄u...	Is when it vomits fire...)

(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 32)

In the above poem 2, Tony Ubesie mirrors his first-hand experience on the battlefield as a Biafran soldier during the Nigerian civil war. He describes the horrendous experience of the people during the war, when fighter jets were used to rain bombs on them. The poem (2), which evokes sorrow, reveals the depth of the poet’s mind at the time it was written, suggesting that the feeling is better imagined than felt. In Emenanjo’s *Utara Nti*, we see another poem, “Ògbunìigwe” (Poem 3) (bomb), written by Madubike, which focuses on the poet’s experience of the Nigerian civil war. In the poem, the poet described a ‘bomb’ as a weapon of mass destruction in a war situation. In the first stanza of the poem (poem 3), the poet describes the bomb as:

Òm̄er̄e dik̄e	(One who impacts on the strong
Ògbu ñim̄kpa	Killer of the full-grown man
E lel̄ia nwa it̄e, ya āgb̄onyūo ōk̄u	A neglected small pot that overflows to quench a fire
An̄u kp̄orō nk̄u n̄a-eju on̄u	Dry meat that fills the mouth

Ògbu nnù ọrịà

Killer of all diseases

(Madubuike in Emenanjo (ed.), N.d., p. 39)

In the introductory verse to the poem “Ogbuniigwe” (poem 3), the poet describes the role of bombs as a weapon of war during the Nigerian civil war. Just like Ubesie’s “Ụgbọ Elu Ọgụ”, poem 2, the theme of the above poem 3 is war and its devastating effects. Another poet in the first decade, who wrote on the theme of war, is J. C. Maduekwe. In his poem ‘Agha’ in *Nkà Okwu* (1979) (Poem 4), the poet describes war as a loving messenger of death and as such is responsible for so many deaths on earth. The message of his poem was so clear in his first stanza, where the poet says:

Agha dị nkọ n’ọrụ, ọ bụ na ọ dị egwù!
Ọnwụ dị egwù, ọ bụ nā ọ dị mkpà n’ùwa.
Agha bụ nwa ọnwụ nwèrè ọ hùrù n’anya,
Ya mèrè o jiri lechaa ya ānyā gùọ yā:
Ọje ngwa ñgwā; ọri mgbè ọ dị ọkụ,
Ògbu na ndù; ọgbu n’ìmìrikiti!
Ò dìghī aha ọtùto ọnwụ na-agùghì agha!

(Maduekwe 1979, p. 35)

(When war is efficient in its works, it is because it is astonishing,
If death becomes a wonder, it means that it is important in the world
War is the beloved son of death that he loves,
That is why, after looking at him, he named him:
He that moves very fast; the one that eats when it is still hot,
A killer, the one that kills en masse!
There is no praise name death did not give to war!)

In poem four above, the poet makes it very clear that nothing good has ever come out of war. According to Maduekwe, the only thing that war offers is destruction and death. Considering the above instances of poems that emerged in the first decade of Igbo written poetry, it is apparent that some of the poems from that period were written years before Igbo written poetry debuted in 1975 with the publication of *Akpa Uche*. This assertion is justified by the fact that, just like in the case of the few poems discussed above, the content of some of the poems in *Akpa Uche* shows that the poets wrote them before they got the chance to publish them.

In 1971, Nwoga and Egudu collected and published some Igbo folksongs, titled *Poetic Heritage*. The text then became the first Igbo oral poetry in print, though it was written in English. As a result, *Poetic Heritage* cannot be considered the earliest written Igbo poetry. F.C. Ogbalu, like Egudu and Nwoga, made a collection of several oral Igbo poems, which he published in 1974 as *Igbo Poems and Songs*, later republished as *Mbem na Egwu Igbo*, cast in the English language, for which they are not considered in this study as written Igbo poetry.

3.2.1. The Proper Birth and First Decade of Written Igbo Poetry (1975-1985)

In 1973, the Oxford University Press organised a literary competition for works written in Nigerian indigenous languages. This platform, provided by Oxford University Press, became the preparatory ground for the birth of written Igbo poetry (Ikwubuzo, 2015) as some Igbo writers, who have been documenting their poetic expressions over the years, seized the opportunity to showcase their works. Igbo writers, such as J. C. Obienyem, C. W. Ajaegbu, L. Amasike, I. O. Iroha, and a few others, submitted their poems for this contest. After the competition, R. M. Ekechukwu, who at that time was a teacher at Uli High School, Ihiala, selected some of these poems and also called on other prominent Igbo writers, whom their works have gained popularity among the Igbo at that time (J. C. Maduekwe, T. Ubesie, T. Nzeako and a few others), to submit their poems for onward publication in an anthology, which he was organising. Ekechukwu was burdened by the state of written Igbo poetry, which had not been given any attention at that time, hence the need to lay a foundation for the development of written Igbo poetry. In the words of Ekechukwu (1975) in which he indicates the aim for his pioneer work, he states:

... We are presenting this work to the public not as an achievement but as a beginning, not as an authority but

as a stimulus, not as the best but as a prototype which artists will look upon to fashion the best (p.viii).

Ekechukwu had the collections, edited them in 1974, and they were finally published as an anthology in 1975 by the same Oxford University Press, titled *Akpa Uche*. The anthology *Akpa Uche* became the first written Igbo poetic work, indigenous to the Igbo, chronicling the varied experiences and situations of the Igbo and the Igbo world. The content of *Akpa Uche* truly reflects the sociological life of the Igbo among others, as opposed to Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo, which was published for Christian religious purposes, and only mirrors the new religious sensibility of the Igbo society. Thirteen Igbo poets contributed poems in *Akpa Uche*. They are K. Amasike, J.U.T. Nzeako, J.C. Obienyem, C.W. Ajaegbu, J.C. Maduekwe, I.E. Akoma, I.O. Iroha, T.U. Ubesie, N.C. Olebara, C. Emenike, M.C. Ogunjiofor, E. Egbuchulem, and R.M. Ekechukwu, who is also the editor.

Akpa Uche was indeed what Igbo scholarship needed in contemporary poetry at that time. Just like Ugonna (1982) observed, the anthology, *Akpa Uche*, deals with subjects that span human experience, including places and things, nature and phenomena, philosophy, politics and society, and elegies, and these issues are expressed in the anthology in the most satisfying Igbo poetic diction. As expected, *Akpa Uche* was greeted with great enthusiasm by the Igbo, as it was the first of its kind. *Akpa Uche* became the centre of poetic discourse and teaching in several schools, where the study of Igbo poetry began with transcribed oral texts. Shortly after the publication of *Akpa Uche*, Emmanuel Obike published his *Eke-Une*, which he (Obike) personally described as 'an original Igbo Ballad'. Unfortunately, *Eke-Une* bears no date of publication, but according to Ugonna (1982), it was published shortly

after *Akpa Uche*. Since *Eke-Une* was published shortly after *Akpa Uche*, it may have been published in 1976.

For two years, *Akpa Uche* and *Eke-Une* dominated the Igbo poetic scene, and their acceptance and influence grew and travelled beyond Igbo interstate borders. To date, *Akpa Uche* has remained one of the best Igbo poetic anthologies. This was why, after its first publication in 1975 by Oxford University Press, it sold in large numbers. It was later republished by University Press Limited (formerly Oxford University Press) in 1979. Since 1979, *Akpa Uche* has been reprinted many times.

In 1977, two years after the publication of *Akpa Uche* and *Eke-Une*, L. O. Ogugua published his poetic text, titled *Obiageli*. Just like *Eke-Une*, *Obiageli* Ogugua does not bear any date of publication. However, Ikwubuzo in a comment (2020) reveals that he has Professor Ugonna's personal copy of *Obiageli*, which Ugonna wrote in 1977 as the date he got his copy of Ogugua's *Obiageli*. Although this might not be the exact publication date, it suggests that *Obiageli* was published in or before 1977. The efforts to confirm the exact date of publication from the publishing company (University Publishing Company, Onitsha) during this study proved abortive. In 1978, F. C. Ogbalu (founder of the Society for Promoting Igbo Language and Culture (S.P.I.L.C.)) was passionately working to raise the status of the Igbo language. He encouraged the teaching of the Igbo language at the primary and secondary levels of education. Noticing the inability of Igbo poets to consolidate on the precedent established by *Akpa Uche*, *Eke-Une*, and *Obiageli*, he felt the need to develop further this poetic genre of written Igbo literature and published his second collection of Igbo chants and folksongs, *Mbem na Egwu Igbo*, in 1978, which he wrote in the Igbo language. However, Ogbalu's work does not count as written Igbo poetry, as he did not create the poems, as we noted earlier. Nonetheless, his effort was

a significant contribution to the highly needed collection and documentation of oral Igbo poetry.

Ogbalu's intention was basically to provide more materials for the study of the Igbo language, literature, and culture. We recall that it was F. C. Ogbalu who worked tirelessly to establish the first Igbo Language and Culture Department at Alvan Ikoku College of Education, Owerri, in 1974. Anizoba (2013) opines that Ogbalu's efforts also led to the development of the Igbo syllabus for G.C.E. examinations in 1976. Ogbalu's efforts also led to the establishment of Igbo Language Departments at Colleges of Education, such as the College of Education, Awka, in 1978, and the College of Education, Okene, in the same year. Ogbalu did not stop there; he also fought for the establishment of the Department of Linguistics and Igbo Language at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, in 1980, and the Department of Igbo at the Colleges of Education, both Eha-Amufu and Nsugbe, in 1981.

After the establishment of Igbo Departments in the above-listed tertiary institutions, one of the challenges that faced the study of Igbo Language and Literature (poetry inclusive) at these institutions was the unavailability of literary texts for literary study and analysis. *Akpa Uche*, *Eke-Une*, and *Obiageli*, being the only Igbo poetic texts available at the time, were used in the study of Igbo poetry across all secondary schools and tertiary institutions where Igbo language and literature were taught. After three years of the dominance of these three poetic texts, the Igbo literary lovers were already getting bored with repeatedly using the same texts. Nolue Emenanjo reached out to Igbo writers to submit poems for another anthology he was compiling at the time. He selected good poems from the pool of entries made, edited them, and published them with the title *Utara Nti*. The text *Utara Nti* then became the second anthology of modern Igbo poetic verse.

Utara Nti bears no date of publication, and efforts in this study to confirm the date of its publication from the publishers (Evans Brothers) proved abortive. However, I. U. Nwadike in his *Akɔnauche* (2006, p. 266) put the date of publication of *Utara Nti* as 1979. Again, in an oral interview session with J. C. Maduekwe in 2018, Maduekwe corroborated Nwadike's position (as regards the year of publication of *Utara Nti*) by stating that it was after he submitted some poems to Emenanjo for publication in *Utara Nti* that his own collection of Igbo poems, *Nkà Okwu* (1979), got published by Longman Nigeria. This suggests that *Utara Nti* was the fourth written Igbo poetic text, published after *Akpa Uche*, *Eke Une*, and *Obiageli*, while Maduekwe's *Nkà Okwu* was the fifth.

Subsequent Igbo poetic works that followed the publication of Maduekwe's *Nkà Okwu* in 1979 included *Mbem Igbo* by Obienyem, also published in 1979 (Nwadike, 2002). This means that three Igbo poetic texts were published in 1979, which include *Utara Nti*, *Nkà Okwu*, and *Mbem Igbo*. Emenanjo again hit the Igbo poetic scene with another anthology, which he edited and titled *Nkemakolam*. Like his *Utara Nti*, this second anthology also does not bear a date of publication, but Ogbuagu (2010) lists the publication date of *Nkemakolam* as 1980. Achebe and Udechukwu edited and published *Aka Weta* in 1982.

In 1982, J.C. Maduekwe also published his second poetry collection, *Okiri 1*, after his earlier collection, *Nkà Okwu*, published in 1979. *Okiri 1*, which was basically children's poetry with pictorials and was also published by Longman Nigeria, won Maduekwe his first prize in Igbo children's poetry at the literary contest in the three major languages in Nigeria, held at the University of Ile-Ife. J.N. Onwuchekwa published his *Akpaala Okwu* in 1983, and in 1984, J.A. Umeh published *Okponku Abu*. Emenanjo published another poetic text, *Ogwumagala*, in

1984. In 1985, two Igbo poetic texts: Achalonu's *Abụ Ụmụ Priamari* and I. Ogu's *Ụka Ndu* were published.

It can be said that among the first generation of Igbo poets, the renowned Igbo linguist, Nolue Emenanjo, stands out. His contributions towards the growth, sustenance, and development of written Igbo poetry in the first decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry are noted mainly in the number of poetic works he edited and also contributed to. He edited three Igbo sound anthologies, *Utara Nti*, *Nkemakolam*, and *Ogwumagala*, and also contributed to them. The other poet worthy of mention is J.C. Maduekwe, who can be seen as the most prominent poet of this decade, given his contributions to the development of written Igbo poetry in this first decade. Maduekwe contributed eleven poems in *Akpa Uche*, seven poems in *Utara Nti* and authored two poetic texts, *Nkà Okwu* and *Okiri 1*. *Okiri 1* won him first prize for the best children's poetry in Igbo, while his *Nkà Okwu* received widespread acceptance and accolades from the Igbo populace.

Table 4: List of Igbo Poetic Texts published in the First Decade from 1975-1985

S/N	BOOK TITLE	NAME OF POET	YEAR OF PUBLICATION	PUBLISHERS
1	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	R.M. Ekechukwu (Ed)	1975	University Press
2	<i>Eke Une</i>	E. Obike	N.D	University Pub. Company
3	<i>Obiageli</i>	L.O. Ogugua	N.D	University Pub
4	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N. Emenanjo (Ed)	N.D	Evans Brothers
5	<i>Nkà Okwu</i>	J.C. Maduekwe	1979	Lantern
6	<i>Mbem Igbo</i>	J.C. Obienyem	1979	University Pub.
7	<i>Nkemakolam</i>	N. Emenanjo (Ed)	1980	Heinemann
8	<i>Aka Weta</i>	C. Achebe & Udechukwu (Eds)	1982	Okike
9	<i>Okiri 1</i>	J.C. Maduekwe	1982	Longman
10	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	J.N. Onwuchekwa	1983	Evans Brothers
11	<i>Okponku Abu</i>	J.A. Umeh	1984	Ceta
12	<i>Ogwumagala</i>	N. Emenanjo(Ed.)	1984	University Press
13	<i>Abu Umụ Prajmarị</i>	C.O. Acholonu	1985	University Press
14	<i>Uka Ndu</i>	I. Ogu	1985	University Pub.

To date, *Akpa Uche* has remained the most criticised, most read, and most popular Igbo poetic text in the world. The poetic collections in them remain evergreen, and the salient themes the poems project are still relevant to date. The level of appreciation *Akpa Uche* has received is occasioned by the quality of the poems and the quality of the poets who contributed to it. The study appreciates the pioneering efforts of R.M. Ekechukwu, who laid a solid foundation for written Igbo poetry, which other contemporary Igbo poets have now built upon.

Table 5: Analysis of the Number of Published Texts on Written Igbo Poetry in the First Decade (1975-1985)

Year	Frequency (No. of published works)
1975	1
1976	1
1977	1
1978	0
1979	3
1980	1
1981	0
1982	2
1983	1
1984	2
1985	2
<i>Total</i>	14

Fig 1: Bar Chart Showing the Frequency of Written Igbo Poetry Texts Published in the First Decade

Figure 1 above is a bar chart showing the number of written Igbo poetry publications and their corresponding values on the primary and secondary axes, respectively, during the first decade (1975-1985). The chart reveals that only one

poetic text was published in 1975, presumably 1 in 1976 and another 1 in 1977. The table shows that none was published in 1978. The chart further shows that three poetic texts were published in 1979, 1 in 1980, and none in 1981. There were two publications of written Igbo poetry texts in 1982, and 1 was published in 1983. 2 poetic texts were published in 1984, and another 2 in 1985.

Myriads of subjects formed the focus of the poems written in the first decade. Some of the poets who contributed during the period mirror their experiences during the Nigerian civil war, as discussed earlier. Some of the poems can also be described, in the words of Ikwubuzo (2009), as political protest poems. This is because many of the poets who wrote in this first decade used the instrumentality of art to criticise the racism and colonialism occurring in Africa at the time (Ikwubuzo, 2009). Although Nigeria was already an independent state when Igbo poetry debuted, modern Igbo poets, through their works, showed solidarity with other African countries still under the powerful grip of colonial masters. For instance, Nnamdi Olebara's two poems, "Iwe di m n'obi" and "Afrika Enwerela Onwe Ya" in *Akpa Uche*, Obienyem's "Aga m Egbu Ochu" and "Afrika Ndidi" in *Utara Nti*, and Maduekwe's "Nne Anyi Afrika" in *Nka Okwu* are all poems that decry the degradation of Africans by the colonial masters. Another example of poems written in the first decade that is also critical of colonial rule in Africa, according to Ikwubuzo (2009), is Oguguo's poem "The Gara Agaala" in *Obiageli*. The likes of African countries such as South Africa, Rhodesia (now Zimbabwe), and Mozambique that were identified by the first decade of modern Igbo poets to be suffering in the hands of colonial masters, as illustrated by the second stanza of Nnamdi Olebara's poem, "Afrika Enwerela Onwe Ya" (Africa is free) (Poem 5) in *Akpa Uche*:

Ma Afrìkà, olee anụrị gị?
 Òlee isi i nwerela ònwe gị?
 Ebe ọtụtụ ụmụ Afrìkà bụ ọbịa n'àlà ha
 Ebe a chụpụrụ ụmụ nnē gị n'ala oma ha
 Chụga hā ebe àla kpòrò nku
 Afrìkà, ọbịa n'àlà ya
 Gèe ntị na *South Afrìkà*, *Zimbabwe* na *Mozambique*
 Nụ olu ụmụ nnē
 Kà iherē onwe gị mee gị
 Tufia! Afrìka, òdo.

(Olebara in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 66)

(But Africa, where is your happiness?
 What is the essence of your independence?
 When a lot of Africans are strangers in their land
 Where many of your brothers are driven out of their good lands
 Chased to a place where the land is dry
 Africa, a stranger in its land
 Listen to South Africa, Zimbabwe, and Mozambique
 Listen to the voice of siblings
 Be ashamed of yourself
*Tufia!*ⁱ Africa, sorry.)

The above stanza confirms our position that some of the poems of the first decade captured the colonial experience of some African nations as well as the problems of ethnicity and racism. This was why Ikwubuzo (2009) regards poets like Olebara and Oguguo as revolutionaries who used their poems as weapons to canvass for social and political change in Africa.

3.2.2 Second Decade of Written Igbo Poetry (1986-1995)

At the end of the first decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry, it was evident that more and more people were encouraged to write poetry. The additions recorded after *Akpa Uche* stirred up interest among other individuals, who wanted to contribute their quota to the growth of written Igbo poetry, hence the continued growth of written Igbo poetry in terms of extant works. The first individual whose work emerged in the second decade was A. K. Obierozie, who published his work *Ekpe Nna* in 1986. The poems contained in this text mirror the sociocultural life of the

Igbo. Two years later, he became a medical doctor. A. B. Chukuezi, who published the first written Igbo drama text, *Udo ka Mma*, published his first Igbo poetic text, *Akọ Bụ Ndu*, in 1988. A year after the publication of *Akọ Bụ Ndu*, Goddy Onyekaonwu published *Uche bụ Afa* in 1989. Later that same year, Ezeuko and Anowai published their Igbo poetic text titled *Echiche*. Four Igbo poetic texts that were published in 1990 are Uba-Mgbemena's *Echiche*, Echebima's *Abụ Ekele Dike*, Nwadike's *Echiche Miri Emi*, an anthology, *Nri Uche*, edited by Nwadike.

After the publication of these poetic works, no other Igbo poetic work was published until 1992, when Inno Uzoma Nwadike again published *Mbido Abụ*, while Ikwubuzo, Ogbulogo, and Okoro's *Omenkà* became the last poetic text in this decade.

Table 6: List of Poetic Texts that were Published in the Second Decade from 1986-1995

S/N	BOOK TITLE	NAME OF POET	YEAR	PUBLISHERS
1	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	A.K. Obierozie	1986	Pacific Publishers
2	<i>Akọ Bụ Ndu</i>	A.B. Chukuezi	1988	Longman
3	<i>Uche Bụ Afa</i>	G. O. Onyekaonwu	1989	University Press
4	<i>Echiche</i>	Ezeuko & Anowai	1989	Etukokwu
5	<i>Echiche Miri Emi</i>	I.U. Nwadike	1990	Kawurit & Mirilla
6	<i>Echiche</i>	A. Uba-Mgbemena	1990	Macmillan
7	<i>Abụ Ekele Dike</i>	G.N. Echebima	1990	Heinemann
8	<i>Nri Uche</i>	I.U. Nwadike (Ed.)	1990	Totan
9	<i>Mbido Abụ</i>	I.U. Nwadike	1992	Pacific Publishers
10	<i>Omenkà</i>	Ikwubuzo, Ogbulogo & Okoro	1992	Logomedia

From the above table, it has become clear that I.U. Nwadike emerged as the leading poet in this decade. As shown in the table, Nwadike published three poetic texts during this period. It is also important to add at this juncture that although, in quantity, the poetic texts published in this decade were not as many as those that appeared in the first decade, the quality of the poems remained very high in terms of

production, the subject matter addressed, the diction employed, and their formal elements.

Table 7: Analysis of the Number of Published Texts on Written Igbo Poetry in the Second Decade (1986-1995)

Year	Frequency (No. of published works)
1986	1
1987	0
1988	1
1989	2
1990	4
1991	0
1992	2
1993	0
1994	0
1995	0
<i>Total</i>	10

Fig. 2: Bar Chart Showing the Frequency of Written Igbo Poetry Texts Published in the Second Decade (1986-1995).

Figure 2 above is a bar chart showing the number of written Igbo poetry publications and their corresponding values on the primary and secondary axes, respectively,

during the second decade (1986-1995). The chart reveals that only one poetic text was published in 1986. None was published in 1987, while 1, 2, and 4 written Igbo poetry texts were published in 1988, 1989, and 1990, respectively. Also, no written Igbo poetry text was published in 1991, while two texts were published in 1992. No publication was recorded in 1993, 1994, or 1995.

With respect to the central theme that dominated the Igbo poetic scene in the second decade, the researcher found that the themes of the poems from the second decade, even into the fourth decade, overlap. This will be discussed in more detail in the next chapter, when we shall examine the predominant themes in written Igbo poetry during the decades under study.

3.2.3 Third Decade of Written Igbo Poetry (1996-2005)

Written Igbo poetry made significant progress in this decade in terms of the quantity of published poetic texts. The number of poetic texts published in this decade is the highest among the two previous decades discussed above. A total of nineteen poetic texts were published in this decade.

Obike, Onuegbu, and Nnabuihe sparked a poetic publication boom in this decade by editing and publishing *Ekenegwuregwu* in 1996. After the publication of *Ekenegwuregwu*, Chinedu Ofomata broke into the Igbo poetic scene with his first Igbo poetic text, *O di m n'Obi*, which was published by his own publishing company, Format Publishers, in 1997. Another Igbo poetic text published in 1999 is *Nnunu Mgbama* by O. Agu, while in 2000 Okechukwu Ihejirika published *Aka Tijie*. In 2001, seven written Igbo poetic texts were added to the list. They are such works as *Echiche M*, *Echezola*, and *Okwu Ndu*, all by Chinedum Ofomata; *Olisa Amaka* by Obakora;

Nsibiri by Onyeji; *Oku Nwanne na Utara Nti Ndi Ozọ* by Ifejika; and *Ako na Uche* by Godson Echebima.

Furthermore, in 2003, Nkechinyere Okediadi published her *Ije Uwa*, while Njelita published *Amandianaeze*. Following these publications, Chinedu Ofomata added another poetic text, *Arima*, in 2004. Agwuna, S., also published *Echiche Amamihe* in 2004. In 2005, Christian Anozie published *Uche bu Akpa*. The same year, Iwu Ikwubuzo, Chukwunke Okoro, and Ejike Eze published *Okpokwobara*, while R.N. Ekegbo published *Uwa Onye na Chi Ya*.

Table 8: List of Poetic Texts that were Published in the Third Decade from 1996-2005

S/N	BOOK TITLE	NAME OF POET	YEAR	PUBLISHER S
1	<i>Ekenegwuregwu</i>	Emmanuel Obike, Onuegbu & Chigozie, B. Nnabuihe	1996	Marie
2	<i>O Di M n'Obi</i>	Chinedu E. Ofomata	1997	Format
3	<i>Echiche M</i>	Chinedu E. Ofomata	1999	Format
4	<i>Nnunu Mgbama</i>	O. A. Agu	1999	Lecta
5	<i>Aka Tijie</i>	Okechukwu C. Ihejirika	2000	Onibonje
6	<i>Olisa Amaka</i>	E. K. Obakora	2001	Claverianum
7	<i>Okwu Ndu</i>	Chinedu E. Ofomata	2001	Format
8	<i>Echezola</i>	Chinedu E. Ofomata	2001	Format
9	<i>Nsibiri</i>	C. Onyeji	2001	Innsang
10	<i>Oku Nwanne na Utara Nti ndi ozọ</i>	D. C. Ifejika	2001	Snaap
11	<i>Ako na Uche</i>	Godson N. Echebima	2001	Evans
12	<i>Echiche M</i>	Chinedu E. Ofomata	2001	Format
13	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	Nkechinyere Okediadi	2003	Fulladu
14	<i>Amandianaeze</i>	O. Njelita	2003	Format
15	<i>Arima</i>	C. Ofomata	2004	Format
16	<i>Echiche Amamihe</i>	S.O. Agwuna	2004	Linal
17	<i>Uche Bu Akpa</i>	Christian C. Anozie	2005	Format
18	<i>Okpokwobara</i>	Ikwubuzo, Okoro, & Eze	2005	Radil
19	<i>Uwa Onye na Chi Ya</i>	R.N. Ekegbo	2005	Mabcom Systems

From the above table (8), it is evident that Chinedum Ofomata emerged as the leading poet in this decade, going by the number of poetic texts he published and also the number of texts that were published in his company.

Table 9: Analysis of the Number of Published Texts of Written Igbo Poetry in the Third Decade (1996-2005)

Year	Frequency (No. of published works)
1996	1
1997	1
1998	0
1999	3
2000	0
2001	7
2002	0
2003	2
2004	2
2005	3
<i>Total</i>	19

Fig. 3: Bar chart showing the frequency of Written Igbo poetry texts published in the third decade (1996-2005)

Figure 3 above is a bar chart showing the number of written Igbo poetry publications and their corresponding values on the primary and secondary axes, respectively, during the third decade (1996-2005). The chart reveals that only one written Igbo poetry text was published in 1996 and 1 in 1997. None was published in 1998. The chart further shows that in 1999, 3 written poetry Igbo texts were published, and none were published in 2000. 2001 witnessed the publication of 7 written Igbo poetry texts, while none were recorded in 2002. In 2003, 2004, and 2005, 2, 2, and 3 written Igbo poetry texts were published, respectively.

3.2.4 Fourth Decade of Written Igbo Poetry (2006-2015)

Written Igbo poetry began to receive more serious attention in this decade than in the preceding ones. However, in terms of the number of published poetic texts, the decade witnessed an unexpected decline. One would imagine that, due to earlier efforts to develop written Igbo poetry, the decade should have seen an increase in the number of extant works published, but the reverse was the case. Inno Uzoma Nwadike opened the poetic door in this fourth decade by editing and publishing an anthology titled *Akọnauche* (2006). Chinedu Ofomata followed suit with the publication of *Ụlari* also in 2006. In 2007, Chinedum Ofomata published yet another Igbo poetic text, *Obi Ocha Ụmụaka*, and also *Ibisi* in 2008. Enyinnaya Ikeokwu and May Onyejekwe published *Uche bụ Ahịa* 2009. Ogochukwu Ifeka published *Ọ Natara Chi* also in 2009, while Chinedu Ofomata published *Ụdara Ọma* in 2013. N.R. Ezejesi published *Abu Ụtọ* 2015, while N.N. Ijeoma's work *Olu Ụmụnwaanyi Mba Afirika* also came out in 2015.

Table 10: List of Poetic Texts that Were Published in the Fourth Decade from 2006-2015

S/N	BOOK TITLE	NAME OF POET	YEAR	PUBLISHERS
1	<i>Akọnauche</i>	I.U. Nwadike	2006	Pacific
2	<i>Ụlarị</i>	C. Ofomata	2006	Format
3	<i>Obi Ocha Ụmụaka</i>	C. Ofomata	2007	Format
4	<i>Ibisi</i>	C. Ofomata	2008	Format
5	<i>Uche bụ Ahịa</i>	E.S. Ikeokwu & M.C. Onyejekwe	2009	Format
6	<i>Ọ Natara Chi</i>	O. Ifeka	2009	Format
7	<i>Ụdara Oma</i>	C. Ofomata	2013	Format
8	<i>Olu Ụmụnwaanyi Mba Afrika</i>	N.I. Nwaogu	2015	Pacific
9	<i>Abụ Ụtọ</i>	N.R. Ezejesi	2015	Pacific

In this decade, Chinedum Ofomata again takes the front row in the publication of Igbo poetic texts. Apart from Ofomata's publications of personal poetic texts, he has also used his publishing company to promote the course of written Igbo poetry in a way that no other person in Igbo literary studies has done. This assertion is evident from the number of poetic texts published by Ofomata's publishing company, Format Publishers, which published five works out of the eight poetic texts published in this decade and eight texts in the preceding third decade. This brings the total number of poetic texts published by Format publishers in the decades under study to fifteen.

Table 11: Analysis of the Number of Published Texts on Written Igbo Poetry in the Fourth Decade (2006-2015)

Year	Frequency (No. of published works)
2006	2
2007	1
2008	1
2009	2
2010	0
2011	0
2012	0
2013	1
2014	0

2015	2
Total	9

Fig. 4: Bar Chart Showing the Frequency of Written Igbo Poetry Texts Published in the Fourth Decade (2006-2015)

Figure 4 above is a bar chart showing the number of written Igbo publications and their corresponding values on the primary and secondary axes, respectively, during the fourth decade (2006-2015). The chart reveals that 2 in 2006, 1 in 2007, 1 in 2008, and 2 in 2009 of written Igbo poetry texts were published. No written Igbo poetry text was published between 2010 and 2012. One text was published in 2013, while 2 texts were published in 2015.

3.3 The State of Study of Written Igbo Poetry in the Four Decades (1975-2015)

The present study agrees with Ikwubuzo (2007), who argues that when discussing the development of written Igbo poetry, we should not only measure its

growth by the number of existing works but also consider how its study has fared. Based on this, it can be said that the study of written Igbo poetry has progressed over the years. It is gratifying to note that Igbo poetry is studied at both the secondary and tertiary levels of education in Nigeria today. At the secondary level of education, it was observed that in many secondary schools where Igbo literature is taught, the study of written Igbo poetry also goes on. At the tertiary level of education, written Igbo poetry is also taught in different colleges of education and universities in Nigeria, where Igbo literature is studied today. Many people now write research projects at the B.A., M.A., and Ph.D levels. This is a feat that proves that one of Ugonna's (1982) questions, which sought to know how much Igbo poetry has grown, is now addressed. The present study also attests to the considerable growth of written Igbo poetry.

However, when comparing written Igbo poetry with the prose and drama genres in terms of research on various issues, we can say that the pace of development in the study of written Igbo poetry remains slow. This may be due to the nature of poetry, which Ikwubuzo (2007) describes as a complex subject. In this first decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry, for instance, no study was carried out on any aspect of written Igbo poetry at all levels of academic research in Nigeria, even though the subject was being taught in institutions of learning. However, all the poems published in the first decade of Igbo written poetry contributed to the growth of Igbo written poetry. It was based on the quantity and quality of Igbo poetic texts published during the decade and on the available mimeographs, and on the study of the genre in institutions of higher learning, on which Ugonna (1982) hinged his appraisal, stating that written Igbo poetry has grown.

In the second decade, just like in the first decade, the study of written Igbo poetry started receiving peripheral attention. Among the four federal institutions of learning where the researcher got his empirical data (University of Lagos, University of Ibadan, University of Nigeria, and Nnamdi Azikiwe University), only the University of Lagos recorded a few B.A. projects that focus on written Igbo poetry in the second decade under study (1986-1995). The B.A. works that were carried out at the University of Lagos include O. Azubuike's (1990) "Ntule Akọ Bụ Ndụ A.B. Chukuezi", C.B. Nnabuihe's (1990) "Omenala n'Abụ Eke Une", and M.A. Ahusim's (1995) "Nnyocha *Echiche*". Also, no B.A. project on written Igbo poetry was recorded at the University of Ibadan. Apart from these B.A. projects, no M.A. or Ph.D. studies were recorded at these two institutions of learning (University of Lagos and University of Ibadan). Due to the challenge of a harmonised database for documenting research projects in Nigeria, which affects the University of Nsukka and Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, the researcher focused only on Ph.D. work carried out at these institutions. The researcher found that, in the second decade, as in the University of Lagos and the University of Ibadan, no Ph.D. studies were recorded at the two institutions of learning. However, the study of written Igbo poetry in this decade was restricted mainly to classroom textual analysis. In contrast, very few empirical studies were published in journals on written Igbo poetry at this time.

In the third decade (1996-2005), the study of written Igbo poetry experienced greater growth than in the preceding decades discussed above. It was observed that the study of written Igbo poetry improved more in higher institutions of learning, as well as in terms of publications of articles on the subject. Some progress was recorded in the study of written Igbo poetry at the undergraduate level at the University of Lagos, where about four B.A. research projects were recorded. The studies include

R.C. Matthew's (1996). "Nnyocha Ndina na Odiđi *Omenka*", N.B. Uzoka's (1999) "Ntule Isiokwu Dịgasị n' *Utara Nti*", A.U. Izuorah's (1999) "Usoo Nkuzi na Nsoḡbu dī n' Ikuzi Abū na Siniḡ Sekḡndiri n' Iḡbado Ukwu na *Mbem Akwamozu* nke Sam Uzochukwu na *Utara Nti* nke Mazi Nwanoluo Emenanjo", C.B. Anyaeche's (2000) "Ntulekorita Akanka *Echiche* Uba-Mgbemena na *Ako Bu Ndu* Anaelechi, B. Chukuezi", G.C.E. Amadikwa's (2004) "Nnyocha Akanka ndi Odee Mazi J.C. Maduekwe na *Nka Okwu* na Oruruo, L. Oguguo n' *Obiageli*". Apart from these B.A. projects, no M.A. or Ph.D. studies on written Igbo poetry were recorded at the University of Lagos in this decade. No B.A., M.A, or PhD study on written Igbo poetry was recorded at the University of Ibadan. As for the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, and Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, no Ph.D. on written Igbo poetry was also recorded in this third decade (1996-2005).

Written Igbo poetry received more serious academic attention in the fourth decade (2006-2015) than in the preceding decades. This is because the study of written Igbo poetry improved in various higher institutions of learning and in published papers. At the University of Lagos, five B.A. projects and two M.A. projects on issues in written Igbo poetry were carried out in this decade. The B.A. projects include V.N. Madu's (2006) "Ntule *Mbem Igbo* nke Chukwuemeka Obienyem", M.M. Okoye's (2007) "Nnyocha Akwukwo Abū *Okpokoobara* nke si n'Aka Chuwuneki Okoro, Iwu Ikwubuzo na Ejike Eze", G.O. Onyeanusi's (2008) "Ntule Abū Otito na Abū İkpè n' *Echiche*", O.M. Okorie-Uka's (2012) "Ntule Asusu Nka n' *Ako na Uche*", I.F. Joseph's (2014). "Nnyocha Akwukwo Abū *E Chezola*". The two M.A. dissertations on written Igbo poetry recorded at the University of Lagos include Nwakaego (2007). "A Thematic Study of L.C. Okoro's Poems" and I.F. Ucheji's (2008) "Literary Appraisal of *Omenka*". Upon completion, the present study

will be the first Ph.D. research on written Igbo poetry submitted to the Department of Linguistics, African and Asian Studies, University of Lagos. The University of Ibadan has yet to conduct any study on written Igbo poetry at any level (B.A., M.A., and Ph.D.) of higher academic research.

It was in the fourth decade that the first two Ph.D. theses on written Igbo poetry were submitted to the Department of Igbo, African and Asian Studies, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. J.O. Ogbuagu's (2010) "Nnamdi Olebara: A Weeping Poet, a Prophet and a Social Critic" and N.M. Nnyigide's (2015) "Abụ Ekerechi Ederede Igbo: Nnyocha Site n'Atùtù Kegburugburu". No PhD thesis was recorded at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, in this decade. The researcher found that studies on poetry at the University of Nigeria in this decade were limited to oral Igbo poetry only.

It is worth noting that, though not covered by this study, from 2016 onward the study of written Igbo poetry has continued to make steady progress, with more Ph.D. works added to the list. For instance, S.O. Agwuna submitted her Ph.D. thesis in 2016 titled, "Igbo Poets as Social Critics: Reflections on Selected Igbo Poems" at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, and in 2018, C.M. Akaeze completed the first Ph.D. thesis on written Igbo poetry at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, titled "Creative Dissidence and Revolutionary Temper in Selected Igbo Poems" as we reported earlier in this study. These new research works bring the total number of Ph.D. theses on written Igbo poetry to four so far.

3.4 An Assessment of the Growth of Written Igbo Poetry

Having discussed the developmental trajectory of written Igbo poetry from its oral state to its present written form, we can boldly say that written Igbo poetry has

grown in quantity. The table and chart below summarise our analysis of the visual representation of the developmental progression of written Igbo poetry. The table also gives information on the total number of extant texts of written Igbo poetry and their percentage change between 1975 and 2015. The aim is to show, visually, the summary of the data analysed earlier.

Table 12: Summary of Written Igbo Poetry Publications in the Decades Studied

Year	Total Number of Publications
1975-1985	14
1986-1995	10
1996-2005	19
2006-2015	9

Fig 5: Bar Chart Showing Decade-by-Decade Percentage Change of Total Written Igbo Text Publications

Figure 5 above is a bar chart showing the decade-by-decade change of total written Igbo text publications. The chart shows that the highest rise in the number of Igbo poetic text publications occurred in the third decade (1996-2000).

From the above chart (fig. 5), likewise, we conclude that, in terms of extant texts, written Igbo poetry has made significant and appreciable progress. However,

the above chart (fig. 5) also reveals that the significant progress in written Igbo poetry witnessed in the first three decades of its existence fell rapidly and unexpectedly in the second and fourth decades, indicating that written Igbo poetry is again being threatened. Factors responsible for the continued decline, and, by extension, the marred development of written Igbo poetry, are discussed below. On the flip side, the study of written Igbo poetry experienced considerable growth in the fourth decade, compared with the previous decades studied. This means there is renewed academic interest in the study of written Igbo poetry than ever before. This assertion is evident in the number of studies recorded in various institutions of learning and learned journals on issues that border on written Igbo poetry.

3.5 Factors that Affected the Development of Written Igbo Poetry

In 2007, a lecturer and poet, Iwu Ikwubuzo, at the University of Lagos, burdened by the state of Igbo written poetry, conducted research in which he discussed its state after three decades of existence. Ikwubuzo (2007) discussed factors that contributed to the growth of written Igbo poetry, many of which became evident in our assessment of the development of written Igbo poetry in this study. The three factors that were responsible for the growth of written Igbo poetry as seen in the three decades earlier discussed (1975-2005), according to Ikwubuzo (2007, pp. 52-53), include author-financed publishing, renewed interest in writing in Igbo by the lovers of the language, and the resolution of orthography controversy. While this study agrees with the position of Ikwubuzo (2007) as regards the factors that contributed to the growth of written Igbo poetry in the first three decades of its existence, it is observed that the author-financed publishing as a factor also adversely affected the development of written Igbo poetry as seen in the fourth decade. It is observed that

the publication of written Igbo poetry declined in the fourth decade, a situation which we will examine next.

Ikwubuzo (2015) discussed in detail factors that constituted early setbacks for the development of indigenous Nigerian (Igbo) literatures, of which Igbo poetry is one of the major genres. Some of the points Ikwubuzo (2015) identified to have constituted early setbacks for the development of written Igbo literature were: the orthography controversy, apathy towards Igbo language and dialectal variations, publishers' suspicion and confusion about the acceptable orthography, lack of incentive on the part of the government, the civil war episode, and lastly the language controversy. All these points Ikwubuzo discussed were in relation to the late emergence of Igbo literature, identifying, in particular, written Igbo poetry as a 'later developer'. However, one would expect that upon the emergence of written Igbo poetry, it would wax stronger and stronger in its growth. However, we observed a sharp decline in the number of extant works published in the fourth decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry. The factors responsible for this include:

3.5.1 Self-Publishing

Though Ikwubuzo (2007) identifies author-financed publishing (self-publishing) as one of the key factors that promoted the growth of written Igbo poetry, it also serves as one of the factors negatively affecting the development of written Igbo poetry. Ikwubuzo (2007) had earlier observed that, because big publishing companies like Longman, Evans Brothers, and a host of others lost interest in publishing Igbo works because there is no ready market to sell them, most Igbo writers (poets included) resorted to author-financed publishing to have their works published. While this was considered a good move as it largely contributed to the growth of written Igbo poetry, it also constituted a significant problem for the further

development of written Igbo poetry. This is because most self-published works do not undergo proper editing, and as a result, many are riddled with spelling errors, and some of the content is poor. This reduced the quality of most Igbo poems from the third to the fourth decades. This has further made people lose interest in reading Igbo poetic works.

3.5.2 Apathy towards the Igbo Language by the Igbo

The Igbo attitude towards their language has continued to pose a challenge to the development of Igbo literature in general, not just poetry. Ikwubuzo (2015) identifies the continuing language apathy as one of the significant factors that affected the development of Igbo literature. This position has not changed; it has grown worse, as the majority of the Igbo cannot read or write in Igbo. This has resulted in a decline in the reading of Igbo creative works by the Igbo generally. The result has been the abandonment of creative (poetic) writing in Igbo, since most Igbo people will not read it when it is published. Many of the Igbo prefer to read English poetry to Igbo poetry. This has resulted in low sales of published poetic works, leading people to lose interest in writing poetry, since they will incur a loss when they do.

Furthermore, this apathy shown towards the Igbo language by the Igbo generally has continued to degenerate. Today, most parents do not encourage their children to speak the Igbo language at home, and as such, their children lose interest in speaking, reading, or writing Igbo. This encourages people who would have naturally become poets to start writing poetry in English, as they cannot express their thoughts in Igbo. Again, the majority of Igbo parents, students, and the elite believe that Igbo is not marketable like degrees in other courses, hence the reluctance of candidates to apply for it or accept admission to an Igbo programme at tertiary institutions.

3.5.3 Government Policy on Education and Lack of Market, which Discourages Publishers from Accepting Manuscripts in Igbo

One of the significant factors that contributed to the development and sustenance of written Igbo poetry in the past decades was the Federal (Nigerian) Government Policy on Education of 1977 and 2004, as regulated by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (N.E.R.D.C.), which made knowledge of and a credit pass in one of the major Nigerian languages (Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba) a sine qua non to gaining admission into Nigerian tertiary institutions. This means that Igbo language and literature were offered not only at the primary and junior secondary school levels but also at the senior secondary school level. Professional examination bodies such as WAEC, NECO, and JAMB recommended literary texts that students were expected to read before taking such exams. This, in turn, promoted the sale of Igbo poetic texts and encouraged more people to venture into creative writing. This was evident in the growth of the number of extant texts in written Igbo poetry in the first - third centuries of its existence, as seen above. Unfortunately, the tables turned in the fourth decade, when the publication of Igbo poetic texts declined to an unprecedented level. One of the primary reasons for this decline was the 2013 National Policy on Education by N.E.R.D.C. While the 1977 and 2004 policies on education mandated secondary school students to offer one Nigerian language before they can gain admission into tertiary institutions in Nigeria, the 2013 policy on education banned students in science and commercial classes from offering Nigerian languages except for students in Arts classes (National Policy on Education, 2013: 11-14). The inclusion of trade subjects in Nigeria's new senior secondary curriculum (which is still used today) restricted the study of Nigerian

languages (including Igbo language and literature) to the humanities classes (Adejuyigbe & Adejuyigbe, 2016). According to this National Policy on Education (2013, p. 13), the compulsory subjects that cut across every field of study at the senior secondary level of education in Nigeria include: General Mathematics, English Language, Trade/Entrepreneurship subject, and Civic Education.

As earlier stated, the direct interpretation and implication of this new policy is that senior secondary school students in science and commercial classes are not allowed to choose any Nigerian language, even if they want to. Even in the humanities classes (arts classes), where students are supposed to offer one Nigerian language, Nigerian students are meant to choose between Nigerian languages and French. This is a significant problem not just for Igbo literature but also for the sustenance and growth of Nigerian indigenous languages in general. This also means that the major Examination Bodies that promote indigenous languages and literatures are not encouraged or supported, and, as such, writing Igbo poetry has become unprofitable, as there is no longer a ready market for the sale of published Igbo works. Consequently, publishers started rejecting manuscripts in Igbo (Ikwubuzo, 2015).

3.5.4. Low or Poor Enrolment of Students for Igbo Programme in Tertiary Institutions

The persistent low enrolment of students in Igbo programmes at various tertiary institutions in Nigeria is another factor that negatively affects the growth of written Igbo poetry. The 2013 Policy on Education in Nigeria, which was earlier discussed, can be said to be in the background of this poor student enrolment in Igbo programmes in tertiary institutions. For any student to enrol for any course at the tertiary level of education, such a student must have offered subjects related to that course at the senior secondary level of education. Since students in science and

commercial classes are no longer allowed to offer Igbo at the secondary school level, this has disqualified any of them who may want to enrol in the Igbo programme or even make it an elective course at the tertiary level of education. Again, as we have stated earlier, even students in the arts classes, where the Nigerian language is restricted, are forced to choose between Igbo (Nigerian) Languages and the French Language.

The researcher observed that, encouraged by the government's attitude towards Nigerian languages, parents, guardians, and teachers of students in the arts classes advise their wards to choose French over Igbo or any other Nigerian language. Most of these parents, guardians, and teachers who do this argue that the French language is more lucrative and internationally acceptable than the Igbo language. The implication of this is that arts students who may have had an interest in enrolling for Igbo language at the tertiary level of education are now disqualified from doing so, and since such students must have a credit pass in the Igbo language at the secondary level before they can be given admission to study Igbo at the tertiary level. As a result, most university administrations now allocate very few admission slots for Igbo programmes.

The point being made here is that if more students enrol at tertiary institutions to study Igbo language and literature, it will lead to an increase in the sale of published poetic texts, which would, in turn, encourage both poets and publishers to continue writing and publishing poetic works.

3.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, we have chronicled the developmental journey of Igbo poetry from its oral origins to its present state of contemporariness, taking into account all

factors that contributed to or marred its development. Some of the earlier attempts at writing the Igbo language, as we have seen in this chapter, were not developed to be used in the writing of Igbo poetry. It was the C.M.S. through the Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge (S.P.C.K.), which published *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Igbo* in 1934, that laid, with their religious poetry, the foundation of written Igbo poetry and thus introduced the Igbo to the Western style of poetic writing. However, the Igbo religious poetry was not considered Igbo, even though it was written in Igbo. This is because it was purely written for Christian religious edification and as such does not mirror the social, cultural, economic, etc., life of the Igbo. In 1975, the first modern Igbo poetic verse, *Akpa Uche*, was published. Since then, several Igbo poetic texts have been published. From the data provided in this chapter, a total of 14 poetic texts were published in the first decade of the existence of written Igbo poetry; 10 works were published in the second decade; 19 texts in the third decade, while eight were published in the fourth decade. Again, factors that contributed to the present precarious situation of written Igbo poetry are also discussed in this chapter. We shall then look at more of the topical issues addressed by Igbo poets in the decades under study in the next chapter.

CHAPTER FOUR

CONTENT OF WRITTEN IGBO POETRY I – CLASSIFICATION OF 1975-2015 WRITTEN IGBO POEMS AND POETS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter examines, over the decades under study, the content of selected Igbo poetry, paying particular attention to topical societal issues and other human concerns reflected in modern Igbo poetry.

As earlier stated in the introductory section of this study, the Igbo poet is a member of the society and, as such, through his art, contributes towards the development of the society. No poet writes in a vacuum. The poet mirrors the sociological life of the society in which they belong and, by doing so, projects images of different aspects of that society for readers to see. The poets do this to contribute their quota towards the development of society. This is why it is important to examine, in detail, key topical issues that predominate and underscore poetic thought over the past four decades of the existence of written Igbo poetry (1975-2015), using the mirror-image approach to the sociology of literature. The adoption of this theoretical framework (mirror-image approach) is best suited for this study, as it will bring to light various societal structures that modern Igbo poets mirror in their art.

There are many topical societal and other issues that modern Igbo poets have written on in the decades under study. Nevertheless, the present study limits its scope of discussion to cultural, political, economic, and ecological issues in which poetic thought has converged over the past four decades. The analysis done in this chapter is content-based, and the issues discussed are limited to the sixteen texts selected as samples for this study.

4.1 Classification Based on the Title of Written Igbo Poetry

The first thing that captures a reader's attention when he opens any Igbo poetic text (or poems in any other language) to read is the title of the poem. Every Igbo poem has a title (subject) that it discusses. The way the poet presents the title of his or her poem to the reader is very crucial. Four or more Igbo poets can write on the same title, but the thought and style of discussing the title would vary. The title of an Igbo poem can be a word, a phrase, or a clause, depending on how the poet wants to capture the thought of the poem for the reader to see at a glance. Two types of poetic titles appear in Igbo poetry: literary and non-literary.

4.1.1 The Literary Title Form

We define Igbo literary poetic titles here as figurative. These types of poetic titles do not reveal the poem's thought merely from its title. Here, the highly skilled poet begins his creative work by structuring the poem's title. By figuratively choosing his title, the poet forces the reader to read the poem over and over before the reader can link the title of the poem to the thought the poem projects. It is only after the reader has read the poem that the reader will understand why the poet chose the title for the poem.

Literary Igbo poetic titles are usually ironic and, in some cases, ambiguous. As such, the reader must decode the image the poet represents in the title through a critical reading of the poem. There are a few written Igbo poems whose titles can be said to be literary in nature, and they can be found among poems published in the first and second decades (1975–1995). Examples of written Igbo poems that have such titles include: I. E. Akoma's 'Ugbọ' (Vehicle) in *Akpa Uche* (p. 48), J.C. Maduekwe's

‘Ichoku’ (Parrot) in *Nkà Okwu* (p. 44), A.K. Obierozie’s ‘Akakpọ’ (Dwarf) in *Ekpe Nna* (p. 31), G.O. Onyekaonwu’s ‘Ọhĩa Ero’ (Forest of mushrooms) in *Uche bụ Ahĩa* (p. 14), C.U. Ogbulogo’s ‘Alụkwaghị m’ (Divorce) in *Omenkà* (pp. 22-23), I. Ikwubuzo’s ‘Ọrĩa Anyị’ (Our disease) (p. 24) and ‘Dibĩa Adụgburuja’ (Fake doctor) (pp. 28-29) both in *Omenkà*.

Let us shed more light on what we mean by literary title by examining the poem ‘Ugbọ’ (Vehicle) (poem 6) written by Akoma in *Akpa Uche* (1975), where the poet writes:

Uwà ntà nà-àlakwuru ñkè ukwu	(Lesser world goes to meet the bigger one
Àhụ na-àlaghachi n’ebe o sì	The body returns to where it came from
Onye nwē ụkwụ ewèrela ụkwụ ya	The owner of the leg has taken back his leg
Onye nwē aka ewèrela aka yā	The owner of the hand has taken back his hands
Ì gà-èsi añaā gafèe gị	How do I cross you
N’atūghị ñgùzo?	Without stopping
Ebe ọ bụ ụzọ dīrị ọhà?	Since it is a public road?
Kà m kèlee gị	Let me greet you
Èkèle ìkpeāzụ	The final greeting
Ebe ìmadù niile gà-àgafè ụzọ a.	Since everyone will have to pass through this road.
Mà gị onye nà-ebe akwā	But you that are crying
Hichaa anya mmīri n’anya	Wipe your tears from your eyes
N’ihì nà ụgbọ ñke buru	Because the vehicle that carried
Hànānāyās nà-èche Sáfajra	Ananias awaits Sapphira)

(Akoma in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, pp. 48-49)

The title of the above poem is composed in such a way that it does not easily give away the thought of the poem at a glance. A student of Igbo poetry who reads the poem would clearly understand the relationship between the poem's title and its thought through the way the poet has manipulated language. The first glance at the title of poem (6), ‘Ugbọ’, reveals the ambiguous nature of the title vis-à-vis the content, and makes the reader wonder what the poet could be referring to. ‘Ugbọ’, as a word in Igbo, is polysemic in nature.

‘Ugbọ’ as a general term in Igbo refers to a vehicle, a means of transportation. However, with respect to the above poem, the poet used the term ‘Ugbo’ in its

figurative (ironic) sense to refer to death as a vehicle to the spirit world. A reader or student of Igbo poetry who sees the title of this poem (Ugbo) from the literal sense of the term would think that the poem is about the usual means of transportation (like cars, boats, or aeroplanes) and everything that surrounds that sense. To further explain what we mean by some titles of written Igbo poetry being literary in nature, let us draw another instance from one of Obierozi's poems, 'Akakpo' (Dwarf) (poem 7).

In the poem, the poet writes:

<p>Akakpo agadi ekwe nka I hapuru ikwu na ibe n'ohia Gbakpuo n'ime ulo je biri Mkpotu gi chue ezi na ulo ura Ebe i na-achughari ada oke.</p>	<p>(Dwarf an elder that has refused to age You left your relatives in the bush Ran inside the house to live Your noise deprives the family of sleep Where you are pursuing the female rat</p>
<p>Akuku ulo m niile i mere nnyocha I kwaghi aru ka obia Ahapuru m ngiga n'elu uko Ma i gara choputa ihe di na ya</p>	<p>You investigated every corner of my house You are not gentle as a visitor I left the fish basket on the shelf. But you went and discovered what is in it.</p>
<p>Ohi niile e zuru n'ulo m I gaghi agonari ha Na azu adikwaghi na ngiga Gosiri na i bu ekperima Ikuanya kwochara akwocha (Obierozi, 1986, p. 31)</p>	<p>All the theft in my house You cannot deny them That there is no more fish in the fish basket Proves that you are a thief. Faded eyebrows)</p>

A reader who reads the above poem seven times will wonder why the poet chose the title 'Akakpo' for it. The reader may also wonder about the relation between the thought of the poem and its title. When we critically examine the image, the title of the poem, "Seven Projects," and the introductory verse, we can understand the poet's figurative use of the term 'Akakpo' as the title of the poem. The term 'Akakpo' is used in both its ironic and metonymic senses. From its ironic sense, the poet does not refer to human dwarfs but to animals that can be classified as dwarfs in the animal world, such as rats and mice, which leave their natural habitat (the forest) to torment

man in man's natural habitat (the house). From its metonymic sense, *Akakpo*, as used in the above poem 7, symbolises a thief or anyone who steals from another person.

Furthermore, a reader who sees the title of the poem 'Alukwaghi m' (Divorce) (Poem 8) by C.U. Ogbulogo in *Omenka* (1992, p. 22) would expect the thought or message of the poem to revolve around issues that relate to the literal sense of marital divorce between a man and his wife. Nevertheless, just like the two examples above (poems 6 and 7), 'Alukwaghi m' (Divorce), as a title in the text, is also used in its figurative sense. A reading of the poem reveals that the title 'Alukwaghi m' in *Omenka* is indeed used in its ironic sense by the poet. The poet protests the influence of Western culture and its effects on Igbo culture and core values, which have now been lost through contact between the two cultures. Hence, the use of 'Alukwaghi m' as the title of the poem refers to a wish by the poet to see the end of the western cultural imperialism in Igboland. In the second stanza of the poem, the poet (Ogbulogo) says:

Gupu n'efere m	(Remove from my plate
Nri akamere	Artificial food
Nke e liri n'ime komkom	That is buried inside a can
Ma mezie ya nsi ogbungwangwa	And made it a fast-acting poison
Butere m efere akpu	Bring me a plate of fufu
Ofe onugbu na ebele mmai	Bitter leaf soup and small wine
Tinyere m ji awayi	Add roasted yam for me
E ji uziza na ose sokpoo anya	That is well-garnished with saint leaf and pepper
Chitara m oka na ube	Bring me maize and pear
Chitakwa aki na ukwa	Also bring dry kernel and breadfruit
Ihe mmeghari onu	Snacks
Ndi lara ezumike nka n'ike	Those that went on retirement by force
Mgbe miiti pai	When meat pie
E ji ataka ede na ogwu azu mee	Prepared with cocoyam leaf and fish bone
Mabatara n'ama anyi	Jumped into our compound.)

(Ikwubuzo, et.al., 1992, p. 22)

Here in poem 8, we can see clearly why the title of the poem 'Alukwaghi m' is considered a literary title. In the above stanza, the reader can deduce the vexation of

the poet from the tone of the poem. The title of this poem does not, in any way, give away its thought, that is, by merely looking at the title. The reader, who comes across such a title, is forced to read the poem in order to understand what the title means.

The literary titles contribute to the overall understanding and interpretation of the poem. It opens the poem to multiple interpretations, thereby promoting its aesthetics and the poet's artistic creativity.

4.1.2 The Non-Literary Title Form

This refers to Igbo poem titles that are transparent in conveying the poem's thought or message. This type of poetic title gives the reader insight into the poem's thought at a glance, even without reading it. It tells the reader what the poet may be saying in the poem. Since the nature of poetry is such that most students consider it a complex subject (Ikwubuzo, 2007), most modern Igbo poets make the titles of their poems unambiguous, direct, to the point, transparent, and easy to understand. The majority of modern Igbo poem titles fall into this category. This means that the thought in most modern Igbo poems is captured and summarised in the poem's title. However, the disadvantage of this type of poetic titles is that it seems to water down the artistic or imaginative character of poetry, making it appear very common. However, different poets may share the same title in their poems, but they obviously do not treat the subject the same way.

The nature of non-literary Igbo poetic titles is such that if the thought conveyed by the poem is satire on laziness as a deviant behaviour, the poet titles the poem 'ngana' or 'umengwu' (laziness) as in the case of T. Nzeako's 'Ngana' in *Akpa Uche* (1975), A.B. Chukuezi's 'Onye ume ngwu' in *Akọ Bu Ndu*, (1988), N. Okediadi's 'Umengwu' in *Ije Uwa* (2003) and R.E. Ekegbo's 'Ọrĩa Ngana' in *Uwa*

Onye na Chi Ya (2005). Similarly, if the poet is writing about the power and universality of death (onwu) as a natural phenomenon, the (Igbo) poet titles the poem ‘Onwu’ as in the case of the following: by T. Nzeako’s ‘Onwu’ in *Akpa Uche* (1975), Obienyem’s ‘Onwu’, Ajaegbu’s ‘Onwu’, Emenike’s ‘Onwu’, all in *Akpa Uche* (1975) Obierozié’s ‘Onwu’ in *Ekpe Nna* (1986) N. Okediadi’s ‘Onwu’ in *Ije Uwa* (2003), Ikeokwu and Onyekekwe’s ‘Onwu’ in *Uche bu Ahia* (2009), to mention but a few. When the poet writes about a particular season, be it rainy, dry, or harmattan seasons, which are the three seasons experienced in Southern Nigeria (Igboland inclusive), the poet makes the season they are writing about, that is, the subject of the poem, the title of the poem. This is the case of ‘Uguru’ by J.C. Maduekwe in *Nka Okwu*, ‘Uguru’ by Obierozié in *Ekpe Nna*, and ‘Uguru’ by N. Okediadi in *Ije Uwa*. In these three poems, the poets take time to describe everything about the harmattan season, which explains why they capture the essence of their poems in their titles.

Let us instantiate this point further by looking at how a title can reflect the thought of a poem in some selected written Igbo poems. In Maduekwe’s poem on ‘Uguru’ (Harmattan) (poem 9) in *Nka Okwu* (1979, p. 41), the poet writes:

Ọ b̄iakwā, òdogwu à àkp̄iri kp̄òrò nk̄u.
 Uḡur̄u, fere mmiri asaà, f̄e mbà àsaà;
 Wakas̄iri, tikas̄iri na-èje, na-àch̄o,
 Ihe gw̄nah̄iri ya ò w̄e z̄òlie ij̄è.

Keṁgbè o rùtèrè, àh̄u ab̄ugh̄ikwa m ah̄u;
 Ọ d̄oḷa m̄ mb̄o n’egb̄ugbere on̄u, nȳe ya on̄ya;
 Ọ f̄uḷa m̄ on̄u n’oghere imi, kp̄oḷo yā nk̄u,
 Aka o bit̄ur̄u m̄ m̄rè àh̄u dum na-àgbakas̄i m̄.

(Maduekwe, 1979, p. 41)

(He has arrived, this hero that has dry throat
 Harmattan that crossed seven waters, crossed seven cities:
 Breaking its way, tearing as it walks, and searching,
 His things finished, and he began his voyage

Since he arrived, my body is no longer my body
 It has scratched my lips with its fingers, leaving an injury

He has blown my nostrils, drying them
His touch itches my whole body.

The title of this poem, 9, 'Uguru', is a non-literary one; It is in concordance with the thought of the poem, which is anchored on the effects of the harmattan season on the poet or people in general. From the title of this poem, the poet gives away what would have taxed the imagination of the reader. The reader understands, even without reading the poem, its subject matter and that it could focus on the positive or negative effects of the harmattan season. In Obieroze's poem of the same title, 'Uguru' in *Ekpe Nna* (1986), the poet's portrayal of the harmattan season is immediately revealed, as in Maduekwe's. In the first and second stanzas of Obieroze's 'Uguru' (Harmattan), (poem 10), the poet writes:

Anyi di atọ achi ụwa Udummiri onye iro uguru Okochi, I gburu kpoo see waa Bia juwa onye na-egbu	(We are three that rule the world Rainy season, enemy of harmattan Dry season, you struck <i>kpoo</i> drew <i>waa</i> Came and started asking who was striking
Oke m unu riri alaghi n'efu Mbọ inara oke m nwere oge Anatara m na nnakpu okuko Ibia kpochapu nku okochi kpara	My share that you people ate did not go in vain. Efforts to reclaim my share have their time. I returned when the hen was about to sleep. Coming to clear the firewood gathered during the dry season)

(Obieroze, 1986, p. 16)

As we can see from poem 10 above, the thought the poem conveys is captured in the title. There is nothing literary about the title, as the title, at a glance, gives a direct idea of the thought of the poem. In the poem, the poet introduces the subject of the poem (uguru) as one of the key seasons in Igboland. According to the poet, the harmattan season follows the dry season, which is why the poet describes the rainy season as the enemy of the harmattan season. The whole of the poem, down to the last stanza, points to the single subject, which also revolves around the title of the poem.

This is also the case of ‘Uguru’ (Harmattan) (poem 11) written by Okediadi in *Ije Uwa* (2003, pp. 13-14) where the poet writes:

Ozurumbaonu!	(Universal phenomenon!
Malite n’onwa Disemba	Beginning from December
Ruo n’onwa Jenuari	Till the month of January
I na-egosi ihe i bu.	You show what you are.
I na-eme ka ubochi juo oyi	You make the day cool
Ebe ala na-abu ntuntu	Where the land becomes dusty
I na-eme nwoke na nwaanyi lezie	You make male and female to take care
anuahụ ha anya	of their bodies
Ma ha emeghi etu a	If they do not do this
I jiri aka gi doziere ha ahụ ha.	You take care of their bodies for them
Anwu na-acha mana oyi na-atu.	The sun is shining but it is cold
Mmiri oyi mgbe dum.	Cold water all the time
Ikuku oyi gi anaghi enwe atu.	Your cold breeze is incomparable
O maghi onye ukwu	It does not know the great
O maghi onye nta	It does not know the small
(Okediadi, 2003, pp. 13-14)	

In the above poem 11, the thought is about the power of the harmattan season as a natural phenomenon. Every verse in this excerpt and the rest of the poem reinforces the title of the poem. In the first verse, the poet introduces the phenomenon to the reader, informing them of the time of year when the Igbo experience the harmattan season. According to the poet, in the excerpt above, the harmattan season usually occurs from December to January. In the second verse, the poet begins to describe the workings of the harmattan season, its effects on humans, and how humans respond to it. Having clarified the nature of Igbo poetic titles, we shall delve into content-based classification of written Igbo poetry.

4.2 Classification of Written Igbo Poetry Based on Sort of Verse

It is important to note that not everything in Igbo verse form is worthy of the name poetry, as there are many verses without poetic touches. Obike in *Eke-Une* (n.d.: p. 78) supports this assertion by stating that “verse in itself is not poetry and

there are many verses without poetic touches”. The fact that a larger percentage (90%) of written Igbo poetry can be regarded as free verses (Obike, n.d) does not give a licence for the conjuring of prose in the form of poetry and the proliferation of the Igbo poetic scene with works that lack virtue. Based on the data used in this study (and many other Igbo poetic texts), written Igbo poetry can be classified into two broad branches: pseudo-Igbo verses and standard Igbo poetry.

4.2.1 Pseudo-Igbo Verses

‘Pseudo’ as a word refers to a verse that has the similitude of poetry, but not necessarily a poem. The concept of ‘Pseudo poetry’ used in this study was adopted from Azuonye (2010), who used the term to refer to an alienated form of poetry written by untrained writers who seek to be seen as poets. According to Azuonye (2010, p. 18), “Younger Igbo writers who have attempted to produce poetry in Igbo without undergoing the process of ‘deschooling’ have generally ended up producing alienated or pseudo-traditional verses.” From Azuonye’s position, we can see that the term ‘deschooling’ (training) is foregrounded because of its importance in creative writing. Azuonye (2010) further stated that there are various instances of these alienated or pseudo-traditional verses in many Igbo anthologies. Although Azuonye (2010) mentioned only a few anthologies in which examples of these pseudo-traditional verses could be found and limited his instances of these pseudo-verses to traditional verses alone in various Igbo anthologies, it has, however, been observed that some modern Igbo poems can also be regarded as alienated or pseudo-verses. This is because the end product of the works of Igbo poets, who did not go through the process of ‘deschooling’ or learning about how to write poetry as suggested by

Azuonye (2010), not only ends up in producing pseudo-traditional verses but also some pseudo-modern verses.

It has become imperative to clarify this point, given the rising number of Igbo poetic texts with many self-acclaimed poets dishing out alienated verses in the name of poetry. While some of the self-acclaimed poets who write these pseudo-verses do so out of an honest desire to salvage Igbo poetry, which has suffered an enormous setback over the years. As pointed out in the third chapter, author-financed publishing has facilitated the proliferation of the Igbo poetic scene, with works that are not worthy of the name of poetry. The effect of this is that the Igbo reading public is gradually losing touch with what it means to have a feel of a good poem. It is in the light of this understanding that the pseudo-Igbo verses are divided in this study into two: pseudo-traditional verses and pseudo-modern verses.

4.2.1.1 Pseudo-traditional verses

Pseudo-traditional verses can be said to be written verses that make use of only traditional or oral material expressions in projecting a central idea (Azuonye, 2010). In pseudo-traditional verses, the only creative input required from the poet is in the area of organisation of the lines to project the thought or message he intends to pass across. The poet does not bring his own creative imagination to bear on writing pseudo-traditional verses, but uses his creative skill to adopt the appropriate traditional expressions in Igbo that properly suit and represent the central idea he intends to convey. Azuonye (2010) explains that in the pseudo-traditional verses, one can readily observe the absurd heights of vulgarity in the use of oral traditional materials. These traditional materials are mostly proverbs and other figurative expressions strung together to convey a thought. The credit given to a person that

writes pseudo-traditional verses is in the area of his style as choice, as he demonstrates strong skill in choosing the right figurative expressions from the pool of other expressions that are available in the Igbo language, fuses them, succeeds in creating a new verse that brings a new feeling to the owners of the language, who have been neglecting these expressions.

For us to understand this concept of pseudo-traditional verses, let us consider an example cited by Azuonye (2010, p. 18), “Ilulu” (Similitude) (poem 12), a verse written by Ogunjiofor, from *Akpa Uche*:

Mma dị nkọ enweghị isi	(The sharp matchet has no handle
Nke nwere isi adighị nkọ	The one with a handle is not sharp
Ada ji akụ kwaa nna ya	Let the wealthy daughter bury her father
Ọ bughị ọkpara kugburu ya	It is not the first son that killed him
E sowe ihe nkịta riri	If we go by what the dog eats
Anụ ya adọrọ erighị eri	Its meat will lie uneaten
Onye tārā āhu jee n’ọba ...	If he that is slim visits the barn ...)

(Ogunjiofor in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 43)

It runs like this in the remaining seventeen lines of the verse. In the above poem (poem 12), one will agree with Azuonye, who rightly posits that there are no formal, technical refinements or linking patterns in the above excerpt or the entire verse in itself; instead, what we have are just strings of proverbs with no form of creativity by the poet in it, except in the area of organisation. Concerning the above poem, Azuonye (2010, p. 18) submits that “this is clearly not poetry but the mechanical stringing together of traditional rhetorical devices.” Several poets who write this type of verse will argue that this type of poetry is peculiar to Igbo poetry.

Regrettably, due to the rising number of these pseudo-traditional verses, Igbo scholars now assign a poetic nomenclature to this type of verse, thus classifying it as “proverbial poetry,” as evident in Nnyigide (2015). This is because whatever must carry the label of poetry must showcase some level of the poet’s creative use of his imagination, which appears to be missing in the above poem 12. Figurative language

is merely employed in written Igbo poetry as a poetic embellishment; thus, it is not poetry in itself, as Ogunjiofor has attempted in the above poem 12.

Another key reason the above verse (poem 12) cannot be considered as poetry is that, except for its rhyming piquancy, it does not project a coordinated thought (theme) or emotion that is needed for its thematic classification. This means that a student of Igbo poetry who reads the above verse cannot analyse it and, as such, cannot explain the central thought the verse projects. We shall recall that for any verse to be considered a poem, such a verse must possess the four key features of written Igbo poetry (thought, emotion, rhythm, and language) (Uba-Mgbemena, 1990). In the case of the above verse (poem 12), there is a deficiency of thought and emotion, since the proverbs do not connect to project a single idea.

Based on the foregoing, this study, however, argues that the concept of “proverbial Igbo poems” (*Abu Ilu*), as used earlier by Ugonna (1980), is only obtainable in oral Igbo poetry or transcribed oral texts as we find in *Abu na Egwuregwu Odinala* (1980) and the like. When the similitude of such verses appears in any written Igbo poetic text (not transcribed texts), they are regarded as pseudo-traditional verses. Another good example of pseudo-traditional verse in *Akpa Uche* is another poem by Ogunjiofor titled “Zere Ohi” (poem 13), where he writes:

Òtu ụbòchị, ụbòchị anwụ,	(One day, a sunny day,
Mbè apụta nà be Ewi;	Tortoise arrives at rabbit’s residence;
Kèlee yā wèe pụta ēzi.	Greets him and goes outside.
Ewī kpurọ Mbè je ohī;	The Rabbit took the tortoise to steal;
Hà jee nà be Ibèziakō;	They went to Ibeziako’s house;
Hà hụ Ibē nà ụmụ ya àtọ;	They saw Ibe and his three children
Kà ha kpùchà òkà n’ ọnū;	As they had corn in their mouths
Hà anòkata, ukwù èjie hā;	They waited, and grew weary
Ewī sị ya gà-àla ala,	The rabbit says that he will go home
Mbè sị ya gà-àla ala;	Tortoise says that he will go home
Hà wèe bilie, kere ụla ...	And they arouse, and left ...

(Ogunjiofor in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 55)

The story goes on and on down to the last verse. Just like the way every Igbo folktale ends with a moral lesson, the verse ended with a warning to everyone who wants to remain alive to avoid stealing. Looking at this verse (poem 13), one can see that it is not a poem but a folktale in verse form. The excerpt showcases all the features of a folk ballad (oral poetry) and is used to teach morals. One of the main features of folk ballads is community ownership (Ikwubuzo & Oraegbunam, 2016), and as such, this verse (poem 13) is clearly not the original creation of the versifier (Ogunjiofor). The verse focuses on the tortoise as the chief character in Igbo folktales. This is why it will be a gross misclassification to refer to the above verse as a poem in any way. This is because the language of the poem is not the work of the writer, and the emotion and thought, though didactic, are not the creation of the writer. This is why poem 13 and every other verse in that form are regarded as pseudo-traditional verses.

Another example of pseudo-traditional verse is “Obodo m” (poem 14), a verse written by G.O. Onyekaonwu in his *Uche Bụ Afa* (1989, p. 13), which Nnyigide (2015, p. 27) classified as proverbial poetry.

<p>Nwa aturu ga-epu mpi Ekwo dikwa ya arò Onye mkpumkpụ ga-ekowe akpa Ebe aka ya ga-eru; N’ihi na onye ekwughị ka o ha, E buru ya gafee ama nna ya; Onye tara ahụ amaghị na ya tara,</p> <p>Odudo ga-ara ya ahụ A na-azotagodu ala ulò Wee gaa zowa nke ezi Onye ulò ya na-agba oku Agaghị eje na-achụ oke; N’ihi na okokporo gbanahuchaa ntụ ututu O maghị diri na-eche ya A tuwa ilu nkiri nkata Onye tara ahụ amara onwe ya.</p>	<p>(A sheep that wants to grow horns Should have a strong forehead A short person should hang a bag Where his hands could reach Because he that fails to state his condition Will be carried past his father’s compound An emaciated individual does not know that he is emaciated, Getting nourished will be challenging for him The land for a house must be first fought for Before fighting for the one outside He that his house is on fire Does not go chasing a rat Because a bachelor that runs from his morning duties, Does not know that it awaits him When a haggard proverb is uttered The emaciated individual re-examines himself)</p>
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(Onyekaonwu, 1989, p. 13)

Poem 14 continues like this in the rest of the other nine lines. Like Azuonye's assessment of Ilulu (poem 12), they are just strings of proverbs, which the poet meticulously lifted from the pool of available Igbo proverbs, for didactic purposes. This verse, like the one in poem 13, is not poetry but pseudo-traditional verse, as one cannot see any creative use of the poet's imagination in bringing out issues related to Igbo sociological life, as expected of the title. There is no gainsaying the fact that Goddy Onyekaonwu writes good Igbo poems and, as such, can be said to be a good poet. However, in respect of the above verse, one can see clearly that it is not poetry, going by our definition of pseudo-traditional verse. He seems to have written it to showcase his artistic freedom, an exercise of his poetic license in his adaptation of the traditional materials—style as choice. The verse above is titled 'Obodo m', but it clearly does not say anything about the title the poet has given it and, as such, does not give a picture of the motif of the verse. Since the components of the above poem 14 are existing expressions in the oral repertoire of the Igbo, the lines lack coherence and, as such, cannot project a single thought.

Another example of pseudo-traditional verse is Chigbo Onyeji's 'E Nwere Mgbe' (poem 15) in Nwadike's (2006, p. 79) *Akọnauche*. We shall only show three stanzas of the text from Onyeji's work:

E nwere mgbe ifufe
Menyere ụmụ anumanụ egwu

(There was a time
Made the animals afraid

O malitere n'oge
Ha agaghịrị enwe ohere
Gbapu gbakpuru n'ime ọhịa ndị
Gbara ha gburugburu n'agbataobi,
Kawado lụwa ka ha napụta ifufe ala ha.

It started at a time
That they will not have time
To run inside the forest of people
Surrounding them in the neighbourhood,
To prepare to fight and retrieve their land
from the wind.

N'ihì na ọ̀ bụ̀ ajọ̀ ifufe
Ha jiri ntumiriiko so ya
Kpokuokwa dibia ukwu, dibia nta
Bụ̀ ndị̀ b́ara gbakọ́ta hawa mmiri

N'udị̀ na mmiri zochaa gbachaa,

(Onyeji in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 79)

Because it is a stormy wind
They followed it with wisdom
Called on great and small medicine men
Those that gathered and started making
rain to fall
In that, after the rain, the wind will seize...)
ifufe alaa...

This narrative continues till the last stanza of the text. Again, a look at the above verse (poem 15) shows that there is nothing poetic about the verse. It is a mere versification of a folktale. The tale, like every other Igbo tale, is not the creation of Onyeji, who can be regarded here as a collector. The tale is part of the oral repertoire of the society from which Onyeji adopted it. Versifying this tale does not make it poetry. Instead, it can be regarded as a folk ballad text.

4.2.1.2 Pseudo-modern verses

Unlike the pseudo-traditional verses, pseudo-modern verses refer to lines put together as verses that cannot be said to be poetic in any way, or simply put, 'non-poetic verses'. Pseudo-modern verses can be said to be the end product of the works of the versifiers who lack the technical skills needed for poetic writing in Igbo. It is indeed important to state at this juncture that poetic writing is a special skill that is either inborn or learnt. This means that not everyone who writes verses is qualified to be called a poet. For a poet, "is no ordinary mortal but a divinely inspired artist, a possessed performer through whom hidden truths of the spirit are revealed and through whose influence mankind undergoes generation and spiritual rebirth" (Obiechina, 1993, p. 207). Obiechina (1993) further states that a poet is one who speaks to other men with a voice of moral authority strengthened by heightened

sensibility. Okediadi (2004, p. 248) supports Obiechina's views by asserting that a poet is seen as a seer, a prophet, a priest, a madman, and a legislator for mankind. In essence, a poet is simply a person with "some background from the society and culture of his time, culture and place" (Jafari & Mahadi, 2013, p. 119). The poet performs all these roles with the use of language in his poem. Ugonna (1982) asserts that what makes a poem an Igbo poem is the language play in it. That is, the way and manner in which language is conveyed to the audience (readers) and how the language is arranged formally within it. This is because "poetry is no mere aesthetic pastime, no simple celebration of verbal ingenuity, and no indulgence of intellectual gymnastics" (Okediadi, 2004, p. 248).

Obike (n.d), in his effort to advance the study of written Igbo poetry, emphasised the need to differentiate poetic verses from non-poetic verses. The non-poetic written verses are thus referred to as pseudo-modern verses. Some of these pseudo-modern verses are mere narratives, while some are just short lines in verse forms, a demonstration of what Okediadi (2004) terms a "celebration of verbal ingenuity". Some of the writers of these pseudo-modern Igbo verses try to make their verses conform to some rhyme, and the end rhymes are usually their tool. However, it does not change the fact that the verses are not poetic and thus lack the qualities of a poem. Again, because these pseudo-modern verses lack poetic qualities, they are impossible to analyse, as they seem very empty and devoid of all poetic features that could qualify them as poetry and warrant any form of analysis.

Okediadi (2004, p. 252) observes that there are just a few Igbo poets who write good poems. She boldly states, "At times, we get some Igbo poets who write good poems. Okediadi and Obike's views confirm the fact that many written Igbo verses are of inferior quality and their writers unworthy of the name poets, and that is

why they are referred to, in this study, as versifiers. Mill (1999) knows that an issue like this may arise at some point and, therefore, in describing the nature of poetry, he states that a question may sometimes arise as to whether a particular author can also be regarded as a poet. Mill, knowing the role of a poet, further answers this question by asserting that some authors cannot be called poets but are instead eloquent writers.

Example of these pseudo-modern Igbo verses can be seen in the work of Ifeka's (2009) *O Natara Chi*, verses such as "Ùgwù" (Honour) (p.7), "Onye ga-abụ ugwo gi" (p.12), "Agbataobi m" (p.21), to mention but a few. Some other examples include: "Echi" in Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe's *Uche bu Ahia* (2009, p. 46), "Ura" by Ofomata in *Okwu Ndu* (2001), and "E Nwere Mgbe" by C. Onyeji in *Akọnauche* (p.79). There are other examples in extant Igbo texts. Let us buttress this point with a typical example of Ifeka's "Ùgwù" (Honour) in *O Natara Chi* (Poem 16), where she writes:

Ubochi a i gwara ya	(The other day you spoke to him
Okwu adighi mma	Unpleasant word
N'ihu ndi enyi ya	In the presence of his friends
I lere ya anya n'ihu?	Did you look at his face?
Ka i choputa ka o di ya	To know how he felt
Ubochi gara aga	The other day
Otu a ka i siri	This is how you
Gwakanye ya okwu	Talked to him
N'eleghi anya n'azu	Without looking back
Gi ni bu nke a?	What is this?
I na-akpu ugwu ya n'ala.	You are disgracing him.

Ugwu bu ihe mmadu	Honour is for human beings
Chere banyere onwe ya	Thinks about himself
N'ebe ndi ozọ nọ	Where other people are
Olulu di na nwunye	Marriage
Anaghi amutacha ihe di na ya	One cannot learn everything in it
Ndi bu di hunu	Husbands
Nwunye unu n'anya	Love your wives
Ndi bu nwunye	Wives
Doonu onwe unu	Submit yourselves
N'okpuru di nke aka unu	To your own husbands

E jila ochie enyi gi	Do not use your old friend
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Tụnyere di maọbụ nwunye	To compare your husband or wife
E kwujọla nwanne gi	Do not speak ill of your brother
E ledala alo ibe gi kpara	Do not look down on the counsel of your fellow
Ugwu bụ ihe mmadụ chere	Honour is what someone thinks
Chere banyere onwe ya	Thinks about himself
N'ebe ndị ọzọ nọ.	Where other people are.)

(Ifeka, 2009, p. 7)

A look at the verse above (Poem 16) makes it clear why some modern verses cannot be considered poems. The above verse is clearly not poetry but rather a manifestation of the versifier's subconscious persona. They are just strings of prose reduced to various lines or clauses in the form of verse, which lacks the quality of poetry. It is clearly a didactic verse that lacks poetic imagery and exhibits poor line composition. The language used in the above verse is known in the Formalist school as “practical language, a term used by formalists to refer to “everyday language. While writing on the formalistic view of art as a device, Selden (1985) opines that the nature of poetry makes it exercise a controlled violence upon practical language, which is usually defamiliarised in poetry, with a view to drawing our attention to its constructed nature.

This explains the study's position that poem 16 above is not poetry but pseudo-modern verse, since there is no compression in the writer's language. One does not need to read the verse twice to understand what the writer is saying. More importantly, analysing the above verse will expose its emptiness. Again, one can readily observe the absence of Igbo poetic rhythm, rhyme, and imagery in the above verse. This is why this verse is seen as pseudo-modern: it is more like a prosaic piece of advice than a poem. Wordsworth (1802, p. 4) rightly affirms that for any poem to be attached any value, such a poem must be written by a man (poet) who has been possessed of more than usual organic sensibility and has also thought long and deeply.

The above verse does not have an iota of proof that suggests that the versifier has thought deeply on the subject she wrote about.

Let us consider another instance of pseudo-modern verse from another Igbo poetic text, *Uche Bu Ahia* (2009). While some of the works in this poetic text (*Uche Bu Ahia*) can be said to be good Igbo poems, some others are just verses that do not qualify to be called poems. For instance, apart from the introductory stanza of “Echi” (Tomorrow) (poem 17) (p. 46), which seems poetic, the rest of the verses are just strings of lines that lack poetic touches. Let us see the three verses that follow:

Ọtụtụ mgbe ka anyị na-asị	(Many a times we say
Anyị ga-eme nke a	We will do this
Maọbụ nke ọzọ	Or the other
Oge ọbụla ka m na-ebu	Many a time I carry
Otu ihe maọbụ nke ọzọ n’obi	One thing or the other in mind
Banyere ihe m ga-eme echi	Regarding what I will do tomorrow
Ma anaghị m ajụ onwe m	But I don’t ask myself
Ajụjụ sị “gini bụ	Question saying “what is the
Ebumnuche	Thought
Chi maka echi?	Of God concerning tomorrow
Ọ kwa ụbọchị a	Just the other day
Ka m kwuru	I said
Aga m eje igote ụgbọala	I will go and buy a car
Ma echi ya	But the next day
Enwetara m onwe m	I found myself
N’ụlọgwụ	In the hospital
Anọgidere m n’ụlọgwụ	I stayed at the hospital to the point
Ụlọgwụ anọgide m	The hospital took its toll on me
Ego ụgbọala gwụ n’ogwụ	The money for the car finished on medications
Ụgbọala aghọzie ogwụ	Car turned to medication
Ọ bụ kwa ụbọchị	It was
Ole na ole gara aga	Some days ago
Ka m ziri nna m	I asked my father
Ka ọ bịa zutu ike na be m	To come and rest a while at my house
Ọ wee gwa m na ya ga-abịa	He told me that he would come
Echi ya	The next day
Ma tupu echi abịa	But before the next day came
Ọnwụ nna m abịa ...	My father died
(Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, 2009, p. 46)	

This continues till the last stanza. Again, this is not poetry but just a narrative in verse form. Apart from the presence of a rhetorical question, which was poorly structured in lines 8-10, the rest of the stanzas are just a versification of prose. Some of the lines in these verses end abruptly and are not balanced in sense by the following lines. Other instances of pseudo-modern verses include, but are not limited to: ‘Azụ Akọ Emu’ in Ifeka’s *O Natara Chi* (2009).

It is a known fact that some of these pseudo-modern verses have continued to grow in their numbers. Obike (n.d, p. 79), having observed the damage these pseudo-modern verses are causing to the development of Igbo poetry, submits thus, “In recent years, Igbo language examiners have tended to assume that there was nothing else the language could present to the world in the form of poetry except folk songs.” Azuonye (2010) also states that such pseudo-verses, in their numerical strength and high vein of vulgarity, pervade the available volumes of Igbo poetry, making it seem that writing in African languages is an exercise in futility. Obike (n.d), however, expresses optimism that Igbo poets can do better, and therefore, warns modern Igbo poets that to accept this situation (pseudo-modern verses) is to preside over the liquidation of Igbo culture. This is why this study has chosen to identify these verses with a view to helping students of Igbo poetry to make distinctions in their study of written Igbo poetry.

4.2.2 Standard Written Igbo Poetry

Here, we refer to works that can indeed be seen as quality Igbo poems written by poets who understand what it takes to write good poems. Igbo poets, who write standard Igbo poems, have the responsibility of using their unique creative skills to promote the cause of humanity and Igbo society through poetry. The group of poems

in this category is well-written and rhythmically structured, with a strong sense of imagery that enhances their aesthetic appeal. This brings to the fore the features of written Igbo poetry, which Uba-Mgbemena (1991) warns that any Igbo poem must possess to be considered a good Igbo poem. Those features of Igbo poetry include thought, emotion, language, and rhythm (Uba-Mgbemena, 1991). Poets like Nolie Emenanjo, A. B. Chukuezi, J.C. Maduekwe, N. Olebra, N. Okediadi, Iwu Ikwubuzo, J. C. Obienyem, I. U. Nwadike, Madubuike, C. C. Anozie, and many more fall under the category of those who write good poems and can be seen as good Igbo poets. It can be said that 70% of all the poems published in the first decade (1975-1985) and the early second decade (1986-1991) of the existence of written Igbo are good. The reason for this is not far-fetched, as it should be recalled that the reputable publishing companies published those works, and they were subjected to thorough editorial scrutiny before publication. Again, the British administrators, through transnational publishing corporations, pioneered the publication of Igbo literature, including poetry (Muoh & Ezinwanne, 2016). Prominent among these transnational publishing corporations that worked in Nigeria and other African colonies to establish markets for the publication of schoolbooks include Evans Brothers, Oxford University Press, Heinemann Educational Books, Macmillan, Longman, and Nelson Publishers (Muoh & Ezinwanne, 2016). These publishing companies published the bulk of Igbo poetic texts from the first and second decades. These companies also took their time to scrutinise poetic submissions and contracted scholars who meticulously edited submissions from various poets before they were published. Nevertheless, since most of these big companies no longer take an interest in publishing Igbo Literary texts due to some economic considerations, most Igbo poets now resort to self-publishing (author-financed publishing) in order to get their works published. Though it (author-

financed publishing) helped in the development of written Igbo poetry, as suggested by Ikwubuzo (2007), it did so at the expense of side effects, which manifest in the poor quality of both the poems and the texts published. A look at poem 1 in this study, which is drawn from *Utara Nti* and written by Madubuike, will better explain what we mean by standard written Igbo poetry.

Ìsì kpùrù ebe dum	(Everywhere is blind
Anyasì nà-èji kà unyi...	Night is dark as charcoal...
Eluigwē anāghì achì ọchì mà ì	Heaven is not smiling at all
Kpakpando – anya abalì – alakpuọla	Stars – eyes of the night – have gone to sleep
Ọnwa na anyanwụ na-ehikwa ọra	The sun and moon are also sleeping
Egwu dī ebe dum	There is fear everywhere

A look at the poem above explains our position in this study: while some verses cannot be called poetry, others can be seen as a true reflection of standard written Igbo poetry. The language play in the above poem 1 says a great deal about the creativity of the Igbo poet, Madubuike, as it does of other poets. A poet takes up what people trivialise and makes an art out of it. This is what Madubuike has demonstrated in his poem 1, here. A poetic analyst, who attempts to analyse the above poem (1), will discover the richness of the poem in terms of its content and form. While the poem evokes different emotions in the reader, it also projects an elevated thought, the analysis of which can take many pages to exhaust. The poem, on the other hand, displays the poet's mastery of Igbo figurative language, both in its literal and literary senses. The language of the poet, here (poem 1), is solid, making the poem possess qualities befitting of a standard poem. Let us also consider another example of standard written Igbo poetry by looking at a poem written by A. B. Chukuezi in *Akọ Bụ Ndu* (1988), which he titled 'Wachie Ubi n'Oge' (Close your farm early) (Poem 18):

Eluigwe rujie	(When the sky becomes cloudy
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Obi amūnye onye ụlọ akiriika n'afọ	A person who lives in the thatched house is gripped by fear, and begins to race
Nzuzu mere nwoke igba oso	Foolishness made a man run,
Mgbe mmiri masigoro ya	After the rain beats him.
Wachie ubi n'oge	Protect farm early
Ka anumanu ghara ibata	So that animals will not enter,
Oma nkiriika akwa	He that ties scraggy cloth
Ma nkiriika okwu	Ties crude talks)

(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 17)

The above poem 18 shows that indeed some Igbo poems are standard in nature. The poem naturally invites any poetry lover to a worthy interpretation. The poem is rich in both content and form. Just like the poem 'Abali' (poem 1), the thought of poem 18 is very deep. Though the poem is concise, it holds profound teachings and thoughts that can take some time to discuss. This is because the poem's language is poetic. Another instance of a standard written Igbo poem is Anozie's poem titled 'Uka' (Church) (Poem 19) in *Uche Bu Akpa* (2005). While the whole of the poem is considered to be standard, we shall only draw the first stanza of the poem for illustration in this study:

Katoliiki bu nkwu ocha	(Catholic is palm wine
C.M.S. bu ngwo	C.M.S. is raffia wine
Sharia bu kaikai	Sharia is dry gin
Igba, ekwe na oyo	Drums, wooden gong, and oyo
Bu uka mmuo nsu	For the spiritual churches
Uka na-eweta udo n'owa	Church that brings peace in the world
Naijiria na-adogbusi onwe ha n'uka	Nigeria stress themselves over church issues
Uka buzi ulo ahia	Church has become a marketplace
Onye obula nwere nke ya	Everybody has their own
Maka ego na-achij uwa	Because money controls the world
Tigbuo zogbuo ejula ala a	Kill and trample on has filled this land
Otuotu atufuola ndu ha	Many have lost their lives)

(Anozie, 2005, p. 80)

In the above poem (poem 19), one can easily notice the quality of the poem. The poem requires the reader to think critically to understand it truly. The thought of the poem is not as deep as that of the two earlier-mentioned poems (poems 1 and 18), but its form is high, as it displays the significant role of language in conveying the

meaning of any Igbo poem. This poem will be discussed in the next chapter, when we shall examine the form of Igbo poetry. Let us consider another example of what we regard as standard written Igbo poetry from one of B.M. Mbah's poems, 'Ezi Agbataobi' (Good neighbour) (poem 20) in *Akọnauche* (2006), first and second stanzas, where the poet writes:

Ewu ezi enyi m	Oh! My good friend
Gịni ka m ga-eme	What will I do
Ka i hapu m aka	So that you can leave me
Ka m hapu ura ngwere, baa	So that I can leave the lizard sleep, enter
Ma za oku udo abali?	And answer the night's peaceful call
N'ike gi niile	In all your strength
Na ndu m niile	In all my life
I tinyere mperi	You added your weakness
I bu nkita noro onwe gi	You are a dog staying on your own
Na-akpo m oku uche	Calling me intellectually
(Mbah in Nwadike (ed.) 2006, pp. 138-139)	

Just like the earlier examples of standard written Igbo poems discussed, the above poem 20 also possesses every feature of standard written Igbo poetry. Any student of Igbo poetry can mine the poem's content and form.

4.3 Classification of Poets in Written Igbo Poetry

Having discussed the development of written Igbo poetry in the preceding chapter and the classification of written Igbo poetry based on various criteria, a classification of modern Igbo poets becomes more apparent. On this note, modern Igbo poets can be grouped into two, based on their contributions to the development of poetry as a literary genre. The two categories are: occasional poets and regular poets.

4.3.1 Occasional Poets:

This group of poets was invited to contribute (and they did contribute) once to an anthology, and they never wrote in any other anthology or published their own poetic works. They made their mark and left the Igbo poetic scene. Some of these poets include Nnamdi Oleabara, Iroha O. Iroha, Emeka Egbuchulam, Chidi Emenike, R.M. Ekechukwu, and C.W. Ajaegbu, as seen in *Akpa Uche*, N. B. Obodo, as seen in *Utara Nti*, to mention but a few.

4.3.2 Regular Poets:

This group of modern Igbo poets has contributed to more than one anthology and even published their own poetic text(s). Examples of the poets in this category include J.C. Maduekwe, J.C. Obienyem, N. Emenanjo, G.O. Onyekaonwu, A.K. Obierozi, A.B. Chukuezi, I.U Nwadike, C. Ofomata, L.C. Okoro, Iwu Ikwubuzo, N. Okediadi, C.B. Nnabuihe, and C.C. Anozie. Some of the poets have even edited various Igbo poetic texts. Poets like N. Emenanjo are among the most prominent in this group, as he has edited over four Igbo poetic texts. I.U follows him. Nwadike and C. Ofomata.

4.4 Conclusion

This chapter has discussed classification issues related to the content of written Igbo poetry. The classification done in this chapter is based on the following: classification based on the title, classification based on the sort of verse of written Igbo poetry, and classification of poets in written Igbo poetry. In the next chapter, we shall discuss some predominant themes in written Igbo poetry between 1975 and 2015.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONTENT OF WRITTEN IGBO POETRY II: SOME PREDOMINANT THEMES IN WRITTEN IGBO POETRY FROM 1975-2015

5.0 Introduction

In this chapter, we examine some predominant themes that have dominated Igbo poetic thought over the past four decades of written Igbo poetry (1975-2015). To do this, the present study adopts the mirror-image approach to the sociology of literature to examine various societal issues reflected in the art of modern Igbo poets.

5.1 Some Predominant Themes in Written Igbo Poetry (1975-2015)

Over the past four decades of Igbo written poetry, modern Igbo poets have addressed a range of societal issues of human concern. Some of the issues the poets wrote about are indeed topical issues that mirror the events of the times they lived. The present study limits its focus to topical societal issues of human concern that engaged the attention of modern Igbo poets in the decades under study, and examines poems that address political, cultural, economic, and ecological issues.

5.1.1 Some Political Issues as Mirrored in Written Igbo Poetry

Here, we focus on some poems written over the past four decades whose themes mirror the political situation in society. It is observed that modern Igbo poets over the past four decades have used the instrumentality of their art to mirror, like other societal problems, the effects of poor leadership and corruption, especially in Nigeria.

Some of the advocates of the ‘mirror image approach’ contend that through the literature of a society (poetry in this case), a reader would be able to see the past of that society (Folorunso, 1998). By examining the thoughts expressed in some Igbo poetry, we can see various aspects of societal life reflected in the poets' art. For instance, some modern Igbo poets do portray the effects of poor leadership and corruption in Nigeria and on Nigerians.

5.1.1.1 Poets' Portrayal of the Effects of Poor Leadership and Corruption in Nigeria

In R.M. Ekechukwu’s poem ‘Obodo Anyị’ (Our Country) (Poem 21), he believes that Nigeria is a blessed nation—one that is genuinely blessed by God, with a lot of resources, both solid minerals and fertile land, which produces a lot of farm produce. However, despite all these immense blessings, the poet believes that Nigerians are still living in abject poverty and starvation, given the high level of corruption in the country. In the first stanza of the poem, Ekechukwu states:

Òbòdo ānyị nwèrè ùba òke ukwuù.	(Our nation has a lot of wealth.
Chukwu nyèrè ya ùba dī ichè ichè.	God gave her different wealth.
Mà òkè a nà-ènweta n’àlà,	Both the ones gotten from the land,
Mà òkè a nà-àghọta n’ugbō.	Both the ones gotten from the farm.)
(Ekechukwu in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, pp. 70-71)	

In the stanza above from poem 21, the poet acknowledges that Nigeria is indeed a prosperous and blessed nation. The poet bases his claim (that Nigeria is a blessed nation) on two important factors, namely, the solid minerals found in Nigeria and its agricultural resources. There are many solid minerals in Nigeria, including Talc, Gypsum, Iron Ore, Lead/Zinc, Coal, Gold, and crude oil, to name a few. These minerals generate significant revenue for the nation in international markets, thereby making Nigeria the economic giant of Africa. On the other hand, the land in Nigeria is

very fertile for agriculture. The fertility of Nigerian lands makes agriculture one of the key businesses that thrives in Nigeria. Agriculture was so strong in Nigeria at independence in 1960 that Ogen (2003) described the Nigerian economy as an agricultural economy. According to Ogen (2003), the reason for this is that agriculture served as the engine driving the growth of the Nigerian economy.

As stated earlier in the introductory section of this study, the mirror-image approach views literature as a historical tool, providing an accurate picture of what is happening in society and its circumscribed social facts (Folorunso, 1998). The poet's portrayal of Nigerian economic strength is not fiction but a historical fact. However, the poet reports that despite all the economic endowments of Nigeria, the nation still wallows in poverty, and its citizens die of starvation. This view was clear in the second stanza of the poem (poem 21) where the poet states:

Òbòdo ānyị nwèrè ùba ñkè ukwuù.	(Our nation has a lot of wealth.
Màna à nà-àhụkwa egbē anya	. But do we even see the kite
Tupu è kwuo nà nwaànyị erīghị ya?	Before it is said that a woman
	does not eat it?
Àkù nnà m nò n'òbà, ò bù àkù?	My father's wealth in the barn, is
	it wealth?)
(Ekechukwu in Ekechukwu (Ed.), 1975, p. 71)	

The intermittent repetition of the first line in both the first verse and the second verse above clearly reveals the poet's thought in the poem. Repetition is mainly used in Igbo poetry to emphasise an idea so that its import may be clearly grasped (Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 109). By repeating “Òbòdo ānyị nwèrè ùba ñkè ukwuù” in lines one of the first and second stanzas, the poet draws the reader's attention to the significant thought of the poem, thereby evoking a feeling of anger and disgust in the reader. The thought of the poem becomes apparent in lines two and three of the above stanza 2. It is clear from the second stanza that the poet is satirising Nigerian leaders for their corrupt acts that are now affecting the lives of millions of

Nigerians. The poet's metonymic representation of wealth as a kite in line two above contributes to the thought the poem projects. What the poet is simply saying in stanza 2 of poem 21 is that, despite all the wealth in Nigeria, the people cannot even access it, let alone feel its impact. Instead, the money is deposited into various personal bank accounts at the expense of the masses. The poet closes the poem by sounding a note of warning to Nigerian politicians when he states in stanza 4 of poem 21 that:

Ọ̀ bụ ezi okwū: anya dị mkpà nà-àso ibe ya.	(It is true, an important eye respects the other.
Mà nà chètakwa,	But remember
Ihe nwa ọkukọ mètèrè n'ọkọchị	What the hen did in the dried season
Na-apụtakarị n'ùdu mmiri.	Always comes to light in the rainy season.

(Ekechukwu, in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 71)

The poet's warning to Nigerian corrupt leaders is wrapped in a proverbial ambiance, intended to evoke deep thought. The poet warns Nigerian leaders to be mindful of the consequences of failing to save for the rainy day, which will destroy the nation's future.

Unlike Ekechukwu, Emenanjo (N.d.) is very vocal in his critique of the political class for mismanaging the Nigerian economy, which has plunged many Nigerians into hardship. In his poem 'Ukọ n'Uju' (Scarcity in plenty) (Poem 22) in *Utara Nti*, Emenanjo wonders why Nigeria should have an abundance of resources, yet people suffer as if the nation is a poor country. The tone of his poem 'Ukọ n'Uju' is that of anger, and as such, the poem evokes the feeling of rage towards the political class. The poet believes the political class is to be blamed for the economic woes of the nation, which is a result of deep corruption by the political class. In the first stanza (poem 22), the poet makes his view known when he says

Kèdụ zi kà a gà-ési nọdụ n'anyịm	(How can we be in the ocean.
Wèrè asō na-àkwọ akā?	And washing our hands with saliva?
Kèdụ kwanụ kà a gà-ési nọdụ n'iyī,	How can we also be in the river,
Kwere nchà ọ̀ bàà anyị anya?	And allow soap to enter our eyes.)

(Emenanjo, in Emenanjo (ed.), N.d., p. 29)

The questions raised by the poet here are the same questions most Nigerians ask to date. The poet here acts as the speaker of many Nigerians whose voices cannot be heard. The poet wonders why Nigeria, with all the resources it has, allows its citizens to suffer hunger and starvation. 'Ukọ n'Uju' mirrors the lack, poverty, or deprivation people suffer in Nigeria, despite the nation's abundant economic resources. The poet's anger becomes vivid in stanzas three and four of poem 22, where the poet states:

Koꝛo m ihe kpatara na Mmadu ga-enwe mgbuli Ma mgbuli ana-agu ya?	(Tell me why Someone will have food Yet hunger for food)
Ego a, A si na anyi nwere n'ijeli n'ijeli Bu n'ikuku ka o di Ego a, A si anyi na o bughu ya bu okwu Bu naani n'akwukwo ka o di (Emenanjo, in Emenanjo (ed.), N.d., p. 29)	(This wealth That is said to be available in billions Is only in the air This wealth, That is said not the problem Is only on paper)

Emenanjo in the above verses mirrors the effect of corruption on Nigerians. There are three basic needs of man. They include food, shelter, and clothing. Among these basic needs, food is the most important, since it guarantees man's survival before he can think of shelter and clothing. This is why Emenanjo speaks of food as a key to the survival of many Nigerians. It saddens the poet to note that, despite Nigeria's status as Africa's economic giant, given its agricultural strength, the poor masses can barely find food in the midst of plenty. The poet observes that this state results from corruption and poor leadership in Nigeria.

Emenanjo's rage in 'Ukọ n'Uju' can be better understood when we recall that Nigeria as a nation is believed to have been ravaged by corruption, which has now become a 'cankerworm' to the development of the nation. Moyosore (2015) confirms

that Nigeria is a nation where corruption is at its peak and where the quest for political power by the political class and the greed for material acquisition have relegated the morality preached by various religions to the background. This explains why every society does all it can to prevent acts that could lead to corruption, by any means necessary. From the Emenanjo's tone, it is obvious that there was so much starvation and suffering in the country during the period of the oil boom in Nigeria, a situation that still subsists today. This is why the poet in his fifth stanza of poem 22 asks:

Kòroṛo m̄ ihe kpātara nà	(Tell me why
M̀madu g̀a-ènwe egbùgbèrè	Someone will have lips
M̀a anw̄ à na-àma yā n'ezē?	Yet the sun beats his teeth
Nri à,	This food,
A s̄ ànyị ọ nà ọ bù atur̄ t̀awa,	That we were told is surplus
Ezùghì atur̄ g̀a-àta,	Turns out to be insufficient
̀Nkè ọ nà-àfòdur̄ mm̀ad̀.	Even for the people)
(Emenanjo in Emenanjo (ed.), N.d., p. 29)	

Emenanjo's worry as at the time he wrote the poem in the 1970s, was not out of place as it will puzzle the mind of anyone who knows the amount of resources that Nigeria is blessed with and yet, due to corruption and the continuous subjugation of the poor by the ruling class through their anti-people policies, the poor masses still suffer a great deal. The poem 'Ukọ n'Uju' can be said to be an accurate reflection of the economic situation in Nigeria – scarcity amid plenty.

Like Ekechukwu and Emenanjo's poems, which x-ray the socio-economic situation occasioned by poor leadership and corruption, Ikwubuzo's poem 'Ọrià Anyị' (Our Ailment) (Poem 23) is the portrayal of the effects of poor leadership and corruption. The literal meaning of the title, 'Ọrià anyị', as used by the poet, suggests a type of community disease suffered by a group of people at the same time. Since there has never been a time such a disease was recorded in Igboland, we have to interpret the title with an associative meaning (Suppes, 2009) as the poem suggests. As earlier stated in the second chapter of this study, it is the associative meaning that makes

imagery possible in poetry (Suppes, 2009). The associative meaning of Ikwubuzo’s title ‘Ọrĩa Anyị’ suggests a type of socio-economic ‘disease’. The poem, therefore, reveals that the type of socio-economic disease the poet refers to is the terrible effects of poor leadership and corruption on Nigerians.

The poet, in ‘Ọrĩa Anyị’, brings to bear the image of the harsh economic conditions, which are occasioned by poor leadership, that Nigerians have to endure. The use of the first-person plural ‘anyị’ (us) as employed by the poet in his title suggests that the poet does not exonerate himself as a Nigerian from the epidemic he writes about. This is another pointer to the fact that the poet (Ikwubuzo), as a member of Nigerian society, has first-hand experience of what he addresses. The poet portrays irresponsibility in handling public affairs, lack of accountability, and poor leadership as the bane of the nation, Nigeria, in his poem. A reader who does not understand the thought in this poem ‘Ọrĩa Anyị’ or who exactly the poet addresses in the poem will have a full grasp of the poet’s message when he/she (the reader) encounters the second stanza of this poem (poem 23), where the poet says:

Òbòdò anyị nò n’ọrĩa	(Our country is sick
Ọrĩa ụkọ	Sickness of lack
Ụkọ akamèrè	Man-made lack
Ọrĩa anyị bụ anyaukwu	Our Sickness of greed
“Naanị m gà-èrì	“I alone will eat
Naanị m gà-àba”	I alone will be rich.”
Ọrĩa anyị bụ àsị	Our sickness is lies
Eziokwu gà-àgwọ ya	Truth will heal it
Ọrĩa anyị bụ nchịgbu	Our sickness is tyranny
Ọgwụ ya bụ nchịzi	Its medication is good leadership)

(Ikwubuzo, Ogbulogo, and Okoro, 1992, p. 24)

One cannot help but agree with the poet that tyrannical leadership is indeed one of Nigeria's many problems. Nigeria is a blessed nation, blessed with both abundant natural resources and human capital, yet bereft of good leaders. It can be said that no nation can grow with insincere and visionless leaders piloting its affairs.

This is the problem the poet thinks Nigeria has. This is why the poet considers poor leadership a disease that can kill. From the poet's perspective in the excerpt above (Poem 23), some symptoms of this Nigerian disease include artificial lack, greed, self-centredness, falsehood, and tyranny. The above excerpt (poem 23) also echoes the burning desire of Nigerians to have good leaders, as seen in lines 2-4 of poem 23, where the poet says:

...Ọrĩa ụkọ	(Sickness of lack
Ụkọ akamèrè	Man-made lack
Ọrĩa anyị bụ anyaukwu...	Our Sickness of greed)

(Ikwubuzo et al., 1992, p. 24)

The greed and selfishness of the political class, which the poet speaks of in the above excerpt, have continuously plunged the nation into artificial lack and poverty. This is what the poet means when he says that the lack and poverty in Nigeria are artificial or man-made, and that they follow the self-centeredness and falsehood of the political class. Ogbeidi (2012) supports the view of the poet concerning Nigerian leaders when he states:

Pathetically, the logic of the Nigerian political leadership class has been that of self-service, as some of the leaders are mired in the pursuit of selfish and personal goals at the expense of broader national interests. Consequently, emphasis has been on personal aggrandisement and self-glorification... (p. 3).

The above view supports the poet's position that poor leadership is a terrible sickness Nigeria is suffering from. The poet, however, proffers a solution to this problem in lines 7-10 of poem 23 when the poet says:

Ọrĩa anyị bụ àsị	(Our sickness is lies
Eziokwu gà-àgwọ ya	Truth will heal it
Ọrĩa anyị bụ nchịgbu	Our sickness is tyranny
Ọgwụ ya bụ nchịzi	Its medication is good leadership)

(Ikwubuzo et al., 1992, p. 24)

In the above excerpt from poem 23, the poet identifies the root cause of Nigeria's sickness (problem) and offers an immediate solution. In these concluding lines, the poet summarises Nigeria's problem and classifies it into two significant instruments of corruption: falsehood and tyranny. According to Ikwubuzo, in the above excerpt (lines 7-10), Nigeria can only be healed of her sickness (of poor leadership and corruption) when honest leaders, not despots, emerge to pilot the affairs of the nation.

In another poem, 'Dibija Adugburuja' (Fake Medicine Man) (Poem 24) in *Omenkà*, Ikwubuzo goes further to mirror the adverse effects of poor leadership and corruption in Nigeria and how such has shaped Nigeria's political history. The poem 'Dibija Adugburuja' mirrors the incursion of the military in Nigerian political affairs, the series of failed leadership and its causes in Nigeria. In the poem, Ikwubuzo mirrors the political experiments of Nigeria and the challenges – the problems of self-centeredness, greed, wrong economic policies, and insincerity on the part of the leaders.

It is important to note that this poet consistently masks his title in a striking, creative manner, which means it will take a reader considerable effort to unmask most of his poems truly. From the title of the poem, 'Dibija Adugburuja', the poet paints an image of fake doctors or medicine men – first one, on invitation, was more interested in his own personal gains instead of solving the problems of the sick, and the other, who imposed themselves on the sick, promising to have the solution, which they do not have. The 'Dibija' as mirrored by the poet is a person who ought to be skilled in healing, but they are said to be 'Adugburuja' (Adigboroja), which means 'adulterated' or 'fake'. The image of Nigeria as a sick nation in dire need of a doctor denotes its

chequered experience of bad leadership, which has led to an increase in corruption that now affects every sector of the nation's economy.

The metaphorical representation of Nigerian leaders as fake doctors in the poem's title says a lot about the poet's creativity and the poem's message. This poem follows the earlier poem 'Ọrĩa Anyị' written by the same poet, in which he describes poor leadership and other negative features of corruption as a significant disease in Nigeria. Typically, every sick person needs to engage the services of a doctor, who is believed to be a professional in the act of healing. However, in this case, Nigeria, as a country, is the sick one, a point the poet acknowledges in another poem, 'Ọrĩa Anyị', hence the quest for a good doctor to heal the nation of all her diseases (years of neglect by the political class). Nevertheless, instead of getting good doctors (good leaders) to render the service, the Nigerian electorate (the masses) keep moving from one quack doctor to another, and this informs the title of this poem 'Dibĩa Adụgburujá' (Adịgboroja). In the poem, the poet mirrors the effects of years of poor leadership on the nation's socio-economic life, which, in turn, has negatively shaped the nation's political history. Let us consider the first stanza of this poem to see how the poet puts it (poem 24):

Dibĩa mbụ anyị kpōrō ọrụ	(The first doctor we called to work.
Uwe agbada kà ọ yiri bịa	He came on agbada attire
Agbada ọnụ ya m̀iri emi	Agbada whose mouth is deep
Fọjuchaa ji anyị n'ime ya	Filled it with our tubers of yams
Fọjuchaa ego anyị n'ime ya	Filled it with our money
Maka dibĩa na-agwọ	Because as the doctor heals
Dibĩa a na-èri	The doctor eats
Ọ làwàrà n'inyo	He left in disarray
Hapụ anyị n'ụkọ	And left us in lack.)

(Ikwubuzo et al., 1992, p. 28)

It is worthy of note that this poem 'Dibĩa Adụgburujá' is divided into two stanzas, with each of the stanzas representing two types of leadership that Nigerians have experienced in their political history – civilian rule and military dictatorship. In

each of the forms of leadership the poet mirrors, he chronicles the failures, greed, and insincerity associated with past leaders who have piloted the affairs of the Nigerian state up to the time the poem was published in 1992.

The poet mirrors, first, the civilian leadership that Nigeria enjoyed after its independence from British administrators in 1960. The civilian leaders or politicians are depicted in lines 1-2 of the poem as doctors who are clad in an agbada; this is why the poet says:

Dibija mbu anyi kp̄r̄ō ọrụ	(The first doctor we called to work
Uwe agbada kà ọ yiri bịa	He came on agbada attire...)

In this excerpt from poem 24, the poet represents the electoral process in his first line with the phrase ‘... *anyi kp̄r̄ō ọrụ*’ (that we called to work for us). The import of this clause represents a ‘collective agreement’ in electing a leader. The poet in the above excerpt demonstrates Nigerians' eagerness to see a democratically elected government emerge, after years of colonial rule, which most Nigerians and scholars believe laid the foundation for corruption in Nigeria. Another mirror held up by the poet in the above verse is the portrayal of Nigerian politicians in line 2 as ‘doctors that came on ‘Agbada’. Since Nigeria was presumed to be economically sick, a sickness it inherited from being under colonial rule for many years, it got its first set of doctors, who came in ‘agbada’. In Nigeria, ‘*Agbada*’ is a long robe worn by men among the Hausa and Yoruba (Blench, 2007). The ‘agbada’ is used here to depict civilian (politicians) leaders who have ruled Nigeria in the past. Unfortunately, these civilian leaders, who were democratically elected as representatives of the people, failed Nigerians. Their administration was marred by gross mismanagement of Nigerians' common wealth – an indication of their self-centeredness, greed, wrong economic policies, and insincerity. This is why the poet describes them in line 3 in the above

poem 24 as having ‘Agbada ọ̀nụ̀ ya miri emi’ (Agbada whose pocket is bottomless), which means civilian or political leaders with deep pockets. These were not the kind of leaders Nigerians needed at a time when they were hoping to survive the age-long milking of Nigeria's resources by the British colonial government. The view of the poet in the above verse is better corroborated by Ogbeidi (2012), who states that:

The First Republic, under the leadership of Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, the Prime Minister, and Nnamdi Azikiwe, the President, was marked by widespread corruption. Government officials looted public funds with impunity. Federal representatives and Ministers flaunted their wealth with reckless abandon. In fact, it appeared there were no men of good character in the political leadership of the First Republic. Politically, the thinking of the First Republic Nigerian leadership class was based on politics for material gain, making money and living well (p. 6).

It is important to add at this juncture that the poet also mirrored not only the first republic leaders but also other figures in his poem. The poet refers to politicians in general. The poet also used the stanza one of poem 24, as shown above, to portray also the civilian rule of the second republic, which Shehu Shagari headed from October 1, 1979, to December 31, 1983. This historical revelation and record is what the poet means when he draws the attention of the readers to the function of the *agbada* that those politicians wore in lines 3-5 in the above stanza when he says:

...Agbada ọ̀nụ̀ ya miri emi	(...Agbada whose pocket is deep
Fojuchaa ji anyị n’ime ya	Filled it with our tubers of yams
Fojuchaa ego anyị n’ime ya...	Filled it with our money...)
(Ikwubuzo, et. al., 1992, p. 28)	

The ‘agbada’, according to the poet in the above excerpt from poem 24, signifies the means of siphoning monies meant for the masses into their personal bank accounts. By doing this, the political class bastardised the economy and promoted systemic corruption. The image of Nigeria’s wealth is depicted in lines 4-5, with

‘yam’ (line 4), which is repeated stylishly for clarity and emphasis in line 5. In the pre-colonial Igbo society, a man’s wealth was judged by the size of his yam barn and his household. This is why the poet used ‘yam’ in line 4 to represent the nation’s wealth. The poor leadership that has encouraged economic looting by the civilian governments over the years leaves the poor masses suffering and worse off than they were under the British government. This was why the poet says in lines 8-9 of the above stanza from poem 24:

...Ọ làwàrà n’inyo	(He left in disarray
Hapụ anyị n’ụkọ	And left us in lack.)

It was this despicable situation of Nigerians caused by the mismanagement of Nigerian resources by the civilian political class that encouraged military incursion into politics, and this led to the end of the first republic and marked the beginning of military rule in Nigeria. The military cited the excesses of the civilian politicians and corruption as the reason for their intervention, promising to fix the problems created by the civilian leaders. This insincere promise by the military to fix Nigeria’s problem is what the poet (Ikwubuzo) mirrors in the opening lines of the second stanza of poem 24 when he says:

Anyị gà-agwọta unù	(We will cure you
Anyị ji ajuogwu bịa	We came with the antidote
Ka dibịa ọkpọta onwe ya gwara anyị	Was what the self-imposed doctor told us
Dibịa uwe kààkị	Doctor on Kaaki uniform
Buru ọgwụ saapụ bịa	Came with S.A.P medicine
Ị sapụ anyị unyi ụkọ	To wash away the dirt of lack
Dibịa agbada terè anyị	Which the doctor on <i>agbada</i> attire smeared on us with
Uwe ha bu àkpà akpa n’ahụ	Their clothes had lots of pockets
Karịa uwe agbada anyị hụrụ na mbụ	More than the <i>agbada</i> we earlier saw
Mgbe a fojuru akpa e bu bịa	When they filled the bag, they came with
Ihe e kwuru n’obịbịa	What was said on arrival
Abụghịkwa ihe e kwuru n’ula	Was no longer what was said on departure

Ìsapu unyi ụkọ ga-ewe oge	Washing away the dirt of lack will take time
Onye unyi tere nwee ndidi	Whoever was smeared with dirt, be patient.)
(Ikwubuzo, et. al. 1992, p. 28)	

Just like in his first verse, the poet uses “Dibija Uwe Kaaki” in this second stanza to represent the military-led government that interrupted the democratically elected government in Nigeria. ‘Kaaki’ here connotes military uniform. Unlike the first line in stanza one of this poem 24, which shows collective agreement in electing a leader, the clause ‘dibija ọkpota onwe ya’ as used in the above stanza connotes ‘self-imposition’, ‘force’, and ‘undemocratic regime’. The poet uses the expression to refer to a government that the people did not elect; they self-imposed themselves forcefully on Nigerians, promising to fix the problems created by the civilian leaders, as seen in lines 1-3 of the above stanza two from poem 24, where the poet says:

Anyị gà-agwọta unù	(We will cure you
Anyị ji ajuogwu bịa	We came with the antidote
Ka dibija ọkpota onwe ya gwara anyị	Was what the self-imposed doctor told us...)

In their bid to turn the country’s economy around for good, the military under the regime of Ibrahim Babangida created an economic recovery programme known as the Structural Adjustment Programme (S.A.P). This situation is what the poet is referring to in lines 4-7 of the above stanza two from poem 24, when he says:

...Dibija uwe kaàki	(Doctor on Kaaki uniform
Buru ọgwụ saapu bịa	Came with <i>Saapu</i> (S.A.P) medicine
Ì sapu anyị unyi ụkọ	To wash away the dirt of our lack
Dibija agbada terè anyị...	Which the doctor on <i>agbada</i> smeared us with...)

Corroborating the view of the poet as regards this programme of the military (Structural Adjustment Programme) and explaining the reason for the creation of the S.A.P. Ogbonna (2012, pp. 52-53) citing (NCEMA, 2008, p. 3) asserts that in a bid to

reverse the dwindling economic fortunes of the nation in terms of declining growth, high rate of poverty in the country, increased unemployment, inflation, worsening balance of payment conditions and enfeeble debt burden, among others, government began to take austerity measures in 1982. In response to the minimal impacts of the government measures, an extensive structural adjustment programme (S.A.P.) was implemented in 1986. Much focus was placed on expenditure reduction and expenditure switching policies, as well as on making the private sector the engine of economic growth through the commercialisation and privatisation of government-owned enterprises. There would not have been a need for the introduction of the S.A.P. programme if the past government had been prudent in their spending, honest, and above all, made policies that would benefit the general public and not just themselves.

Unfortunately for Nigerians, despite creating this structural adjustment programme, the military plunged Nigeria into a worse economic situation than the civilian leaders. That is why the poet describes them in lines 8-9 as wearing clothes with more pockets than those worn by civilian leaders. In the words of the poet:

Uwe ha bu àkpà akpa n’ahụ	(There were lots of pockets on their clothes)
Karịa uwe agbada anyị hụrụ na mbụ...	More than the <i>agbada</i> attire we earlier saw)

These military leaders were worse because their system of leadership was autocratic. They did not ask for approval before doing certain things. The military was so corrupt that the promise of good leadership they made to the people upon taking over power from the civilian leaders was never fulfilled. This is captured by the poet in lines 10-12 of the second stanza from poem 24, where the poet says:

Mgbe a fojuru akpa e bu bịa	(When they filled the bags, they came with
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Ihe e kwuru n'òbìbja
Abùghikwa ihe e kwuru n'ùla...

What was said on their arrival
Was no longer what they said on their
departure.)

Here, the poet alludes to the military's disappointing statement intended to calm the apparently disappointed people when the government's failure was apparent. The poet, however, ends the poem by encouraging Nigerians that, although fixing Nigeria's problems will take longer than usual, they should be patient and hopeful for better days. He made this clear in the last two lines (13-14) of his second stanza above, when he states:

...Ìsapu unyi ùkọ ga-ewe oge (...Washing away our dirt of lack will take
time.
Onye unyi tere nwee ndidi... Whoever gets dirty, be patient...)

Dirt is anything that symbolises shame, which in the case of the above excerpt is lack, bad economy, occasioned by poor leadership and corruption. This is why the poet, having mirrored the effects of poor leadership and corruption, concludes by satirically crediting the concluding statement to the military, who were encouraging the people to be patient with the structure, as it would take a while to fix things.

Ogbulogo (1992), in his own poem 'Ọtanisi' (Poem 25) in *Omenkà*, mirrors a subsisting socio-economic reality in Nigeria. The reason for this is that the dire socio-economic situation in the country (Nigeria), as at the time Ogbulogo wrote his poem 'Ọtanisi', has continued unabated and can be said to have even grown worse. The poem can be seen as a true reflection of the distrust most Nigerians have towards their leaders. The poem portrays the despicable effects of poor leadership and the country's corruption, which is perpetuated by the ruling class at the time and even prior to the poem's publication. The poet expresses his utmost displeasure at how corruption has ravaged Nigeria's economy. The poem captures the views of the general public and

the poor, who feel the direct impact of the bad leadership and corruption. The thrust of the poem ‘Ọtanisi’ can be seen in the first stanza of the poem (Poem 25) where the poet says:

Onu m edetughi ya, Bu nri e siri n’akukù Naija;	(My mouth did not taste it The food that was cooked beside the Niger
Anya m ahughikwa ya, Bu akpa ego e bufèrè òfesi Iji wuo obodo oku na-enwu n’elu Ma na Sùwizi mà nà Nuyokù Nke e ji òbàrà m tee mgba ihu na azu	My eyes did not also see it The bag of money taken oversees To build the developed nations Both in Switzerland and New York Which my blood was used to paint front and back
Ma jiri okpokoroisi m choo ukpo ya mma (Ikwubuzo, et. al., 1992, p. 29)	And beautified with my skull)

From the tone of the poet in the above stanza of our poem 25, it is clear that the poet is sad at the way corruption has plunged the economy of the nation into ruin, as the ruling class siphons the nation’s funds to foreign lands. When the poet says in lines 1-2 (Poem 25) that his mouth did not taste the food cooked beside the Niger, he refers to millions of Nigerians who sat hungry and watched as their national treasury was emptied by the political elite (the rich and powerful). At the same time, there was so much hunger in the street. The actions of successive governments and their devastating effects on many Nigerians appear to be the primary reason the poet (Ogbulogo) wrote this poem.

Economic historians record that, with Babangida as Nigeria’s Head of State, from August 1985, corruption was officially institutionalised in Nigeria (Osoba, 1996; Nwobi, 2004; Aluko, 2009). It was under the leadership of Ibrahim Babangida, whose regime introduced various austerity measures and economic policies that past military governments implemented, that the poet (Ogbulogo) appears to be referring to in his poem ‘Ọtanisi’, which is the Igbo coinage for austerity. Despite various government efforts to revamp the nation’s economy, money belonging to the entire country keeps

disappearing and is deposited in offshore Swiss and New York banks, while the masses suffer. This is what the poet refers to in lines 4-7 (poem 25) when he says:

...Bụ àkpa ego e bufèrè òfesi	(The bag of money taken oversees
Iji wuo obodo oku na-enwu n'elu	To build the developed nations
Ma na Sùwizi mà nà Nuyokù	Both in Switzerland and New York
Nke e ji òbàrà m tee mgba ihu na azu	Which my blood was used to paint front and back.)

At the time the poet wrote this poem in 1992 (and even to date), 60% of Nigerian citizens were (and are) living in poverty (African News Service (ANS), cited in Nnamani, 2004). This poverty is rooted in homelessness, hunger, unemployment, and infrastructural decay, to mention a few. It is this view of the poor that the poet portrays in the second stanza of his poem (poem 25) 'Otanisi' when he says:

Ahughị m idei ahụ	(I did not see that flood
Nke bufuru ehie m	That carried away my afternoon
Nke zafuru olileanya m	That swept away my hopes
Ma refuo odiniihu umu m	And sold the future of my children)

(Ikwubuzo, et. al., 1992, p. 29)

In the above excerpt, the poet (Ogbulogo) summarises the thoughts, fears, and concerns of most Nigerians, who awake to news of looting and lies from the political class. The poet, here, demonstrates that he was not writing in isolation but as a member of a society that shared those fears and thoughts. In the stanza above, from poem 25, the poet mirrors the psychological state of most Nigerians who have lost hope for the future in the face of poor leadership and widespread corruption in the country. All the lines in the above stanza promote a single thought, which is anchored on the state of hopelessness. As the stanza above shows, the future appears bleak. That is why the poet refers to corruption as a flood that swept away the hope and future of many Nigerians.

Ogbulogo’s portrayal of the effects of poor leadership and corruption focuses more on its psychological and emotional effects on the general public. The second verse of the poem summarises the poem's thought, thereby making the emotion it evokes more apparent: anger and hatred against the insensitive and corrupt government. The two stanzas discussed above evoke pity, sadness, and deep sorrow. This emotive response that the poem stirs up follows a proper understanding of the gravity of the issues the poet raises.

Another poet who addresses the issue of poor leadership and corruption in Nigeria is Okediadi. For her, poor leadership and corruption in Nigeria manifest as tyranny, bribery, and greed. Okediadi also believes that Nigeria is indeed a blessed nation, but the nation has been unlucky in terms of leadership. Okediadi begins her poem with praise for the Nigerian nation, itemising the key blessings it is endowed with. In her opinion, some of the blessings that God gave to Nigeria include honey, milk, riches, and fertile land. She makes this known in the first stanza of her poem, “Niajiria” (Nigeria) (poem 26), where she says:

Obodo mmanu ańụ,	(A nation of honey
Mmiri ara ehi na-eru n’ime ya	Milk flows in it
Akunauba ka Ekè ji chọọ gị mma	Wealth is what the Creator beautified you with
Ala oma bukwa ugwu nye gị	Good land is also a thing of honour to you)
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 20)	

Indeed, the poet is right in her views as regards to the Nigerian state in the above stanza. The blessings, which God gave Nigeria, according to the poet in the above stanza (poem 26), are both natural resources and a landscape that is devoid of natural disasters like earthquakes, volcanoes, and other forms of natural disaster that are witnessed in other parts of the world. The reason for this praise is to prepare the mind of the reader to see the point she is about to make in the poem. Despite all these praises for Nigeria, the poet makes a sharp turn and begins to satirise Nigerian

leaders, whom she strongly believes are responsible for the country's poor economic situation. The poet refers to Nigerian leaders as tyrants who enjoy bribery and corruption and, in doing so, have put the nation to shame. The poet brings this thought to bear in the third stanza of poem 26, where the poet states:

Ndị ọchịchị nchịgbu	(Tyrants
Unu eteela ala anyị unyi n'ihu	You people have put our nation to shame.
Fo nfoju akpa bu egwu okukụ na	Bribery is your beat and
Egwu ọgbugba unu	Your dance steps
Ndị kama ọ ga-adọ n'ite	People who insist than rather than leave it in the pot
Ka ọ dọrọ n'afọ.	Let it be left in their bellies.)

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 20)

Two aspects of corruption portrayed in the above stanza are tyranny and bribery. The poet's reference to Nigerian leaders as tyrants here (stanza three of poem 26) depicts their cruel and wicked style of leadership, which they exercise by giving and taking bribes to enforce anti-people policies that serve only their selfish needs and egos. The poet believes that the two weapons of corruption identified in the stanza have indeed given Nigeria a bad name on the international stage. The idiomatic expression employed in line 2 in the above excerpt is used to depict the shame or disgrace that the leading class has brought on the nation. The poet further notes that greed and covetousness are significant problems that drive Nigerian leaders to accept and offer bribes.

In her fourth stanza, the poet accuses Nigerian leaders of enriching themselves at the expense of the poor masses, which is why she likens them to mosquitoes. In the words of Okediadi in the fourth stanza of her poem, she states:

Chei! Unu bu anwunta.	(Chei! you are mosquitoes
Unu amikpọla umu mmadu ọbara	You have sucked all the human blood
Nti unu dizi ka nke awo nujuru mmiri afo	Your ears is like a toad that drank water in excess
Afo unu dizi ka ite mmiri	Your tommy is like a pot of water
Onye rie, o ga-erifokwara onye ozo?	He who eats, will he remain for another person?)

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 21)

The metaphorical representation of the Nigerian political class as a mosquito in the stanza above depicts their undying hunger to feed on the resources of the poor masses. The above stanza four portrays the day-to-day experiences of the poor in a nation like Nigeria. The poor masses, who strive to feed their families, are daily subjected to several kinds of extortions by the political class. All these are what the poet refers to in the second line of the above stanza four from poem 26, when she talks about “Unu amikpoola umu mmadu obara” (You have sucked all the human blood). The ‘blood’, here, signifies anything that helps the poor to survive, which in this case is their resources. The poor are forced to pay taxes, higher rents, utility bills (electricity, water, security, etc.), and higher prices for foodstuffs. At the end, these monies find their way into the pockets of the politicians in the corridors of power. That is why in lines 3-4, the poet employs a simile to represent greedy politicians who have amassed public funds. In the last stanza of poem 26, the poet blames Nigerian leaders for being too greedy, which is why they easily fall prey to the temptation of corruption.

Ndi oke ochicho!	(Greedy people
Unu hiwere amuma di iche iche	You organised a lot of prophesies
O bu nke gini?	What is it for?
I nyere ndi uwa na-atu n'onu aka	To help the less privileged
Onye ka o rukwaranu aka?	Who even received it?
N'akpa unu ka ha bachara.	They entered into your pockets.
Ndi ochichi nchigbu ndonu!	Tyrants sorry!

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 21)

Here (stanza 5), the poet summarises her thought in the poem by alluding to all the false campaign promises the leaders make, as seen in lines 2-5. The poet believes that this is also the basis of corruption, as these politicians raise people's hopes, only to shatter them. However, instead of fulfilling those promises, they divert

public funds to their personal bank accounts. This is what the poet is referring to in line 6 when she writes “N’akpa unu ka ha bachara” (They entered into your pockets). This view is supported by Moyosore (2015:23), who believes that corruption is responsible for so many dashed hopes and broken promises that now characterise the lives of many Nigerians. ‘Pockets’ in the fifth stanza of poem 26 above is used to refer to individual bank accounts. Based on this poem, we can categorically state that Okediadi’s portrayal of the effects of poor leadership and corruption focuses more on satirising corrupt politicians who prey on the poor masses for personal aggrandisement.

Ekegbo is another poet who criticises poor leadership and corruption in Nigeria in his poem, “Ngari” (Bribery) (poem 27) in *Uwa Onye na Chi Ya* (2005). In this poem, the poet bemoans the adverse effects of corruption on Nigeria, identifying bribery as a significant form of corruption. According to Ekegbo, in the first stanza of the poem:

Ngari na aka azu na-atu ka gari na mbido,
Ndi na-eri ha nke oma na-eji ha etu onu:
Mana n’ezie o na-ahapu otutu n’oke aguu,
Na-abukwa nnukwu ihe mgbu nyere obodo.
(Ekegbo, 2005, p. 29)

(Bribery and corruption are as sweet as garri at the beginning,
Those who indulge in them well boast in it:
But truthfully, it leaves many in great hunger,
Furthermore, it is a source of great pain to the nation.)

As seen here, Ekegbo views bribery as an aspect of corruption that has done more harm to Nigeria than good. No wonder Otite (1986) sees corruption as the perversion of integrity or affairs through bribery, favour, or moral depravity. Indeed, Ekegbo rightly captures the Nigerian situation in the stanza above, as it has been observed over the years that the political class is usually the one that continuously

perverts the course of justice and social order, and causes inflation in Nigeria through bribery and corruption.

However, the poet acknowledges that, though some leaders have made recent attempts to combat corruption in Nigeria, the level of bribery and corruption will be impossible to eliminate, since it has become a culture in Nigeria. In the words of the poet (Ekegbo) in the last stanza of the poem:

Naijiriya chalitere n'ikpeazu site n'ihe ndi a,
Ma garigari ha bu nke kwesiri onyinyo;
Ka ajo ihe banyechagaro otutu n'ime okpukpu,
O ga-esi ike isi n'ihe ndi a nwetakwa ezi mbido.

(Ekegbo, 2005, p. 30)

(Nigeria awoke lately from these things,
But their efforts are something that should be suspect;
After bad things have entered the bone marrow of many people,
It will be challenging to have a fresh start from these things.)

From the tone of the poet in stanza four of poem 27, it is obvious that the poet, having been in Nigeria for too long, has seen how long the political class has promoted corruption through bribery and other forms of corrupt acts in the past. This is why the poet is doubtful of the Nigerian government's supposed fight against corruption, as he believes it is insincere. Again, the poet believes that the menace of bribery and corruption has extended to every sector of the Nigerian public and has already destroyed the fabric of Nigeria's economy.

Adding her voice to the problem of poor leadership in Nigeria, Oleru in her poem 'Ochichi' (Leadership) (Poem 28) in *Akonnauche* (2006) bemoans the insincerity of Nigerian politicians and leaders who go about making campaign promises but when they eventually get elected into office, they turn their back on the people; therefore, basic infrastructure in the nation continue to deteriorate. The tone of her poem suggests that, like every other Nigerian, the poet is unhappy with how Nigerian leaders have managed the country's finances. In the poem, the poet (Oleru) satirises

Nigerian past and present leaders for their nonchalant attitude towards developing the nation's basic infrastructure. In the second stanza of the poem, the poet says (poem 28):

Aga m aga n'elu gaa biri
Ndi bi n'ala ahujuola anya
Tunyere m vootu, tunyere m vootu
Aga m enye unu oku, mmiri,
ezigbo uzọ, gi tunyere ha, ha merie, n'ikpe azu
Eju olee nne gi, kukororo.
Nrugbu gbaa afo onye a na-arugbu amara
Mmadu o na-emegbu dibia na-agwo ya?
Ndi ochichi ga-aza nke a

(Oleru in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 18)

(I will go to the sky
Those living on the ground have seen a lot
Vote for me, vote for me
I will provide you, people, with light, water,
good roads, when you vote for them, and they win, at last
Did they keep their promise?
When cheating is entrenched, the victim finds out
Does someone maltreat the doctor who heals him?
The leaders will answer this.)

From the image of Nigerian leaders' leadership style, as presented by the poet in the stanza above, one can see the self-serving attitude of most Nigerian leaders, a problem Nigeria still faces to date. They always know the people's needs and use them as a tool for campaigning, and people vote for them in the hope that their basic needs will be taken care of. However, instead of fixing the problem, they exploit people's emotions to win elections, only to turn around and abandon them. All the basic amenities listed by the poet: electricity, water, and good roads have always been issues of great concern to Nigerians, due to their poor state. This is why the poet, in the stanza above, frowns on the insincerity of Nigerian leaders, who turn a blind eye to the people's fundamental challenges after winning elections.

The poet (Oleru) further blames Nigerian leaders for the insensible dilapidation of basic needs in the country, such as rising insecurity, an epileptic power

supply, and a fallen standard of education. The poet, like every Nigerian, believes that these are results of poor leadership and corruption. The poet expresses this thought clearly in the third stanza of poem 28, where she says:

Aga m aga n'elu gaa biri	(I will go up and live
Ujọ ụwa atugbuola	I am afraid of the world
Umụ mmadu ofufu ofufu	People missing
Ego nri, i huru n'abee?	Money for food, where will you go?
Oku mpinyumpinyu	Epileptic power supply
A guo akwukwo taa, onwa ato a gubeghi ozo	School in session today, and three months not in session
Onye ga-achuru Mbieri ndi ara?	Who is going to drive mad people away for Mbieri?
Ndi ochichi ga-aza nke a.	The leaders will respond to this.)

(Oleru in Nwadike (ed.) 2006, pp. 18-19)

Here, the poet mirrors the everyday experience of Nigerians, who feel the effect of the poor leadership of the leading class. Every picture of society presented in the third stanza of poem 28 above, by the poet, captures the pain Nigerians endure daily. Kidnapping has now become a form of business to some people. In some cases, the kidnappings are politically engineered and targeted against political opponents. Some irresponsible unemployed youths have also taken to kidnapping and other vices as a means of survival. This is the view expressed in lines 3 of the above third stanza when the poet says “Umụ mmadu ofufu ofufu”. This goes to say that people are not even safe in the nation anymore.

Apart from these unscrupulous elements in society, some responsible Nigerians who want to make an honest living are denied the power supply needed for different small-scale businesses. The same goes with many other families and businesses that depend on power supply to make a living. Incessant power outage is the point expressed by the poet in line 5 of stanza 3 of poem 28, where she says “Oku mpinyumpinyu”.

From the foregoing, it is apparent that Igbo poets are unanimous in their conviction that poor leadership and corruption are the key problems confronting the Nigerian state. According to the poets, the political class is to blame for the destruction caused by poor leadership and corruption to the moral fabric of society. This amounts to people suffering in a country with abundant wealth.

5.1.2 Some Cultural Issues Mirrored in Written Igbo Poetry

As a people, the Igbo are known for loving and cherishing their culture. Everything the Igbo do is according to the way their culture stipulates it, hence the expression that ‘omenala’ (culture) means more than just a word to the Igbo. For the Igbo, their culture embodies their ways of life, fashion, beliefs, religion, trade, etc.. All these are combined in the term *ome-na-ala*, which literally translates “what obtains in the land”. When a person’s practice contradicts the way things are usually done in the land, it is often said that such an individual does *ome n’elu*.

The Igbo way of life is also mirrored in their literature (oral and written). This means that some cultural issues are captured in the Igbo poetic works from the decades under study. The cultural issues discussed in this study are among the significant issues that some poets have focused on.

By way of introduction, just as other human concerns that capture the attention of modern Igbo poets do, cultural issues draw their attention, hence the prevalence of cultural themes in written Igbo poetry over the four decades under study. Let us highlight some of them.

5.1.2.1 Representation of the *Ogbanje* Phenomenon as a Socio-Cultural and Psychological Problem in Written Igbo Poetry.

The belief in the existence of the *ogbanje* among the Igbo is deeply rooted in Igbo belief. Belief systems have been described by Uche and Uche (2013) as one of the integral pillars of any society and, as such, help people provide answers to many occurrences that cannot be logically explained. Six Igbo poets each wrote a poem to explain the menace of the age-long phenomenon known as *ogbanje* among the Igbo. The poets whose works mirror the Igbo belief in the *ogbanje* phenomenon include, I.E. Akoma in *Akpa Uche* (1975:8), J.C. Maduekwe, in his *Nkà Okwu* (1979:18), J.N. Onwuchekwa, in *Akpaalokwu* (1983:16), A.K. Obierozie in his *Ekpe Nna* (1986:5), A.B. Chukuezi, in his *Akọ Bụ Ndu* (1988:28), and J.A. Onuoha in *Akọnauche* (2006:191).

The modern-day medicine and health education have tried their best to dismiss the *ogbanje* phenomenon as superstition. However, despite all modern interventions, the *ogbanje* phenomenon has persisted across different Igbo societies. Uche and Uche (2013) argue that the *ogbanje* phenomenon remains the reference point for discussing the social and medical challenges faced by children and adults whose sickness cannot be scientifically diagnosed. *Ogbanje* is one of the phenomena that have defied scientific and logical explanations. The complex nature of the *ogbanje* phenomenon explains why scholars also add their voices to explain it. Scholars such as Uzuoku (1982), Achebe (1986), Okafor (1998), Ilechukwu (2007), Harler (2013), Ekwakor (2013), and Uche and Uche (2013) have contributed to the discussion of the *ogbanje* phenomenon. Among all these scholars, Achebe's (1986) study on the *Ogbanje* is most comprehensive and detailed. Uzuoku (1982), while discussing the Igbo world and ultimate reality and meaning, explains that *ogbanje*, in line with the Igbo belief, is the composition of the human person. Achebe's (1986) book on *ogbanje*, *The World of Ogbanje*, provides a deeper understanding of the phenomenon by revealing its

types, their character traits, and possible ways society has handled issues related to it in the past. Okafor (1998) mentions *ogbanje* as one of the metaphysical beliefs of the Igbo. Ilechukwu (2007) studies the cultural conceptualisation of the *ogbanje* phenomenon, viewing it as psychopathological. Harler (2013) and Ekwakor (2013) all explain *ogbanje* from the scholars' point of view. Let us investigate how the six modern Igbo poets have represented the *ogbanje* phenomenon in their works.

I. E. Akoma's poem, "Ogbanje" in Ekechukwu (Ed.)s *Akpa Uche* (1975) (Poem 29) focuses on the *ogbanje* phenomenon. Akoma's poem mirrors the devastating effect of *ogbanje* on families. The poet draws readers' attention to the dangers this phenomenon poses to society, both psychologically, socially, and spiritually. The poet begins the exposition of *ogbanje* by mirroring it as a malevolent spirit who takes the shape of a child about to be born, only to die shortly after, leaving the family heartbroken and destabilised. The image of *ogbanje* that Akoma presents also draws people's attention to measures a parent or parents can take to prevent the birth of an *ogbanje* child in their families. The poem reveals the Igbo belief that an *ogbanje* child can be born to a family up to seven times before it decides to terminate the earthly circle. Each time the *ogbanje* dies, it leaves the victim exhausted, broken, and psychologically battered (Orji, 1999). It is this state of grief and misgiving that inspires the tone of the first six lines of Akoma's poem (p.8). The emotion in the poem is heightened in lines 7-12, when the poet reveals the parents' past efforts to confirm whether their child is truly an *Ogbanje* and to pacify the spirit to show mercy and break the *ogbanje* detestable circle (poem 29).

... Nwa alō àhusiela anyā
Nke a ọ bughị mkpịsiri aka ochie?
Anyị dābirì ya ka ị ghara ịbịa ọzọ

E nyēwo ụmụ ebiri òkè
E mēela ụmụ akā sarakā

(Nwa alo has suffered
Is this not the old finger
We cut it off to prevent you from
coming again
The age grade has been given its due
The children have been hosted to a feast

Ihe ndị à bù kà o si chọọ... All these are the way it wants it
 Ò bù gini fòdùrù? What is remaining? ...)
 (Akoma in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 8)

Here, the poet clearly portrays the feelings of most families who are unfortunate enough to have been visited by the *ogbanje* spirit children. The speaker (a father) in this poem recognises the child he believes has been coming and going (dying). This is a man who has done virtually everything he could think of to prevent subsequent births of the *ogbanje* child, but he has repeatedly failed in his attempts, and now he is going to bury the *ogbanje* child for the fifth time. He is disturbed, heartbroken, and psychologically disturbed (a common feature of all those who are once faced with this type of problem).

In traditional Igbo society, when parents suspect that they have an *ogbanje* child, they perform some rituals to prevent the child from dying. Some of those rituals include leaving marks on the baby's body, giving some sacrifices to the marine spirits (in a case where the child is believed to have come from the 'Nne mmiri'), preparing a feast of 'saraka', which is ceremonial feast for children in order to procure the favour of the spirits to free the child, from dying as reflected in Akoma's poem. However, after all these attempts to prevent the child who is believed to be an *ogbanje* from dying, and the child eventually dies, the corpse of the child is usually subjected to some forms of indignity and, in some cases, mutilated with a view to preventing the return of the spirit child. Uche and Uche (2013) are of the view that there has not been any scientific explanation for the mutilation and scars that are left on the body of the child, to identify and track the child as they come. This is why the poet talks about the child's finger being amputated in lines 8-9 (poem 29). Cutting off the child's finger, toe(s) or leaving a significant mark on the *ogbanje* corpse before its burial proves to be an effective way of tracking an *ogbanje*'s visits, confirming if a child is an *ogbanje*

or not. Unfortunately, when such a child reincarnates, the child comes bearing those marks. This is one of the things that makes the *ogbanje* too complex to understand and, as such, it defies every form of scientific explanation.

J.C. Maduekwe is the second poet who mirrors the aftereffects of the *ogbanje*'s demise on the family left to mourn. In Igbo society, when a child discovered to be an *ogbanje* dies, people do not cry or try to mourn the way a non-*ogbanje* child is mourned. Usually, the *ogbanje* is buried in a shallow grave in a bid to punish and disgrace it so that it should not bother to return. The corpse is usually manhandled and, in some cases, burnt as depicted in Akoma's poem. In a bid to put the *ogbanje*, whose intention is usually to see the family heartbroken, to shame, some Igbo families resolve not to shed tears for the *ogbanje* child when it dies. This is the case presented in the first verse of Maduekwe's poem 'Ubochi Nwata Nwuru' (The day the child died) (Poem 30) in *Nka Okwu*, where the poet says:

Nwatà ahụ ànwụọla!	(That child has died
Ọ bughị ọrụ dịrị ndị okènye àlà,	It is not the responsibility of the elders of the land
Itīwērē ya abịà na ìkūwa ekwe.	To beat the <i>abịa</i> and play the wooden gong in its honour
Ò kweghị dị ndụ sòro mee ihe ndị à.	It does not want to live to do these things
Ihe onye mèrè nà-àbịara ya ụlò ọnwụ.	The things one does attend their funeral.)
(Maduekwe, 1979, p. 18)	

Here, Maduekwe presents a mirror image that focuses on the Igbo burial of an *ogbanje*. There are individuals for whom the Igbo society does not honour their death. First are the person(s) who commit(s) suicide or take their own life. Secondly, someone killed by the oracle or gods as a result of an oath, which he or she took or an evil he or she has done. It is these two types of death that Noon (1942) refers to as *onwu mkpuchi* (covered death). Because the *ogbanje* child is believed to be aware of when it wants to die and does as planned, some see it as a type of death that can be classified as suicide, which does not require the honour of a second burial.

The position the poet gives the speaker in this poem is a position of strength, and not of despair, as Akoma does in his picture of *ogbanje*. The speaker, having lost the *ogbanje* child to another round of death, encourages himself to be strong and not let the spirit child, which enjoys seeing people suffer, see her as weak. Maduekwe ends the poem by also mirroring the treatment given to the corpse of an *ogbanje* in Igbo land. This is seen in the last stanza of Maduekwe's poem (poem 30).

Nwa ̄ogbanje, ̄ biakwa ̄z̄o n'ulo à
 Kà o mere ̄n̄ ̄nw̄ akugh̄i mkpuru n'ụwa,
 O bù àpà ala, ò bugh̄i ah̄ ̄ pàrà b̄ia ala
 M̄a e bègh̄i ya m̄kp̄is̄i aka, a map̄ ̄ ya nti.
 Ihe onye n̄a-èmè na-àb̄iara ya ̄lo ̄nw̄
 (Maduekwe, 1979, p. 20)

(The *ogbanje* child has come again to this house
 It has made the mouth of death so that no seed can be planted on earth
 It is going with scars; it is not going with the same body it came with
 If its finger is not cut off, the ear will be cut off
 The things one does attend their funeral)

In the above excerpt from poem 30, the poet acknowledges that indeed it is an *ogbanje* child and agrees with Akoma about the mutilation of some parts of the *ogbanje*'s corpse as a way of punishing the spirit and breaking the chain of its succession of birth or rebirth. This treatment of the *ogbanje* in Maduekwe's poem demonstrates its rejection by society. This is why the speaker in the poem takes solace in the fact that even the *ogbanje* spirit has received a considerable amount of punishment, going by the fact that it is not returning to the spirit world the way it came.

J.N. Onwuchekwa's poem "Ogbanje" in *Akpaala Okwu* (Poem 31) is the third poem that also reflects the Igbo's hatred of the *ogbanje*. Just like those of Akoma and Maduekwe, Onwuchekwa's poem 'Ogbanje' mirrors the Igbo understanding of *ogbanje* as a group of malevolent spirits who roam in search of families to destroy. Because the Igbo do not consider *ogbanje* as capable of any good, they abhor it and

warn it never to return, even though they subtly know that warning the *ogbanje* alone never to return does not usually prevent the *ogbanje* from returning to that same family. The mood that ushers in Onwuchekwa’s poem on *ogbanje* is that of bitterness, where the speaker, at the point of burying the *ogbanje* child, warns the *ogbanje* never to return to their family again. Onwuchekwa ends the poem by confirming the Igbo belief that the *ogbanje* does not work alone; instead, they are spirits on assignment and, as such, work as a group. This is why the poet writes in the last stanza, saying (poem 31):

Ha dunye gi edunye,	(If they send you,
Abiaghachila ozo.	Do not come again
Ya kwara na nke i biara abia	Let it end with your present visit.
Soro ugba gbafuo	Follow the ugba and run away.
Chee ihu ebe i chere ekwo gi	Face where the back of your head faces
Esitela uzo a ozo	Never travel this road again)
(Onwuchekwa, 1983, p. 16)	

The use of the third-person plural pronoun “Ha” in the first line, as used by the poet, depicts a group that sends the *ogbanje* spirit on an assignment. The Igbo believe that this group, which the *ogbanje* spirit originally belongs to in the spirit world, is one of malevolent spirits that work together and carefully choose their victim (to whom the *ogbanje* spirit is sent). This group of spirits has the power to decide which family members to visit and when to die (Harler, 2013). It is not clear what criteria the *ogbanje* uses in selecting its victims, or whose service it is performing by entering a particular family or womb. The poet points out in the above excerpt that some discussion takes place in the spirit world, and in that discussion, a victim is chosen before an *ogbanje* is sent to gain entry into that home.

A.K. Obierozie in *Ekpe Nna* better captures the Igbo understanding of the world of *ogbanje*, when he x-rays the reasons the *ogbanje* usually compromises its earthly experience. From the image of the *ogbanje* as portrayed by Obierozie in his

poem ‘*Ogbanje*’ (Poem 32), it becomes clear that the *ogbanje* better enjoys the company of its spiritual peer group (*ndi otu mmuo*) than the family it visits. The implication is that the *ogbanje* peer group does not leave any of its members on an earthly assignment; they visit such a person from time to time to keep their company. This explains why the *ogbanje* is known to always be in discussion with unseen people (Ekwalor, 2013). (Ilechukwu, 2007, p. 240) explains that:

These companions or peer group (*ndi otu* in Igbo) are said to communicate supernaturally, often contacting each other through hallucinatory experiences or dreams. They are said to use such media to socialize, share group largesse, indulge sexual and other appetites, or impose group discipline and punishment, which manifest as strange illnesses.

This level of social interaction, the *ogbanje* is believed to share with the group, better explains why the *ogbanje* usually finds its early home boring and as such makes sure it compromises their earthly existence. Unlike the three poems on *ogbanje* earlier discussed above that focus on the effects of *ogbanje* on individuals and families, Obierozie’s poem on *ogbanje* mirrors the social life of *ogbanje* by giving a voice to the *ogbanje* to understand why it behaves the way it does. Obierozie’s poem begins with a mirror of the *ogbanje*’s account of its sojourn on earth, describing the joy its parents felt when it was born. The first stanza of Obierozie’s poem mirrors the way the Igbo receive news of a newborn child.

For the Igbo, nothing can compare to the joy of having a child. Whenever an Igbo man decides to marry, one of the basic things he looks forward to is having a child (Ekwalor, 2013). When the cry of a newborn baby is heard in most parts of Igboland, it is usually met with great excitement (Ubesie, 2004). Women rejoice by dancing, shouting, and spreading the good news. The men, on the other hand, declare

a feast, drinking and celebrating. This is the mood the *ogbanje* in Obierozie's poem describes the family it visits are in, when it arrives:

Ụbọchị nne mụrụ m	(When my mother gave birth to me
Eji m ákwá pụta uwa	I came into the world crying
Ma nne jiri oñụ nabata m	My mother received me with joy
Nna m gbapuru egbe	My father released a gunshot
Gwa oha olu Chukwu luru	Announced to the public the work of God)

(Obierozie, 1986, p. 5)

Obierozie paints a picture of an *Ogbanje*, who has everything going on for it here on earth, but is in a dilemma of which world to choose. However, due to the agreement the *ogbanje* has with its peers in the spirit world before the earthly journey, that is, to die at an agreed time, it cannot stay. This death of the *ogbanje* usually comes through a strange ailment or an accident (Ilechukwu, 2007). The *ogbanje* in the above verse (poem 32) hopes to fulfill one goal, which is to inflict a high degree of psychological and emotional injury on an individual or family, where such exists. The objective of the *ogbanje*, as believed by the Igbo, is captured in the fourth stanza of Obierozie's poem (poem 32) when he says:

Otu ihe bu mkpa m	(My only need is
Ka m too uwa akpiri	To make the world salivate
Were nkenke oge gosi onwe m	Show myself for a short while
Ma m lowa ije m biara	When I am returning from my journey)

(Obierozie, 1986, p. 6)

The above stanza from poem 32 explains why the Igbo abhor the *ogbanje* and do everything possible to prevent the repeat of the *ogbanje*'s visit. Obierozie's image of *ogbanje* shows that *ogbanje* is one of the wicked groups of spirits in existence. Nevertheless, the *ogbanje* is said to stop the circle when a traditional doctor, who is gifted in knowledge of *ogbanje*, locates the *ogbanje*'s *iyi uwa* (life contract- oath) and destroys it. Destroying the *iyi uwa* severs the ties the *ogbanje* has with her peers in the underworld (Achebe, 1986; Ilechukwu, 2007).

A. B. Chukuezi's poem 'Ogbanje' in *Ako Bu Ndu* (poem 33) focuses on the psychological effect and social challenges faced by most mothers who give birth to *ogbanje* in Igbo society. Chukuezi's poem focuses on the state of mind of the individual who has been a victim of *ogbanje*'s torture over the years. Most mothers who give birth to *ogbanje* are usually left traumatised, devastated, and heartbroken. As a medical doctor and poet, Chukuezi examines the possible health problems women who are victims of *ogbanje* could experience. Apart from the psychological problems which are common to every woman who has had an *ogbanje* experience, Chukuezi draws the attention of the readers to the state of the woman's womb, given the number of times she would have to conceive a child and go through the strenuous childbirth. Let us see the way Chukuezi paints this image (poem 33)

Dibia agwoola ka ike ya ha
 O biara taà laa echi
 Bù nwa akpōghì m ihu
 Oke òmùmù esetjala àkpà nwa m ...
 (Chukuezi, 1988, pp. 28-29)

(The doctor has healed to the best of his knowledge
 It arrives today and leaves tomorrow
 I did not set my eyes on the child
 Too much pregnancy has overstretched my womb ...)

Chukuezi brings his experience as a medical doctor to the fore by focusing on the area where earlier poets, who wrote on the *ogbanje* phenomenon, neglected: the state of the woman's womb, left in a delicate situation given the high number of conceptions. Here, the poet draws the reader's attention to the risks women face from the time they become pregnant until the child is born. The poem heightens emotion by revealing that, among other psychological risks, there could be complications that may arise as a result of multiple pregnancy and other health risks.

J. Onuoha's poem *ogbanje* (Poem 34) satirises the phenomenon *ogbanje* for all its evil deeds. Onuoha's poem chronicles the life and times of the *ogbanje*, who is

believed, by the Igbo, to have a different life apart from their earthly life. Just like Obierozie, Onuoha explains the reason the *ogbanje* always compromises their earthly experience. The poet believes that the reward of an *ogbanje* has been promised in the underworld by the *nne mmiri* (river goddess), and that is the reason the *ogbanje* would always compromise their earthly experience. Onuoha also believes that *ogbanje* considers its life in the underworld superior to the life it leads here on earth. According to the poet (Onuoha), the river goddess promises the *ogbanje* of more riches for embarking on any assignment. The reward promised by the river goddess is different from the husbands', house, servants, and many other things the *ogbanje* has in the underworld, which they abandoned for their earthly assignment. This whole life of the *ogbanje* is captured in the fourth stanza of Onuoha's poem, when she writes:

Tuḡiakwa	(Tuḡiakwa
Leenu ya ka o na-eto	Look at it growing
Ahu ya bu so mma	Her body looks so good
Mana jḡodi ya ase oḡulu di	But ask her about getting married
O ga-aza gi "Aluola m di"	She will answer you, "I am married."
Di mmiri o bu di?	Is River Husband a husband?
Ulo mmiri o bu ulo?	Is River House a house?
Ndi ohu na-efe gi ofufe	Servant are serving you
Gini di ka ha na-eri?	What are they even eating?)

(Onuoha in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 191)

From the image of *ogbanje* as mirrored by Onuoha, it becomes clear that the visit of *ogbanje* here on earth is an assignment that forces the *ogbanje* to abandon its whole life for a short while, with the hope of returning to the life it left behind with a reward when it is done with its assignment. This is why the *ogbanje* always prefers to die as children, as they cannot wait for too long to return to their lives in the underworld. The poet (Onuoha) adds a self-propelled road accident as one of the means the *ogbanje* uses to facilitate their death. This is a point various scholars like Achebe (1986) Ilechukwu (2007) who had written on *ogbanje* did not mention. In the seventh stanza of poem 34, the poet says:

O jee n'akpati ya, efe aburū aturū tawa
 O tūkōta ukwū ya abuo, ugboala akpogharia
 Chi m oo! Di m oo! Nna m oo!
 O fuola, laghachi na mmiri.
 O zarala obara umu mmadu, zighachi na mmiri

(Onuoha in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 191)

(When it goes to its box, there are many clothes
 When it crosses its two legs, the car somersaults
 My God oo! My husband oo! My father oo!
 It has disappeared, back to the water
 It has sieved people's blood back into the water.

The above stanza reveals many things about the mission of *ogbanje* here on earth. While some scholars consider *ogbanje's* departure and the means it uses (strange illnesses) to be personal to the *ogbanje*, the poet in the above excerpt believes that the *ogbanje's* mission on earth is bigger than inflicting pain on the family it has visited. The poet, just like many Africans, believes that some spirits spiritually engineer some of the major accidents on our highways in a bid to drink the blood of people. Instead of blaming the driver for reckless driving or poor car maintenance which usually lead to fatal accidents on the way as a result of bad tires and other car components that are in poor state, the poet blames it on the *ogbanje* whom she believes uses that medium (road accident) to exit their earthly life and also take some souls along as a gift to their master – the *nne mmiri* (Water mother). Onuoha is the only poet out of the previous poets who writes about *ogbanje* and believes that *ogbanje* possesses the power to cause an accident on the highway. The poet summarises the poem by placing a curse on the *ogbanje* for its evil deeds when she says:

Ogbanje a na m abū gi ọnu	(<i>Ogbanje</i> I curse you
Aga m eji mma oge gburisie gi	I will slice you in pieces with a cutlass
N'ihī ndū umu mmadu i laworo n'iyi	Because of people's lives you have wasted
Tufiaa gi	<i>Tufiaa</i> you
I gbakwaa aka gi.	You are empty-handed.”)

(Onuoha in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 191)

In Igboland, before someone is cursed, that individual must have committed a heinous offence against their parents, another person, the community, or the deity of the land. The poet's rain of curses on the *ogbanje* confirms the evil deeds of the spirit. The poet seems not to have a problem with the *ogbanje* spirit returning to the spirit world, since everyone knows its *modus operandi*. However, the *ogbanje*'s facilitating the deaths of others through road accidents was what led to the curse in Onuoha's poem.

From the foregoing, it has become apparent that the Igbo believe the *ogbanje* are malevolent spirits, who go about tormenting people. From the discussion above, the *ogbanje* is never welcomed in any home, and the poets have shown the kind of treatment given to the corpse of the *ogbanje* before it is given a shallow burial.

5.1.2.2 Representation of the Igbo Concept of Destiny by Poets in Written Igbo Poetry

The concept of destiny is one of the topical issues of human concern that modern Igbo poets address in three of the four decades under study (1986-2015). It is an issue that has not only drawn the attention of modern Igbo poets alone but also that of Igbo philosophers. The reason for this is that Africans (including the Igbo) have a strong belief in the supernatural world (Ukwamedua & Omokpo, 2016). They also believe that the world beyond is higher than the human world and, as such, controls it (Ugonna, 1984).

The Igbo are usually in a dilemma, not knowing whether their life and death on earth are such as have been pre-destined by a superior metaphysical force (Ukwamedua & Omokpo, 2016). In most cases, some Igbo surrender to fate and, as such, believe that it does not matter what he or she does, and that whatever path has

been chosen for him or her by his or her creator cannot be changed, a situation described by philosophers as ‘fatalism’. This belief raises a fundamental question about whether there is no free will in the Igbo world. Ukwamedua and Omokpo (2016) asked, " Are the Igbo really free to chart their own path and actualize their dreams in life? Or is it that their lives are already destined or determined by some metaphysical forces, and they have no control over their lives? Ikwubuzo (2008b), in his examination of the Igbo drama text *Ojadili*, in order to understand the Igbo perception of destiny through the lenses of Odunke Artists, submits that, by the exercise of freewill, an individual can become the architect of his own destiny.

In this section, however, we shall explain the Igbo concept of destiny through the lenses of five modern Igbo poets who have portrayed Igbo understanding of destiny in their works. This is because, according to the exponents of the mirror image, literature reflects the society (Ogunsina, 2006), which is in this case Igbo society. By investigating the works of Igbo poets to seeing how they portray the concept of destiny, we can truly tell if the Igbo tow the path of fatalism or freewill in their understanding of destiny as a concept.

To many of the Igbo, whatever a person (as an agent in this world) will become, even the way he or she is going to die is predetermined by their creator before the person is born into this world. They also believe that this role assigned to each individual by their creator is written on the person’s palm, which gives rise to the compound word ‘akara’ (mark) and ‘aka’ (hand/palm). It seems that A.K. Obierozie wrote his poem ‘Akaraaka’ (Poem 35) in Ekpe Nna based on this understanding of the Igbo worldview. In his introductory stanza (first stanza), the poet begins by saying (poem 35):

Uli chi dere obi aka m
Aguru m akwukwo nke ukwu

(God’s writing on my palm
I am well educated

Ma amamihe m erughi ya	But my wisdom does not match it
Agbaala m mbọ ịgụ ya	I have tried to read it
Ma mkpụrụ akwụkwọ ya gbara gharị	But its letterspages are perplexing.)
(Obierozi, 1986, p. 2)	

The writings or marks that the poet is referring to, which he claims God wrote on his palm, are the palm lines on everybody's palm. The Igbo believe that, just as there can never be two people with identical fingerprints, the palm lines on our palms are also peculiar to every individual. This is why the Igbo believe that the lines on our palms reveal the path our creator has charted for us even before we were born into this world. These markings cannot be understood or read merely by examining our hands, which is what the poet is talking about in lines 2-5 of the above stanza one of poem 35, when he explains that despite being well-educated, he still cannot read his palm. What he is saying, in other words, is that the knowledge of his destiny is hidden away from him. The poet (Obierozi) makes his view even more apparent in the second stanza of his poem (35), when he says:

Ọ bụ mkpụrụ akwụkwọ a	(It is this writing
N'edu m, na-edu gị	That lead me, that is leading you
Na chi anyị foro na chi anyị jiri	That our day breaks and our night falls
Ọ bụ n'obi aka anyị k'ọ dī	It is on our palm
Chi ka ụta na otuto dīrī	To God is the blame and praise)
(Obierozi, 1986, p. 2)	

Obierozi's understanding of destiny becomes very clear in the above excerpt. Although the poet accepts, from lines 1-2 of the above stanza 2, that destiny is not visible to man, he also, like every Igbo person, believes that the marks on our palms reveal a little to us about our destiny in life. The poet believes that each person is guided by their destiny and that our fortunes in life are predetermined by our Chi (Personal god) and not by us. This thought is what the poet seems to be referring to in lines 3-5. By this thought, the poet, just like most of the Igbo, believes that the thought of 'freewill' is an illusion, and that man is being controlled by forces higher

than him. The popular Igbo saying “O mewere ma chi ekweghi, onye uto atala ya” (He that tries his best but was not accepted by God, should not be blamed) restates the Igbo view of fatalism, which belief in *akaraka* (destiny/fate) entails. However, despite this understanding among the Igbo of a predetermined beginning, the Igbo vigorously pursue and live a life of free will (Igbokwe, 2015). However, living a life of free will depends on a person’s realisation of their destiny, thus acting according to the plan of their creator. Ikwubuzo (2008b) asserts that although an individual is free to determine his own actions, he or she can never be greater than his *Chi*. This is why the poet ends the above stanza by saying “Chi ka uto na otuto diri” (To God is the blame and praise).

Igbokwe (2015) also explains that the Igbo believe that anyone who discovers their destiny excels in life, while those who do not will keep going in circles. That is why, in Igbo traditional society, people usually visit the *dibia afa* (diviner) to have their palms read in an attempt to understand their role on earth. It is upon this view that Obierozie concludes his poem, when he says in the last stanza of poem 35 that:

Oganiihu di n’obi aka	(Progress in on the palm)
Ndaghachi di n’obi aka	Retrogression is on the palm
Ebulere chi gi uto oso	Do not run ahead of your <i>chi</i>
Chota ebe akaraaka gi di	Discover where your destiny is
Ka i were okwa gi n’uwa.	So you can take your position on earth.

(Obierozie, 1986, p. 3)

Here, Obierozie summarises the Igbo view of destiny. Obierozie’s portrayal of the Igbo concept of destiny in the above stanza is in line with the view of Igbokwe (2015), who explains that among the Igbo, for one to discover his destiny (*akaraaka*) means to discover the features we are born with - ones that his determined origin provides him or her. Igbokwe further states that it is only by using such features to his or her own advantage that one fulfils his or her destiny. To use the features God has deposited in individuals means exercising their free will to become whatever they

want to be. This is why Ikwubuzo (2008b) opines that, by exercising free will, an individual can become the sole architect of his destiny. This is also why the poet (Obierozi) in lines 4-5 of the last stanza above encourages the reader first to discover the features his or her determined origin provides before he or she can fulfil destiny.

Like Obierozi in his poem, 'Akaraaka', G.O. Onyekaonwu, in his poem 'Akaraaka (Destiny)' (Poem 36) in *Uche bu Afa*, further portrays the Igbo concept of destiny. Onyekaonwu views destiny from the angle of 'fatalism', which implies the belief that the destinies of men are controlled and determined by metaphysical or unseen forces instead of their will (Ruiu, 2012; Gellman & Turner, 2013). This fatalistic perception of destiny is what informs the two stanzas of Onyekaonwu's poem, "*Akaraaka*. In his first stanza, the poet begins by saying:

<p>Onatara chi bu onatara chi Ka a gwopu ya n'ogwu abughi ezi I mee elu ma mee ala Iji wee gbanwo ekere chi O dighi ofere, o bughị n'ezi Ihe e dere, e dego ya.</p>	<p>(What we received from God is what we received from God. To remove it with medicine is impossible. No matter what you do To change a destiny It is not easy, it is not simple What is written is written.</p>
<p>(Onyekaonwu, 1989, p. 21)</p>	

To Onyekaonwu, as seen in the above stanza (poem 36), the fate of man is sealed by his Creator even before his birth. The poet seems not to share Obierozi's view in respect of the fact that though man is born with a determined origin, he or she has the power of freewill. In the above stanza, Onyekaonwu holds up a mirror to the belief of many Igbo people, who hold that man is helpless in the hands of supernatural forces and is always at the mercy of the metaphysical or unseen forces, who direct man at will. This is why in lines 3-6, the poet clearly upholds the view that whatever has been decided for man by his *Chi* (Personal god) cannot be changed by the man, no matter how hard the person tries. Since death is also a common destiny that awaits every individual (Ogbujah, 2008), Onyekaonwu's view, by extension, implies that the

power to grow rich or poor and the power to live long or die young are determined by unseen forces rather than by humans themselves. This view is vivid in the second and also the last stanza of Onyekaonwu's poem (36), when the poet says:

E kee gi n'ala, i chowa elu	(When you are created on land, you start seeking the sky
Ma o bu nye gi elu, i chowa ala	Or give you the sky, you start looking for the land
E mee elu mee ala, i ga-ahụ	Whatever that happens, you will see
Na ihe e kwere gi ka i ga-abụ	That whatever you are allowed to be is what you will become
Ọgba ọsọ agbanahụghị ya	The runner cannot run away from it
Ọgwọ ọgwụ agwọtaghị ya	The medicine man cannot prevent it
Aha a gurụ onye ka o ga-aza	The name given to someone is what S/he bears
N'ihì na akara aka adìghì nhichapụ	Because destiny cannot be cleaned.)

(Onyekaonwu, 1988, pp. 21-22)

In stanza 2 of poem 36, Onyekaonwu portrays the Igbo belief in a fatalistic course of life, a position shared by most people in Igbo society. Many who share Onyekaonwu's thought allow their fatalistic convictions to shape their behaviours, including their choices of occupation, savings decisions, preparedness for natural disasters, and other aspects (Rui, 2012). It follows the thought that no matter the effort an individual puts into changing his or her life, the individual cannot help but fall into the original predetermined plan for his or her life even before birth, as seen in lines 1-4 of the above stanza 2. Although many Igbo people share this belief, it is considered counterproductive because it encourages laziness and unproductivity in men. From Onyekaonwu's portrayal of destiny as seen in the above excerpt, it can be seen that even the poet acknowledges man's effort to live a free life in lines 5-6 when he says:

Ọgba ọsọ agbanahụghị ya	The runner cannot run away from it
Ọgwọ ọgwụ agwọtaghị ya	The medicine man cannot prevent it

The implication of this view is that man can only try to be the architect of his destiny, but all his effort towards attaining that which he wants for himself crumbles

at the face of the forces of his *chi* (personal god). To Onyekiaonwu, therefore, freewill is an illusion.

Like the earlier discussed poets, who mirror the Igbo concept of destiny in their poems, D. Epuchie's portrayal of the Igbo concept of destiny also shows that it is rooted in fatalism. Epuchie begins his poem by reinforcing the views of the other poets, who have written on the same issue, *Akaraaka*. The poet (Epuchie) believes that a person's fate is long determined by their *Chi* (personal god) before their birth, and as such, no matter what the person does on earth, their fate cannot be changed. The poet captures this view in his first stanza (poem 37), when he says:

I bụ ogaranya	(If you are wealthy
I bụ ogbenye	If you are poor
Anya idi mma	Well-behaved
I bụ onye ara	If you are insane
I bụ ekwueme	If you do as you say
I bụ okwuchaa ogwu	If you have the final say
O bụ osinachi	It is God-given
O nweghi mmeghari	It cannot be changed.)

(Epuchie in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 74)

For a fact, the majority of the Igbo share the view expressed by the poet in the above stanza as regards the concept of destiny. The thought expressed above supports the view of fatalism. That means the poet does not believe that people have free will to choose their paths in life. However, Epuchie's portrayal of the Igbo concept of destiny takes a different turn in his second stanza: whatever an individual is cannot be changed, as it is divinely assigned. To further reinforce his portrayal of the Igbo concept of destiny, in the second stanza of poem 37, the poet writes:

N'akaraka ka o di	(It is in the destiny
Icho di a hughị	Searching for a husband but to no avail
Ihu di lughị	Finding a suitor but not getting married
Ihu ego ataghị ahuhu	Making wealth effortlessly
Ita ego ataghị	Not having money to spend
Oke Chukwu ka o bụ	It is the gift of God
Onye o kenyere ya were	Whomever S/he gives, let him or her take

O dighi ntupu	It cannot be removed
O nweghi mmeghari	It cannot be changed.)

The above stanza summarises the thrust of Epuchie’s position as regards the Igbo concept of destiny. The Igbo concept of destiny, as mirrored in the second stanza of poem 37 above, portrays man as helpless. The poet's position, as seen in lines 2-5 above, exonerates humans from the consequences of their actions. The poet says,

Icho di a hughu	(Searching for a husband but to no avail.
Ihu di lughu	Finding a suitor but not getting married
Ihu ego ataghi ahuhu	Making wealth effortlessly
Ita ego ataghi	Not having money to spend
Oke Chukwu ka o bu	It is the gift of God)

This means that humans can never be blamed for their experiences on earth; all blame should be transferred to their chi, even when the person vehemently rejects the guidance of their *chi*. Though Epuchie’s portrayal of the Igbo concept of destiny aligns with the views of other poets, as discussed earlier. His belief in the fatalistic nature of destiny can be said to have been taken to the extreme. This is because, if indeed supernatural forces control human affairs the way Epuchie captures it in the above stanza, then life is meaningless. A semantic implication of lines 2-3 in the above stanza is that, when a promiscuous lady fails to find a suitor, or when one who continues to reject suitors until she grows past marriageable age, these two classes of ladies should blame their *Chi* for their misfortune instead of themselves. This seeming position advanced by the poet plays down the Igbo belief that ‘Onye Chukwu na-azọ, na-azọ onwe ya’ (Whoever that is helped by God should also help himself). This goes to say that, because a person’s birth activates their destiny (Igbokwe, 2015), how the individual achieves that destiny is up to them.

Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe’s portrayal of the Igbo concept of destiny is less intense than that of the other poets discussed above. In the work of Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe’s poem, ‘Akaraaka’, as seen in *Uche bu Ahia*, (Poem 38), the poets also

portray destiny as God-given, which any other individual cannot take away. The poets begin the poem by stating that whatever an individual is destined to become is what will eventually be. The poets (Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe) also added that destiny can be regarded as ‘birthright’. Let us consider the way these poets capture it in their first stanza, when they say (poem 39)

Ihe onye ga-abụ n’ụwa	(Whatever a person will be in this world
Nke ahụ ka ọ ga-abụ	That he shall become
Ebu m pụta ụwa	A genetic make-up
Dibịa anaghị agwọpụ ya	The medicine men cannot remove)

(Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, 2009, p. 49)

Here, the poets mirror the Igbo belief that whatever destiny the Creator bestowed on individuals before they were born is inalienable. The inalienable nature of destiny, according to the poets, follows the fact that it is a natural trait or even a genetic make-up. In the second stanza of the poem 38, the poets emphasise the futility of human effort in the face of the determinism of fate. Whatever a person achieves is not determined by physical strength; otherwise, people whose work requires great physical strength would have been richer than others. This is why the poets write:

Akaraaka abughị ihe	(Destiny is not something
A na-enweta n’ike	That is acquired with force
A sị na ọ bụ ike kete, o rie	If having something is a sheer strength
Ndị na-akwa baro gaara abare ọhịa	Truck pushers would have been very wealthy
Akaraaka mmadụ jiri pụta ụwa	The destiny one came to the world with
Mmadụ apughị ihicha ya	Man cannot be cleaned off.)

(Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, 2009, p. 49)

In the above stanza, the belief of the Igbo in the fact that it is the Creator who shapes the destiny and peculiarities of humans becomes apparent. By alluding to the truck pushers in (line 4), who make a living daily through the use of their physical strength, the poets assert that human achievement is not a function of strength or might. The view of these poets here is shared by the majority of the Igbo who believe

that the realisation of their destiny is always in line with the plan of their *chi* (personal god).

From the above portrayal of the Igbo concept of destiny in written Igbo poetry, as reflected in modern Igbo poetry, it has become clear that the Igbo consider destiny fatalistic. This means that the Igbo believe their destinies are controlled by the supernatural rather than by human will. Hence, the belief that man is not entirely free to choose his own path; instead, a person must travel the path predetermined for him by some metaphysical forces (his/her Creator). This path includes people's fortunes and misfortunes.

5.1.2.3 Kola Nut Culture as Portrayed in Written Igbo Poetry

The kola nut (*cola acuminata*), known as Oji by the Igbo, is the most revered fruit in Igbo culture. All over Igboland, the kola nut is respected and honoured and as such held in high esteem due to its spiritual and cultural significance. The kola nut tree is also considered by the Igbo to be the first tree on earth (Obineche, 2017). Throughout Igboland, the kola nut is renowned for its ritualistic powers to promote prosperity, peace, and long life; in most cases, it is believed to serve as a significant link between the living and the gods (Obineche, 2017). This view portrays the Igbo as highly religious. This supports Mbiti's (1969) view that Africans are notoriously religious. Mbiti further reveals that Africans carry religion with them everywhere they go. The Igbo (as a major ethnic group in Nigeria) are no different. That is why, everywhere the Igbo gather, the kola nut must make an appearance. Due to the high respect accorded to the kola nut in Igboland, it is often seen as the chief of all events, that without its presentation at any Igbo event, the event cannot hold. The offering of kola nut is one cultural practice and rite that all the Igbo have in common, which is why

Obineche (2017) suggests that the term ‘oji’ could be an etymological acronym, which the three letters that make up the word are, “**O**” which stands for Omenala (customs), “**J**” which stands for Jikotara (unites) and “**I**” which stands for Igbo, meaning “the custom that unites the Igbo”.

Four Igbo poets represent the role and significance of the kola nut in the Igbo worldview in their poems. The poets are: T. Ubesie in *Akpa Uche* (1975), A.K. Obierozi in *Ekpe Nna* (1986), and R.N. Ekegbo in *Uwa Onye na Chi Ya* (2005) and F. Mbanugo in *Akponauche* (2006).

Ubesie, in a poem titled ‘Oji’ in *Akpa Uche* (1975) (Poem 39), describes the kola nut as very sacred, noting that it is the only fruit that both humans and the spirit share in communion. In the view of this poet in the fourth stanza of his poem (poem 39),

Oji bu nri mmuḡo na mmadu	(Kola nut is the food of the spirits and men.
Nke anyi na mmuḡo na-eriko	Which we eat in communion with the spirits
A si na anya huru ndi mmuḡo	It is said that the eye that sees the spirits
Anaghị anò ndù na-etù onū	Does not live to brag
Mmadu na mmuḡo na-ata oji	Men and spirits eat kola nut
E mecha mmadu adi ndu	Later man lives)
(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, pp. 40-41)	

This view, expressed by Ubesie, brings to the fore why the Igbo regard the kola nut as a sacred fruit. The Igbo believe strongly that the living and the dead constantly interact with each other. The breaking of the kola nut is one of the events the Igbo use to communicate with the spirits. The spirits here refer to the pure spirits (that is, spirits that have never lived in human form) and the hallowed spirit of the dead (the ancestors) (Ugonna, 1984). Chidume, Osioma, and Echem (2015) explain that, to the Igbo, the kola nut symbolises social and ritual bonds between the living and the dead. This bonding is better captured in the Igbo line “Nke anyi na mmuḡo na-eriko” (Which we eat in communion with the spirits) (communion) in the above

excerpt of the poem. The poet, in the stanza above, mirrors the Igbo belief that the departed, or the spirits of dead ancestors, do not leave their families; instead, they constantly watch over their loved ones, protecting and providing for them. This explains why the traditional Igbo pray with the kola nut every morning, summoning the spirits of their ancestors to fellowship with them and to continue watching over them and their families. The Igbo not only call on the spirit of their ancestors when praying with the kola nut, but also summon various deities or gods that they and their ancestors served to join in the communion. The poet (Ubesie) buttresses this point in the fifth stanza of his poem (40) when he says:

Okènyè jìde ojī, sùọ udè	(If an elder holds a kola nut and hums
Ndị mmūọ àna-àna ntị	The spirits will pay attention
Ihe ìmadụ nà-àkpọ hā ọkụ	The reason men beckon on them
Kà ha bịa gèere mmādù ntị.	For them to come and listen to men
Okènyè jìde ojī n'aka	The elder holds a kola nut in his hands
Ọ na-àrịọ màkà ndụ mmadụ.	He prays for people's lives.)
(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 41)	

In breaking the kola nut in Igboland, there is a protocol to follow. That is why the *Ojī* is seen as a ritualistic element. If that protocol is not followed, the prayer is believed not to have any effect. In many parts of Igboland, the oldest person at the gathering where the *ojī* is presented is responsible for praying with the *ojī* (Nzeako, 1979). Some of these places, according to Nzeako (1979), include Onitsha, Nnewi, Njikoka, and Awka, to name but a few. This position is mirrored by the poet (Ubesie) in the first and second lines of the above stanza. It is believed that because of this respect given to the most senior person in a gathering where the *ojī* is presented to pray with it, the spirits and gods present, seeing the level of harmony amidst those present, will honour the prayers that the elder is going to make. The view of the poet that when the elder holds up the kola nut, the spirits open their ears to listen to his prayers. It is important to note that the concept of the elder here is not about the age,

but about seniority. This is why, even among young men, when a kola nut is presented at a youth meeting in Igboland, the oldest person among these youths is the one who has the right to pray on the *oji*. This goes on to say a lot about respect and honour among the Igbo. It contradicts the position of some non-Igbo persons who believe that, because the Igbo society is egalitarian, there is no order.

Furthermore, when an elder begins to pray, it is believed that as an elder, he is in the best position to know the everyday needs of most people present at that occasion. This is why he must pray for the good of everybody present at the occasion, meeting, or any other event where the *oji* is served. That is what the poet captures in the fifth and sixth lines of the above stanza five from poem 39. When the elder begins to pray, the people present will begin to agree with his prayer by replying, *Isee!*, which means “Amen” as used by Christians. The poet mirrors this view in the sixth to the eighth stanzas of the poem.

Just like Ubesie in his poem on *oji*, in the same vein, Obierozie (1986), in his poem, ‘*Oji*’ (Poem 40), also describes the kola nut as the chief guest of all events in Igboland. Events here include welcoming a guest, a marriage ceremony, title-taking, coronation, a burial ceremony, the offering of sacrifice, peace talks, and child dedication, to name but a few (Nzeako, 1979). In Igbo land, before any of these events start, there must be the breaking of the kola nut ceremony, variously known as *Iche Oji*, *Iwa Oji*, *Isu Oji*, and *Ita Oji* (presentation of kola nut). There are protocols involved in the kola nut ceremony, which is another reason *oji* is seen as a ritualistic element and held in high esteem among the Igbo. Obierozie captures all these in the first stanza of his poem when he writes:

Oji onye isi okwa obia
Ozorọ nwa mgbenyi n’ihu ogaranya
Ahughị ebuli na elighi dike
Ihe oriri a na-eji usoro eri

(Obierozié, 1986, p. 7)

(Kola nut the head of the visitor
The saviour of the poor in the presence of the rich
Without you, nothing happens
An edible that is eaten with protocol)

Here, the poet refers to the kola nut as the chief of all events, and that without its presence at any event among the Igbo, the event cannot hold. This is why the poet here refers to the kola nut as the *onye isi* (chairman). The metaphoric use of the expression ‘Onye isi’ by the poet in the above stanza from poem 40 reveals the revered place of the kola nut among the Igbo.

Usually, when the chairman of any occasion is not present, the occasion or event cannot start until the chairman arrives. This is why the poet metaphorically refers to the kola nut as the ‘chairman’. The view of the poet about the kola nut is better captured in the Igbo expression that “*a naghị ekwukpo ojì okwu*” (no one speaks when the kola nut is being presented), which implies the reverence accorded to the nut because of its spiritual significance. The poet concludes this introductory stanza by stating that the kola nut is not eaten like any other fruit in Igboland; instead, there is a protocol that must be strictly adhered to during the kola nut-eating ceremony. These protocols that the kolanut must follow are well documented by Nzeako (1979), Ubesie (1978), and Ekwálor (2010) in their works on Igbo culture. Furthermore, the poet (Obierozié), like Ubesie, in his poem, also asserts that the kola nut is the only fruit that men and spirits eat together. This view is seen in the third stanza of poem 40 when the poet states:

E weta a kpowa mmụọ
Ìgba nriko mmụọ na mmadu
E weta a chowa ikwunne na nwadiala
Onye obia anoro ka obia.

(Obierozié, 1986, p. 7)

(When presented, the spirits are summoned
The communion between spirits and men)

When presented, they begin to search for maternal relatives and sons of the soil.
The visitor will sit as a visitor.

The communion between men and spirits, as opined by the poet in stanza three above, is vital to the Igbo, who believe that through the kola nut, the gods and spirits can give them messages about things to come or reveal things that happened in the past.

Ekegbo (2005), in his own poem, ‘Oji’ in *Uwa Onye na Chi Ya* (Poem 41), also agrees with earlier poets that the kola nut is the chief guest in all Igbo gatherings. In fact, the poet refers to the kola nut as the head of Igbo culture in the poem, “Oji”. The poet considers the kola nut to be the only message that the gods understand, which is why the Igbo pray with the kola nut at all times. In the words of the poet, in the first stanza of the poem (poem 41):

Oji, isi omenala!
O nweghi onye Igbo amaghi gi
N’omenala, o nweghi ihe di mkpa ka gi
Anaghi ahapu iji gi bido ogbakọ o bula.
Ekpere bu ihe mbu a na-enye Obasi;
Ozo bu iji gi hanye ndu n’aka Chineke
N’ihe ndi di ka ogbakọ ndi obia na imalite ikpe,
Maka udi ihe ndi a e ji gi adọ ala aka na nti.
(Ekegbo, 2005, p. 23)

(Kola nut, head of culture!
All the Igbo know you
In culture, there is nothing as important as you
You cannot be left out of starting any meeting
Prayer is the first thing given to God
Another is to hand life into the hands of God with you
In some things, like meetings with visitors, starting a judgment, and the
Because of these things, you are used to warning the land.)

This stanza makes it quite clear that the Igbo see the kola nut as the primary means of communication with the gods. In the pre-colonial Igbo society, Igbo religion, like that of every other ethnic group in Africa, was traditional. In Igbo traditional religion, even to this day, the kola nut plays a vital role as it is the first

thing a believer uses in praying to the gods, along with *nzu* (white chalk). As in every other religion, prayer is considered an important aspect of Igbo traditional religion, usually performed using the kola nut as a communication link between the Igbo and the gods. This is the point the poet stresses in the fifth line of the above verse when he says that prayer is the first gift given to God. It is also important to note that only the Igbo see the kola nut as a sacred fruit. This view is represented by the poet (Ekegbo) in the second stanza of his poem (Poem 41) when he says about the kola nut:

Anyị bụ Igbo na-ahụ gị ka ihe ukwu!
A sị na a na-akụ gị na Yoruba,
Ndị na-ata na-ere gị ere bụ ndị Awụsa;
Ma anyị bụ Igbo na-enye gị ugwu.
(Ekegbo 2005, p. 23)

(We, the Igbo, see you as a great thing
It is said that the Yoruba plants you
Those who eat and sell to you are the Hausa
But we, the Igbo, revere you.)

This is a common belief held by people because the Hausa eat kola nut in large quantities for its caffeine content; it is mainly produced in large quantities by the Yoruba and is highly revered by the Igbo. In essence, from the way Igbo poets have mirrored the role of the kola nut among the Igbo, it has become clear that the nut is not just any fruit for the Igbo but a communication tool with which the Igbo commune with the gods and spirits.

Like the other poets that wrote on ‘Ojị’ as discussed above, F. Mbanugo’s portrayal of cultural relevance of the kola nut in his poem, ‘Ojị’, in *Akọnauche* is in the area of its value to the Igbo and various roles it plays in Igbo society or Igbo world view by extension. Some of the roles the kola nut plays in Igbo society, as discussed by the poet (Mbanugo), include receiving of guest(s), asking for forgiveness or peace-making, and its role in consulting the gods.

The poet begins the poem with an apostrophic reverence for the subject of discourse, evident in the first stanza. However, in the second through fourth stanzas, the poet takes his time to discuss the important role the kola nut plays in receiving guests in Igbo society. In all of Igboland, when a guest visits a person, the first thing expected of the host is to present a kola nut to the guest as a sign of respect and to demonstrate that the guest is truly welcome (Ekwealor, 2013, p. 59). Presenting a guest with a kola nut in Igbo society is so important that, even if a host should kill a cow or throw a feast for the guest without offering the guest a kola nut, the guest will believe that the host did not welcome him into his house and will go home feeling hurt. This is the view Mbanugo expressed in stanzas two to four in his poem (Poem 42) when he says in stanzas 2-4:

Oyibo mebichara ihe Igbo dum Ma gi aburu ugiri kworo enwe eze	(The whites have spoilt every Igbo thing . However, you became the fruit that aches the tooth of the monkey.
... Ọ bụ gi ka e ji egosi obi ọma E nwere maka onye ọbịa batara ụlọ	You are used to show kind-heartedness Towards a guest that enters the house
Gbutuoro ya otu ehi naanị ya Were ire rachaa ya ahụ dum Were nsị ọ nyurụ tee ala ụlọ Ị mebebeghị ihe gosiri obi ọma	Kill a cow just for him Lick all his body with your tongue Paint the floor of the house with his feaces You have not done what portrays kind heartedness.)
Ọ puo n'uzo akuko a na-aga Na ya biara na be gi I nyeghi ya obuladi oji Ma ya fodu nke zuru oke	When he is on his way, stories will continue That he visited your house You did not give him even a kola nut. Let alone the complete one)

(Mbanugo in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 150)

The above stanzas capture the role of the kola nut in welcoming a guest in Igbo society more vividly. The poet (Mbanugo) reveals to the reader in stanza two, without mincing words, that in Igbo society, it is the kola nut that is the key item used in welcoming guests. To further clarify his point, the poet in stanza three above explains in clear terms that no matter how good you treat a guest or how much you try

to impress him, if you do not present the guest with a kola nut, you (the host) have ruined everything. The guest will never value everything the host has done in a bid to impress him. Again, in stanza three above, the poet meticulously portrays various images of the extraordinary treatments a host can give to a guest in Igbo society. First is the killing of a cow for the guest, as seen in line 1. Second is licking the body of a guest and painting the floor of the house with the feces of the guest, as seen in lines 2-3 in the third stanza above, too. The concept of licking the guest's body or painting the floor with his or feces is hyperbolic. It is simply a way of telling the reader that in Igbo society, even if a person does the extraordinary for a guest, without presenting the kola nut to the guest as a way of showing good heart towards him/her and that his visit is appreciated, the guest will take it that he/she is not welcome. In some cases, such a guest may never visit that host again, while in some cases the guest will leave and start telling other people how badly the host has treated him, as seen in stanza four of the poem (Poem 42) where the poet says:

Ọ pụọ n'ụzọ akụkọ a na-aga	When he is on his way, stories will continue
Na ya bịa na be gi	That he visited your house
I nyeghi ya ọbụladi ọji	You did not give him even a kola nut.
Ma ya fọdu nke zuru oke	Let alone the complete one)

The next cultural significance of the kola nut in Igbo society, as portrayed by Mbanugo in his poem, is that it is used to seek forgiveness. In Igbo society, when someone offends another and wants to make amends, he must go to the person with a kola nut to seek his forgiveness. This is to prove to the person that he offended that he has genuinely come to ask for forgiveness. The reason for this is that, since the kola nut is used in communion among men and between men and gods, it usually symbolises peace, goodwill, or the love a person has for his brother or friend. This cultural significance is what Mbanugo is referring to in the fifth stanza of his poem (Poem 42) when he says:

Ihe oji na-arụ ebuka ibu	(The function of the kola nut is numerous.
I mejọọ mmadụ ga-ariọ ya	When you offend someone and want to ask for his forgiveness
I gaghi iji oji n'aka na-ariọ	You must have a kola nut in your hand while asking
Nke ndi mmuọ bu akwaghi akwa	The one for the spirits is unfailingly)
(Mbanugo, 2006, p. 150)	

There are two types of forgiveness in Igbo society that are mirrored in stanza 5 of the poem above. The first is the forgiveness a man seeks from another man, as portrayed in lines 2-3, while the second is the forgiveness a man seeks from the spirits, as shown in line 4, also in stanza 5 of poem 42. In these two forms of seeking forgiveness in Igbo society, the offender must offer a kola nut to the person or spirit he offended before he can be heard. That is what Mbanugo mirrors in the fifth stanza of the poem.

The last significance of the kola nut in Igbo society, as mirrored in Mbanugo's poem, is its role in consulting the gods or seeking their favor. The Igbo, like other African societies, believe in the relationship between man and other metaphysical forces. As earlier stated in chapter three of this study, the Igbo depend on the help of the gods for a whole lot of things, which include, but are not limited to, protection, provision, guidance, and a host of other needs. The Igbo also firmly believe that the only language the spirits understand is the language spoken with the kola nut. This belief of the Igbo is what the poet mirrors in the sixth stanza of his poem when he says:

E nweghi ike bugara arusi ihe,	(There is no way anything can be taken to the gods.
Oji aghara ibu ihe mbuuzo	Without the kola nut coming first
E jide oji n'aka, e sedo ala	When the kola nut is in the hand, you pray to the Earth,
Sedo ndi mmuọ aka na nti	Hold the ear of the gods)
(Mbanugo, 2006, p. 150)	

Here, the poet teaches the reader about Igbo culture, specifically the kola nut's cultural relevance to the Igbo. In the Igbo tradition and society, anyone who wishes to

draw from the wisdom of the gods or consult them for any reason must come bearing kola nut(s). Without the kola nut, the gods will never listen. This is also another reason the Igbo pray with the kola nut. They do this so that the gods and spirits of their ancestors can hear and fellowship with them. There are two types of kola nut in Igbo, and they have two specific colours: red and white. The white kola is known as *Oji Ugo*. This type of kola is not common and, as such, is regarded with high respect. When a person presents *Oji Ugo* to the gods, it is believed that the gods will take the person's matter seriously because the person has honoured them. The other type of kola nut is the normal Igbo kola, used for various ceremonies in Igboland.

Having discussed the portrayal of the kola nut culture in written Igbo poetry, it has now become clear that just as many of the Igbo, Igbo poets also portrayed the kola nut as the chief of all fruits in Igboland. While some poets focused on the kola nut as a sacred fruit, others focused on its sociocultural role among the Igbo. We shall then examine some economic issues as portrayed in written Igbo poetry.

5.1.3 Some Economic Issues as Portrayed in Written Igbo Poetry

In this section, we shall discuss key economic issues of human concern that drew the attention of modern Igbo poets in the past four decades (1975-2015). Several economic issues have, over the years, attracted the attention of modern Igbo poets; however, the issues chosen for discussion in this section are major subjects in which poetic thoughts converged during the decades under study. Based on this, two economic subjects were identified and discussed in this section: the poets' portrayal of the effects of money on society and the palm tree as an important economic plant in Igbo society.

5.1.3.1 Poet's Portrayal of Money as Economic Tool or Resource in Igbo

Society

Since the Nigerian currency was introduced, it has evolved tremendously into the Naira notes in use today. Since paper currency (naira notes) became legal tender in Nigeria, it has become one of the most sought-after materials in human history. This, perhaps, explains why it drew the attention of modern Igbo poets, who mirror the positive and negative effects of money in Igbo society in their works. Some of the poets in the decades under study who, through their works, portray the effects of money in Igbo society include J.C. Obienyem, I. Madubuike, J.N. Onwuchekwa, A.B. Chukuezi, N. Okediadi, C.C. Anozie, E.S. Ikeokwu, and M.C. Onyejekwe.

Obienyem's poem, 'Akwwkwọ Orụ Ego', in Akpa Uche (Poem 43), mirrors the adverse effects of money in Igbo (Nigerian) society. In his poem, the poet portrays money in the title as legal tender, received or given as a reward for work done. In the poem, the poet chronicles in detail how the love of money affects society's value system. The poet focuses on how desperate members of society are to earn money to improve their lives and those of their families. Due to the country's economic situation, where resources are scarce, and everyone fights to meet the demands of their immediate families, many people are desperate to make money by any means necessary. The love of money has also contributed to the high crime rate in society today. This is the picture Obienyem portrays in the first seven lines of his poem (poem 43), where he says,

Ihe na-alanye mmadu ikwu udo
Ihe nwaanyi soro ju di ya
Were gbasowe di amosu
Ihe lagara onye isi, na ngwuro ohi
O bughị ya mere ndi Ndiya ji ere umu ha?
Ookwa ya butere ogu na mgba niile di n'awa taa?
Ookwa ya kwanyere uko Chukwu na mkporo?
Olee ihe a na-akporo nwa ogbenye 'Onye mmuo'

Ọ bughị na o nweghị otu ọ ha ya?...

(Obienyem in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 42)

(What drives people to commit suicide
What makes a woman reject her husband
And run after a wizard husband
What leads the blind and the lame to steal
Is it not the reason Indians sell their children
Is it not what leads to all the fighting in the world today?
Is it not what has pushed the priest into prison?
Why is the poor man referred to as “a nobody”
Is it not because he does not have anything?...))

The issues raised in poem 43 by Obienyem are some of the challenges arising from the class struggle for economic empowerment in society. Most of the world's problems, including Igbo society today, stem from a love of money. While the rich in society continue to strive to remain rich, the poor make desperate moves to join the league of the rich. This unquenchable quest and lust for money have shredded the moral fabric of the modern (Igbo) society. It has led a lot of people to join different occult secret societies, which make different demands on them and cause a lot of people to sell their souls. Others have committed heinous crimes against humanity in their quest for profit. This has thrown a lot of people into a state of depression, leading to an increase in suicide cases in society. This situation is what the poet mirrors in the lines above. Other societal problems associated with people's love of money, as reflected in Obienyem's excerpt above, include a high divorce rate (lines 2-3), theft or armed robbery (line 4), and child trafficking (line 5).

We live in a society that adores its rich, regardless of the source of their wealth, and scorns the poor for their efforts to make an honest living. In most Igbo societies today and in other societies around the world, the poor are not regarded as part of the scheme of events because of their economic status. This is why the poet asks in lines 8-9 in the above excerpt, saying

... Olee ihe a na-akporọ nwa ogbenye ‘Onye mmụọ’
Ọ bughị na o nweghị otu ọ ha ya?...

A ghost is seldom seen or heard by people. They also do not have rights, since the idea of fundamental human rights is for humans and not for spirits. Therefore, the idea of ‘Onye mmuo’ as used here by the poet is used to refer to the place of the poor in the Igbo society. The poor are often neglected, their voices unheard, and their rights unrespected. This is why the poet says that the poor are often referred to as “onye mmuo,” meaning “a no-body” ghost in the society. It is the need to run away from this despicable state of poverty in society that drives people into different vices in a bid to become rich.

Like Obienyem, Madubuike, in his poem, “Naira”, in *Utara Nti* (Poem 44), also mirrors the negative impact of money on the Igbo/Nigerian society. Madubuike’s portrayal of the negative impact of money on Igbo society is purely didactic, written with the aim of discouraging people from their dangerous quest for riches. The poet begins his monologue by first portraying the value placed on money as a means of exchange. This image is portrayed in the first four lines of the poem (Poem 44) when the poet says:

Aha m bu Ego	(My name is Money
Ọ bu m ji ụwa	I am in control of the world
Mụ bu isi; buru ọdụ	I am the head and the tail
Onye enweghi m o na-ebe...	He who does not have me, cries...

(Madubuike in Emenanjo (ed.), N.d., p. 44)

The above excerpt better captures the value of money to the human race. This explains why there is such an intense craving for money among humans. Since money is the only acceptable legal tender, without which no trade can happen, it only makes sense that people do everything necessary to make more money. From the image of money as portrayed by the poet in the above excerpt, we understand that there is no problem money cannot solve, explaining why Bible states that “money answers all things” (Ecclesiastes, 10 v. 19b). Having presented the value of money to human race

in his first four lines in the first stanza of his poem, the poet took a swipe at the already personified money in the poem and began to portray the consequences or challenges associated with wealth in the Igbo society. This image is what the poet portrays in lines 5-12 of poem 44, where he says:

...Mgbe ụfọdụ inwe naira dị ka	(Sometimes having naira is like
Ịkpata nkụ ahụhụ	Fetching a log of wood filled with ants
Mgbe ahụ ọ bụrụ ihe na-eweta	Then it becomes what brings
Nsogbu obi na-ezughị ike	The problem of lack of peace of mind
Ọ dị ka atụrụ jị ọkpa kpakwuru onye ụgwọ	It is like a sheep that walked to a debtor.
Onye nwere ego achọghị ịda ogbenye	A rich person does not want to become poor
N'ihì na a naghị eme e rikata n'òkù	Because it is not after eating from a plate
E riwe n'ala	One starts eating on the floor.)

(Madubuike in Emenanjo, (ed.) N.d., p. 44)

The above excerpt underscores the burden associated with wealth in the (Igbo) society. The proverbial expression in line 5, which the poet explains in lines 7-8 of the excerpt above, brings to the fore the challenges associated with wealth. Lines 5-8 are in tandem with the thought the poem projects, which is to re-echo the need for contentment. Generally speaking, the poor look up to the rich and wish to be very wealthy. Most of the poor think that the moment they become rich, all their problems will end. This is the notion the poet hopes to correct with the above excerpt. The poet is simply telling the reader not to be deceived by the affluence, but to know that riches come with their own kind of problems. The common fear of every rich person is poverty. This is why the poet believes that most rich people do not have peace of mind: they have tasted the sweetness of wealth and will continue to do everything possible to remain rich. This is what the poet is saying in lines 6-8 (lines 10-12) of poem 44, as shown in the above excerpt, where the poet states:

...Onye nwere ego achọghị ịda ogbenye	(A rich person does not want to become poor
N'ihì na a naghị eme e rikata n'òkù	Because it is not after eating from a plate
E riwe n'ala	One begins to eat on the floor.)

It is this desire among the rich to remain rich at all costs and the desperate move by the poor to become rich that give rise to several societal problems. These problems are what the poet describes in the second stanza of his poem (Poem 44) as Nigeria's problems. The poet in the second stanza holds up a mirror to Nigerian society, showing the various moral fabrics of the society that have been negatively affected by people's desperate quest for money. The poet says (stanza 2 of poem 44):

Ufodu si na naira bu oria Najiria	(Some say that naira is Nigeria's success
O bu ya butere ohi	It is what caused stealing
O bu ya butere ikpo asi	It is what caused hatred
O bu ya butere inye na iri ngari	It is what caused the giving and taking of bribes
Naira butere oke ndorondoro ugbu a	Naira caused a lot of tussle now
Ihe ndi a bu ihe ojoo	All these are bad things
Ma onye enweghi naira	But whoever does not have naira
O na-ebe so akwa	Only cries)

(Madubuike in Emenanjo, (ed.) N.d., p. 45)

The poet, in the stanza above, mirrors some of the challenges posed by people's love of money and how that has further divided society along class lines. The metonymic representation of 'problem' with 'oria' (ailment) in the first line of stanza two above draws the reader's attention to the weightiness of the issue discussed. Some of those problems, which can be considered in the position of the poet as 'symptoms' of the Nigerian sickness (problem) include: 'stealing' as seen in line 2 where he says "O bu ya butere ohi" (It is what caused stealing), 'hatred' as seen in line 3, where he says "O bu ya butere ikpo asi" (It is what caused hatred), 'bribery' as portrayed in line 4, where he says "O bu ya butere inye na iri ngari" (It is what caused giving and taking of bribes) and 'huge tussles' as shown in line 5, where the poet says "Naira butere oke ndorondoro ugbu a" (Naira caused a lot of tussle now). All these issues are capable of destroying any society, including Nigeria. The poet also notes in lines 8-9 of stanza two above that, notwithstanding the negative impacts of money on society, money is still essential to human existence.

The poet, however, warns in his last stanza that, despite the benefits that come with wealth, there is a need to exercise caution regarding the negative impacts of money on society; money is still essential. In the words of the poet:

Eee! Ego dī uto dī ebube	(Yes, money is sweet and glorious
Ma cheta na o bughī ka ihe nracha si ato	But remember, you do not indulge in
	consumption of something simply
	because it is tasty.
Ka e si aracha ya	That it is leaked
Onye sowe uto anu	If a person is allured by the taste of
	meat
O righi anu udele	Does not eat vulture meat
O rie nke mmadu	He eats that of a human
O ji nti nuru	He that has ears hear.)
(Madubuike in Emenanjo, (ed.), Nd., p. 46)	

The poet's intention in writing this poem becomes apparent in the last stanza above, which is to teach a lesson. The poet closes the poem by warning the reader against unnecessary cravings for riches. As seen in line 1 of the above last stanza, the poet agrees that wealth is indeed a good thing, but if the desire for wealth is not tamed and managed, it can lead to destruction. This is what the poet is referring to in lines 2-5 in the above stanza.

J.N. Onwuchekwa's portrayal of the money motif in her poem "Ego" (Money) in *Akpaala Okwu* (Poem 45) mirrors money (wealth) as the key to power. The sense of power, as indicated by Onwuchekwa in the poem, refers to social control. The poet (Onwuchekwa) sees money as a status symbol and an agent of economic and social control. This is why in her first stanza (Poem 45), the poet begins by saying:

Ego bekee dī uto	(English money is sweet
Okpogho bekee bara uru	English money is useful
Onye ji ya nwere nsopuru	Whoever has it has respect
Ma onye o koru n'onuma.	But whoever lacks it is in annoyance
Ma i mutara akwukwo	Whether you are learned,
Ma i mughiri amu	Or you are not learned,
Ego na-achi uwa	Money rules the world
Ego na-eme ihe uwa adi mfe	Money makes things easy)
(Onwuchekwa, 1983, p. 36)	

There is no gainsaying that one of the most effective and powerful ways to exercise control over others is through economic power. The economic power and control the poet is talking about boils down to riches or wealth. This is the point expressed in the above excerpt. It is unfortunate that, today, both the educated and the uneducated in society submit to the power of money. That is the power the poet is referring to in lines 1-2, when she says that money is sweet and it is also useful. The usefulness of money in society is reflected in how it is used to control different events, including, but not limited to, gaining respect that comes from being placed in a high social status, as seen in line 3. The rich who gain this high social and political status, even when not educated, control both the elite and non-elites in the society, as expressed in lines 5-6 above, where the poet says

...Ma ì mụtara akwụkwọ	Whether you are learned,
Ma ì mughiri amụ	Or you are not learned,

The points discussed by the poet in lines 3-6 are summarised in line 7 when the poet states in clear terms that money rules the world – an indication that money is power. The poet buttresses this thought in the second stanza of the poem (Poem 45) where she says:

Ikwu na ibe adighi,	(There are no kinsmen
Ma ego bekee kọ gi.	When you have no money
Uwa dum bụ nke gi,	The whole world is yours
Ma ì nwere okpogho bekee.	When you have money.)
(Onwuchekwa, 1983, p. 36)	

The above excerpt captures the poem's thought. It portrays the value of money in the Igbo (human) society. Today, the poor are avoided like a plague, even by their relatives and kinsmen. This is the thought expressed in lines 1-2 of the above stanza. On the other hand, as expressed in lines 3-4 of the above stanza, the rich gain everything, even what they do not deserve, because of the power of money. The

poet's portrayal of money as a social status indicator becomes more apparent in stanza 5 (Poem 45), where the poet says:

Ego na-enye nsopuru na ugwu	(Money gives respect and honour
Kariadi imu oke akwukwo.	Even more than being well educated
Ihe e ji ego eme daa,	When it comes to the things done with money
Ugwu na nsopuru ha aputa.	Their dignity and respect will surface
Ndi oke akwukwo alaa azu,	The highly educated will withdraw
N'ih i nsopuru uwa nyere ego.	Because of the value the world attaches to money
Ya mere ajo ihe ji di,	That is why there is evil
Bu icho ego n'uzo o bula.	Manifest in searching for money by all means.)

(Onwuchekwa, 1983, p. 37)

From the image painted here, we can see that our society has misplaced its priorities because of the value the world places on money. No doubt, the Igbo society, in its microcosmic nature, is also influenced and affected by changes happening in the macrocosm. Before now, people pursued education believing that knowledge is power, but today, because of the much value attached to money, the philosophy has changed to money is power. This is the view the poet is expressing in the above stanza in lines 1- 6 of the above stanza 5. The poet further reveals that the world's great value placed on money has put it in a precarious situation. Today, our youths seek money by all means. Some of them kill, steal, and commit other vices just to make money, which will give them the power. This is what the poet is referring to in lines 7-8 when she says:

Ya mere ajo ihe ji di,	(That is why there is evil
Bu icho ego n'uzo o bula.	Manifest in searching for money by all means.)

The point advanced by the poet in the above lines is that the love of money is indeed the root of all evil. In a world like ours, which is controlled by money, there must be a multiplicity of evil over good. The reason for this is simple: since everyone is in dire need of being wealthier than others, there cannot be an absence of greed,

covetousness, bribery, armed robbery, money rituals, and many other manifestations of evil.

While Onwuchekwa, in her poem, ‘Ego’, identifies the quest for money as being responsible for all the problems in society, C. C. Anozie, in his poem of the same title ‘Ego’ (Poem 46) in *Uche bu Akpa*, mirrors in detail those evil deeds people do in society in their quest for money. Anozie portrays money as being in the background of all the atrocities happening in Igbo society today. Some of those atrocities that men do in a bid to make money include women forsaking their husbands, people performing a lot of blood rituals which include plucking the eyes, cutting of human head, breast, vagina, penis, and tongue. Other evil things people do for money, as mirrored by the poet, include the selling of human parts, prostitution, and child trafficking. All these evil deeds are portrayed in various stanzas of the poem. In stanza 4 (poem 46), for instance, the poet says:

Ajọ ihe juru gị ahụ	(You are full of evil
Ibere isi mmadụ	Cutting the head of a human being
Isi onye dị ndụ	The head of a living person
Tinye ya n’azu ụgbọala	Put it at the back of the car
Gurụ mkpuru anya abụọ mmadụ	Pluck the two eyes of a person
Kpuo ya isi	Make him blind
N’ihi ego	Because of money
Ibere ara nwaanyi...	Cutting the breast of a lady
Ara nwaanyi ji azu nwa child with)	The breast the woman raises her

(Anozie, 2005, pp. 96–97)

It is indeed heartbreaking to see what the Igbo society has become just because of money. The picture painted by the poet (Anozie) in the above stanza is less compared to what people do today in their quest to become rich. This is why the poet believes that money is at the root of all the evil going on in the world today. Another heinous crime people commit in a bid to make money, as mirrored by the poet (Anozie) in his poem, can be found in stanza ten, where he says:

Ego butere ashawo	(Money caused prostitution
Jiri ahụ mmadụ mere ngwaahịa	Making the human body a commodity
A na-arụ ahụ mmadụ ọnụ?	Is the human body bargained for?
Ịtoro na irefu ụmụaka	Kidnapping and selling of children
Ụmụaka Chukwu zitere	Children sent by God)

(Anozie, 2005, p. 98)

One may not understand the gravity of these crimes unless one understands the nature of the traditional Igbo society, which has metamorphosed into today's society. Today, many people who commit atrocities to make money are given chieftaincy titles, while some of them are made chairmen on occasions, just because society now worships money. It is important to add that this cultural change is not peculiar to Igbo society but has become a global problem. Today, prostitution, which the poet satirises in line 1 of his tenth stanza, is now seen as a line of business. Kidnapping and child trafficking captured in line 4 have become a social menace. All of these are done in an effort to make money. This is why the poet (Anozie) strongly believes that money is behind all the evil going on in society today.

The position of the exponents of the mirror-image approach, that literature reflects society, is better appreciated again by looking at Ezeuchegbu's representation of money in his poem "Ego" (Poem 47). The poet, like some other poets, begins by reflecting on the societal values that have been lost since money was introduced as a legal tender. The poet made this view known in his first stanza (Poem 47), where he says:

Ego! Ọ bịaara ala ghasaa	(Money! is that which came, and the
society	scatters
Ego! O mebiri mbà na mbà	Money! The destroyer of community ties
Ego! O mere nwanne amaghị nwanne ya	Money! The one that made siblings not
	recognise one another
Ewo! Ego nwa jiri ree nne ya	<i>Ewo!</i> Money that made a child sell their
	mother
Ọ bụ uru ka ọ bụ ahụhụ?...	Is it a benefit or a punishment?)

(Ezeuchegbu in Nwadike (ed.) 2006, p. 116)

In the above excerpt, all the lines reinforce the central thought, which is captured in the first line: “Ego! O bɪara ala ghasaa”. The poet, as a member of society, appears flabbergasted by the level of social vices and moral degradation that has been ongoing since the introduction of money in human society. This is why the poet acknowledges that society became polarised since money was introduced. Because of money, different communities, states, and nations are set against one another in their quest for economic dominance. Even among family members, siblings are set against one another, while children even sell their parents, and in some cases, use their parents for money rituals. All these evil deeds, which the poet captures in lines 1-4 in the above excerpt, are alien to Igbo culture. Unfortunately, the loss of our morality in society tends to get worse by the day. This maleficence seems to have informed the thought in the fifth line of the excerpt above, where the poet wonders whether the introduction of money is a blessing or a curse for Igbo society.

The poet does not stop there; he does not seem to understand why something created by humans controls them in such a manner that money does today. In stanza two, the poet goes on to show the reader images of social structures that have been affected since the introduction of money in the Nigerian state. The two fundamental issues raised by the poet in the second stanza are the subjugation of the poor by the rich and the fall of the Igbo justice system. In the words of the poet

Ego bɪ aka mere ya	(Money is man-made
Ma ɔ bɪrɪla ɔkpara ka nna	But it has become the first male child that is bigger than the father
Umɔ mgbei enwekwaghɪ ɔnɔ okwu	The poor no longer have a say
N’ihi ego ɔgaranya nwere	Because of the wealth of the rich
Ikpe nkwumotɔ aburɪla ihe akuko	Justice is now an illusion
Maka na ikpe na-amazi eziokwu	Because the truth is now found guilty.)

(Ezeuchegbu in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 116)

The poet deplures the state Igbo society has fallen into, due to the excessive value placed on wealth over human lives. Human society has become a place where money is worshipped, and the single voice of the rich has subsumed the many voices of the poor. There is no more justice as the truth can now be bought over. This despicable situation is what the poet condemns in the stanza above. From the image of society the poet presents in the poem, we can see that he, as a member of society, is not writing in isolation; he is also affected by changes in society, hence his portrayal of it in this manner.

5.1.3.2 Economic Trees and Their Importance as Portrayed in Written Igbo Poetry

One of the economic plants that captured the interest of Igbo poets in the decades under study is the palm tree. Tagbo Nzeako and Tony Ubesie, both in *Akpa Uche* (1975), Joseph. C. Maduekwe in *Nkà Okwu* (1979) and Anelechi, B. Chukuezi in *Akọ Bụ Ndu* (1988) are some of the modern Igbo poets who, through their poems, projected the economic importance of the palm tree, *Nkwụ*. The poets mirror the role and usefulness of the palm tree as a major cash crop in the people's economic life. Let us look at each poem in more detail.

Tagbo Nzeako, in his poem “Nkwụ” in *Akpa Uche* (Poem 48), highlights the various needs the palm tree serves for the people. In his portrayal of the economic tree, the palm tree is the most important tree crop in Igboland. This is because every part of the palm tree serves a purpose. The economic usefulness of the palm tree as revealed in Nzeako’s poem can be categorised into three: domestic, agricultural, and industrial. This is why in his first stanza (Poem 48) the poet notes:

Ọ dị osisi bāra nnù urù?

(Is there a tree so useful?)

<p>Ò dighī ihe dī n'àhụ ya na-ala n'iyì. Mà mgbè ọ dī ndụ, gùzoro ọto, Mà mgbè ọ tọgbòrò n'àlà n'ọnwụ.</p>	<p>There is nothing on its body that is a waste. Both when it is alive, standing, And when it's lying on the ground in death)</p>
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(Nzeako in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 16)

The poet's view here (Poem 48) can be better appreciated if one understands the role the palm tree played in the economic history of the Igbo prior to the twenty-first century. Prior to this century, the palm tree was considered one of the most important trees in Igbo life. It is the numerous uses of the palm tree that the poet acknowledges in the first stanza of his poem. For the Igbo, every part of the palm tree is considered very useful, both while it stands as a tree and when it is hewed down. That is what the poet is restating in lines 2-4 of the above stanza. Having introduced the subject of the poem, the poet begins to explain to his reader, in stanza two, the reason for his introductory remarks by stating that:

<p>Mgbè nkụ dī ndụ nà-èto, Di òchì nà-àga tee mmāī. Igu ya nà-ènye azịzà nà igbègiri. Mà osisi yā, kà a nà-àmanyere jī.</p>	<p>(When the palm tree is alive and growing, The palm wine tapper goes to tap wine. Its leaves supply brooms and large containers produced from palm branches Nevertheless, its rachis is used as a yam stake.)</p>
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(Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 16)

The above stanza from poem 48 portrays some economic importance of the palm tree to the Igbo which include its usefulness in virtually all the social events in Igbo culture like wedding, burial and coronation ceremonies, to mention but a few and in providing a source of livelihood for the palm wine tappers who tap and sell the wine to people, who in turn use them for social events.

The second importance of the palm tree, as portrayed by Nzeako in the second stanza above, is its domestic usefulness. As the poet rightly captures in line 3, palm leaves are used to make brooms from their branches, known as *igbegiri*. Although

these items are used for domestic purposes, in most cases, they are produced in large quantities and sold in the market, providing a source of income for some people who engage in the trade. The palm tree's last importance, as portrayed in the stanza above, is its agricultural uses. Farmers use the rachis of the palm tree as a yam stake on their farms.

The poet (Nzeako) also projects what is already known: that the palm tree is a source of palm oil, palm kernel, and the pomade produced from the kernel. The fact that palm fruits also provide food for squirrels and that the kernel epicarp is used to make fire explains why the palm tree is considered the most important economic tree by the Igbo. The poet portrays these views in his fourth stanza of poem 48 when he says:

Akwū nā-enye mmādù akū nà mmanụ,	(Palm tree supplies man with kernel and oil,
Mà ènwè na òsa na uzè nà-àta akwū.	Both monkey and squirrel eat palm fruits.
Ò bughī n'akū kà a nà-ènweta ūde?	Is it not from the palm tree that the local cream is prepared?
Mà jiri ichèrè akū na-èmenwu okū.	And fire is kindled with the kernel (epicarp).
(Nzeako in Ekechukwu, (ed.), 1975, p. 16)	

To better appreciate Nzeako's poem, one can refer to the economic history of palm production in Southeastern Nigeria. Economic historians have revealed that the growth of trade among the Igbo and the recognition of the Igbo in the international market were the result of palm oil and palm kernel production, which originated in West Africa and was domiciled in Southeastern Nigeria. The earliest information about the socioeconomic life of the Igbo, which stems from various archeological finds in Igbo-Ukwu, Ugwuele, and Nri, suggests that the early Igbo made a living through various crafts such as weaving, pottery moulding, metalworking (Northrup, 1972, p. 218), farming, and hunting. The Igbo took agriculture very seriously as it

provided the Igbo with not just enough food to feed their families, but also used some of the farm produce as a means of exchange in trade. The principal crops the Igbo were known for and which they gained economic power in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries were yams, palm oil, and palm kernel (Northrup, 1972, p. 219; Ekechi, 1981, p. 35; Lynn, 1997, p. 34). This is another primary reason the Igbo attach so much importance to the palm tree. Various economic benefits of the palm tree are captured in the poet's eleventh stanza of the same poem 50 when he writes:

Nkwụ nà-ènye mmādu ọtutu egō,	(Palm tree yields revenue for people
Mà ọ chọghị onye ume n̄gwu.	But it does not need a lazy person.
N'ihì ọtutu ọrụ ọ nà-ènye mmādù.	Because of the numerous jobs it gives to
	people
Mà nkwụ nwèrè ume n̄gwu.	But the palm tree is lazy.)
(Nzeako in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 17)	

As someone who understands the history of his people (Igbo), the poet here (stanza 11 of poem 48) sees the palm tree as a revenue-yielding tree and as a means of employment that does not require laziness. Although the Igbo planted and produced other crops, the palm tree was the major tree crop that paved the way for economic boom in Igboland in the past. Towns like Ozubulu, Ihiala, Owerri, Orlu, Okija, and many other Igbo towns were considered a rich palm tree belt (Ekechi, 1981). It employed the youths of these towns and for others who came there in search of greener pastures. Due to the interest of major European companies in the palm oil business in Igboland, the trade dominated their commercial activities.

Tony Ubesie's own poem 'Nkwụ' in *Akpa Uche* (Poem 49) reveals the universality of the palm tree all over Igboland. In the first stanza of the poem, Ubesie writes.

Ị bàta n'òbòdò ndị Igbò	(When you arrive in Igboland
Legharịa anya n'àlà ndị Igbò	And look around the whole of Igboland
Ị hụ ihe kwū ọtọ dī elū	You will see something standing high
Nā-enye gị èkèle dī elū	Giving you high greetings)
(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 30)	

This stanza points out that, in Igboland, the palm tree is not just any other tree but a significant landmark. Ubesie's view here aligns with that of scholars such as Northrup (1972) and Ekechi (1981), who assert that the palm tree is indigenous to Southeastern Nigeria. Furthermore, Ubesie's poem is more of an eulogy to the palm tree as an outstanding tree crop that has sustained the Igbo over the years. In the seventh stanza of poem 49, the poet states:

Otu ahụ gị si dị mma	(The way your body is good
Ka echiche gị si dị mma	Is the way your thoughts are good
I dị ọgò buru onye ukwu	You are tall and also a great person
Nye di ochi ebe o na-azọ ukwu	Provide the palm wine tapper a place to step on)

(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 31)

Here, the poet (Ubesie) eulogises the palm for its numerous benefits. This is why in lines 1-2 of the above stanza seven, the poet describes the palm tree's body as well as its thoughts as good. By describing the body and thought of the palm tree as good as implied in lines 1-2, the poet is referring to all the economic importance of the palm tree, like the provision of raw materials for domestic, industrial, and architectural usage. Another implied thought in the above stanza is that the palm tree provides a means of employment to those who engage in palm wine tapping, as seen in line 4, where the poet talks about the palm wine tappers. Other poets who share this thought include Tagbo Nzeako and J.C. Maduekwe.

Ubesie's praise of the palm tree in his poem is geared towards describing its physical properties, with a view to stimulating readers' interest in the numerous economic benefits of the palm tree. Just like Nzeako, Ubesie also itemises some of the domestic and commercial products that could be derived from the palm tree as seen in the ninth and tenth stanzas of his poem (Poem 49):

Urù a nà-ènwe gī bù ajā?	(The benefits for you are numerous?)
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Ò bù àzìzà e jì àza ụlò?	Is it the broom that is used in sweeping the house?
K' ò bù òkàtà e jì èkpo ajā?	Or is it the basket that is used in packing sands?
K' ò bù igù e jì àrụ ụlò?	Or the fronds used in building?
Ò bù akụ si n' àhụ gī?	Is it the wealth that comes from your body?
K' ò bù mmanya a na-ènwe gị?	Or is it the wine gotten from you?
Ò bù eriri e jì èke ihē?	Is it the rope that is used in tying things?
K' ò bù mmanu e jì èri ihē?	Or is it the oil used in eating?

(Ekechukwu (Ed.), 1975, p. 31)

The above stanzas underscore some of the economic importance of the palm tree to the Igbo. Some of the end products from materials obtained from the palm tree, as reflected in the stanza, include brooms, baskets, branches or rachis used as roofing sheets, wine, ropes, and, most importantly, palm oil. The raw materials used to produce the above-listed items are all derived from the palm tree. In most cases among the Igbo, they are all produced in large quantities and sold at the market, thereby adding to the internally generated revenue (I.G.R.) of the Southeast.

There is no gainsaying that some poets are more skilled at crafting the titles of their poems than others. This is the case of J.C. Maduekwe, who has a captivating title to his poem on the palm tree 'Osisi na-amị Ego' (Tree that grows money) in *Nkà Okwu* (Poem 50). From his title, the reader can infer that the poem portrays the economic importance of the tree that serves as its subject, 'Nkwu'. Just like Ubesie in his own poem, 'Nkwu', Maduekwe also confirms the universality of the palm tree in Igboland as a significant landmark. Maduekwe, however, adds that the palm tree is native and peculiar to the Southeast. In the first stanza of the poem 50, the poet states:

Otù yā ebe à, otù yā obeeye,	(One of it here, one of it there,
Kà ha gùzòchàrà, bù mkpurụ àlà à;	As they are standing, the fruit of the soil;
Dị òkpù dì kà àlà, dì kà eluigwē.	As ancient as the earth, as the heavens.
N'elu ēlū ahụ osisi nwa oma à,	On the very top of this good tree,
Àkù fòrò ya yie abọ a fòrò akpụ	Riches abound in it like a cassava-filled up basket;
Mkpurụ egō, mmiri egō, eriri egō;	Seed of money, juice of money, rope

of money;
Onye nwērē nkwū kowèrè àkù n'elū. He who has a palm tree hangs money on top.)
(Maduekwe, 1979, p. 57)

Maduekwe's portrayal of the palm tree in the stanza above summarises both its place as an important tree in Igbo life and its economic benefits. In lines 1-3, the poet introduces the poem's subject by revealing that the history of the palm tree in Igboland cannot be traced, as many believe it to be primordial and not necessarily planted by the Igbo. Zeven (1972, p. 275) confirms this claim by stating that the majority of the palm trees found in Igboland are semi-domesticated. This means that they were not grown from palm tree seeds or by transplanting seedlings. This is what the poet seems to mean in line 2 of the above stanza when he says, "Kà ha gùzòchàrà, bụ̀ mkpuru àla à" (As they are standing, the fruit of the soil). It was much later, when the Igbo discovered that palm oil was highly needed and could serve as a means of wealth generation, that most people in many Igbo communities began to practice the full domestication of the palm tree to boost their economy. Having recognized the economic value of the palm tree, the Igbo began mining it to its full capacity. The economic value of the palm tree is captured in line 6 of the above excerpt when the poet says, "Mkpuru egō, mmiri egō, eriri egō" (Seed of money, water of money, rope of money). Having presented the economic importance of the palm to the Igbo, the then poet concludes in line 7 that indeed whoever has a palm tree is rich indeed.

In the second stanza, the poet begins to itemise some of the ways the Igbo make money with the palm tree and its domestic value. The poet writes:

Mkpuru ya nyèrè mmanū, nyere akụ, nyèrè nku;
Ifuru ya nyèrè mmanya, nyèrè nri àlà, nyèrè owa;
Ogwè ya nyèrè ubiri, nyèrè ahijia ubi, nyèrè nku;
Alakā ya nyèrè eriri, azizà, oforò.
A choo ikpō ahà sị cheta akwarà, urimù nà òmunkwù;
Àhụ nkwū dum kwurù ekpiri egō, wèe kwuo;
Onye nwèrè nkwū kòwèrè àkù n'elū.

(Maduekwe, 1979, p. 57)

(Its fruit gives oil, gives kernel, gives firewood;
 Its flower gives wine, gives food for the earth, gives a light stick.
 Its trunk/stem gives rachis, farm grasses, and firewood.
 Its branch gives ropes, brooms, and stems.
 If names are to be mentioned, do remember the roots, flowers, and tender fronds.
 All the parts of the palm tree are full of money, and say;
 Whoever has a palm tree hangs wealth on top.)

The poet's view here gives the right picture of the place and uses of the palm tree among the Igbo, both in traditional and contemporary Igbo society. Each of the lines in the above stanza mirrors the usefulness of the tree crop in the economic life of the Igbo. It is due to all these benefits of the palm tree that the poet concludes the poem by saying that anyone who has palm tree indeed is a wealthy person.

Like the three poets, whose poems on the palm tree focus on the economic importance of the tree to the Igbo, discussed above, A.B. Chukuezi's poem, 'Nkwu' (Palm Tree), in *Ako bu Ndu* (Poem 51), focuses on the economic and domestic importance of the palm tree to the Igbo. According to Chukuezi in the second stanza of the poem, some of the materials obtained from the palm tree include ropes, brooms, rachis, and tender fronds used to tie corpses and mark boundaries on the farm. In the words of the poet:

Eriri e jiri ke ibu ulo, ke ogbà	(The ropes used in tying house roof, tying barn
Aziza e jiri zaa ulo	The broom used in sweeping the house
Igu e jiri wachie oba na mgbala	The leaves used in guarding the barn and compound garden
Ha niile si gi n'ahụ.	All of them came from your body
Omụ e jiri kwaa àjà	Tender fronds used in sacrifice
Nke e jiri kee ozu	The one used in the tying of the corpse)
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 4)	

Here, the poet portrays some key traditional uses of the palm tree. Each of the points raised in the above excerpt is, in most cases, commercialised by the Igbo as a way of engaging in legitimate business. In traditional Igbo society, ropes used for various purposes are made from palm tree fibers. This is what the poet mirrors in the first line of the above excerpt. Again, it is not new knowledge that brooms are made

from the leaves of the palm tree, which is what the poet reminds the reader in line 2 of the above excerpt. Another traditional importance of the palm tree, as portrayed by the poet (Chukuezi) in the above excerpt, is ritualistic (used for traditional worship and funeral rites) as seen in lines 4-5 of the above stanza.

From what has been examined in this section of the study, it has become clear that, in Igbo society, apart from yams, the chief tree crop for agricultural life is the palm tree, which is of great economic importance, as depicted in various poems.

5.1.4 Some Ecological Issues as Portrayed in Written Igbo Poetry

In this section, we shall discuss some key ecological issues that attracted the attention of modern Igbo poets in the decades under study. The points discussed in this section show that apart from political, cultural, and economic issues, modern Igbo poets also took an interest in some ecological issues and the ecosystem. Ecology is defined as the study of organism-to-organism interaction and how organisms interact with their environment (Worku, Teklu, and Aragaw, 2002). The term ecology summarises the whole levels of biological organisations. Key among these biological organizations is the ecosystem, which serves as the central organizational concept in ecology (Currie, 2011). An ecosystem is also defined as the community of living (man, plants, animals) and non-living things (water, sun, soil, air) that work together (sc-s.si, n.d.). The main parts of an ecosystem include plants, water, animals, light, water temperature, soil, and air (Sc-s.si, n.d.), and they all work together. Other examples of ecosystems include deserts, rainforests, aquatic ecosystems, human ecosystems, coral reefs, forests, littoral zones, marine ecosystems, prairies, and savannas, to name a few. Of all these environmental issues, the poets were most

interested in writing about the sun and the moon. We shall go on to discuss the representation of the sun and moon in written Igbo poetry.

5.1.4.1 Poets' Portrayal of the Sun as a Source of Energy and Light in Written Igbo Poetry

The sun is a key part of the ecosystem, as it supplies heat needed for the development and survival of living and non-living things (Christian, n.d.). Worku et al. (2002) note the important role the sun plays in sustaining an ecosystem, asserting that ecosystems are open systems that are not self-sustaining and, as such, require, along with nutrient input, energy input from the sun to sustain them. Four poets who wrote on the Igbo perception of the role of the sun in their poems in the decades under study include R.N. Ekegbo, U. Ndunagum, Onyejekwe, Ikeokwu, and N.R. Ezejesi.

Ekegbo, in his poem ‘Ọnwa na Anyanwụ’ in *Ụwa Onye na Chi Ya* (Poem 53), mirrors the sun as a significant source of light and energy. In the first stanza of his poem, Ekegbo presents the light from the sun as marking the day- total absence of darkness occasioned by *Abali* (night). In the words of the poet in the first stanza,

Ndị a bụ isi ihe ndị a ma ama	(These are the sources of common knowledge.
Enyemaka anya na ihe nke ụwa	Help of the eyes and the light of the world.
Ihe ndị e si na ha ahụ ụzọ nke ọma	The light through which men see clearly
Nwee ike igosi ihe ọ bụla nye ha nkọwa	Be able to show everything and give interpretations)

(Ekegbo, 2005, p. 15)

Ekegbo, in poem 52, suggests that the sun is a source of natural light, a fact common knowledge among the Igbo, as seen in line 1. Another point Ekegbo made in the above stanza is that their light from the sun cannot be compared to artificial lights

as seen in lines 3-4. The poet, in the third stanza of the poem (Poem 52), writes on the benefit of the sun to the ecosystem when he states:

Ebe oge abali na-abu oge nke onwa	(Since nighttime is for the moon
n'ehihie ka anyanwu na-enye ihe nke ya	The sun gives its own light in the day
Ihe na-esi n'anyanwu na-aburu uwa isioma	The light coming from the sun is
	beneficial to the world
n'ihie na uwa na-esi na ya enwe ezi nchawa	Because the world glitters through it)
(Ekegbo, 2005, p. 15)	

The light that the poet (Ekegbo) is referring to in the above third stanza of his work is the energy from the sun, which provides heat, which keeps both plants and animals warm. The word 'nchawa' as used by the poet in line 4 connotes life and sound health. Among the contemporary Igbo, 'nchawa' is a slang that means to shine and blossom both in wealth, health, academics, and other fields of endeavours. So, by saying "n'ihie na uwa na-esi na ya enwe ezi nchawa", the poet means that every creature (uwa) draws energy for good health from the sun.

In her portrayal of the sun as a key aspect of the ecosystem, U. Ndunagum in her poem 'Anyanwu' (Sun) (Poem 53) in *Akponauche*, eulogises the sun and also writes about the benefits of the Sun to the ecosystem. In her first stanza, the poet begins by eulogising the sun as very beautiful, describing it as the day's beauty. In the words of the poet,

Anyanwu, mma ehie	(The Sun, beauty of the day
Igbo ji gi ekwu okwu na-asị	The Igbo speaks about you
"Ututu oma na-eji anwu awa	A good morning rises with the sun
Mma gi amaka nke bu na	Your beauty is so good in that
Nwaanyi maa mma nke ukwu	When a woman is so fine
A kpo ya, "Anyanwu Ututu".	She is called "Morning Sun")
(Ndunagum in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 258)	

Ndunagum, in the above stanza (Poem 54), summarises the Igbo figurative understanding of the sun. Night time, which brings darkness, is believed by the Igbo to harbour a lot of evil, which is why the Igbo have a common name 'Abalidiegwu'

(Night's terror) for anyone who perpetrates evil under the cover of darkness that nighttime provides. The day, which begins with the rising of the sun, is considered beautiful because it illuminates the whole world, giving people time and energy to make a living. The principal element that distinguishes the night from the day – the sun-is what the poet is referring to in line 1, when he refers to the sun as “mma ehie (beauty of the day). In the remaining lines of the stanza above, the poet reinforces his belief that the sun is the essence of the day, thereby evoking a sense of love in the reader. In the second stanza of poem 53, the poet begins to explain the role of the sun to the ecosystem by stating that:

I dị mkpa maka ndụ ihe niile	(You are very important for the survival of all living things.
I na-azụ anụahụ mmadụ n'otu ụzọ	You nourish the human body in one way,
Ihe akụkụ si na gị adị ndụ	Plants draw their life from you
O bu umu anumanu bu ndi na-achoghi gi?	Are animals that do not need you?)
(Ndunagum in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 258)	

The three main species that gain energy from the sun, as the poet mirrors in the stanza above, include plants (line 2), man (line 3), and animals (line 4). In humans, sunlight synthesizes vitamin D in the skin, leading to the production of Vitamin D, which is required for bone health and prevents rickets (Mead, 2008). This seems like the point the poet is making in line 2. On the other hand, sunlight is instrumental to the overall development of plants, since the two main processes (photosynthesis and nutrient mineralisation) that support plant development are driven by the sun (Christian, n.d.). Plants receive energy from the sun through the process of photosynthesis. This process is what the poet is referring to in line 3 when she says “Ihe akụkụ si na gị adị ndụ” (Plants draw their life from you). In line 4, Ndunagum likewise discusses the animals, stating that they draw energy from the sun. Worku

et.al. (2002) summarise the role of the sun towards the sustenance of the ecosystem by stating thus:

The transfer of energy through a biological community (or an ecosystem) begins when the energy of sunlight is fixed in a green plant by photosynthesis. Photosynthesis converts radiant energy into useful, high-quality chemical energy in the bonds that hold together organic molecules. The transfer of this captured energy from organism to organism is basic to the functioning of ecosystems (P. 25).

This view of Worku et al., here, brings to the fore the key role of the sun in the ecosystem, a view shared by Ndunagum in her poem.

For Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe in their poem ‘Anyanwụ’ (Sun) (Poem 54) in *Uche bụ Ahịa*, they see the sun as merely a source of light, illuminating every area of darkness occasioned by nighttime. The poets, just like Ekegbo, in their first stanza eulogise the sun for its beauty, while in the second stanza of the poem, the poets say

E lee ka I si enwu vaa	(Look how you radiate
Ị dika olaedo	You are like a gold
Ị na-erughari	You always flow around
Ka eruru nkwu	Like the wine that us tilted
Ahụ gị na-akwọ mụrụ mụrụ	Your body is smooth
ka nwa oheru	Like a newborn baby
I mara mma oyoyo	You are stunning.)

(Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, 2009)

In this stanza, the poet focuses on the sun's physical features. The aim is to draw the reader's attention to the sun's role as an integral part of the ecosystem. Lines 1-2, for instance, refer to the shiny or bright nature of sunlight. This shiny or bright nature of the sun is captured in the poets' use of the Ideophone “Vaa, which is used to represent ‘high-level brightness. Lines 3-4 refer to the cloudy look of the sun, while lines 5-7 refer to the smooth surface of the sun, making it extraordinarily beautiful. Having taken time to describe the sun and its nature, the poets, in the thrust of their

writing, in stanza three, wrote on the illuminating function of the sun as a part of the ecosystem. In the words of the poets:

Ọ bụ gi	(It is you
Ka ụwa ji ahụ ụzọ	That the world see with
Ị tikasịa	When you manifest
Onye ukwu n'ụzọ	The great to the road
Onye ntà n'ọhịa	The small to the bush
Ịchọ ihe afo ga-eri	In search of what the tommy will eat)
(Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, 2009)	

The thought in the above stanza is compressed in lines 1-2, in the above stanza where the poets talk about the sun in terms of its illuminative feature. According to the poets, the sunrise offers people a new opportunity to make proper use of their day. The poet's portrayal of the sun only in terms of its illuminative functions exposes its other importance to the ecosystem. When the sun rises, it allows humans to carry out their daily activities, during which they produce waste that other animals or insects feed on.

Ezejesi in his poem “Anyanwụ” (Sun) (Poem 55) in *Abụ Ụtọ* (2015) gave a more detailed account of the importance of the sun to the ecosystem. In the first stanza of his poem (Poem 55), the poet begins by eulogising the sun for its uniqueness and multiple functions as a key unit of the ecosystem, when he says:

Ị na-egbuke egbuke	(You radiate
Ọ nweghị onye na-eche gi mgba	No one competes with you
Ị na-awụ ka ọza	You jump down as the rabbit
Ọtụtụ ọrụ ka Ị na-arụ	You perform numerous tasks
Anyanwụ, onye ọma	Sun, good person)
(Ezejesi, 2015, p. 16)	

This introductory stanza focuses on the poets' acknowledgment that the sun is integral to the ecosystem and that its role cannot be overemphasised. Starting from its radiating nature, which is captured in line 1, the sun's power, both as a source of energy and light, is incomparable, and that is why the poet says in line 2, “Ọ nweghị onye na-eche gi mgba” (No one competes with you). The personification of the sun in

line 3, with its simile, alludes to the rising of the sun every morning. The poet goes on in line 4, revealing to the reader why he believes the sun to be in a league of its own. In stanza two, the poet goes on to mention some of the importance or functions of the sun. In the words of the poet in his second stanza,

I na-etiri ndị mma na njo	(You shine for both the good and the bad)
E ji gi agụ awa	You are used to knowing the time
I na-eme ka àkùkù ubi mee	You make crops to develop well
Ọrịa dị iche iche ka I na-agwọ	You treat a lot of illnesses
Anyanwụ, enyi ụwa niile	Sun, friend of the whole world)

(Ezejesi, 2015, pp. 16-17)

The poet in the above stanza identifies four primary reasons for the sun's importance to other creatures and plants. First, the illuminative functions as seen in the first line, where the poet says *I na-etiri ndị mma na njo* (You shine for both the good and the bad). Secondly, time functions as seen in the second line (2) where the poet says “E ji gi agụ awa” (You are used to knowing the time). The sun, as part of the ecosystem, helps men number their days. The sun, through photosynthesis, helps crops and plants grow well. This is the point the poet made in lines 3 and 4, when Ezejesi discusses the therapeutic uses of the sun. Some of the illnesses that exposure to the sun reduces or treats include osteoporosis, acne, skin disorders, mood disorders, and anxiety (Anurag, 2017).

In essence, to the modern Igbo poet, the sun is not just a light source but also an energy source. The energy from sunlight exposure is beneficial for the development of crops and other plants.

5.1.4.2. The Representation of the Moon in Written Igbo Poetry

The moon is one of the ecological issues that caught the attention of most poets in the decades under study. Some of the poets who wrote poems on “Ọnwa” (Moon) include

J. C. Obienyem in *Akpa Uche* (p.6), A. K. Obierozie in *Ekpe Nna* (p. 30), N. Okediadi in *Ije Uwa* (p. 24), Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe in *Uche bu Ahia* (p. 68). Although the moon is not part of the ecosystem, it dominates poets' thoughts because it serves as a source of light at night. This relates to the fact that modern Igbo poets also write about things in their environment.

J. C. Obienyem, in his poem “Onwa” (Moon) (Poem 57), portrays the moon as a source of light that shines through the night. According to Obienyem, the moon's brightness at night is very soothing and can be compared to that of precious jewelry.

In the words of the poet:

Onye ihu ya na-achaputa n'abali	(One whose face shines at night
Agbogho ochi ya na-atu ka akpali	The lady whose smile enchants like the
	breaking waves
O buru akwa eke amaghim	If it is a python's egg, I do not know
A koo ji na ya, ahughi m	If yam is planted in it, I did not see
Alulu mmiri na-agbaru ya ihu	Rain cloud makes her frown
Ehie na-elu ya ihu	The day is bitter to her
Ma o na-eso m achu udara n'abali okochi	But it follows me in search of cherry at
	nights of the dry season
Onwa, onye agadi na okoro na-anuru onu	The Moon, whom both the old and
	young rejoice for)

(Obienyem in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, pp. 6-7)

Here (poem 57), the poet personifies the moon as a lady whose beauty is beyond description. The poet's portrayal of the moon as a lady in lines 1-2 mirrors the Igbo understanding of women. Beautiful ladies in the traditional Igbo society are adored and, as such, are not supposed to be seen working during the day to avoid the heat of the sun. This is why the Igbo have praise names for ladies, such as Apunanwu (one who does not go out under the sun). Since the Igbo consider the sun to be a male primordial being (Nwoye, 2011, p. 307), the moon is then projected as feminine. This explains why the poet (Obienyem) personifies the moon as a lady whose smile breaks the waves, as seen in line 2. The use of 'ochi' (similes) here relates to the tenderness

and soothing nature of the moon on humans and their environment, since it is not as harsh as the scorching of the sun in the day. In lines 3-4, the poet further describes the beauty of the moon when he writes,

O bụrụ akwa eke amaghim	(If it is a python's egg, I do not know
A kọọ ji na ya, ahughị m	If yam is planted in it, I did not see)

The metaphorical use of *Akwa ekē* (python egg) to describe the moon in the above line three alludes to the round and fluorescent nature of the moon at night. It is a common belief among the Igbo that the egg of a python contains a diamond (Ekechukwu, 1975, p. 76). Diamonds are known to be reflective precious objects; hence, the metaphorical representation of the moon as a diamond, since it also reflects the light from the sun gently and soothingly at night. Nevertheless, the moon's beauty is constantly interrupted whenever the clouds roll in, since they always cover it. This is what the poet meant in lines 5-6. Despite this fact, the moon is considered to be of great importance to the Igbo, which explains why in lines 7-8, the poet writes:

Ma ọ na-eso m achọ ụdara n'abalị ọkọchị	But it follows me in search of cherry at night.
Ọnwa, onye agadi na okoro na-anụrụ ọnụ	The Moon, whom both the old and young rejoice for)

One of the important aspects of the moon to the Igbo ecology is its illuminating powers. Nighttime is characterised by total darkness, and as such, humans cannot do anything meaningful at night. However, the moon's appearance at night illuminates the earth (Igbo world), giving people the opportunity to complete other tasks for the day. This is what the poet means in line 7 when he says *Ma ọ na-eso m achọ ụdara n'abalị ọkọchị* (But it follows me in search of cherry at night of dry season). 'Icho ụdara n'abalị' (the search for cherry at night) here represents tasks,

which by extension could be attendance to meetings at night, playing (moonlight plays), cooking, doing dishes, and many more. This is why the poet declares in the last line (8) that both the old and young rejoice at the sight of the moon.

Similarly, A.K. Obierozie, in his poem ‘Onwa’ (Moon) (Poem 57) in *Ekpe Nna*, also underscores the moon's importance in various Igbo communities. Just like Obienyem, Obierozie also personifies the moon as a newly married woman. In the first stanza of his poem, ‘Onwa’, the poet (Obierozie) portrays the moon as a newly married bride who is very shy to stay around people. In the words of Obierozie in his first stanza, he says:

O dī ka nwaanyi luru dī oḥu	(She is like a newly married bride.
O jiri akwa ocha kpuchie ihu	She covers her face with a white cloth
O pīoputa ihu ka o hū uwa	She peeps to see the world
Naani otu akuku ka o gosiri	She shows only one side
Ndi huru na ndi ahughi	Those that see and those that did not see
Tiwe mkpu inabata agboghohu	Started screaming to welcome the new lady
Ma ino odu ekweghi ya	But she could not stay for long
Maka ihu ihere ya	Because of her shyness)
(Obierozie, 1986, p. 30)	

The simile of the moon as a lady in the above stanza is similar to the personified representation of the moon as a lady in Obienyem’s poem, with its metaphoric undertone. There are two points made in the above stanza. The first one is the appearance of the moon and how that appearance is welcomed by the people (the Igbo). Regarding the moon's appearance, the poet claims that only a part of the moon is seen because the moon is shy and does not want people to see her. This is why in lines 2-4, the poet writes

O jiri akwa ocha kpuchie ihu	She covers her face with a white cloth
O pīoputa ihu ka o hū uwa	She peeps to see the world
Naani otu akuku ka o gosiri	She shows only one side.

The shyness of the moon is what the poet describes when he says that the moon covers her face with white clothes in line 2, and she also peeps to see the world (line 3), showing only one side of her (line 4). On the other hand, lines 5-6 describe how the Igbo welcome the moon's appearance. According to the poet, in lines 5-6, the people rejoice at the sight of the moon with much shouting. In the second stanza of the poem, the poet begins to list some of the activities that take place under the moon's brightness in traditional Igbo societies. The points mentioned by the poet in the second stanza were all summed up in the seventh line of Obienyem's poem "Onwa" (Poem 57), where Obienyem says, *Ma o na-eso m achọ ụdara n'abalị okochi* (But it follows me in search of cherry at nights of dry season). In the words of the poet:

Ọ lakpukwara jikere maka ngosi	(She goes in and prepares for another appearance.
Amụ o mụkepuru, nyere mmadụ niile obi anụrị	Her smile brings happiness to everyone
Umụaka gbakọọ maka egwuregwu	Children gather for play
Ndi okenye tụtụlie mkpanaka ije abalị	Elders pick up their torch for night movements
Okoro na agboghọ atughị egwu mkpakorịta	The bachelor and spinster are not afraid of chatting
Okeokpa na nnekwu chezọọ na chi ejuela	The cock and hen forget that it is night
N'ihii ihu oma gi ihe chi kere na-ekiri	Because of your radiating face , every creature watches
Were chezọọ na akwà ha na-eche ha	And forget that their beds await)
(Obierozie, 1986, p. 30)	

This stanza mirrors why most people rejoice at the sight of the moon in traditional Igbo societies. Some activities that take place at night under the moonlight in Igbo society include moonlight plays, meetings, and romantic chats on the streets. It can be understood that the moon's soothing reflection encourages these activities, since it is not harmful to the skin or eyes.

Just like Obienyem and Obierozie, Okediadi's poem "Onwa" (Moon) (Poem 59) also focuses on the sociological importance of the moon to the Igbo society. While she introduces the subject of her poem in the first stanza, the poet in the second stanza identifies some of the social activities that take place in Igbo society when the moon's reflection illuminates the darkness of night. The poet in her second stanza says:

Ihu gi bu so mma	(Your face is charming
I ji aziza azacha obodo	To sweep the town with a broom
Ebe niile a na-amukesi	Everywhere glittering
Ije aguwa agadi	The old craves for a walk
Umụ ntakiri ana awuli elu	Children jumping up
Obodo a na-ekpo oku	The city bubbling
Abali adika ututu	Night looks like day
Chi kere gi mere ihe ukwu	The God that created you did a great thing.)

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 25)

The activities that take place at night, as identified by the poet in the stanza above, explain why people rejoice in Igboland when the moon is mentioned. The poet, here (Poem 58), presents a mirror of a fun-filled night that is made possible by the appearance of the moon. This explains why the Igbo work hard during the day, hoping to enjoy their leisure hours at night, under the gentle reflection of the moon. It is not only the old and the children who rejoice at the appearance of the moon in Igbo society; Okediadi also mentions that the youths (bachelors and spinsters) seize the opportunity to socialise. In the third stanza, the poet says:

Ebube gi na-atu n'onu	(Your glory satisfies
Umụ okoro na umụ agboghọ na-atu anya gi	Bachelors and spinsters anticipate your visit
Maka uro ha ibiri oku	Just for their plans to kick start
Onwa biawa ngwangwa!	The moon comes quickly
aburu okwu ha kpu n'onu	Becomes a trending issue on their lips)

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 25)

The poet (Okediadi), as a member of society, mirrors the social lives of the people in her art, as shown in the stanza above. In the stanza above, the poet mirrors the activities of the youths when the moon appears in Igbo society. Okediadi's view, here, seems to be in tandem with the views of the two poets who, as we have discussed in their poems on 'Ọnwa', shared similar views in their works. This explains why most poets revere the moon, praising it for its role in promoting social relationships in Igbo society.

Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, in their poem 'Ọnwa' (Poem 59) in *Uche bụ Ahịa*, just like Obienyem in his poem 'Ọnwa', personify the moon as a fair, pretty lady, who illuminates every darkness. This view is observed in their first stanza, where the poet says:

Agbọọ ọcha	(Fair lady
Ite mma kụwara n'isi	The pot, beauty breaks its head
I na-eti wara wara	You sparkle wara wara
Ebe niile nchake nchake	Everywhere glittering
Abali bụ ehihie	Night becomes day
Ọchịchiri hụrụ gi	Darkness saw you
Ọsọ apụọ ya n'ụkwụ	And took to his heels)
(Ikeokwu & Onyejekwe, 2009, p. 69)	

The portrayal of the moon as a lady in the stanza above, a view shared by Obienyem, suggests that the moon is indeed considered feminine, while the sun is considered masculine. The masculinity of the sun depicts that men must work during the day. At the same time, the moon's femininity, as shown in the figurative portrayal of the moon in the stanza above and those before it, follows the role it plays in giving the man, who has toiled through the day, a place of rest and calm. The above stanza focuses on the illuminating role the moon plays in traditional Igbo societies. In their second stanza, the poets go on to explain why most people rejoice in the Igbo society by citing the moon.

Gịni mere e jiri hụ gi n'anya?	(Why are you loved?)
Nwantakiri huru gi hapu nri	The child saw you and abandoned his food
Ebe o na-aga igwu egwu gi	Where he is running to play
I tiwaa, ije agwa ngwooro	When you shine, the lame longs to walk
Agboghọ	A young lady
ka i bu	That is who you are)

(Ikeokwu & Onyejekwe, 2009, p. 69)

The main reason children rejoice at the sight of the moon in Igbo society, according to the poets in the above stanza, is due to the moonlight's play. Moonlight plays are always a venue for children to socialise in most Igbo communities. Since the full moon is not a regular occurrence, when it does appear, children take advantage of it to play and socialise, while adults turn to other engagements.

From the poets' perspective, as discussed above, the moon is an important aspect of Igbo ecology. Its appearance is always welcomed with excitement in various Igbo societies. The poets show that it is not only children who are excited upon seeing the moon; both the young and the old also rejoice at its appearance. This is because the moon illuminates the community, creating a suitable environment for promoting interpersonal relationships.

5.2 Conclusion

In this chapter, we have examined the content of some written Igbo poems, focusing on the variety of thoughts expressed by the poets. More importantly, the present chapter also examines various topical social issues of human concern, where poetic thoughts converged during the decades under study. These issues were divided into three categories: political, cultural, economic, and ecological. Having finished the discussion on the content of written Igbo poetry in this study, we shall go on in the next chapter to discuss the form of written Igbo poetry as regards the artistic style employed by modern Igbo poets in addressing the societal issues.

CHAPTER SIX

THE FORM OF WRITTEN IGBO POETRY (Ọdịdị Abụ Ederede Igbo)

6.0 Introduction

Having examined the content of some poems selected from the four decades of written Igbo poetry under study (1975-2015) in the preceding chapter, the present chapter explores the form of written Igbo poetry. Our analysis in this chapter is conducted through the lens of defamiliarisation, the key tenet of formalism.

Since formalism focuses on the formal features or specialised use of language in literary works, it seems more appropriate to apply it in this section of the study to see how modern Igbo poets create art from the ordinary language people are familiar with. As earlier stated in the introductory section of this study, defamiliarisation, as a central tenet of formalism, investigates how poets deviate from the linguistic norm in a language in their bid to make the readers see the language, which they are familiar with, in an unfamiliar or rather in a strange way – estrangement (Pourjafari, 2012). Formalists, like Jakobson (1921) cited in Abrams & Harpham (2012), opine that in examining a literary work of art, the object of study in it is not the literature itself (the content) but the “literariness” (the language play) in it. To this end, in examining the form of written Igbo poetry in this chapter, our primary emphasis is on determining the structure of rhythm and language in written Igbo poetry.

6.1 The Rhythm of Written Igbo Poetry

Rhythm (Ndanusoro) is one of the most important features without which any verse, be it verbal or written, can be termed poetic. In Igbo written poetry, rhythm plays an important role in bringing out the aesthetic qualities of the poems. Several

Igbo scholars, such as Ugonna (1982), Uzochukwu (1982, 1987, 1992, 2001, 2002), Uba-Mgbemena (1990), Nwadike (2003), Anozie (2007), and Oraegbunam (2018), have agreed that without rhythm, no Igbo verse can be termed poetic. Uba-Mgbemena (1990, p. X) asserts that one of the basic functions of rhythm is that it stirs up the emotion of the reader in every Igbo poem. This is why rhythm is also considered one of the end products of defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry.

As stated earlier in this study, Igbo written poetry has been influenced by the Western tradition of poetic composition, which emphasizes lines and stanzas (Ugonna, 1982, p. 24). In the view of Ugonna (1982), Igbo poetic rhythm, just like Western poetry, is metrical, and it also conforms to definite laws of prosody measured in rhythmic units. Ugonna's view, here, implies that rhythm in Igbo poetry is achieved by regular alternation of high and low tones as obtained in English poetry. Another person who shares Ugonna's view about rhythm in Igbo poetry is Obike (n.d), who also believes that Igbo rhythm is metrical. In his work, *Eke-Une* (n.d.) explains that one can determine the rhythm of a line in Igbo poetry by grouping stressed and unstressed syllables into foot patterns. Obike further asserts that a foot (in written Igbo poetry) is a unit of a line and a line is a unit of a verse, and just like in Western poetry, there are four types of feet in Igbo poetry, and they include: iamb, anapaest, trochee, and dactyl.

Obike tries to justify his position about the foot as a significant determinant of the metric system in Igbo poetry by giving examples of what he believes could be taken as the iamb, anapaest, trochee, and dactyl. According to Obike (n.d, p. 77), an iamb is an unaccented syllable followed by an accented syllable. He gives the following examples:

a way a way war planes and bombs
u ja n kita nube nwamba

An anapaest, according to him, refers to two unaccented syllables followed by the accented syllable, as in:

De di cate retaliate jubiliate
w e ma ta we chug ha ri ku te

Trochee refers to one accented followed by one unaccented syllable, as in:

Old robes wel come once more resume
o r i m b a A n u Oke

Dactyl refers to one accented syllable followed by two unaccented syllables, as in

Gate way forked laughing ly
Or iri ụ ta ra

Having seen what Obike considers to be examples of the foot in Igbo poetry, which he also believes forms the metric system that constitutes rhythm in Igbo poetry, it is evident that Obike is influenced mainly by his knowledge of English poetry and also his dialect. Most of his expressions in the above examples do not apply to the standard Igbo variety, as they are dialectal.

We must not lose sight of the fact that every language is complete on its own, even though it sometimes borrows some words from other language(s) (a significant characteristic of all languages of the world). The structure of every language must be according to the way the owners or speakers of such language have designed it.

Again, since rhythm is a significant criterion for evaluating the quality of poetry in any language, it is understandable why the present study examines the rhythm of written Igbo poetry as part of its form.

It is imperative to remember that “Igbo is a syllable-timed, tone language like Yoruba or Efik. It is not a stressed-timed, intonational language like English. Nor is it a pitch-accent language like Nembé” (Emenanjo 2015, p. 47). It is on this premise that this study agrees with the position of Uzochukwu (1982, 1987, 2001, and 2012) who maintains that Igbo poetic rhythm, both in oral and written Igbo poetry, is non-metrical and thus depends not on meter but on the following rhythmic factors: (i) the regular recurrence of breath pause (ii) the regular recurrence of equal time duration in consecutive utterances, and (iii) the regular recurrence of sense balance, producing the rhythm that is tied not to the structure but to the sense.

Similar to the Igbo language is the Yoruba Language, which is also a tone and syllable-timed language as observed by Emenanjo (2015). Due to this fact, rhythm in Yoruba poetry is also not metrical; instead, it is achieved by some overlapping stylistic devices (Babalola 1974, p. 14). Those devices include: stylistic repetition, balance of sense (as in Igbo poetry), parallelism, lexical matching, tonal contrast at segment-ends and tonal counterpoint (Babalola, 1974, p. 14).

Uba-Mgbemena (1990, p. X) agrees with Uzochukwu’s position, by stating that rhythm in written Igbo poetry arises out of breath pause in consecutive utterances. Uba-Mgbemena also added that the number of syllables in those consecutive utterances (or lines) may or may not be equal before rhythm can be achieved in Igbo poetry; instead, what is important is that the beats in those consecutive utterances must be equal for rhythm to be achieved. Uzochukwu (1982, 1987, 2001 and 2002)

justifies his claim that Igbo poetic rhythm is not achieved by meter with ample instances from oral Igbo poetry.

It is also important to note that three things promote rhythm in Igbo poetry (oral or written). They are: repetition (kwunkwukwa), parallelism (kwunkwugha) (Uzochukwu, 1982), syllable structure (ọdịdị sịlabul), and tone harmony (ndakota ụdaolu) (Uba-Mgbemena, 1990, p. XI). Igbo poets use all these to defamiliarise the language by painting images in the reader's mind and, in doing so, evoke emotive responses that make the poem delightful. That said, let us examine how these constituents of Igbo poetic rhythm contribute to the language of Igbo poetry being strange (estrangement).

6.1.1 The Regular Recurrence of Breath Pause (Bịambịakwa Nkwusị Nkuru Ume)

Uzochukwu (2001, p. 78) explains that the importance of the regular recurrence of the breath-pause, as a rhythmic factor in Igbo poetry, is to be appreciated if “it is recalled that the basis of Igbo poetic rhythm, which is the line, is delimited by the breath-pause. Moreover, the line is an essential distinguishing feature, not only of Igbo poetry but of poetry generally.” This rhythmic feature is what Uba-Mgbemena (1990, p. X) refers to when he opines that rhythm in Igbo poetry is achieved by breath-pause. The role of this rhythmic feature is that it determines the tempo of the poem (Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 79). There are two breath-pauses in Igbo poetry: short and normal breath-pauses (Uzochukwu, 1985 and 2001). The short breath-pause delimits short lines, which results in a quick tempo or fast rhythm, while the normal breath-pause, which delimits lines of average length in Igbo poetry, results in a slow tempo or lines that are neither too fast nor too slow. The short

breath-pause is usually marked with a single stroke, while the regular or extended breath-pause is marked with double strokes.

Uzochukwu (1982, 1987, 2001, and 2012) discusses this type of rhythm in oral Igbo poetry in detail. Therefore, in this study, we will focus on how this type of rhythm manifests in written Igbo poetry. Let us consider an example of a normal breath pause from the third stanza of J. C. Maduekwe's poem, "The Egwu Anyị" (Our musical instruments) in *Nkà Okwu* (1979, p. 2): (Poem 60)

Òjà abughị n'ìdà fìo fìo kà ọrụ ya kwàrà ;//
 Ọ mààrà, ndị gūzō ọtọ ète egwū dāwa mbà, //
 Ewu ìmū n'ogbū ajọka n'ebe okènye nọ àlà. //
 Kà ha buru ike agwū àlà bù ọrụ o kètàrà. // ...
 (Maduekwe, 1979, p. 2)

(The work of the flute does not end in *fìo fìo* sound
 He knows those who begin to slumber from dancing
 The goat giving birth on a tether while the elder is seated is bad
 Its responsibility is to keep them active. ...)

In the stanza above from poem 60, the lines are standard and of average length. Again, the tempo is neither fast nor slow, which is why they are marked with double strokes to indicate a regular rhythm. The tempo of most of Tony Ubesie's poems in *Akpa Uche* is neither fast nor slow, and this results in a normal breath pause. Let us consider another example of a normal breath pause as observed in the fourth stanza of A.B. Chukuezi's poem, "Akwa Arịrị" (Elegy), in *Akọ Bu Ndu* (1988, pp. 1-3) (poem 61), where the poet says:

O nwere ihe dakwasara m//
 Ihe mere anya mmiri jì jù ìgba m n'anya//
 Enweghị m ụmụ nwoke ga-agba egbe ma m nwụo//
 Agaala m njem n'ozara//
 Na nnukwu ozara mmadu kporo ndu//
 Mmiri wee maba m n'okpukpu//
 Ogwu di nkọ ka mma wee mawasija m ukwu//
 Aga m echipu garuo ebe ezumike//
 Enweghị m ikwu, enweghị m ibe, enweghị m nwa//
 Onwu emenyola ezi anyi anya//
 (Chukuezi, 1988, p. 2)

(There is something that has befallen me
 That made tears well up in my eyes
 I do not have male children who will shoot the gun when I die
 I have journeyed through the forest
 In a big forest, a man calls life
 And the rain beat me up to my bones
 Sharp thorns like a knife pierced my legs
 I will set off to a resting place
 I do not have relatives, and I do not have a son
 Death has dealt seriously with our family.

Uzochukwu (2012, p. 17) rightly asserts that when the rhythm of a poem is slow, it means that the thought expressed in that verse is profound and, in most cases, evokes an emotion of sorrow. This assertion is confirmed in the above stanza, where the poet mirrors the disadvantage of not having a male child in Igbo culture, as in other African cultures. The thought expressed in the above stanza (poem 61) is so deep that it not only evokes the emotion of sorrow but also of pity. The breath-pause is normal, and the lines are of average length. The tempo of the stanza is neither fast nor slow. Another example of a poem that has a normal breath-pause is ‘There’ (Shame) written by C.C. Anozie in *Uche Bu Akpa* (2005:75) (poem 62), first stanza, where the poet says:

Ana m adi n’egedege ihu//	(I am situated at a forehead
Ana m eburu onye m ji ụzọ//	I go before my victim
Onye ahụ na-esoghari m n’azu//	The person follows behind me
Ukwu onye m ji esighi ike n’ala//	The legs of my victim are not firm on the ground
Ọnụ na-ete ya ririri/	His mouth palpitates/quivers
Aka na-ama ya jijiji/...	His hand trembles jijiji)
(Anozie, 2005, p. 75)	

The issue discussed in the stanza above of poem 62 is not particularly deep. It is a didactic stanza that focuses on the need to avoid any act that could bring us shame and reproach. The tempo of the above stanza is neither fast nor slow, and the lines are of average length. Another instance of regular recurrence of breath-pause, which is occasioned by slow tempo rhythm, is the poem, ‘Ihe a dikwaghi ebe o na-adi’ (Things

fall apart), which is written by Romanus Ezeuko in *Akọnuche* (2006:220), first stanza of poem 63:

Mgbe ụwa tọrọ ute ihe dum na-eri igburu//
Mgbe ndị mmadụ ji ụkwụ aga Onitsha//
Mgbe ndị mmadụ ji ahụhụ enwe ańurị//
Mgbe ndị mmadụ dọgara osisi ezumike n'ụzọ//
Mgbe ee bụ ee, mba buru mba/

(Ezeuko in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 220)

(When the world is pleasurable, everything eats *igburu*
When people travelled to Onitsha on foot
When people rejoiced in suffering
When people dropped the stick of relaxation
When yes was yes, no was no)

A first glance at this stanza reveals the role of the regular recurrence of the breath-pause as a rhythmic factor in Igbo poetry. While reading this stanza (poem 63) and the succeeding stanza (stanza two of the poem), the reader cannot help but notice that the rhythm is neither fast nor slow; in other words, the lines are of average length, which delimits normal breath-pause. Again, the poet's creativity here plays out in the way normal words are defamiliarised to create new images in the minds of readers, who are forced to read the verse more than once to understand the point the poet is making. The role of defamiliarisation here makes the verse striking and draws readers' attention to it, encouraging them to read it more than once. The stanza focuses on the changes that have occurred in society due to the influence of Western civilisation. Due to the seriousness of the issue discussed, the breath-pause is normal—this means that the tempo of the stanza is neither too fast nor too slow, and the lines therein are also of average length. The stanza evokes an emotion of disgust.

On the other hand, when the lines of poetry are short, the breath pause will be short, which implies that the rhythm will be fast. To buttress this point, let us consider an example from a poem written by Madubike in *Utara Ntị* (n.d, p. 41), the fifth and

sixth stanzas of the poem, which he titled “Nwayọọ bụ Ije” (Take Life Easy) (poem 64)

Anyà ukwu bụ ohī/	(Envy is thievery
Anyà ukwu bütèrè asìrì/	Envy ignites gossip
Anyà ukwu bụ ekwòrò ya nà iwe obi/	Envy is jealousy and anger
Anyà ukwu bụ ìkpō asi/	Envy is hatred

Mà ñdìdì nyìrì ùwà/	But patience is ideal in the world.
Ñdìdì bụ ìmmiri ndù/	Patience is water of life
Ñdìdì bụ ọmìkō/	Patience is compassion
Ñdìdì bụ mgbaghara/	Patience is forgiveness.
Ọkwa ya bụ ọkàchà mmā/	It is the best ...)

(Madubuike in Emenanjo (ed), N.d., p. 41)

In the above stanzas (poem 64), it will be observed that, unlike the case of regular rhythm, the lines are short, which makes the production of this line fast and, in turn, amounts to fast rhythm. That is why they have been marked with a single stroke as suggested by Uzochukwu (2001). The stanzas are didactic and focus on the disadvantages of impatience as seen in stanza 1 of poem 64, and the gains of patience as depicted in the second stanza (poem 64). The fast rhythm evokes a sense of awe. Again, from the above excerpt, a reader can also clearly see the role of parallelism in promoting rhythm in written Igbo poetry in lines 1-4 of the first stanza and lines 2-4 of the second stanza. Another example of a poem where the short breath-pause delimits short lines is another poem written by A.B. Chukuezi, titled “Mmadu Bụ Nnu” (Man is salt), in *Akọ bụ Ndu* (Poem 65), where the poet writes:

Anyị kpọkuo nna anyị ha/	(We call on our forefathers
Ha aza/	They answer
A kpọkuo ndị dị ndụ/	When we call on the living
Ha aju/	They refuse
A na-asụ nri/	When pounding food
Nkịta na-ete/	The dog dances
Ụwa dị ka ahịhịa Chukwu/	The world is like God’s grass
Na-anaghị agwu agwu/	That does not finish
Ka ọkụ dabara na mmiri/	As a fire that falls inside water
Na-anaghị anyu anyu/	That does not quench
Ka osisi akpu/	Like cassava stick
I bere ya ọdu/	When you cut its tail

O puo/	It grows
I bere ya isi/	If you cut off its head
I bere ya isi na odu/	If you cut off its head and tail
O ga-epuriri/	It must grow
Mmadu bu nnu/...	Man is salt.)

(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 27)

It continues like this until the following six lines of the poem. Here (poem 65), one can readily observe the shortness of the lines, which makes the tempo of the poem quick, thereby evoking an emotion of surprise. This results from a short breath-pause that culminates in a fast rhythm. The issue discussed here, as we can see, is not too deep: it concerns the fragility of man, hence the quick tempo. Let us also draw another instance of fast rhythm from the first stanza of one of N. R. Ezejesi's poems "Eziokwu" (Truth) in *Abu Utu* (2015), where the poet writes (poem 66):

Eziokwu bu ndu/	(Truth is life
I dika oriona/	You are like a lantern
I na-ekwu okwu n'ohia/	You speak in the forest
Na-ese elu na mmiri/	Floots on the waters
Nkirinka ogodo ndi mmuo/	Tattered cloths of the spirits)

(Ezejesi, 2015, p. 11)

In the above stanza, one can see likewise that the lines are short, an indication of short breath-pause. Just like the preceding poem (poem 66), the tempo of the above stanza (poem 60) is also quick; therefore, the rhythm is fast.

6.1.2 The Regular Recurrence of Equal-Time Duration in Consecutive Lines

(Biambiakwa Nhata nha Oge n'Ahiri na-esote onwe Ha):

Uzochukwu (2001) describes this rhythmic feature as the most common Igbo poetic rhythm in oral Igbo poetry, but it is less common in written Igbo poetry. The reason for this is that the structure of oral Igbo poetry is not entirely the same as that of written Igbo poetry. For instance, in the structure of Igbo funeral songs, there can be chants with prompters, where the prompting could either be vocal or instrumental

(Uzochukwu 1981, 1982, and 2001). The rhythm of the lines is designed to rhyme with the beats, since the artist is face-to-face with his audience and, as such, the chant is accompanied by musical accompaniment. However, in written Igbo poetry, the poet is not face to face with his audience and as such the focus of written Igbo poetry is on the stylistic representation of thought. This is why regular recurrence of equal-time duration is not common in written Igbo poetry, as opposed to the oral form of Igbo poetry.

In written Igbo poetry, the regular recurrence of equal-time duration as a rhythmic factor arises from the fact that consecutive lines may or may not contain the same number of syllables, yet rhythm will be achieved. Provided that those consecutive lines have the same number of beats, which is an indicator that the lines have equal-time duration in the way they are produced when they are read. That is to say that equality of time duration is predicated on the number of beats in each line, regardless of the number of syllables in them, as exemplified in A. B. Chukuezi's poem "Chukwu ndị Isi Ojii" (God of the Blacks) (Poem 67), lines 12-14. Let us consider a more practical instance of regular recurrence of equal time duration in consecutive lines as a rhythmic factor in Written Igbo poetry, but, in this case, promoted by immediate repetition. In the last stanza of Madubuike's poem "Abụ" (poetry) in *Utara Ntị* (N.d., pp. 43-44) (Poem 68), the poet writes:

Edebeghị m abụ ahụ	(I have not written it
Abu ahụ ga-edogharị ụwa	The poem that will transform the world
A GA-EDE YA	IT WILL BE WRITTEN
A GA-EDE YA	IT WILL BE WRITTEN
A GA-EDE YA	IT WILL BE WRITTEN
N'ihì ntugharị ga-adiriri	Because there must be a change)
(Madubuike in Emenanjo (ed.), N.d., p. 44)	

In the stanza above from poem 68, lines 3-5 are foregrounded, so they are written in uppercase. The lines also repeated to draw the attention of the reader, both

to the seriousness of the poet's desire and to its rhythmic ambiance. The rhythmic factor enhanced here by repetition is the regular recurrence of equal-time duration, which is evident in lines 3-5, as shown below:

	No. of Sylls.	No. of Beats (when read)
A GA-EDE YA	5	5
A GA-EDE YA	5	5
A GA-EDE YA	5	5

Because the above rhythmic factor is promoted by immediate repetition, there is correspondence between the number of syllables and the number of beats. In immediate repetition, the repeated lines (utterances) follow one another consecutively (Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 110).

To further illustrate the rhythmic feature of regular recurrence of equal-time duration in written Igbo poetry, let us also consider a poem written by Iwu Ikwubuzo, which is titled "Ụbọchị dike lara" (The day the hero passed on) in *Omenkà* (1992, p. 16) (poem 69), second verse.

	No. of Sylls.	No. of Beats (when read)
Ụbọchị dike lara	7	7
Ụda egbe ebe a	7	7
Ụda egbe ebe nii	8	7
Ụzụ akwa ebe a	7	7
Ụzụ akwa ebe nii ...	8	7

(Ikwubuzo et al., 1992, p. 16)

(The day the hero passed on
The sound of a gun, here
The sound of a gun, there
Loud cries, here
Loud cries, there ...)

In the above stanza, there is no correspondence between the number of syllables. However, there is correspondence between the number of beats in each of the consecutive utterances, which is again made possible through the device of syllable lengthening. As earlier explained, syllable lengthening is a feature of oral

poetry, but it is seen in “ebe nii”, which is a dialectal word for ‘there’. It is also clear from the above poem 63 that equality of time duration as a rhythmic feature is reflected in the same poem in the equality of the beats. Just as Uzochukwu (1982, p. 40) explains,

To achieve the equality of time duration, an important device employed is overlapping... Other devices employed to accommodate the rhythm are syllable lengthening and elision. At times, the number of syllables corresponds to the number of beats, but whenever there is syllable lengthening, elision, or overlapping, there will be no correspondence in number.

Although these features are more prominent in oral Igbo poetry, they can be occasionally noticed in written Igbo poetry when the poets intend to achieve rhythmic effect. In the above poem 69, by lengthening the last syllable, /i/, in lines 3 and 5, the syllable assumes one sound which amounts to a single beat. This gives the verse a rhythmic ambiance, thereby achieving equal-time duration that is not tied to the number of syllable but to the beat produced in the stanza and, in turn, making the poem aesthetically pleasing. Also, one can see the role parallelism played in promoting this rhythmic factor in the poem (69). The partial repetition of the phrases ‘uda egbe’ (line 2-3) and ‘uzu akwa’ (lines 4-5) draws the attention of the reader to the rhythmic composition in the above verse. This agrees with the view of Uba-Mgbemena (1990, p. XI) and Anozie (2007, p. 11) who both see parallelism as one of the features that promote poetic rhythm in written Igbo poetry.

Let us draw another instance of the role of parallelism in enhancing regular recurrence of equal-time duration as rhythmic feature in written Igbo poetry. Consider this excerpt from “Ura” (Sleep), a poem written by I.U. Nwadike in *Akọnauche* (2006) (Poem 70) second stanza:

	No. of Sylls.	No. of Beats (when read)
Ọ bù ị nà-ekposà.	7	7
Ọ bù ị nà-adọsà.	7	7
Ọ bù ị nà-etisà	7	7
Ọ bù ị nà-etipịà	7	7
Ọ bù ị nà-akupịà...	7	7

(Nwadike in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 227)

(You are the one who scatters
 You are the one who separates
 You are the one who puts asunder
 You are the one who smashes
 You are the one who breaks ...)

In the above poem 64, the beauty of the regular recurrence of equal-time durations as a rhythmic feature in written Igbo poetry is better appreciated in the way this verse draws attention to itself through the sequential arrangement of the lines. In the above excerpt, the number of syllables coincides with the number of beats, therefore producing a rhythm that is achieved by equal-time duration.

Again, the poet could be said to be immersed in Igbo because of his mastery of the language, which he displays in the language play at work in the above excerpt. Since *ura* (sleep) is a natural phenomenon that is general to everyone, and as such, its function in human life is a common one. In order to create art from what everyone is familiar with, the poet foregrounds the effects of sleep, as a natural phenomenon on humans, by organising them sequentially, thereby drawing more attention to the phenomenon in the lines. By defamiliarising the impacts of sleep, the poet creates a deviation that sets up patterns in the sound and syntax of poetic language, giving rise to rhythm. In discussing this aspect of defamiliarisation, Abrams & Harpham (2012, p. 139) assert that such patterns in the sound and syntax of poetic language include those in grammatical construction, speech, rhythm, rhyme, and stanza forms. They

further state that these lead to the setting up of images, which is the primary concern of defamiliarisation.

6.1.3 The Regular Recurrence of Sense-Balance (Bjambjakwa Echiche namaju Ibe Ya):

This rhythmic feature is very prominent in written Igbo poetry, as it appears to drive the sense in most Igbo poems. This rhythmic feature is appreciated when we recall that Igbo poetry is written in lines and, in most cases, the sense of a preceding line is completed or balanced in the next line or lines that follow it. Uzochukwu (1982; 2001; 2012) explains this rhythmic feature by stating that, in Igbo poetry, we may have two parallel utterances (lines) which have no identical syntactic structure, no equal beats and definitely do not have the same time duration, balancing each other in a logical sequence, therefore producing a type of semantic rhythm that is not tied to the structure but to the sense the lines project. Uzochukwu (1982) further explains that in this type of rhythm, an action may be sense-balanced by its significance, or even an offence may be sense-balanced by its punishment. Since this rhythmic feature is not tied to the structure of the lines, as the previous two rhythms discussed earlier are, it allows room for variety and for the poet to improvise (Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 85). However, this improvisation must not be haphazard but follow a logical sequence. There must be a sense group, which coincides with a rhythmic unit, and these rhythmic units must be made up of two or more rhythmic segments (Babalola, 1966, p. 346, cited in Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 85). Let us consider the following excerpt from the fifth and sixth stanzas of Tony Ubesie's poem 'Ngwere' (Lizard) in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 13-14) where the poet writes (Poem 71),

Ụkà a kpara akpa
Isi ka e ji ekwe

(An earlier discussion
Is confirmed

Ngwere achoghi okwu	The lizard does not look for trouble
Nke o ji achọ ụka	Nor does he look for strife
Onye na-achoghi ya	Whoever that does not want his trouble
Ọ hapu ya n'udo	He leaves him in peace
Onye kpata nku ahuhu	Whoever fetches ant-infested firewood
Ngwere abiakwute ya uri	Receives the lizard as his guest
Okokporo biri	Where the bachelor lives
Ngwere abia bidewe ya	The lizard comes and lives next to him
Ọ zoọ ukwu n'ala	If he steps on the floor
Ngwere emee n'elu ulo	The lizard moves on the roof
Ọ hapu ulo puwa	When he leaves the house
Ngwere a na-echere ya ulo	The lizard guards his house
Okokporo bi n'ulo	A bachelor that lives in a house
Na-ama okpara ngwere,	Knows the first son of the lizard
(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 14)	

The beauty of regular recurrence of sense-balance as a rhythmic factor in written Igbo poetry is better appreciated by reading the above lines. In the above stanzas, we can see a semantic balance of thought in every other line of the poem as it begins with “Uka a kpara akpa”. Uzochukwu (2001) refers to this type of balancing of thought as semantic parallelism, which contrasts with syntactic parallelism. In semantic parallelism, the sense balance occurs in lines (utterances) that repeat the same idea and, by so doing, produce a rhythm that is tied to the sense (instead of the structure as in the case of syntactic parallelism).

There are four rhythmic segments in each of the two stanzas above (poem 71). In the first stanza, for instance, each of the rhythmic segments has two rhythmic units. The first rhythmic segment comprises lines 1 and 2, which constitute two units; the second, lines 3 and 4, another two rhythmic units; the third comprises lines 5 and 6; and the fourth rhythmic segment comprises lines 7 and 8, each with two units. The sense in each of the rhythmic units (lines) in a segment is sense-balanced by the other unit in a logical sequence. That is to say, a preceding line in a rhythmic segment is sense-balanced by the succeeding line, as seen in the first stanza above. In the first rhythmic segment, unit 1 (line 1), the action is balanced by unit 2 (line 2), which is the

result of the action in unit 1. In the second rhythmic segment, unit 1 (line 3), which is the nature of the subject discussed, is sense-balanced by the consequence of the subject's nature in unit 2 (line 4). Furthermore, in the third rhythmic segment, the thought in unit 1 (line 5) is balanced in unit 2 (line 6) with the reaction; while the action in the fourth rhythmic segment, unit 1 (line 7), is balanced by the consequence of such action in unit 2 (line 8).

In the same vein, there are four rhythmic segments in the second stanza, also (which is the sixth stanza of the poem (65)), and each of the segments has two rhythmic units. In the second stanza above, the result of the action in unit 1 of the first rhythmic segment is felt in unit 2 of the same segment. In the second rhythmic segment, the action of the bachelor's life in unit 1 is balanced by the reaction of the subject of the poem in unit 2. Also, in the third rhythmic segment, the first unit (line 5) is balanced by the reaction in unit 2 (line 6). In the fourth rhythmic segment, the action in unit 1 (line 7) is also balanced in unit 2 of the same rhythmic segment (line 8). Let us use a graphic analogy to explain this analysis further.

The graphic representation of the logical sequence of thought in the second stanza is shown below:

From the above analogy, the regular recurrence of sense balance as a rhythmic feature in written Igbo poetry is obvious. Consider another example from the first stanza of a poem written in the second decade by A.B. Chukuezi titled “Akwa Nwunye Di M” in *Akọ Bu Ndu* (1988, p. 79) (Poem 72) where the poet writes:

Ndị kwụ ọtọ	(Those standing
Ha kwurū ọfuma	They should stand well
Ndị nọ ala	Those seated
Ha nọdu ọfuma	They should sit properly

Ndị na-anya anwụ	Those that are sun-bathing
Naranụ m ekele	Receive my greeting
Unu ndị ichie	You chiefs
Si ebe dị iche iche	From different places
Ekele dịrị unu	Greetings to you
Etu unu si	How you
Tunyere anyị ugwu ụbọchị taa	Honoured us today)

(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 79)

The graphic representation of the logical sequence of thought in the stanza is shown below:

Here, there are five rhythmic segments, and each has two rhythmic units, except the fourth, which has three rhythmic units (three lines). The first rhythmic segment is units (lines) 1 and 2; the second is units 1 and 2 (lines 3-4); the third is

units 1 and 2 (lines 5-6); the fourth is units 1, 2 and 3 (lines 7-9); while the fifth segment is units 1 and 2 (lines 10-11). Each of these units is sense-balanced by the succeeding unit in a logical sequence. For instance, the subject identified in line 1, “Ndi kwu otu”, is balanced by the speaker’s desire or expectation in line 2, “ha kwuru ofuma”. Again, the subject identified by the speaker in line 3, “Ndi no ala”, is sense-balanced by the speaker’s desire (expectation) in line 4, “Ha nodu ofuma”. The subject, again identified by the speaker in line 5, “Ndi na-anya anwu”, is balanced in sense by the speaker’s desire in line 6, “Naranu m ekele”. The thought on the group identified by the speaker in line 7, “unu ndi ichie” and their location in line 8, “si ebe di ichie ichie”, is sense-balanced by the desire of the speaker in line 9, “Ekele diri unu”. The earlier action identified by the speaker in line 7 is acknowledged again in line 10, and balanced by the action they performed for the speaker in line 11.

Being a type of rhythm that is most frequent in written Igbo poetry, as earlier mentioned, there is a need for further illustration of the incidence of regular recurrence of sense balance as a rhythmic feature in written Igbo poetry. In another excerpt from a poem “Chineke bi n’Igwe” (God in Heaven) by Nkechinyere Okediadi in *Ije Uwa* (Poem 73) we have:

Obinigwe!	(Obinigwe!
Eluigwe ebe obibi gi	Heaven your dwelling place
Uwa ebe mgbakwasa ukwu	Earth your footstool
Onye okike!	The Creator!
I kere ihe niile naani gi,	You created everything alone,
I nyere anyi ha dum	You gave it all to us
Na-anaghi ego.	Without collecting money
I bu ome mma!	You are an altruist!
Nwoke obodobo anya!	The man with huge eyes!
Anyanwa eru uwa niile	Eyes that oversee the whole world!
Onye oma! Mere gawa...	Good person! Keep on doing...
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 32)	

Here is a graphic representation of the logical sequence of thought (sense balance) as it appears in the above stanza below:

In the above stanza from poem 73, there are three rhythmic segments. The first rhythmic segment is made up of the first three lines (unit 1-3); the second rhythmic segment starts from lines 4-7, while the third rhythmic segment starts from lines 8-11. The first unit (line 1), in the first rhythmic segment, talks about the phenomenon (God) that the poet is addressing in the poem, which is sense-balanced by the description of the home of the said phenomenon (heaven and earth) in lines 2-3 (units 2 and 3). Similarly, in the first unit of the second rhythmic segment (line 4), the poet again refers to the Phenomenon, which is the subject in the poem, by calling him out and then balancing the sense in the succeeding unit (lines 5-7) with the functions performed by the phenomenon being acknowledged. In the third rhythmic segment, the poet continues with praises for the phenomenon being addressed as in lines 1 & 4, but, in this case, the poet first describes the attributes of the phenomenon, and then balances the thought with a combination of another attribute and function of the phenomenon in a poetic style line in 11.

To further illustrate our discussion on the regular recurrence of sense balance as a rhythmic feature in written Igbo poetry, let us consider yet another example from the first stanza of a poem “Udara” (Cherry) written by Ezejesi in *Abu Uto* (2015, pp. 30-31) (Poem 74), where the poet writes:

Udara bu osisi di nsọ	(Cherry is a sacred tree
Ebe di ọcha na nsọ ka ọ na-epu	It grows in sacred and neat places
Udara bu mmadu dika osisi	Cherry is a human-like tree
Ndi mmuo ru ru ulo ukwu ya	The spirits built their temple.
(Ezejesi, 2015, p. 30)	

There are two rhythmic segments in the above stanza (poem 74). Each rhythmic segment has two rhythmic units. The first rhythmic segment comprises lines (units) 1 and 2, while the second segment comprises lines 3-4 (units 1 and 2). Each thought in a unit is balanced in the succeeding unit. The action (the subject) in line 1, for instance, is sense-balanced in line 2, with the residence of the subject. The metaphoric comparison of the subject of discourse, “Udara”, with a living being in line 3, is balanced by the reason the tree is considered sacred by the Igbo in line 4.

Based on the foregoing, it is clear that rhythm is one of the most important features of written Igbo poetry, enhancing the poetic quality of the literary texts. Again, it is clear with the copious instances from written Igbo poetry across the four decades of its existence in focus, that, Igbo poetic rhythm is not achieved by meter as suggested by Ugonna (1982; 1984) and Obike (n.d) but by the three basic features (regular recurrence of breath pause, regular recurrence of equal time duration and regular recurrence of sense balance) as suggested by Uzochukwu (1982; 1987; 1992; 2001; 2002) and supported by Uba-Mgbemena (1990) and Anozie (2007).

6.2 Use of Language in Written Igbo Poetry and the Process of Defamiliarisation

Language use is the next important feature of written Igbo poetry (See Uzochukwu, 1981, 2001, and 2012; Uba-Mgbemena, 1990). It is a feature that brings out the aesthetics of any poetic work (Anozie, 2007, p. 11). When the term ‘poetry’ is mentioned, the first thing that strikes the mind is the art of making through the use of language. This is why formalists believe that what is important in poetry is not really what is said in the poem, but how it is said (the language used). Therefore, the idea of language in this study does not refer to the ordinary or day-to-day use of language, known in the formalist school as the literal use of language, but to the creative use of language, which implies a deviation from the literal use of language. As stated earlier in the introductory section of this study, it is by deviating from day-to-day use of language, through the process of defamiliarisation, that language is used to create art. When poets deviate from the literal use of language, they produce literary or figurative language. This is why, in talking about the language of poetry, most Igbo literary scholars refer to it as ‘Asụsụ Nkà’ (artistic language). This literary language forces users of the language to see the language they are already familiar with in a new light (estrangement).

It is important to understand what figurative language means to understand the role it plays as a key tool for defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry. Let us consider the view of Abrams & Harpham (2012, p. 130), which this study believes aligns with the Formalist school of language in poetry. Abrams & Harpham (2012, p. 130) explain that

Figurative language is a conspicuous departure from what competent users of a language apprehend as the standard meaning of words, or else the standard order of words, in order to achieve some special meaning or

effect. Figures are sometimes described as primarily poetic, but they are integral to the functioning of language and indispensable to all modes of discourse.

From the above assertion, it is obvious why language is significant for ascertaining the form of written Igbo poetry. Just like rhythm, no verse can be considered poetic without its language (figurative use of language). Again, without language, poetry cannot be considered an art. Emenanjo (1983, p. 9) opines that when examining the language of poetry, the analyst must consider ways in which the figurative use of language in the poem projects the thought and topic of the poet. Uba-Mgbemena (1990, p. x) agrees with Emenanjo (1983), by asserting that what brings out the thought and also promotes the aesthetic quality of any Igbo poem is the language of the artist or poet. Uba-Mgbemena (1990) further states that the language of Igbo poetry is always firm, filled with imagery, and beautified with proverbs. This is in concordance with the view of Shklovsky (1965), who opines that by defamiliarising the everyday language, poetry becomes a way of thinking in images. Furthermore, Anozie (2007, p. 11) summarises both the thoughts of Emenanjo (1983) and Uba-Mgbemena (1990) by stating that:

Asụsụ abụ tosiri ịka aka iji welite abụ ahụ elu, mee ka abụ ahụ kaa aka ma nye ezi echiche dī elu. Asụsụ ndī ahụ tosiri ịnwe ilu, asịnilu, ụkabūilu, mburū, myiri, egbeokwu, dgz. Asụsụ abụ na-eme ka abụ tọọ uto na ntị ma mee ka e chebaa echiche ime tupu a ghotā abụ.

(The language of poetry is supposed to be firm in order to promote the poem and elevate thought. Such language is supposed to be embellished with proverbs, witticism, anecdotes, metaphors, similes, hyperbole, etc. The language of poetry makes the poem pleasing to the ear and also makes one think deeply before understanding the poem.)

The language spoken of here is a language that is meticulously chosen to serve a particular purpose (Uba-Mgbemena, 1990). This is why Gillespie, Fobseca, and

Sanger (1996, p. 989) opine that poets, in a bid to appeal to the readers' imagination while they read their works, do not only use language that literally communicates images but also make use of figurative language that describes emotions and compares images. In this section, however, our focus is to identify various artistic skills employed by modern Igbo poets to defamiliarise language in written Igbo poetry.

Uzochukwu (2012) identifies four ways in which language is used in Igbo poetry, and they include conformity to the norm of the language (*ndagba asụsụ*), deviation from the norm in the language (*ndacha asụsụ*), and use of figures of speech and sound devices. In a like manner, our investigation in the present study confirms Uzochukwu's position by showing that modern Igbo poets defamiliarise language in written Igbo poetry through what we have termed (i) stylistic conformity, (ii) stylistic deviation, (iii) figures of speech, and (iv) sound devices. Let us examine selected Igbo poems to see how modern Igbo poets defamiliarise language through their artistic skills, as manifested in these stylistic devices. The excerpts selected for this section are representative of the four decades in focus.

6.2.1 Stylistic Conformity as Defamiliarisation Techniques in Written Igbo Poetry (*Ndagba Asụsụ n'Abụ Ederede Igbo*)

Stylistic conformity refers to a situation where the poets do not create new words in the language but conform to the existing norm (Uzochukwu, 2012, p. 8). The creative prowess of a poet does not only manifest in creating new communicative possibilities that were formerly inexistent in a language, but can also be seen in how the poet utilises the existing possibilities in the language. However, the poet is at liberty to manipulate the existing norm in a language in such a way that it will give

fresh thought to the reader. It is the devices employed by the Igbo poet to manipulate the norm in the language, giving a fresh thought that the present study refers to as defamiliarisation techniques. Some of the techniques employed by Igbo poets to achieve stylistic conformity in written Igbo poetry, as suggested by Uzoichukwu (2012) and adopted in this study at various levels, include phonological cohesion, lexical cohesion, and grammatical cohesion. Let us look at them one after the other.

6.2.1.1 Phonological Cohesion (Ndagba Fonoloji)

Phonological cohesion in poetry investigates how words are vocalised, the sound patterns, the incidence of alliteration, assonance, rhyme scheme, and consonance (Mohamed, 2019, p. 160). In Igbo written poetry, phonological cohesion manifests as alliteration, assonance, and tonal rhyme (Uzoichukwu, 2012, p. 8). These features, along with other linguistic ones, differentiate poetry from day-to-day discourse (Nofal, 2011). Let us examine how modern Igbo poets conform to the norms of the language by using these phonological features in their poems.

6.2.1.1.1 Alliteration and Assonance (Bjambja Mgbochiume na Bjambja Udaume)

Alliteration as an artistic device is the repetition of identical consonant speech sounds in sequence of syllables or words (Connel, 1913). Assonance, on the other hand, is the repetition of identical vowel sounds, also in sequence of close words (Abrams and Hartpham, 2012: pp. 10-11). Both assonance and alliteration contribute to the melodic effect of written Igbo poetry. Connel (1913) asserts that alliteration is not supposed to distract the attention of the reader from the matter discussed in the poem. Alliteration and assonance, in written Igbo poetry, are promoted by repetition

or parallelism in consecutive lines. Modern Igbo poets employ alliteration and assonance in their bid to make their poems aesthetically melodic, as seen in the following stanza from J.C. Maduekwe’s poem, “Onyinye Chukwu” (God’s Blessing) (Poem 75) in *Nkà Okwu* (1979, pp. 9-10), where the poet writes:

Ya bugara aka ebe o hudara, rụta ihe oriri
 Ya bugara ọnụ ebe o kwukwere kwute akụ na ụba
 Ya bugara anya ka o kirie ihe gūrū ahụ
 (Maduekwe, 1979, p. 9)

(It drove the hand to a place where it bent and got food
 It drives the mouth to a place where it talks to get riches,
 It drives the eyes to watch the things that satisfy it.)

In the above stanza from Maduekwe’s poem (poem 75), there is an element of parallelism where alliteration is noticed in the way the following consonant sounds are repeated in a sequence: y, b, g, r, and k. There is also assonance in the manner these vowel sounds are repeated in a sequence: a, ụ, a, e, and ọ. As can be seen in the lines above, the alliteration is mixed with assonance, which produces a sound effect.

For a better illustration of the role of alliteration and assonance in promoting the melodic aesthetics of written Igbo poems, let us consider the fifth stanza of another poem, “Onye nọchiri anyị ụzọ?” (Who stands in our way) (poem 76), written by A.B. Chukuezi in *Akọ Bụ Ndu* (1988), where the poet writes:

Anyị na-egbu cham cham	(We kill <i>cham cham</i>
Anyị na-agba dum dum	We shoot <i>dum dum</i>
Anyị na-egbu na mbara ala	We kill in the open ground
Anyị na-egbu na mmiri	We kill in the water)
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 71)	

In the above stanza of Chukuezi’s poem, assonance is combined with alliteration. There is assonance in the way these vowel sounds follow in a sequence: a, i, e, and u. There is also alliteration in the way these consonant sounds follow each other: ny, n, gb, and m. The organisation of these sounds to achieve alliteration and

assonance gives a melodic effect to the poem, thereby attracting or luring the reader to pause and reread it.

So far, we have seen that in written Igbo poetry, the basic feature that promotes alliteration and assonance can be parallelism. To further confirm this claim, let us consider another poem, “Ekwentị” (Telephone) (Poem 77), which C.C. Anozie writes in *Uche bu Akpa* (2005, p. 68), where the poet says:

Ụdị m buru ibu	(I am of many brands
Enwere m nke ndị Mtel	I have the one for Mtel
Enwere m nke ndị Celtel	I have the one for Celtel
Enwere m nke ndị MTN	I have the one for MTN
Enwere m nke ndị GLO	I have the one for GLO

(Anozie, 2005, p. 68)

In the above stanza (poem 77), the role of parallelism in promoting alliteration and assonance becomes more apparent. There is assonance in the way the vowel sound ‘e’ is repeated in a sequence. There is also alliteration in the manner these consonant sounds are repeated in a sequence: nw, r, m, n, k, and d. There is no doubt that the incidence of assonance and alliteration in the above stanza has promoted a melodic effect in the above poem. The use of this artistic device (assonance and alliteration) does not, in any way, distract the attention of the reader from the matter discussed in the poem, which focuses on the types of telecommunication providers in Nigeria. Those phonological features added melodic flavour to the poem, in a way of colouring the sound. Let us consider another excerpt from the fifth stanza of a poem, “Eze kwe m” (Poem 78), written by Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe in *Uche Bu Ahia* (2009, p. 5).

...Ma onye ọma	(Both the good
Ma onye ojọọ	And the bad
Ma onye ukwu	Both the great
Ma onye nta	And the bad)

(Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, 2009, p. 5)

In the above excerpt from poem 78, there is alliteration in the way these consonant sounds are placed in a sequence: /m/ and /ny/. On the other hand, there is assonance in the arrangement of these vowel sounds: a, o, and e. Having discussed the first manifestation of phonological cohesion in written Igbo poetry, let us look at the second aspect, which is tonal rhyme.

6.2.1.1.2 Tonal Rhyme (Ndakorita Udaolu)

There are not many cases of syllabic rhyme in Igbo poetry (Uzochukwu, 2012, p. 8), but there are a few instances of tonal rhyme. It is also important to add that tonal rhyme is not common in written Igbo poetry. Tonal rhyme here refers to a few lines that end with the same tone. Let us instantiate this point with the second stanza of a poem, “Abali di egwu” (Terror of the Night) (Poem 79), written by E. Egbuchulam in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 46-48), where the poet writes:

Igwe ọcha na-alamikwā	(The bright sky goes inside
Igwe ojii aputakwā	The dark sky comes out
Ihe ga-eje n'usọ nke yā	Light will go to its own corner
Ọchịchị ga-anọchi yā	Darkness will replace it)
(Egbuchulam in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 47)	

In the stanza above from poem 79, all the lines share the same tonal end rhyme. They all end with the same down-step tone. By making the lines end with the same tone, the poet makes the stanza aesthetically pleasing to read. This shows that tonal rhyme is another artistic skill used by modern Igbo poets to create art from the literal use of the Igbo language. The poet does not make new words here; instead, he defamiliarises the literal language by manipulating the original possibilities in the language to give the reader a fresh feeling of the language in the way it was arranged. Let us consider another example of tonal rhyme, also in *Akpa Uche*, by looking at the

second stanza of a poem “Ngwere” (Lizard) (Poem 80) written by T. Ubesie, where the poet says:

Mmadu daa nkwū	(A person who falls from the palm tree
A na-ele ya anya onwū	People expect him to die
Ma ngwere daa elū	But when the lizard falls
O bilie tikapu osō	It rises and runs
Onye dara elū	Who falls
Bu onye rituru ngwā	Is the person who descends quickly
Mmadu ajāghī yā	If it is not praised
Ngwere ajāa onwe yā	The lizard praises itself)

(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 13)

Here (Poem 80), we can see that all the lines end with the same tone, indicating the same tonal rhyme. A look at the lines shows the important role tonal rhyme plays in promoting the aesthetic quality of written Igbo poems. Another example of tonal rhyme in written Igbo poetry is evident in the fifth stanza of another poem written by C.C. Anozie, titled “Ura” (Sleep), (Poem 81) in *Uche Bu Akpa* (2005, pp. 72-73), where the poet writes:

Mmadu abuo meriri urā	(Two people defeated sleep
Ndi dinta meriri urā	The hunters defeated sleep
Oru ha napuru ha urā	Their work denied them sleep
Warim, kpatum, o bu anu?	<i>Warim, kpatum, is it meat?</i>)

(Anozie, 2005, p. 73)

Here, all the lines end with the same tonal rhyme. They all end on a high note. A reader who reaches the stanza above will appreciate the poet's skill in introducing a melodic effect and giving the reader a refreshing sense of melody. Another instance of tonal rhyme that makes readers appreciate the skills of modern Igbo poets is found in the poem “Mmuta bu ike” (Knowledge is power) (Poem 82), written by O. Njelita, in *Akponauche* (p. 129). There, the poet says:

Ike agwula gi	(Do not be weary
Otutu ka chi ha tiere aki	Many have their palm kernels broken for them
	by their benevolent god.
Ma onye ga-enwe mmeri echī	But whoever will have victory tomorrow
Bu onye tukwasiri obi na Chi	Is who puts his trust in God)

(Njelita in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 129)

In the above stanza (poem 82), all the lines end with the same tone, a case of tonal end rhyme. They all end with a down-step tone, thereby making the stanza melodic. From the foregoing, we can see the role of phonological cohesion as a stylistic device in defamiliarisation. We shall then look at lexical cohesion as a process of defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry.

6.2.1.2 Lexical Cohesion (Ndagba Okwu)

Lexical cohesion in texts focuses on the relationships between lexical items and their organisation within discourse to sustain continuity of thought (Halliday & Hasan, 1976). The whole concept of lexical cohesion is anchored on lexical patterning. Halliday and Hasan (1976) opine that, through careful selection of vocabulary, lexical cohesion is achieved in texts. The key concept in lexical cohesion is reiteration (Halliday & Hasan, 1976; Gonzalez, 2015). Gonzalez (2015) explains that reiteration arises when lexical items are semantically related to those that come before them through four strategies: repetition, superordinate, synonyms, and general word. In the English language, repetition is considered to be the most direct form of lexical cohesion (Gonzalez, 2015, p. 4). In written Igbo poetry, superordinate is found to be the most direct form of lexical cohesion employed by modern Igbo poets. Therefore, when discussing lexical cohesion in written Igbo poetry, two factors are considered: lexical matching and the chronological arrangement of hyponyms (Uzochukwu, 2012).

Uzochukwu (2012) explains that lexical matching appears in Igbo poetry through the combination of two antonyms from different lexical sets. It is important to understand that in talking about lexical cohesion, the interest is always domiciled in the class of general nouns (Halliday & Hasan, 1976, p. 275). As such, lexical

matching relates to two lexical items that are semantically opposed to each other or are near synonyms. The poet is at liberty to choose the correct lexical item that better captures the thought he intends to project in his poem. In written Igbo poetry, poets are found to achieve lexical cohesion through the superordinate arrangement of antonymous lexical items in consecutive lines. This is done with a view to describing some structural reality of the Igbo cosmic hierarchy. For instance, in the poem “Onwụ” (Death) (Poem 83) by C. Ajaegbu in *Akpa Uche* (1975, p. 6), there is lexical matching in the fourth stanza where the poet writes:

Onwụ! I nwekwee ọmiko?	(Death, do you even have pity
Ị maghị onye <i>ukwu</i> ;	You do not know the great;
Ị maghị onye <i>nta</i> ;	You do not know the small;
Hei! Ị dị egwu	Hei! You are wonderful.)

(Ajaegbu in Ekechukwu (ed.) 1975, p. 6)

There is a superordinate arrangement of antonymous lexical items, *ukwu* (great) as against *nta* (small). This is no coincidence. The poet, as a member of the society, is simply describing the structural reality of the Igbo worldview, in which the great is acknowledged before the small, indicating a hierarchical situation in Igbo cosmology. In the poem, “Mgbe m bụ nwata nta” (When I was a little child) (Poem 84) by G. Onyekaonwu, in *Uche bụ Afa* (1989, pp. 31-32), the poet also upholds this understanding in his first stanza, when he writes:

Mgbe m bụ nwata nta	(When I was a little child
Anyị ka m ji ele uwa	I watched the world
M lee <i>elu</i> , m lee <i>ala</i>	I looked up, I looked down
A hụcha nke a	After seeing this
A hụkwa nke ọzọ	I saw the other)

(Onyekaonwu, 1989, p. 31)

There are two lexical items matched in line 3. On line 3, it is no coincidence that *elu* (up) comes before *ala* (down). In the Igbo worldview, *elu* (heavens, sky) is above *ala* (the earth). This is because many forces that are believed to control the affairs of the world are believed to be living in the sky: *Chi Ukwu* (great God),

Amadiḡha (god of thunder), *Anyanwu* (god of sun), *Onwa* (moon goddess), and other pure spirits. These forces are believed to be higher than those of other deities and gods who dwell on land and beneath the earth (see Ugonna, 1984; Nwala, 1985). In fact, Ugonna (1984, p. 16) states explicitly that “From the start, Igwe has been regarded as mightier than Ala, the earth deity. Thus, he is also called Igwekaala.” For this reason, in speech, the Igbo tend to place *elu* before *ala*.

In N. Okediadi’s poem “Echi” (Tomorrow), in *Ije Uwa* (2003, p. 23), there is lexical matching in the way the poet arranges some lexical items in the stanza. In the first nine lines of the poem (Poem 85), the poet writes:

Ọ bụ ngwugwu e kere eke	(It is a wrapped package
Onye toghete <i>mma</i>	Whoever unwraps to find good
Onye toghete <i>njọ</i>	Whoever unwraps to find bad
Ya na chi ya	He and his personal god
Echi di ime	Tomorrow is unpredictable
Onye ma ihe ọ ga-amụ	Who knows what it has in stock
Ọ ga-amụ <i>nwoke</i> ?	Will it give birth to a boy?
Ọ ga-amụ <i>nwaanyi</i> ?	Will it give birth to a girl?
Ọ dighị onye ma...	No one knows...

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 23)

In the above excerpt, poem 85, there is lexical matching between “*mma*” (good) and “*njọ*” (bad) in lines 2 and 3. There is also lexical matching between “*nwoke*” (male) in line 7 and “*nwaanyi*” (female) in line 8. As earlier explained, the matching of these words also follows the structural reality of the Igbo understanding of the cosmos, where good is believed to be superior to evil, as seen in lines 2 and 3. A male child is taken to be more desirable than a female child, as suggested by placing “*nwoke*” before “*nwaanyi*”. It is worth noting that this poet (Okediadi) is a female poet, yet her feminine orientation as a woman does not change the structure of Igbo belief in her poem, placing the girl child before the male child.

Let us draw another instance from the fifth stanza of a poem written in the fourth decade by N. R. Ezejesi in *Abụ Ụtọ* (2015, pp. 19-21) titled “Ekpere” (Prayer) (Poem 86) where the poet writes:

Aga m ekpe ekpere n’ <i>ututu</i>	(I will pray in the morning
Kpee n’ <i>ehihie</i>	Pray in the afternoon
Kpee na <i>mgbede</i>	Pray in the evening
Kpekwa na <i>ndeeri</i>	Pray also at midnight
Ka aha m dī n’akwukwọ nke ndu	For my name to be in the book of life
E nwere ekpere nchekwa	There are protective prayers
Ekpere e ji ebu ajọ mmuọ agha dīkwa	There is also a prayer to fight demons
A na-ekpekwa ekpere ngozi	People also pray for blessing
Ekpere oru esepukwaghi aka	Prayer without ceasing
Aga m ekpe ekpere mgbe niile	I will pray all the time
Maka o si anyi yoo na anyi ga-ayota	Because he told us to ask that we will receive
Nti ya echichi echi	His ear is not deaf
Inu ihe obula anyi rioro	To hear anything we ask)
(Ezejesi, 2015, pp. 20-21)	

There is lexical matching between “*ututu*” (morning) as seen in line 1, “*ehihie*” (afternoon) as seen in line 2, “*mgbede*” in line 3, and “*nderi*” (midnight) as seen in line 4. As seen in the stanza above, the lexical items that denote different times of the day (*ututu*, *ehihie*, *mgbede*, and *abali*) in poem 86 are arranged in a structural order, as in the other instances cited above. *Ututu* comes before *ehihie*, *mgbede* follows *ehihie*, while *nderi* rounds off the day. One can readily notice the chronological arrangement of these lexical items, which portrays the Igbo understanding of time.

Apart from antonymous lexical matching, Uzochukwu (2012) opines that another way lexical cohesion is noticed in Igbo poetry is through chronological arrangement of lexical items by their level of importance or hierarchy. What Uzochukwu (2012) refers to by this assertion is the reiteration strategies suggested earlier by Halliday & Hasan (1976), known as near synonyms that belong to the same

lexical set. For instance, in the first stanza of the poem “Ala Ezi” (poem 87), written by J. Onwuchekwa in *Akpaala Okwu* (1983, p. 22), the poet writes:

<i>Obasi</i> dī n’elu, ekele	(God in heaven, greetings)
<i>Ala Ezi</i> , i meela	Earth goddess, you have done well
<i>Nna m ochie</i> ha, oka unu	My forefathers, I salute you
Ihe oma mee, nke ojoo emela	Good things should happen, the bad should not happen.)

(Onwuchekwa, 1983. p. 22)

Here (poem 87), there is a hierarchical arrangement of lexical items that belong to the same lexical set and their place of abode. These are not new words, but the poet chose to arrange them in this manner and, by so doing, forces the reader’s attention to the import of these terms (lexical items). In the Igbo worldview, God lives in heaven and is believed to be higher than the earth goddess, who is considered one of God’s agents (Ugonna, 1984). This is why the poet makes God (*Obasi*) come before *Ala*. Again, the earth goddess (mother earth), which controls the earth, is believed to be superior to the *Nna ochie* (ancestors or forefathers), also known as *Ndi mbu na ndi egede*. This is why *Ala Ezi*, the Earth goddess, takes the second line before the forefathers (*Nna m ochie*), who are believed to dwell under the earth, in the third line. Based on the foregoing, it is now clear that the modern Igbo poets employ lexical matching to defamiliarise language in their art.

6.2.1.3 Grammatical Cohesion (Ndagba Ntqasusu)

Grammatical cohesion is one of the profound ways by which modern Igbo poets defamiliarise language in written Igbo poetry. Uzochnikwu (2012) explains that the concept of grammatical cohesion in Igbo poetry focuses on how poets break the rules of language or rearrange its structure in their poems. The role of the critic, who is examining grammatical cohesion in written Igbo poetry, is to discover the ways in which the poets break the rules of language in their poems. It is only by going outside

the norm of the language that Igbo poetry is defamiliarised in writing. It is important to note that the Igbo critic who hopes to embark on this literary journey must be someone who understands the norm of the language before they can recognise the defamiliarised form of language in works of art. When we say the norm, we refer to the code or rule that every grammatical structure in a language must follow before a sentence can be considered a well-formed sentence. In the Igbo language, for instance, a well-formed sentence should follow the Subject Verb Object (S.V.O.) structure. For instance:

Obi	siri	Nri
(Obi	cooked	Food)
S	V	O

The subject in this example is ‘Obi’, while the verb ‘siri’ tells us the action the subject ‘Obi’ performed. This is the norm or the known chronological order that the Igbo language is supposed to follow. However, poets, in their attempt to create an art from this normal (literal) use of language, defamiliarise language by breaking this rule of chronological order of grammatical structure. They do this through rearranging the known structure and, by so doing, make the language appear strange (estrangement) to the listeners or the owners of the language. In the hands of the poet, the above structure can become:

Nri	Obi	siri
(Food	Obi	cooked)
O	S	V

By reorganising the structure of the language in such a manner, the speaker of the language, who understands the norm of the language, is forced to take a second look at what the poet has said, ponder over it, and in some cases, may not recognise

the original structure. At this point, the language has been remodelled by the poet and estranged for the reader or listener. Changing the grammatical structure means that the poet does not create new words; instead, he manipulates the existing grammatical structure in the language. There are several instances of grammatical cohesion in written Igbo poetry, but only a few examples will suffice for illustration. In the third stanza of J.C. Maduekwe’s poem “*Nne anyị Afrika*” (Our Mother Africa) (Poem 88) in *Nkà Okwu* (1979, pp. 5-6), the poet writes:

Ma taa, nne anyị Afrika,	(But today, our mother Africa
Ndị kpọrọ gị asị na-ahụzị gị n’anya	Those that hated you now love you
<u>Ndi na-eto gị taa, kwutoro gị n’oge gboo</u>	Those praising you today, spoke ill
Na-atuzi ụjọ gị n’ihi ihe ị pụrụ ime	of you in the early days
Umu gị gukọọ ọchị e jiri gị kparịa mgbe ochie	Fearing you because of the things
Uta adighiri ha ma ha zochie n’oke iwe	you are capable of doing
	If you children count how you were
	mocked in the olden days
	They cannot be blamed if they appear
	in great anger.)

(Maduekwe, 1979, p. 5)

In the underlined line in the above stanza, the literal (general) language is defamiliarised by rearranging the chronological order of the structure to force the reader’s attention to the message contained in it. The process used in achieving this defamiliarisation in line 3 of poem 88 above is a grammatical principle known as end-weight. Nordquist (2020) explains that end-weight is a grammatical principle whereby longer structures occur later in the sentence than shorter structures. Nordquist further explains that when a structure that starts a sentence is longer and considered clumsy, the structure can be rearranged in a way that the longer structure, which carries the weight in the sentence, is made to occur later while the shorter structure is made to come first, and by so doing, make the sentence less clumsy. This is the device used in line 3 of poem 81, by the poet (Maduekwe). They said line 3, in the regular usage of the structure, reads

Ndi kwutoro gi n'oge gboo, na-eto gi taa
(They that spoke ill of you in the early days, praise you today)

In this everyday (literal) use of the structure, the first and longer clause “Ndi kwutoro gi n'oge gboo” makes the sentence clumsy. The clause carries the weight in the sentence, thereby making the sentence clumsy. However, in a bid to promote rhythm in the poem, the poet rearranges the structure of the sentence by moving the weighty structure to the end of the sentence and making the shorter structure “na-eto gi taa” occur first, leaving the subject of the sentence in its original position. This adds rhythm to the poem by making the sentence less clumsy.

Let us consider another example of grammatical cohesion as a device for defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry by looking at the first stanza of C. Ogbulogo's poem “*Agbaramikwu*” (Poem 89) in *Omenka* (1992, pp. 50-51), where the poet writes:

<u>Ndu ka anya na ihe oma gbara</u>	(Covenant is what the eyes and good things have.
<u>Oriko ka Chioma na Uchechi gbara</u>	Communion is what Chioma and Uchechi have.
<u>Di na nwunye ka ha luritara</u>	Marriage is what they have.
Ndi si ofe ikpa asaa	They that came from across seven forests
Osimiri asaa na uzọ asaa...	Seven seas and seven ways)
(Ikwubuzo, et.al., 1992, p. 50)	

The poet's intention to create art by defamiliarising everyday language is evident in lines 1-3 of the excerpt above. Here (poem 89), the poet deliberately breaks the chronological order of sentences with a view to making the standard language appear very strange to the owners of the language. The expressions in lines 1-3 are already common among the Igbo. For instance, line 1 is a popular Igbo saying: “Ihe oma na anya gbara ndu” (The eyes and good things covenanted). To make the Igbo appreciate this line, the poet defamiliarises the language through a linguistic process known as “focusing”. Nweya (2018, p. 187) defines linguistic focusing as placing

greater emphasis on a particular part of the sentence to identify new information. The exact process (focusing) applies to lines 2-3. Hence, the standard chronological order of lines 1-3 in everyday language is:

Literal form	Defamiliarised form (poetic language)
Ihe ọma na anya gbara <i>ndụ</i>	<i>Ndụ</i> ka anya na ihe ọma gbara
Chioma na Uchechi gbara <i>oriko</i>	<i>Oriko</i> ka Chioma na Uchechi gbara
Ha lụrịtara <i>di na nwunye</i>	<i>Di</i> na nwunye ka ha lụrịtara

In this literal (everyday) form of the lines shown above, no part of the structure is focused. However, in a bid to make the structure fresh to the owners of the language by means of identifying new information, the object of the sentence in the literal forms of the lines were focused by the poet in the poem by moving it to the sentence initial position, using the focus marker “ka” (See, Nweya, 2018, pp. 187-195). The point being made here is that lines 1-3 have a uniform grammatical order. The underlined part of the sentence is given more prominence in the poem than the other part of the sentence in the everyday use of the language, using the focus marker ‘ka’. In the poem, for instance, “*ndụ*” in the normal usage is focused in line 1, by moving it to the sentence-initial position. “*Oriko*” in line 2 is focused by moving it to the sentence initial position, and “*di na nwunye*” in the literal usage in line 3 is focused in the poem by moving it to the sentence initial position.

In the poem, “F.C. Ogbalu Odezulumba” (Poem 90) by N. Okediadi in *Ije Uwa* (2003, pp. 65-69), another strategy for focusing, known as cleft construction, was used to achieve grammatical cohesion. In the second stanza of the poem, the poet writes:

F.C. Ogbalu ome nkà

(F.C. Ogbalu the artist

<u>Gi bu aha umu afo Igbo kpu n'onu mgbe dum</u>	You are the name on the lips of the Igbo all the time
N'ihe gbasara utoasusu na agumagu Igbo	In things relating to Igbo grammar and literature
Oru aka gi jupatara n'ala Igbo taa...	Your handiwork fills all Igbo land today.)

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 66)

Here (poem 90), grammatical cohesion is achieved by focusing on the cleft construction. Cleft construction is a type of grammatical construction where a single clause is split into two separate segments, and each of the segments has its own verb, one that manifests in a dependent wh-clause (Crystal, 2008). Crystal (2008, p. 79) further explains that “the variants affect the distribution of emphasis within the sentence, and correlate closely with patterns of intonational prominence. In the English language, cleft construction is usually marked with “It is you”. Likewise, in Igbo, cleft construction is marked by “gi bu” or “gi nwa” (You are). In line 2 of poem 90, the line starts with a cleft construction marker “Gi bu...” which places more emphasis on the subject. However, in the normal usage, the object was not focused, hence line 2 in the literal sense reads:

Literal form	Defamiliarised form
Umụ afo Igbo kpu aha gi n'onu mgbe dum	Gi bu aha umu afo Igbo kpu n'onu mgbe dum

or

O bu aha gi ka umu afo Igbo kpu n'onu mgbe dum

(Your name is what the Igbo have on their lips at all times)

These two grammatical structures in the literal form mean the same thing; however, in the defamiliarised form of the structure, the sentence is rearranged, and

prominence is given to the focused object in the sentence. Another instance of grammatical cohesion in Igbo can be seen in the third stanza of H. Oleru’s poem, “Ochichi” (Leadership) (Poem 28), where the poet writes:

Aga m aga n’elu gaa biri	(I will go up and live
Ujọ uwa atugbuola	I am intensely afraid of the world
Umụ mmadu ofufu ofufu	People missing
<u>Ego nri, i huru n’abee?</u>	Money for food, where will you see?)

(Oleru, 2006, p. 18)

Here, the underlined line is rearranged to achieve grammatical cohesion. The method used in achieving grammatical cohesion here is topicalisation. In the standard structure, the underlined line 4 in the above stanza reads:

I huru ego nri n’abee?
(Where do you see money for food?)

In a bid to defamiliarise language in poetry, the poet unintentionally achieves grammatical cohesion by troping “ego nri”. The comma used after “ego nri”, in line 4, foregrounds the role of “ego nri” in the language of the poet, as the topic of the sentence. This topicalisation places more emphasis on “money” than on its place in the literal expression of the structure. To this end, we conclude that grammatical cohesion in written Igbo poetry is achieved through the process of linguistic end-weight and focusing.

6.2.2 Stylistic Deviation as Defamiliarisation Process in Written Igbo Poetry

Having discussed the concept of stylistic conformity in written Igbo poetry, let us now delve into the second aspect of language use as a way of defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry. While stylistic conformity in this study refers to how modern Igbo poets create art by conforming to the linguistic norm of Igbo, stylistic deviation

refers to how they defamiliarise the language by deviating from that norm. According to Uzochukwu (2012), deviation in written Igbo poetry occurs at three levels: the lexical, phonological, and graphological levels.

6.2.2.1 Lexical Deviation (Ndacha Okwu)

At the lexical level, stylistic deviation in this study refers to how modern Igbo poets defamiliarise language in their works by manipulating lexical items to deviate from the language's regular use and, in doing so, create an effect. In written Igbo poetry, lexical deviation is achieved through the use of coined words, loanwords, and dialectal words (Uzochukwu, 2012). Let us examine these points one by one to see how poets defamiliarise language in Igbo poetry.

6.2.2.1.1 Use of Coinages or Coined Words (Okwu Mmewe)

Coinage, as a form of neologism, is defined as the act of creating new words or phrases that, when accepted, are used by members of the public (Bhagavan & Priyadarshani, 2013). Coinages are one way modern Igbo poets defamiliarise language in written Igbo poetry. Citing the poem, “Ọnwụ” (Death) (Poem 91), written by Obienyem in *Akpa Uche* where the poet coined the term *Ọmaraire* as a replacement for “antidote or cure for death”, Uzochukwu (2012) explains that in a bid to shorten the length of the words in a poetic line, modern Igbo poets, sometimes, coin or form new words that are appropriate for capturing the thought they want to convey. It is important to add that for coinages to be understood, the coined word must reflect the milieu in which it was coined and used. Many other coined words feature in Igbo poetry to make the language of poetry strange to its users. For instance, in the third

stanza of poem 46 (Ego na-ekwu) in *Nkà Okwu*, the poet coined the term “mpurum”, which is used to refer to “a thief”. In the words of the poet J. C. Maduekwe:

Ego na-ekwu	(Money speaks
Ma olu okwu ya adighi ada mma mma mgbe dum;	But its voice does not always
	sound good all the time;
Okwu ya adighi ebute ahụ idi mma mgbe niile.	Its words do not bring good
	health all the time,
Olu ya na-ezuru dimkpa ohi anya ocha n’abalị;	Its voice snatches sleep from the
	eyes of a full-grown man at night
Nwa amadi ipu, ghoṣ <u>mpurum</u> , bu ego gwara ya...	For a young man to go and
	become a snatcher is what money
	has told him...)

(Maduekwe, 1979, pp. 30-31)

The word “mpurum” in “Nwa amadi ipu, ghoṣ mpurum, bu ego gwara ya” (For a young man to go and become a snatcher is what money has told him) as used in the fifth line above is a coined word. The word is derived or coined from the old Igbo expression “ndi na-apunari mmadu ihe” (those that snatch people’s items). The term, as used in the poem, connotes thief, armed robber, or anyone who unleashes terror on others at night in a bid to pillage their possessions. By using a newly coined lexical item to capture the thought that is understood in a sentence, the poet demonstrates his skill at manipulating the language. Again, the coinage “mpurum’ draws attention to itself, by forcing the reader who is a speaker of Igbo and one who knows the norm in the language to pause and ponder on what the poet could mean by that linguistic choice of lexeme.

In the poem, “Biko, ka m werekwa onwu” (Please, let me choose death) (Poem 92) by G.O. Onyekaonwu in *Uche bu Afa* (1989, pp. 34-38), the poet coined a word *nkatanaka*, which he used to refer to a situation where someone becomes so old that he begins to beg for death. In the seventh stanza of the poem, the poet writes:

Uwandu wee diwa ndu	(Uwandu continues living
Digide ndu, naani ndu	Lives life, only life
Wee gbaa nari afọ na iri	And became three hundred and ten years

Nká wee buru nkatanka Old age becomes abundant
(Onyekaonwu, 1989, p. 34)

The coined word, “nkatanka”, in “Nká wee buru nkatanka” (Old age becomes abundant; age became plenteous) is coined for its aesthetic effects in the poem. It balances the sounds of the lexemes “nka” and “nkatankà”, enhancing the effect. It actually does not exist in the Igbo linguistic corpus, but the meaning, as derived from its use in the poem, suggests a sort of overstretched antiqueness.

Special attention is also drawn to the title of one of the I. Ikwubuzo’s poem “Ehiehiedjegwu” (Day-light Robber) (Poem 93) in Omenka (1992, p. 37), which is a coined word. The term “Ehiehiedjegwu” is indeed another practical show of poetic creativity and utilisation of the poetic licence. The thing about coinages is that, over time, they become common among people because of their continued use. Before now, the term “abalidjegwu” (literally meaning “night is terrifying”) was a coinage used by the Igbo to refer to armed robbers. Today, because of the general acceptance of the coined term “abalidjegwu” among the Igbo, it is common in Igbo prose narratives and is gradually becoming literal. However, in a bid to defamiliarise (estrangle) the language in poetry, making it more elevated than the language of prose and drama texts, the poet (Ikwubuzo) remodels the literary meaning of “Abalidjegwu” into a new coinage “Ehiehiedjegwu” which does not only refer to armed robbers but everyone who engages in illegitimate businesses, aimed at duping people in broad daylight, like internet fraudsters, pickpockets and the like. The divergence between the concept of the general term “abalidjegwu’ and Ikwubuzo’s “ehiehiedjegwu” lies in the time of their activity.

Furthermore, in the poem “Ule” (Examination) (Poem 94) by C.C. Anozie in *Uche bu Akpa* (2005, pp. 89-90), the poet uses the coined term “omokirikiri” to refer

to materials used in examination malpractice by students. In the third stanza, the poet writes:

Ule dị aghughọ	(Examination is deceitful
Ị na-aghọrị ụmụ ntorobia	You deceive young men
Ị na-etinye ha na igwe bụ ike	You put them in collective strength
Igwe bụ ike abughị ogwu gi	Collective strength is not your antidote
Mmekpa ahụ naanị ka ọ na-enye gi	It only troubles you
<u>Omokirikiri</u> ekporola ha uche	Exam malpractice has taken over their brains)

(Anozie, 2005, p. 90)

Here (poem 94), the coined word “*omokirikiri*” in “*Omokirikiri ekporola ha uche*” (Exam malpractice has taken over their brains) represents exam malpractice. The word “*omokirikiri*” is gotten from two languages: Yoruba and Igbo. The Yoruba term “*omọ*” means “child,” while the Igbo term “*kirikiri*” means tiny pieces. Hence, the small pieces of paper on which students write answers and bring into the exam hall for cheating are regarded as “*omokirikiri*”. The use of this coined word in the poem suggests that the poet understands the dubious strategies students employ to pass exams. In the poem “*Nwaanyi*” (Woman) (Poem 95) by G.I. Nwaozuzu in *Akọnauche* (2016, pp. 92-94), the poet writes:

Nwaanyi	(Woman
A mụọ gi,	If you are born,
Ihu agbaruo onye iberiibe	The fool will become unhappy
Ọ sị na a mụrụ <u>amaonyeozo</u>	He will say that another man’s compound is born)

(Nwaozuzu in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 92)

Here, the term “*amaonyeozo*” in “*Ọ sị na a mụrụ amaonyeozo*” (another-man’s-compound) in line 4 is a coined word. The term is coined from the widespread belief among most Igbo men that the girl-child belongs to another man’s home. Some Igbo men do not regard the girl-child as important because they believe that they will grow up to marry into another man’s home, hence the coined word “*amaonyeozo*”.

The import of the coined word in this poem is used to mirror the patriarchy mentality of most of the Igbo.

6.2.2.1.2 Use of Loanwords (Okwu Mbite)

Lexical borrowing is one way many languages develop and expand their vocabulary. No language in the world is complete in itself. Every language borrows to develop itself. Many words in the English language were borrowed from Latin and French (Uzochukwu, 2012). There are words in the Yoruba language that were borrowed from English, Hausa, and Igbo languages. Similarly, the Igbo language borrows from other languages such as English, Hausa, Yoruba, and Efik. These borrowed words, sometimes, are used by poets in their works to beautify their works. There are various borrowed words that feature in written Igbo poetry. Most of the borrowed words in written Igbo poetry are 'Igbonised' to give it a native sound (Uzochukwu, 2012, p. 28). Borrowed or loaned words in written Igbo poetry are used to promote thought in the poem. For instance, in the first stanza of the poem "Akuko nwa Ogbenye" (Tales of the Poor) (Poem 96) by Ogunjiofor in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 51-52), the poet writes:

...Ihe ozo m na-eme di uzo ato;	(There are three other things I do
Nke a bu nri m na-ana <u>Mama</u> ;	This is the food I collect from
	mother;
Nke a bu egwu m na-aguru <u>Bombo</u> ;...	This is the song I sing for
	Bomboy.)
(Ogunjiofor in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 51)	

There are two borrowed words in the above excerpt. The first is 'Mama' in line 2, while the second is "Bombo" in line 3, a clipped form of "Bomboy". The two borrowed words were adopted from English, but they have so far become part of the Igbo vocabulary, hence their importance in the poem. The etymology of the word "Mama" shows that it originated in Britain and is a baby's way of calling mother.

Now it is used all over the world to refer to mothers or as a slangy way of referring to a girlfriend. It is used in the above stanza (poem 87) to refer to the mother. Again, the etymology of the term “Bom̄b̄o” (Bomboy) is not clear, but it is a term in Nigerian English that refers to a healthy male child (Blench, 2007, p. 3). The use of these loanwords in the above excerpt is to beautify the poem. The two terms have Igbo translations, but their use here adds variety to the poem.

In the first stanza of the poem “Onye Poliisi” (Police man) (Poem 97) by I. Ikwubuzo in *Omenka* (1992, p. 38), the poet borrows two words from the English language when he says:

I na-anako <u>taaksi</u>	(Are you collecting tax
Ka i na-anako <u>reeti</u>	Or are you collecting rate?
Akpa ego ole ka i na-amachi onu n’ubochi?...	How much money do you make in a day?

(Ikwubuzo, et al 1992, p. 38)

It is important to note that the very title of the poem 97, “Poliisi,” is also borrowed from the English word “Police”. The Igbonised term “Poliisi” is retained for its communicative effect. In the above excerpt (poem 97), likewise, the underlined words borrowed from the English language promote thought in the poem. The borrowed words, “taaksi” (tax) in line 1 and “reeti” (rate) in line 2, appear to reinforce the satiric sense of the poem, thereby highlighting the thought in the poem. The two borrowed words are near synonyms that mirror the way Nigerian police extort Nigerians on the roads. In C.C. Anozie’s poem, “Radio” (Poem 98) in *Uche bu Akpa* (2005, pp. 109-113), the use of the loanwords there contributes to the thought in the poem. In the fifth stanza, the poet writes

Ihere eme	(Shameless
<u>Ashawo</u>	Prostitute
I na-eto ezigbo mmadu	You praise the good
Na-eto ajo mmadu	And praise the bad)

(Anozie, 2005, p. 110)

The word “Ashawo”, as used in line 2 above, is a word borrowed from the Yoruba language and refers to a prostitute. Its use in the poem brings an additional thought to the poem. The nature of the prostitute makes them sing the praise of anyone who pays them well for their services; their loyalty changes from time to time. This is the same thought that the borrowed word brings to the poem. The radio, as a vital aspect of social media, is controlled by the rich and the highest bidder. As such, its patronage, like other forms of electronic media, changes over time. In G.I. Nwozuzu’s poem ‘Chaara m ka m kpara ego’ (Out of my way let me make money) (Poem 99) in *Akọnauche* (2006, pp. 94-96), loanwords were employed for variety and quick grasp of the subject in question. In the third stanza of the poem, the poet writes:

Ndi ọgbara ọhuru,	(New generation people
Burunu ọzọ chọba	First seek
Ego <u>baskulu</u> tupu nke <u>moto</u>	Money for a bicycle before that of a car
Ma <u>moto</u> abiaghi taa	But if a car does not come today
Si chọba isi nne maọbu nna	Look for mother or father’s head
O buru nke nwanne, si gbute	If it is a brother's head, cut it.
(Nwaozuzu, 2006, p. 95)	

Here, the use of loanwords “baskulu” and “moto” in “Ego baskulu tupu nke moto” (Money for a bicycle before that of a car) adds variety to the poem. By Igbonizing the borrowed words, which also have equivalents in Igbo, the poet eases the reading and understanding of the thought expressed in the stanza. Let us consider yet another example of the use of loanwords in written Igbo poetry by looking at the seventh stanza of the poem “Ejula” (Snail) (Poem 100) by N.R. Ezejesi in *Abu Uto* (2015, pp. 34-36), where the poet says:

Gaa Bini	(Go to Benin
Ka a hu ebe i no	To see where you are
N’okporo ọzọ	On the road
N’odu ọgbọala	At the park
Egbereghe gi nokwa	Your fried version is also available
Na <u>shookesi</u>	In the showglass)
(Ezejesi, 2015, p. 36)	

In the above stanza, poem 100, the poet borrows the term “shookesi” from English. The word in the English language refers to a showcase. The showcase is used to display items that are put on sale for the customers to see easily. The use of the loanword in the stanza above conveys a sense of contemporariness to the reader who is conversant with the term and helps them form images more quickly.

6.2.2.1.3 Use of Dialect (Olundi)

It is expected that the language of literature should be in the standard language, as this promotes wider readership. However, there are a few occasions when the poet's individuality comes through in their works. One way this happens is through their use of dialect. This is permissible in literature, more especially in poetry, for two reasons. One is that the poet is a member of the society and, as such, is influenced by the language of his immediate community. Secondly, the poetic licence enjoyed by literary writers avails them the power to manipulate or use language the way they think will better make an art out of the language. To this end, the use of dialectal words is another way by which poets defamiliarise language in written Igbo poetry. Uzochukwu (2012) believes that the use of dialectal words also promotes rhythm in Igbo poetry by shaping the poem's tone through alliteration and assonance. Use of dialect in poetry also distinguishes the style of a poet from that of another. As expected, there are various instances of the use of dialectal words in written Igbo poetry. In the poem “Egwurugwu” (Rainbow) (Poem 101) by K. Amasike in *Akpa Uche* (1975, p. 1), the poet employs the dialectal word, “Beelusọ” for rhythmic effect in the third stanza of the poem:

Nne m kọrọlam m sị

(My mother narrated to me saying.

<p>Ọ bụrụ na egwurugwu pụta n'igwe, mmiri agaghị ezo <u>Beelusọ</u> mgbe egwurugwu chirila Ọcha ya niile, chibaa ha n'ime igwe</p>	<p>If the rainbow shows up in the sky, it will not rain Except for when the rainbow retreats All of its brightness, into the sky)</p>
--	---

(Amasike in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 1)

The word “Beelusọ” means “Ma e wepụ” (except) in the standard Igbo variety. The main reason for the use of the didactical word “Beelusọ” in the above stanza is for economy of words. Instead of writing “Ma e wepụ”, which is longer, it was substituted for another dialectal word that projects the same thought and also sounds better in that context.

In the fourth stanza of the poem, “Akọ bụ ndụ” (Wisdom is life) (Poem 102), in *Akọ bụ Ndu* (1988, pp. 1-2), the poet uses the dialectal term “ntụ” instead of “asị” (lie), where he says:

<p>...Enwela ọnụ <u>ntụ</u> ma ọ bụ gbaa ama Nke onye bụ ka o ji ala mmụọ...</p>	<p>(Do not have a lying mouth or divulge information Whatever anyone has is what he dies with.)</p>
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(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 8)

The use of the dialectal word “ntụ” in the above excerpt serves a defamiliarising purpose in the poem. Since the term “asị” (lie) is common to the Igbo, the choice of “ntụ” is a deliberate attempt by the poet to showcase the synonymic richness of Igbo. Another instance of the use of dialect for defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry is seen in the seventh stanza of poem 19, “Ụka” (Church), wherein the poet (Anozie) writes:

<p>Nnukwu nsogbu dịkwanụ Kọnfuuзу ga-adịmakwa n'ụka <u>wosha</u> N'aha Jizọs Amenu</p>	<p>(There is a huge problem There is a lot of confusion in churches nowadays In Jesus name Amen)</p>
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(Anozie, 2005, p. 81)

There is no gainsaying the fact that the use of the dialectal word “wòsha” in the above stanza estranges the above stanza. A reader who reads the above stanza will be forced to pause and reread the second line with a view to understanding what the poet is saying. An interview with the poet (Anozie) reveals that “wòsha,” as used in the stanza above, is an Nsukka dialect word meaning “nowadays” in standard Igbo. Its import in the poem can generate different interpretations for many who are puzzled by what the word means.

In the poem “Ụwa ka onye njo” (Whose world is the worse) (Poem 103) by L. Ofodile, in *Akọnauche* (2006, pp. 136-137), the poet employs the dialectal expression “echi gara aga” (yesterday) found in the Owerri dialect of Igbo in her first stanza, where she writes.

Mgbe ahụ, naanị <u>echi gara aga</u>	(That time, only yesterday
Mgbe ibe hụrụ ibe anya	When a sibling sees a sibling
Mgbe ọha na-ejere eze ozi,	When the masses run errand for the king
Maka nche eze chere ọha	Because the protection of the king is the responsibility of the masses
E nwere ọha na eze	There is the people and the king.)
(Ofodile in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p.136)	

The use of the underlined expression in the above stanza, “echi gara aga” (Yesterday), adds variety to the poem. It also showcases the richness and multiplicity of dialect varieties in the Igbo language. Another instance of the use of dialectal expression in Igbo poetry is found in the poem “Ụwa dị ka m si hụ ya” (The world as I see it) (Poem 104) by E. Ugwunkwo in *Akọnauche* (2006, p. 103), first stanza, where the poet says:

Onye m zutere <u>nnyahu</u> ka ọ nọ ala	(The person I met yesterday, seated.
Ọọ kwa ya guzo ọtọ taa?	Is he not the one standing today?
Onye m zutere nnyahu ka ọ no ekpo ahịhia	Who I met yesterday packing wastes
Ọọ kwa ya nọ ebe ọkụ na-enwu n’elu?	Is he not the one in a developed place?)
(Ugwunkwo in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 103)	

In the above stanza (poem 104), the poet used the dialectal expression “nnyahụ”, which is the Onitsha dialect for the central Igbo expression “ụnyahụ” (Yesterday) that is obtained in the standard Igbo. The use of the dialectal expression adds a touch of genuineness to the poet's work, demonstrating her versatility in Igbo.

6.2.2.2 Phonological Deviation (Ndacha Fọnọlọji)

Uzochukwu (2012, p. 29) explains that the purpose of phonological deviation in Igbo poetry is to promote sound effects in the poem. In Igbo poems, phonological deviation is achieved by omitting a syllable in a word or by not writing the sentence in the line in full (Uzochukwu, 2012). There are various instances of phonological deviation in written Igbo poetry. For instance, in the second stanza of Emenike’s poem “Atịlogwụ” (Poem 105) in *Akpa Uche* (1975, p. 27), where the poet writes:

Egwu ndị ikolobịa na ụmụ <u>agbogo</u>	(Dance of the bachelors and spinsters)
Egwu ike na ndị rijuru afo	Dance of the strong and well-fed
Onye ike na-adighi anaghi agba gi	He that is weak cannot dance it
O bu gi ka e jiri mara ndi Igbo	You are what the Igbo is known for.)

(Emenike in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 27)

There is a phonological deviation in the manner in which the poet clipped the word “agboghọ” (spinster) in the first line of the above stanza (poem 105). The phonological deviation makes the line aesthetically pleasing while reading the poem. The syllable /bia/ was dropped to achieve free flow in the production of the line, thereby promoting the rhythm of regular recurrence of the breath-pause. Similarly, phonological deviation is also observed in the first stanza of the poem “Ndinyom” (Ladies) (Poem 106) by Onwuchekwa in *Akpaala Okwu* (1983, p. 28-29). There, instead of writing ezinaulo (family), the poet writes “ezi” dropping three other syllables that make up the word /na/, /u/, and /lo/:

Ndinyom bu ugwu <u>ezi</u> ,	(Ladies are the pride of the family,
Ha burukwa ugwu <u>ulo</u> .	They are also the pride of the home.
Ulo ha anoghi na-aju oyi	Any home they are absent from is
	always cold.
Onye enweghi ha bu okokporo...	Whoever does not have them is a
	bachelor.)

(Onwuchekwa, 1983, p. 28)

Here, the words “ezi” in line one and “ulo” in line two are clipped versions of the word “ezinaulo”. By clipping the words in line one and line two (poem 106), the poet promotes the rhythm of the poem, occasioned by the regular recurrence of sense balance. In the second stanza of Ikwubuzo’s poem “Nsuala” (Sacrilege) (Poem 107) in *Omenka* (1992, p. 35), instead of writing “Agboghobia”, the poet writes “Agboo”, and “Okoro” instead of “okorobia”.

Nwaanyi ajula ogodo	(The woman has rejected clothes
Nwoke agbapuola nti	The man has pierced (his) ear
<u>Agboo</u> n’odu trawuza	Spinster in trouser shop
<u>Okoro</u> n’odu iyeri...	Bachelor's in the earrings market)

(Ikwubuzo et al., 1992, p. 35)

Here, by removing the syllables “gho” in “Agboo”, line 3, and “bia” in “Okoro”, line 4, the poet deviates from the regular usage of the words, thereby using the style to achieve rhythmic effect and lexical matching. In the second stanza of poem 104 “Uwa di ka m si hu ya” (The world as I see it) by E. Ugwunkwo, the poet phonologically deviates from the norm, when in her first stanza instead of writing “O bu kwa”, she writes “Oo kwa”.

Onye m zutere nnyahu ka o no ala	(The person I met yesterday seated
<u>Oo kwa</u> ya guzo oto taa?	Is he not the one standing today?
Onye m zutere nnyahu ka o no ekpo ahijia	Who I met yesterday packing wastes
<u>Oo kwa</u> ya no ebe oku na-enwu n’elu?	Is he not the one in a developed place?)

(Ugwunkwo in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 103)

Here, the phonological deviation in lines 2 and 4 is done with the view to promoting rhythm in the poem. There is vowel elongation of the first letter “O” which assimilates the sound of the word/syllable “bu”. In essence, phonological deviation is

employed as a defamiliarisation technique in written Igbo poetry to promote rhythmic effect in the poem.

6.2.2.3 Graphological Deviation

In examining how modern Igbo poets deviate from the norm in the language of their works at the level of graphology, the critic's interest should focus on punctuation marks, stanza, and spelling in the poem (Uzochukwu, 2012, p. 31). Examining the graphology of a poem is necessary, given that poets, as creators, write their lines the way the thought drops in their heads (Uzochukwu, 2012). The raw idea, when written with passion, showcases divergent graphological deviations, hence the need to examine it in this study. In the sixth stanza of the poem, “Onwụ” (Death) (Poem 108) by C. Emenike in *Akpa Uche* (1975, p. 45), the poet writes:

Ọ dị ndụ g’aghota ihe ọ kuru; (The living shall reap what he sows
Ezi osisi g’amita ezi mkpuru A good tree will bear good fruit.
Osisi ojoo amatakwa mkpuru ojoo... Evil tree will bear evil fruits.)
(Emenike in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 45)

In the above stanza, there is graphological deviation in the way the auxiliary verbs “g’aghota” and “g’amita” in lines 1 and 2 were written. These spellings are spelled wrong as the apostrophe (’) used there is not used in writing auxiliary verbs in Igbo. The correct spelling of the verb should be “ga-aghota” in line 1 and “ga-amita” in line 2. In a similar vein, in the first stanza of poem 102, Chukuezi writes:

..A turoo omatra (When a proverb is said to the knowledgeable
Nke choro ndu tinye akọ n’akpa The one that wants life put knowledge in your
pocket)
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 7)

Here (Poem 102), there is a consonant cluster in the spelling of “omatra” which is supposed to be “omatara”. In the spelling structure of the Igbo language, two consonants are not supposed to follow each other consecutively in a word because

consonants do not have sound on their own. In the spelling of an Igbo word, a vowel must come immediately after a consonant to give the consonant a sound in a syllable. This is why the word “omatra”, as used in the poem by Chukuezi, is considered incorrect. The possibility of this being a typographical error cannot be ruled out. In a like manner, there is a wrong spelling of the word “osikapa” (rice) in the fifth stanza of the poem “Ire” (Tongue) (Poem 109), by N. Okediadi in *Ije Uwa*, where the poet says:

Oru oma gi kariri oru ojojo gi	(Your good is more than your evil works
Mgbe i noghi oru	When you are not working
Ji, ede, <u>sikapa</u> na ihe oriri di iche iche	Yam, cocoyam, rice, and other foods
agaghi eme njem...	Will not travel)
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 5)	

In line 3 above, rice, which is “osikapa” in the Igbo language, is spelled as “sikapa”, an indication of typographical error. Also, in the first stanza of poem 42 (Oji) (Kola nut), “hughi” (did not see) is spelt as “highi.”

O di nkenke eme ire	(Small but mighty
Anu kporo nku na-eju onu	Dry meat that fills the mouth
A gbawo diki izu	If discussion excludes the hero
A <u>highi</u> ebule na e lighi diki.	If the ram is not seen, the strong will not be buried.)
(Mbanugo in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 150)	

This wrong spelling “highi” instead of “hughi” is also believed to be a typographical error.

6.3 Figurative Language as a Stylistic Device for Defamiliarisation in Written Igbo Poetry

Figurative language can be defined as a language whose meaning and interpretation are different from the original meaning it has in the everyday use of the language (Glucksberg, 2001). In other words, figurative language refers to the departure from the literal (everyday) meaning of an expression. The use of figurative

language in Igbo poetry is grouped into figures of speech and sound devices (Uzochukwu, 2001). For this reason, in respect of written Igbo poetry, the term ‘figurative language’ points to figures of speech and sound devices. This study observes that modern Igbo poets employ figurative language as a stylistic device to foreground language in their works. Some of the figures of speech used by modern Igbo poets in their works include simile, metaphor, rhetorical questions, personification, metonymy, euphemism, hyperbole, idioms, proverbs, oxymoron, allusion, and apostrophe. On the other hand, the sound elements employed by modern Igbo poets are ideophones and repetition. Let us examine the figurative language used by modern Igbo poets to see how it serves as a tool for defamiliarisation in their poems.

6.3.1 Figures of speech

Another name for figures of speech is “rhetorical figures” (Abrams & Harpham, 2012, p. 130). In literature, figures of speech are imaginative tools used to convey ideas, speech, or language beyond their everyday usage (Fadaee, 2011). The nature of the meaning of any language relates to its standard form (literal), and different departures from the standard use of the language are regarded as figures of speech (Abram, 1964, cited in Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 90). Therefore, in this study, the concept of figures of speech refers to all the non-literal uses of language. Uzochukwu (2001) claims that figures of speech are the most popular stylistic devices employed by oral Igbo poets in their art. In written Igbo poetry, we also observe that modern Igbo poets commonly use figures of speech in their works.

6.3.1.1 The Use of Simile (Myiri)

The term ‘simile’ means resemblance or likeness (Fadaee, 2011). A simile is a figure of speech that compares two objects based on their resemblance to each other (Ngoesi, 2000). Abrams & Harpham (2012) explain that, in a simile, two distinct things are compared by the use of “like” or “as”. Simile in literature serves two primary functions: communicative and cognitive (Fromilhague, 1995). By communicative function, Fromilhague advances the view that simile helps the writer (poet) communicate more efficiently and concisely. Secondly, by cognitive function, a simile serves as a tool for thought, helping us think about the world in the literary work. This second function of simile is what we shall term image creation.

In Igbo poetry, the simile is the most common figure of speech employed by modern Igbo poets. A simile is achieved with markers such as “dịka” or “ka”. There are a few written Igbo poems that lack similes. The use of simile by modern Igbo poets enhances the aesthetics of their art and extends the thoughts from the lines to the practical world. There are many instances of the use of simile in written Igbo poetry, but few instances will surface here. A look at the poem “Agadi Nwaanyi” (Old woman) (Poem 110), by Nnamdi Olebara in *Akpa Uche*, confirms that the use of simile in written Igbo poetry does not only serve aesthetic functions but also promotes thought in the poem. In the second stanza of the poem “Agadi Nwaanyi”, the poet writes:

Ji a kòrò taà, echi ò nwụọ	(The yam planted today, tomorrow it dies.
Ñke à bù ndù nwaànyị	This is the life of the woman.
N’agboghò, ọ nà-èto <u>dị ka okwuru</u>	As a maiden, she grows like an <i>Okro</i> plant
Na-ègbu àmùmà <u>dị ka akpukpu igwē</u>	Sparkling like the bright sky
Dị nwurị <u>dị ka ùnenē chāra acha</u>	Soft as ripe banana
Nka bịa, ya èmebie mmā	Old age comes, and spoils the beauty.)

(Olebara in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 23)

In the above stanza of poem 110, the use of simile as a stylistic device exceeds its aesthetic functions to include its cognitive role as a tool for promoting imagery (thought) in the poem. Here, the poet writes about the changes women undergo from their youthful days to old age, hence the reference to the maiden stage of womanhood in line 3. In line 3, the poet, through the use of a simile, compares the fast growth and development of ladies to the *okro* plant. The *okro* plant is known to grow tall and develop very fast. Among the Igbo, when people want to speak of anything that grows or develops very fast, it is often compared with the *okro*. This is why the poet compares the physiological development of women to that of the *okro* plant, rather than to that of men. In lines 4 and 5, the use of the simile, there, also refers to the beauty, elegance, and tender nature of the ladies. Unlike men who are trained to be strong and encouraged to work hard (even under the sun), the physiological build-up of ladies entails beauty, tender skin, and a soft voice. This is why some of the pet names given to ladies in Igbo culture include “Apunanwu”, “Akwaugo”, “Ugooyibo”, to mention but a few. This nature of the lady is the thought the poet projects in the above stanza, hence the use of a simile as a stylistic device.

Let us consider another instance of the use of simile as a stylistic device in written Igbo poetry by looking at the third stanza of the poem “Onwu” (Death) (Poem 111), written by A.K. Obierozie in *Ekpe Nna* (1986, p. 13), where the poet writes:

I mere obodo, o maa jijiji	(You made the city tremble
Buru ubiam suo nwoke na nwaanyi	Made both men and women poor
Mee onye iro rja onye ka ya elu	Made an enemy to climb the person above him
Chugaa umu nne muru <u>ka umu okuko</u>	Separates children of the same mother like chicks.)

(Obierozie, 1986, p. 13)

Here (poem 111), the use of simile as a stylistic device plays the role of creating imagery. In line 4 of the above poem 111, the simile manifests as action and

its consequences. Since the poem is about disasters caused by death as a natural phenomenon, the simile in line 4 reinforces the thought and emotion in the reader's mind. This is with a view to implanting an image of sibling separation, analogous to that of chicks (from the mother hen), which depicts the aftermath of the loss of a loved one. The action performed by the subject “Ọnwụ” (Death), which is captured in the main clause “Chụgaa ụmụ nne mụrụ” in line 4, is completed by the consequence of such grievous action through the use of a simile as a stylistic device. When parents die, the children are left to suffer or fend for themselves, and, in some cases, siblings scatter in their quest to survive. This thought is what the poet captures through the imagery of scattered or separated chicks in the stanza above. Hence, the import of the simile in line 4 above evokes a feeling of fear, sadness, and pity in the reader.

Another example of the use of simile as a stylistic device in written Igbo poetry can be seen in the third stanza of a poem “Ọrịa Mmịnwụ” (HIV/AIDS) (poem 112), written by C.C. Anozie, in *Uche bụ Akpa* (2005, pp. 73-74), where the poet writes:

Ezinaụlọ m batara	(The family I enter
<u>Na-akuwa ka akwa okuko</u>	Breaks like a chicken's egg
Iwe na ọnụma na-adị	There is annoyance and anger
Ụta m gaara mara esobe	Blame of if I had known follows
Ihere agba ha gburugburu	Shame surrounds them)
(Anozie, 2005, p. 74)	

In the above stanza (poem 112), the thought expressed in the simile used in line 2 is derived from the preceding line 1, which focuses on the effect of H.I.V and AIDS on families. The use of the simile in poem 112, as a stylistic device, serves cognitive functions which help the readers to think of the socio-cultural problems associated with HIV, AIDS, and the stigmatisation the carrier faces in society. A chicken's egg is very fragile and, as such, requires a lot of care. In the same manner,

when someone is known to have tested positive for HIV, the family of the person is shattered, traumatised, and stigmatised. What is created by the use of the simile is the image of a “shattered, broken egg,” which is an irredimable loss. This thought is what the poet summarises through a simile, a stylistic device, as seen in line 2.

In the third stanza of another poem, “Otu Ezuola” (One is enough) (Poem 113), by O. Ifeka in *O Natara Chi* (2009, pp. 31-33), the poet also uses a simile to project her thought as seen below:

Na mbu, o ziri m	(At first, he showed me
Ihunanya e nweghi atu	Incomparable love
Mana nke ugbu a buzi	But now it is
I ga-anwu nwuo	If you want to die, die
<u>Okwu ya na-atọ ka mmanu anu</u>	His word that was as sweet as honey
A ghoala aki ilu ugbu a	Has become bitter kola now)
(Ifeka, 2009, p. 31)	

The use of simile as a stylistic device in line 5 of the above stanza (poem 113) serves a comparative function in the thought the stanza conveys. The poet, in trying to create an image of two seasons (seasons of love and hate) in the reader's mind, employs the simile of a sweet, soothing, loving, and encouraging manner of speaking, like honey. The poet draws the reader's attention to the comparison between honey as used in line 5 and bitter kola as seen in line 6. By saying that the words of the subject (husband or lover), which used to be soothing, hence its comparison with honey in line 5, have become bitter in line 6, means the place of love has changed to hate, and the relationship has turned sour.

The above discourse proves that modern Igbo poets employ simile as a stylistic device to defamiliarise the literal use of language. By employing simile as a stylistic device, modern Igbo poets beautify the language of poetry. It has been shown here that, in addition to its aesthetic function, simile in written Igbo poetry also serves

communicative, cognitive, and comparative functions. This is why it is considered a standard tool for defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry.

6.3.1.2 The Use of Metaphor (Mburu)

Just like a simile, the meaning of a metaphor is foregrounded in the concept of comparison, where the meaning of an object or idea in the literal usage is substituted for, or applied to another thing without stating a comparison (Abrams & Harpham, 2012). Metaphor is used in literature to suggest the similitude of features that are common to the reader, thereby drawing a clear sketch of the thought the author (poet) intends to pass across (Ojo, 2013). In Igbo, this comparison is usually done to show the similarity between the idea or object and what it is compared with (Ngoesi, 2000, p. 144). This substitution of ideas is usually done based on the individual's experience of the other object (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). To this end, speakers or writers use metaphors to express new meanings. Citing Abrams (1964), Uzochukwu (2001, p. 92) explains that various figures of speech we know now are actually species of metaphor. Figures of speech like personification, euphemism, hyperbole, metonymy, and synecdoche are all species of metaphor. In Igbo, "bu" as in "Chuka bu agu" (Chuka is a leopard) is used to mark a metaphor.

In Igbo written poetry, metaphors are used to extend the thought on the subject or issue being raised. Since the poet is not at liberty with words like the prose writers, the poet has to code the associative meaning of his thought in figures of rhetoric that create images, such as a metaphor. In the ninth stanza of poem 51 "Nkwu" (Palm Tree), as earlier shown in the fourth chapter, while writing on the subject of palm tree and its socio-economic benefits, the poet writes:

Urù a nà-ènwe gī bù ajā
Ọ̀ bù àzìzà e jì àza ụlọ?

(The benefits in you are sand
Is it the broom that is used in sweeping the house?)

K' ò bù òkàtà e jì èkpo ajā? Or is it the basket that is used in packing sand?
 K' ò bù igù e jì àrù ọ̀lò? Or the fronds used in building?
 (Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 31)

The image “aja” (sand) in the metaphorical expression “Uru a na-enwe na gị bù aja” (The benefits in you are numerous), as used in the first line and its hyperbolic undertone, is to say that he (the poet) cannot begin to list the many benefits of palm tree just as sand is so numerous to count. In the interpretation of this metaphoric device used in the above excerpt, the reader must know the associative meaning of the images that are compared. The subject of the poem is “Nkwù” (Palm tree), and its economic importance is compared with “aja” (sand). Since *Aja* is an uncountable noun, its symbolism, in the line, explains the thought the poet is conveying.

A similar usage of metaphor as a stylistic device in written Igbo poetry features in the fourth stanza of the poem “Diokpara” (First male child) (Poem 114), written by A.K. Obierozié in *Ekpe Nna* (1986, p. 9), where the poet says:

Akụ nna bù ihe o dewere	(The wealth of the father is the legacy he left
Nke m dī ya, ka onye ọ̀bùla kwuru	My own is there, says everyone
<u>Anya cheere gị bu kpakpando</u>	The eyes looking at you are stars
<u>Onụ na-ekwu bù aja</u>	The mouth speaking is sand)
(Obierozié, 1986, p. 9)	

Here, the use of metaphors, as seen in lines 3-4, also has hyperbolic implications. In line 3, for instance, the metaphor “kpakpando” (stars) in “Anya cheere gị bù kpando” (The eyes that awaits you are stars) and its implied hyperbole is used to say that the subject of discuss in the poem “Diokpara” (first male child) is being carefully watched by people who are looking to see if he can pilot the affairs of the family properly. The second metaphor “aja”, in line 4, and its implied hyperbolism means that, not only is the “Diokpara” under the microscopic eyes of accusers, but the number of people talking (gossiping and discussing) about him (both for good and bad) is too many to number, hence the use of “aja” which connotes uncountable.

Another example of the use of metaphor in written Igbo poetry is seen in the fourth stanza of the poem 70, where the poet writes:

<u>Ura bu ogboogu</u>	(Sleep is a settler of fight
Ndị ọrụugbo na-agbasa ọgụ na mma	Farmers drop their hoe and cutlasses
Ndị ọrụ bekee edosa mkpisiodee	Civil servants drop their pens
Mekaniiki achikọọ ngwaọrụ	A mechanic packs his tools
Ọzụahịa akpọchie ụlọahia ya	The trader locks up his shop.
(Anozie, 2005, p. 76)	

In the above stanza from poem 70, the metaphor “Ogboogu” as in “Ura bu ogboogu” as seen in line 1 is used to portray the helplessness of man to the forces of nature, which is sleep in this case. In the above stanza from poem 70, the subject of the poem, “sleep,” as a natural phenomenon, is considered a leveller that pauses all human struggles. In the above excerpt, Abrams and Harpham’s (2002) definition of metaphor becomes evident. The literal meaning of “sleep” in humans denotes a reduction in awareness of environmental stimuli (Mandal, 2020). Sleep is a natural phenomenon common to all animals; it cannot be denied or rejected when it comes. This means that when a person sleeps, they are motionless and unaware of what happens around them. Many times, sleep is when the body heals itself. This is why, when a person is exasperated after working so hard, it is natural for that person to fall asleep easily at some point in the day or upon getting home. It is this understanding of the helplessness of man against the forces of nature (sleep) that the poet applies to another situation that also performs the same function. In the case of “ogboogu”, which is the metaphoric comparison of sleep in the above stanza, “ogboogu” refers to a person or something that settles quarrels and brings peace to troubled situations. The common denominator that gave rise to the metaphoric comparison of “sleep” to “dispute settler” is peace. Sleep is a period of calm and peace, as the body is quiet and motionless. It is important to note that the four succeeding lines after line 1 in the above stanza from poem 70 reinforce the metaphoric thought projected in line 1.

Lines 2-5 focus on the fact that men work hard daily to make a living, a situation the poet captures as struggle, and, as such, denies himself rest in a bid to make ends meet. However, when sleep comes, it ends all these struggles and forces man to rest for a while.

Another creative use of metaphor in written Igbo poetry is seen in the fourth stanza of the poem “Iduuazi” (Novel) (Poem 115), written by O.C. Kanu in *Akọnauche* (2006, pp. 44-45), where the poet says:

Ndi kporo gi asi kporo mma asi	(Those that hate you hate beauty.
<u>Obi ha bu obi Jezibel</u>	Their heart is the heart of Jezebel
Ma cherekwa! koo akuko n'isi nwanne m	But wait! tell a story on my sibling)
(Kanu in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 44)	

Here (poem 115), the metaphor “Jezibel” and its allusive implication in “Obi ha bu obi Jezibel” (Their heart is the heart of Jezebel) is used by the poet to portray a wicked person who has lost all traces of compassion and pity. The use of this metaphoric device and the manner in which it is deployed by the poet in the above excerpt mirrors the conviction of the poet, who believes that whoever does not enjoy prose narrative must be considered a terrible person whose heart is full of evil. Again, full appreciation of the metaphor used in poem 115 is made possible in its implied biblical allusion to Jezebel, wife of King Ahab, who killed Naboth, a poor man, in a bid to take over his vineyard and satisfy her husband, Ahab (1 Kings 21, v. 5-16). The image of Jezebel connotes wickedness and heartlessness, hence its usage in the above excerpt to refer to the hearts of those who do not like prose narratives.

6.3.1.3 Use of Personification (Mmemmadu)

Generally speaking, personification is anthropomorphism, which arises in the need to give human forms and attributes to nonliving beings, higher entities, or

abstract things (Krašovec, 2016, p. 575). Ojo (2015) describes personification as a stylistic device that endows inanimate things with animate qualities and strength. In some cases, an idea or animal is made to talk and act like a human being (Emenanjo, 1983, p. 13). Personification is an important literary device that contributes to the aesthetics of literary works, more especially poetry. In literature, personification is understood in its metaphorical sense (Krašovec, 2016). In Igbo poetry, personification is used metaphorically to magnify images, thereby contributing to the aesthetic nature of the poems.

There are many instances of personification in Igbo poetry. However, we shall examine a few applications of personification in Igbo poetry. In the third stanza of Tagbo Nzeako's poem, "Ngana" (Laziness) (Poem 116) in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 18-19), 'Ngana' is personified in such a way that makes it look and act like a complete human. In that stanza, the poet says:

<u>Ngana na-eji ike ogwugwu</u>	(Laziness goes with tiredness
<u>Wee gaa n'ulo enyi ya bu mmadu</u>	And visits the house of his human friend
<u>Igba asiri, izu ohi na igwu egwu</u>	To gossip, steal, and play
<u>Ha bu ihe ngana na-eji aru oru</u>	They are the tools laziness works with.)
(Nzeako in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 18)	

There is personification in every line of the above stanza (poem 116). The subject, being the personified abstract concept "Ngana" (Laziness) in line 1, portrays qualities of a lazy person. Laziness, which is also personified in line 2, is given human qualities and made to appear capable of walking, visiting, and gossiping like a human. The beauty of the use of personification in the above stanza is embedded in its metaphoric implication and can be understood in line with its literary meaning. The attributes/traits listed on line 3, such as "Igba asiri", "izu ohi", and "igwu egwu" (gossip, stealing, and play), which are familiar to all lazy people, reinforce the role of personified laziness. This is also seen in line 4, where we learn that all the attributes

mentioned in lines 1 and 3 are tools the personified laziness operates with. The manner in which the poet deploys personification as a device in the above stanza promotes the aesthetic quality of the poem itself. This is because the term “ngana” was defamiliarised and given human features, thereby foregrounding its original meaning. Another interesting use of personification as a literary device in written Igbo poetry is seen in the third stanza of L. C. Okoro’s poem “Ndu bu nga” (Life is imprisonment) (Poem 117) in *Omenkà* (1992, pp. 24-25), where the poet writes:

Echi dika o ga-aka mma	(Tomorrow looks like it will be better
Ma ubochi o bu la putaranu	But every breaking day
<u>Ndu, i na-eme ka ahuhu m bawanye</u>	Life, you increase my suffering
<u>Na-enweghi omiko ebe m no</u>	Not having compassion upon me)
(Okoro, 1992, p. 25)	

In the above stanza, “Ndu” (life) is personified and made to look like a human that can suffer imprisonment. The personification of an abstract entity, “life,” in the stanza, is the poet’s way of saying that life is complicated and never fair. The contribution of the personification to the emotive projection of the above stanza lies in the manner in which life is foregrounded. The use of the comma immediately after “Ndu” (life) in line 3 above draws attention to life in that line, not as it is known in the general sense of the word, but as the subject (person) of the line. The poet further reinforces the focus in line 4, which is a subordinate clause that qualifies the personified subject, which is “Life. Life is given the position of a human that the poet can see and speak to. This style of personification intensifies the emotion of pity that is already evoked in lines 1 and 2.

In Okediadi’s poem, “Mmiri Ozuzo” (Rainfall) (Poem 118) in *Ije Uwa* (2003, p. 43), the poet employs personification to promote the thought and also the aesthetics of the poem. Since the poem focuses on the importance of rainfall both to humans, animals, and crops, the use of personification as seen in the fifth stanza of the poem

projects the devastating effect of delay in rainfall to the human race. Hence, in the fifth stanza, the poet says:

Ma ọ buru na i biaghi n’oge,	(If you do not come early
Ọtutu anu ohi na-anwu,	A lot of wild animals die
<u>Nriaria na-efe efe na-esi n’ikuku</u>	Communicable diseases come from the wind
<u>ezuru ndi mmadu</u>	To steal people
<u>Aguu na-apia ndi mmadu utari</u>	Hunger deals with people)
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 42)	

There is personification in the last three lines of the above poem 118. Sickness is given the attributes of a flying animal that comes through the wind in line 3 and steals a human being in line 4. In the same manner, hunger in line five is given the attributes of a human being who can flog another person. The personified hunger in “Aguu na-apia ndi mmadu utari” refers to a situation in which people are subjected to hunger and starvation. Again, “utari”, which is an instrument for corporal punishment in that same line, is used in its literary sense to mean pain caused by hunger, hence the personification of hunger. In the third stanza of poem 63 (Ihe adikwaghi ebe o na-adi), the poet also employs personification:

Agharagha aghagbuola	(Carelessness has finished
<u>Nsogbu esonyela ogwu ntaramahu</u>	Trouble has planted the thorn of punishment
Aghugho aghosaala elu na ala	Disseas has deceived up and down
Onu na-ekwu mma na-afuzi opi onwu	The mouth that speaks good now blows death trumpet
<u>Onwu na ndu bu ha na-azozu okpu eze</u>	Life and death are the ones fighting for the crown.)
(Ezeuko in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 220)	

In line 2 in the above stanza from poem 63, the personification of “Nsogbu” (Trouble) in “Nsogbu esonyela ogwu ntaramahu” (Trouble has planted the thorn of punishment) by the poet gives an abstract thing like “trouble” the attributes of a person that can plant a seed, which, in this case, is a seed of pain. More so, by personifying “Onwu” (Death) and “ndu” (life) in “Onwu na ndu bu ha na-azozu okpu eze” (Life and death are the ones fighting for the crown) in line 5, the two natural

phenomena are given human qualities and as such the image of the two phenomena are magnified to promote didactic thought and engender emotion of fear about this changing world.

From the way modern Igbo poets use personification in their works, as shown above, one can see that personification as a literary device not only serves aesthetic effects but also creates images that help account for the unsaid in the poem under the umbrella of imagery.

6.3.1.4 Use of Hyperbole (Egbeokwu)

Hyperbole is a figure of speech by which there is unwarranted or untrue exaggeration of statements made (Henkemans, 2013) to capture the attention of the listener or reader (Altikriti, 2016). Hyperbole is also one of the ways by which literary artists defamiliarise language in their works. According to Quintilian (1969), hyperbole can manifest in two ways: exaggeration can present things as bigger than they are, or as smaller than they are initially. Modern Igbo poets employ hyperbole as a device to magnify ideas, making them seem bigger than their original state, with a view to drawing the reader's attention to the exaggerated issue.

The significant difference between what is said in hyperbole and what is implied by way of exaggeration, according to McCarthy and Carter (2004:158), is not one of a kind but of the degree. Therefore, the only corrective response to exaggeration is to downscale or upscale what is said and marry it to reality. Similarly, to find how language is defamiliarised through the hyperbolic use of language in written Igbo poetry, the reader must up or downscale the expression, in a bid to marry it to reality. In the second line of the first stanza of the poem "Oluku" (Fool) (Poem

119) written by I.E. Akoma in *Akpa Uche* (1975, p. 50), the poet employs hyperbole where he writes:

Oluku, gini ka i na-ezuzu?	(Fool, what are you fooling around for?
I bewo akwa bejuo <u>ite mmiri</u>	You have cried and filled a pot of water
Jezibel anaghi nti	Jezebel did not listen
I ziela ozi, dee leta	You have sent messages, written letters
O nyeghi gi osisa o bula	She did not give you any response.)
(Ekechukwu in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 50)	

By saying that the subject has filled a pot of water with tears in “I bewo akwa bejuo ite mmiri” (You have cried and filled a pot of water) (line 2), the poet exaggerates the crying in such a way that the import of the hyperbolic effect in that line evokes an emotion of compassion and pity in the reader. An attempt to recover this literary use of language (line 2) back to its literal meaning will reveal that the poet is simply saying that the subject of discourse in the poem has spent a lot of time crying over a love that has never been his, justifying the title of the poem “Oluku”. Again, in another example of the use of hyperbole in written Igbo poetry, seen in the third stanza of “Ogbanje”, poem 29, the poet writes:

Chukwu kere m ehighi ura	(God that created me did not sleep
<u>O jiri mma saa m ahu</u>	He bathed me with beauty
Any a huru m, lere m abua	The eyes that saw me looked at me twice
Ndi muru m, jiri m mere anya ha	Those that gave birth to me made me their eyes
Okoko osisi ka m bu, nye oha	I am a flower to the crowd)
(Obierozie, 1986, p. 6)	

Here, the speaker's self-praise is hyperbolic. In the above stanza, the speaker “ogbanje” praises herself for her preconceived physiological features. Oftentimes in Igbo, hyperbole is employed in describing the nature of a thing, just as it plays out in the above stanza. It is important to state that all the lines in the above stanza from poem 29 have implied hyperbolic effects. However, the use of hyperbole as a device in the above stanza is more apparent in its line 2, where the speaker praises itself in

hyperbolic terms like “O jiri mma saa m ahụ” (He bathes me with beauty). The speaker, here, exaggerates ‘her’ beauty to mean that everything on ‘her’ body is magnificent. The hyperbole in the above excerpt is a conscious exaggeration to heighten the emotional effect.

In the poem, “Obodo Ọnịcha” (Onitsha City) (Poem 120) by N. Okediadi in *Ije Uwa* (2003, pp. 10-12), the poet employs hyperbole in describing the enormity of pain caused by armed robbers to the people. In the third stanza of the poem, the poet says:

Obodo Ọnịcha	(Onitsha Town
Obodo ndị abalịdịegwu	A town of night terrors/ criminals
Ndị jiri abalị mere ehie	Those that night their day
Ma were ehie mere abalị	And made day their night.
Ụlọ ọbụla ha wakutere	Any home they besiege
Egbe na mma a na-ada	The sound of guns and knives is heard
<u>Anyammiri ejuputa anya obula</u>	All eyes filled with tears)
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 10)	

Here, the hyperbolic generalisation of crying in “Anyammiri ejuputa anya ọbụla” (All eyes filled with tears) is used to refer to a whole community that suffers in the hands of robbers. The exaggeration of “all eyes” paints the whole city of Onitsha in tears, evoking pity and fear towards its inhabitants.

Again, in Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe’s poem “Ọnwụ” (Death) (Poem 121), in *Uche bu Ahia* (2009, pp. 16-17), there was usage of hyperbole in the first stanza, where the poets write:

Ọtụtụ <u>bu mmiri n’anya</u>	(Many carry water in their eyes
Ebe ha na-eche	Where they are thinking
Ma na-erikwa anụ	And also destroy
Ahụ onwe ha	Their bodies
Maka ihe ị mere ha	Because of what you did to them.)
(Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe, 2009, p. 16)	

Here, the hyperbolic expression in line 1, “Ọtụtụ bu mmiri n’anya”, is used to express the intensity of sadness and sorrow that is felt in many homes as a result of

the loss of loved one(s) to death. In the above stanza, the exaggeration of tears as water carried in the eyes conveys that the tears shed by the family of a deceased person are unending. It is a type of pain that is renewed anytime the thought of the deceased comes to mind.

6.3.1.5 Use of Metonymy (Ahaṅṅochi)

Metonymy is a figure of speech that involves speaking of a thing by the name of another thing that is similar or connected with it (Uzochukwu, 2001). The key function of metonymy as a figure of speech in literature is to help the reader or listener (in oral literature, for instance) recognise the special characteristics of the referent (Song, 2011). The modern Igbo poet writes, sometimes, to prove his mastery of the language and, as such, demonstrates his creativity by the use of metonymy. There are many instances of metonymy in written Igbo poetry, but only a few will be cited here. In the excerpt from Obienyem’s poem “Ọnwụ” (Death) (Poem 122) in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 3-4) that follows, neologistic expression, *omaraire*, is used as metonymy to represent ‘cure’ or ‘antidote’:

O nweghị onye nọ n’akụkụ	(There is no one on any side
Ebe ị naghị agaru	Where you do not reach
Ma ọ bụ maara <u>omaraire</u>	Or knows the antidote
Nke nwere ike igbote gi	That can prevent you)

(Obienyem in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 3)

Here, the sense in line 4 provides insight into the meaning and implications of the metonymy used in line 3 in *omaraire*. Indeed, the poet demonstrates his mastery of language by deploying metonymy as a literary device to promote thought in the stanza above. It is also important to state that, though the metonymic term, “omaraire”, contributes to the thought in the above stanza, it also serves aesthetic functions as it adds more flavour to the stanza. In a like manner, in the first stanza of

the poem, “Oluku” (poem 119), as earlier discussed, the name “Jezebel” is used as a metonymy to represent a wicked or hard-hearted lady. Again, in the poem “Ogbanje” poem 31, by Onwuchekwa, *unyi* (charcoal) in the second stanza is used as a metonymy to represent darkness:

Soro ụzọ atọ ndị a na-ala	(Follow these three roads and leave
Anyị esorokwanụ ụzọ ọzọ	We follow another route
Nke anyị laghachi	Our own return
Gị na <u>unyi</u> bụ enyi	You and <i>charcoal</i> are friends
Soro ya lawa	Follow it and leave
Abiala ozo, laa, noruo	Do not come again, leave, remain there.)

(Onwuchekwa, 1988, p. 16)

In the Igbo linguistic repertoire, there is nothing darker than charcoal; that is why whenever darkness is spoken of, the Igbo equate it with charcoal. The poet (Onwuchekwa) in the stanza above demonstrates mastery of Igbo lexemes by using *unyi* as a metonym for darkness. The line can still read “Gị na ọchịchịrị bụ enyi” (You and darkness are friends), which is, in a literal sense. By defamiliarising darkness and replacing it with “charcoal”, the poet promotes imagery in the poem.

Furthermore, in the fourth stanza of the poem, “Anya Ukwu” (Greed), (Poem 123), by Obierozie in *Ekpe Nna* (1986, pp. 24-25), “*akajiaku*” is used as a metonymy to represent a rich man/person:

Anya ukwu	(Greed
Ọ dị m ka m bụrụ <u>akajiaku</u>	I wish to become a rich man
Jụọnu mgbe bidoro kpawa...	Ask when he started saving...)

(Obierozie, 1986, p. 24)

Here (poem 123), the concept of *akajiaku* refers to a wealthy person. The poet is deliberate in his choice of words because, instead of using “Ogaranya”, which means the same thing in general usage and common parlance, he adopts another linguistic expression, ‘*akajiaku*’, which is not as commonly used as the former.

In the third stanza of the poem “Obodo Ọnicha” (poem 120, discussed above), the poet employs metonymy to describe the works of criminals. In the words of the poet:

Obodo Ọnicha	(Onitsha town
Obodo ndi <u>abalidiegwu</u>	A town of night robbers/ criminals
Ndi jiri abali mere ehie	Those that make night their day
Ma were ehie mere abali	And make day their night.
Ulo obula ha wakutere	Any home they besiege
Egbe na mma a na-ada	The sound of guns and knives is heard
Anyammiri ejuputa anya obula	All eyes filled with tears)
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 10)	

Here, the neologistic term *abalidiegwu*, which has gained wide acceptance among the Igbo, is used, as in the stanza above from poem 109, as a metonymy for armed robbers or criminals. The sentential noun “*abalidiegwu*,” which has its root in three words: *Abali* (night) – *di* (is) – *egwu* (fearsome), is used in the above context to depict the nefarious activities of some unscrupulous individuals who go around at night unleashing mayhem on the people. Because of the activities of these individuals, nighttime becomes a fearful time, hence the use of the term *abalidiegwu* to represent these criminals in the poem.

In the same vein, in the poem, “Idula Mmụọ” (Sending to the Land of the Spirit) (Poem 124) by B. Obodo in *Akọnauche* (2006, pp. 58-60), the soldiers are referred to as those whose cloth is *kaki*:

<u>Ndi afe kaki</u> atọ azọrọla ije na-aputa	(Three kaki clothed people are marching out
Ha busi egbe ka ndi na-aga agha	They carry guns as people going to war.
Ha akwusila n’ike, makpuru ala wee nọrọ jii	They stopped abruptly, lay down and remained still.
Ha tudoro onye ahụ egbe	They pointed their guns at the person.)
(Obodo in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 59)	

Here (poem 124), the poet, writing about execution by firing squad, describes the soldiers, metonymically, as “*Ndi afe kaki*” (Kaki clothed people). This expression

refers to soldiers whose uniforms are made of kaki material; hence, they are metonymically represented as “Ndi uwe kaki” in the poem.

From the foregoing, one understands that in written Igbo poetry, metonymy serves referential functions, and the images used by modern Igbo poets in metonymy are usually ones readers can relate to. This helps the readers to appreciate a poet better, in terms of his choice of register in his works.

6.3.1.6 Use of Paradox (Igbuduokwu)

This figure of speech is a statement that sounds and looks absurd on the surface, but when one ponders it, it turns out to make great sense (Emenanjo, 1983; Ngoesi, 2000; Abrams & Harpham, 2012). A reader who does not think deeply will dismiss a paradox as foolish talk (Emenanjo, 1983). Paradox is another figure of speech that modern Igbo poets deplore in their art, promoting elevated thought in their poems. In the poem “Echiche bu ndu” (Thought is life) (Poem 125) by J. Onwuchekwa in *Akpaapala Okwu* (1983, p. 65), the poet employed paradox in the third stanza, where it says:

<p>Ekwela o kwa gi, ikpo onu n'ala <u>Turu ji, turu mgborogwu</u> <u>Ha abuo bu ndu</u> Uzọ ihe abuo akwaghi mmadu Itinye ihe dum n'otu nkata, Ukwu kpo gi onwu ike abia</p>	<p>(Do not let it pass you by, to hit your mouth on the flour Peck at the yam, peck at the root Both is life Two things do not pass humans by Putting everything in one basket, Once you have a misfortune, untimely death comes.)</p>
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(Onwuchekwa, 1983, p. 65)

Here, the popular wellerism “Okwa si umu ya, onye turu ji ya turukwa mgborogwu” (Wild fowl told her chicks, he that pecks the yam should also peck the root) is defamiliarised by way of clipping to create the paradox in lines 2-3. A reader who comes across lines 2-3 at first instance will only decode the absurdity of the line,

but a closer examination of the lines will reveal the deep thought embedded in them. When the poet says, “turu ji, turu mgborogwu, ha abuo bu ndu” as seen in lines 2-3 in the above stanza (poem 114), the poet is simply advising the people to endure good times and bad times, for both of them form human experiences in life and help them become better.

Another use of paradox in written Igbo poetry is seen in the second stanza of A.B. Chukuezi’s poem “Akọ bu ndu” poem 102, where the poet says

<u>Mmiri na-ama ohu</u>	(The rain that beats a slave
<u>Na-asa ya ahu</u>	Bathes him
O ji akwa asa ahu	He that bathes wearing cloths
Mara onwe ya...	Mind yourself...)
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 7)	

The paradoxical expression in *Mmiri na-ama ohu, na-asa ya ahu*, as seen in lines 1-2 above, appears very absurd on the surface, but it has a profound meaning. The use of the paradoxical device in the above excerpt is to say that the ill treatment meted out to the poor by the rich, unintentionally, trains him and makes him better and more equipped.

6.3.1.7 Use of Oxymoron (Nhadigeokwu)

Abrams and Harpham (2002, p. 267) are of the view that a paradoxical utterance that combines two contradictory terms in the literal usage is called an oxymoron. This means that an oxymoron is a figure of speech that conjoins two contradictory words or terms in a sentence. The concept of an oxymoron, being contradictory terms that are joined in an utterance, is rooted in the fact that one of the terms in the structure that makes up an oxymoronic expression negates the other (Ruiz, 2015). It is important to note that the relationship between paradox and oxymoron is that both figures of speech involve a contraction found in the linguistic

expression of the people themselves (Ruiz, 2015). In written Igbo poetry, oxymoron is employed to create additional or further meaning to the poem by the use of opposing terms together in a poetic line. In many cases in written Igbo poetry, the use of oxymoron draws the reader's attention to the poem's thought. For instance, the literary title of the poem “Ụkọ n’Uju” (Lack in midst of plenty/abundance) (Poem 22) by Emenanjo in *Utara Nti* (1979) is an oxymoron. The two terms that form the title contradict each other in a way that the negative thought expressed in “Ụkọ” (Lack) is more pronounced and supersedes the positive thought expressed in “Uju” (abundance). Let us further instantiate this point by taking a look at an excerpt from the first stanza of Chukuezi’s poem “Nkịta” (Dog) (Poem 126) in *Akọ bụ Ndu* (1988, p. 13) where the poet writes:

Nri m bụ nsị	(My food is feaces
Ezi bụrụ m ebe obibi	Outside is my residence
Ejiri m <u>anyasị mere ehihie</u>	I make night my day
Maka mụ na ndị mmụọ na-etukwu na-akpa nkata...	Because the spirits and I sit down to discuss...)

(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 13)

In the expression ... *Nri and nsị* (food and feces) in “Nri m bụ nsị” (Feces is my food), line 1, two words that contradict each other are cojoined literarily in the line. Again, *anyasị mere ehihie* (make night day) in “Ejiri m anyasị mere ehihie” in line 3 above can still be paraphrased as *anyasị ka m ji arụ ọrụ ndị ọzọ na-arụ n’ehihie* (I do the work others do in the day at night). The term ‘anyasị’ contradicts ‘ehihie’ in a way that the thought in the first term becomes more pronounced, and it depicts the time of the speaker’s activity in the poem. In this context, the use of an oxymoron adds additional meaning to the thought expressed in the poem by making the reader think of possible ways that the dog lets night become its day. Let us consider yet another use of oxymoron that features in the third stanza of G. O. Onyekaonwu’s

poem, “Nndidi” (Patience) (Poem 127) in *Uche bu Afa* (1989, pp. 30-31), where the poet says:

Nndidi! Gịnị dị ka gị?	(Patience! What is it like you?
I maka, ị dị mkpa	You are beautiful, you are important
Onye nwere gị	Whoever has you
Mmeri bu nke ya	Victory is his
Ma ị bu <u>o dị nso eru aka</u>	But you are close yet far
Iwu gị ebughi ibu	Your rule is not much
Mana o na-ara ahụ ndebe...	But it is challenging to keep...)
(Onyekaonwu, 1989, p. 30)	

When the poet refers to patience as something close but yet far, he is simply saying that though the virtue of patience is in everyone, it is difficult to be patient in the face of some serious situations. The contradictory nature of the two terms ‘nso’ (near) in “o dị nso” and “eru aka” (unreachable) reinforces the claim that oxymoron is used to add additional thoughts to the poem. Its use in the above stanza also draws the reader’s attention to the seriousness of the issue raised in the poem. Let us consider another poem where the poet’s use of oxymoron is apparent. In the first stanza of the poem, “Abụ” (Poetry) (Poem 128), written by N. Anarado in *Akọnauche* (2006, p. 24), where the poet says:

Abụ, o dị nkenke na-eme ire	(Poetry, small but mighty
<u>O dị mkpumkpu ma tokwaa ogo</u>	He that is short and also long
Abụ, e lelịa nwa ite	Poetry, when a small pot is not respected
O gbonyuọ oku	It quenches the fire.)
(Anarado in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 24)	

The oxymoronic expression, *O dị mkpumkpu ma tokwaa ogo* (He that is short and also tall) in line 2, is a literary way of saying that though poetry is short in its appearance in a text, it speaks volumes in terms of the thought it projects. There are two contradicting terms used in creating an oxymoron in line 2, “mkpumkpu” (short) and “Ogo” (tall). Here, the oxymoronic effect used by the poet adds further meaning to the thought the poem projects. It forces the reader to pause and think of the features of poetry that warrant such expression, which was used to qualify it by the poet.

6.3.1.8 Use of Allusion (Nruṭụaka)

Allusion can be defined as an indirect reference that evokes associations that transcend the common substitution of a referent (Irwin, 2001). A more precise definition of allusion is provided by Abrams and Harpham (2012), who define it as a reference made in passing that does not have explicit identification with a place, event, literary or historical person, or even another literary work.

Four types of allusion feature in written Igbo poetry. They are historical, mythical, biblical, and literary allusions. Three of these four types of allusion are common in written Igbo poetry: historical, mythical, and biblical allusions, while literary allusion is not common. Allusion in Igbo poetry adds further meaning to a poem and also serves a similitude role. The historical allusion in written Igbo poetry is often connected with issues relating to the Nigerian civil war, child trafficking, natural disasters, education in Nigeria, colonisation of African countries, death, and politics. The mythical allusion, on the other hand, is often connected to issues relating to crops such as yams and kola nuts. The biblical allusion is often connected to death, sin, and destruction as a consequence of sin. Literary allusion is not common in Igbo poetry, but it does appear, as will be seen in our analysis.

In the poem “Ọnwụ” (Death) (Poem 129) by T. Nzeako in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 4-6), the poet reminisces on the death of his friend and brother as a result of the Nigerian civil war and makes a historical allusion to the Nigerian civil war by saying:

Ọnwụ, m gaghị echefu ihe ojọọ ị mere m	(Death, I will not forget the bad thing you did to me.
Gbuo nwa nne m na enyi ọma m	Killed my brother and good friend.
<u>Onukwube na enyi m Akunna nwurụ n’agha</u>	Onukwube and Akunna that died in war.
Agaghị m echefu ha n’ụwa	I will never forget them in this world.)

(Nzeako in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 5)

The allusion in the above stanza (poem 118) reflects the grave loss felt by many families among the Igbo as a result of the civil war. The Nigerian civil war of 1967 to 1970 left a devastating blow on many Igbo families who lost brothers and sisters during the war. Through this historical allusion, the poet takes readers down memory lane, prompting them to recall the tragedies of war, thereby evoking sorrow. Also, in the last line of his poem “Ugbo” (poem 6), Akoma makes a biblical allusion when he says:

...Ma gi onye na-ebe akwa	(But you that are crying
Hichaa anya mmiri n’anya	Wipe your tears from your eyes
N’ihi na <u>ugbo nke buru</u>	Because the vehicle that ferried
<u>Hananayas na-eche Safaira</u>	Ananias waits for Sapphira.)

(Akoma in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 49)

The biblical allusion here (poem 6) refers to a couple who died as punishment for lying to Peter, the leader of the early church, as documented in Acts of the Apostles, chapter 5:1-11. The Bible records that Ananias came ahead of his wife, Sapphira, and lied to Peter. After telling the lie, he died on the spot and was removed before his wife came in. Not knowing what had happened to her husband, Sapphira also told the same lie as her husband, and Peter told her that she would face the same fate as her late husband. She died immediately. This account was what the poet alluded to in the last line above, referring to death as a vehicle that carried Ananias and was waiting to carry Sapphira. The purpose of the allusive device used in the above stanza from poem 6 is to expand the thought in the poem, making the reader recollect this biblical account and connect it to the poem, and by so doing, have a full grasp of the death motif (ugbo), which is the subject of the poem.

On the other hand, J.C. Maduekwe employs mythical allusion in the first stanza of his poem “Ji” (Yam) (Poem 130) where he writes,

Anyi putara uwa kwudo mkpuru ubi a chiri eze

Ee, nna anyi ha mgbe ochie koro akuko
Ji à putara mgbe ahihia mbu puuru anyi n'ala
Nwa n'ala ka o bù; O bughị ede, onye ala ozo.
Ufiojiokū jiri ya chere ndi ketara ibi n'ala a;
Mkpara iji chedo ndu ka chi kere ji kere

(Maduekwe, 1979, p. 20)

(We came to the world and met this king of crops
Yes, our forefathers told tales
This yam appeared when the first crop germinated for us
He is the son of the soil; it is not cocoyam, someone from another land
Ufiojioku presented it to those who chose to stay in this land
The stick for life preservation, that is what the god that created yam created.)

There is a mythical allusion in every line in the above stanza. All the lines point to one thing: the Igbo cosmological worldview, rooted in Igbo creation myths. The use of poem 130 reflects the Igbo belief that yams are a crop given to man by God, hence their status as the king of crops among the Igbo. This is the thought the mythical allusion used in the above stanza projects. According to Igbo mythology, Eri's family, being the first family created by *Chukwu* (God), was given yam seed to grow, which eventually multiplied (Ohadike, 1996). In line 1, for instance, the poet alludes to the origin of the yam seed, referring to it as the king of crops and the oldest crop in line 2, whose story has traversed generations. The direct allusion in lines 3 to 5 refers the reader to the Igbo creation myths, which claim that yams were the first crop presented to man by *Chukwu* himself. Ufiojiokū/Ahijokū/Njokū whom the Igbo believe to be the god of yams mentioned in line 5, is one of the gods that serves the interest of *Chukwu*. Therefore, when the poet (Maduekwe) in his allusion in line 5, says *Ufiojiokū jiri ya chere ndi ketara ibi n'ala a* (Ufiojioku presented it to those that chose to stay in this land, he is still reinforcing the Igbo mythological belief that yams are the oldest crop given to man by *Chukwu* to survive, as seen in line 6.

Furthermore, in the poem "Igba Mkpu" (Rescue) (Poem 131) by J. Onwuchekwa in *Akpaala Okwu* (1983, pp. 6-7), the poet makes a historical allusion to

the flooding in Ibadan in 1978 and 1980. In the words of the poet in the second stanza, it says:

Mkpu unu na-agbara	(The call you people responded
Umụ nne unu bi n'Ibadan;	Your brothers living in Ibadan;
<u>Bu ndi ideyi mere aru</u>	Those that flood dealt with
<u>N'ime afo 1978 na 1980</u>	In the year 1978 and 1980
Ziri na idi n'otu di.	Shows that there is unity.)

(Onwuchekwa, 1983, pp. 6-7)

Here, the historical allusion is connected to flooding, a natural disaster. The allusion refers to the catastrophic flooding in 1978 and 1980. Ecological scholars report that the Ibadan metropolis has a history of flooding, first officially recorded in 1951. Babatunde, Owolabi, Olalekun, and Bolanle (2012) report that more flood cases were recorded in Ibadan in the 1960s, 1970s, and 1980s, and that the majority of these incidents occurred between August and September, which is the first peak of rainfall and the rainfall break. The heaviest flooding in Ibadan occurred in 1980, when the metropolis recorded 274mm of rainfall in a single episode (Babatunde et al., 2012; Ajayi, 2017). It is perhaps this account in Nigerian history that the poet (Onwuchekwa) alludes to in the above stanza (poem 131). After the tragic incident, the poet also applauded the response of several Igbo groups to some Igbo living in Ibadan who were affected by the flooding.

In G. Onyekaonwu's poem "Naijiria bu Enyimba" (Nigeria is a giant) (Poem 132) in *Uche bu Afa* (1989, pp. 24-25), the poet makes a historical allusion to colonial rule in African countries. In the third stanza of the poem, the poet puts it this way:

Naijiria bu Enyimba	(Nigeria is a giant nation
Obodo achoghi mmegbu	A nation that needs no victimisation
Lee! Onwu umu akwukwo	Behold the death of students
<u>Ndi uwe ojii gbagbusiri</u>	Shot dead by the police
<u>Na Soweto</u>	In Soweto
Na-agba ya anya mmiri	Makes her shed tears
N'ih na a hubeghi	For it has not been seen
Ihe di otu a na ya.	Anything like this in it.)

(Onyekaonwu, 1989, p. 25)

The allusion used here (poem 132) refers to the 1976 Soweto uprising in South Africa that saw the shooting and killing of many young black students by the Afrikaner police (Schick, 2001). The students who revolted against the cruel force of the Afrikaner police in Soweto were shot dead as they protested on the streets of Soweto. It was a heinous crime against humanity, one that shook the whole world. It was based on the terrible account of the colonial masters' activities in Africa that the poet (Onyekaonwu) makes this historical allusion in the stanza above. The import of this allusion here evokes a feeling of hatred for the ruthless colonialists and pity for the African nations for the suffering that they were subjected to in the past.

In the introductory stanza to his poem “Nwaanyi” (Woman) (Poem 133) in *Uche bu Akpa* (2005, pp. 86-87), C.C. Anozie uses biblical allusion to introduce the speaker in the poem to the reader. In the first stanza of the poem, the poet says:

<u>Chukwu kere nwoke, kee m</u>	(God created the man, and created me
M na-ebinyere nwoke na Chukwu	I live with man and God
Ihunanya m na nwoke buteere m ajo aha	The love between the man brought me bad name
<u>Mkpuru osisi m nyere nwoke ka afo ju ya</u>	The fruit I gave the man to satisfy him
<u>Umu uwa na Chukwu kpoo ya njo</u>	Humans and God regarded it as sin)
(Anozie, 2005, p. 86)	

This biblical allusion reflects the biblical account of creation as recorded in the book of Genesis, chapter 3, verses 1-6. Here, the allusion serves an introductory function. It was used by the poet to help readers understand the historical context of the speaker or subject of the poem. The allusion takes the mind of the reader back to the biblical account of creation and the fall of man, which most Christians blame the first woman (Eve) for. The first allusion in line 1, poem 133, refers to the Christian account of the creation of man, and the woman is said to be created from the rib of the man to help man (Genesis 2, verses 21-22, NKJV). The second biblical allusion that is

more apparent in lines 4-5 in poem 121 above refers to the story where Eve (the wife of Adam), after eating the forbidden fruit, gave it to Adam to eat, causing Adam to sin against God. After this act, both the man (Adam) and God blamed the woman for perpetuating the fall of Adam, by making the man sin against God. Since the poem is written through a female speaker, the woman in the poet's imagination tries to provide her reason for giving the man the fruit, as recorded in the Bible.

As earlier stated, the only type of allusion that is not common in the Igbo literary scene is literary allusion. However, literary allusion features in the third stanza of I.U. Nwadike's poem "Ndi ntọri mmadu abiakwa oo" (Kidnappers have arrived oo) (Poem 134) in *Akọnauche* (2006, pp. 245-247), where the poet says:

Enyi m,	(My friend
Mana ọ tụtụ gi n'anya	But it surprised you
Na ndị i kporo enyi	Those you call friends
<u>Ga-atughari, na-ewo gi opio n'ahu ka Brutus</u>	Will turn around to leave holes on
	your body like Brutus
<u>Na-ebo gi ebubo ugha ka ndi Farisii</u>	Accusing you falsely like
	the Pharisees)

(Nwadike in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 246)

Two types of allusion feature in the above stanza (poem 134): literary allusion as seen in line 4 and biblical allusion, which is evident in line 5. The manner in which the allusive device was used in the above stanza shows that it has implied simile connotations or performs simile functions. The literary allusion in line 4, as in "Ga-atughari, na-ewo gi opio n'ahu ka Brutus" (Will turn around to leave holes on your body like Brutus), alludes to William Shakespeare's drama text *Julius Caesar*. In the text *Julius Caesar*, the central character, Caesar, was betrayed by his closest and most trusted friend, Brutus, who joined the other senators in stabbing Caesar. By alluding to this betrayal in this literary text (*Julius Caesar*), the allusion used in the stanza also performs similar functions. Again, on line 5, the biblical allusion reflects the thorny

relationship between Jesus Christ and the Pharisees, who constantly criticised and falsely accused Jesus in a bid to gain public approval (See Luke 11, vs. 38-44; Mark 12, vs. 25-40). The use of this biblical allusion here, just like in line 4, implies a similar connotation.

6.3.1.9 Use of Rhetorical Questions (Ajuju Nsaraonwe)

A rhetorical question is defined as a question asked, which, when asked, does not require any response (Ngoesi, 2000). Emenanjo (1983) asserts that answers are not expected when a rhetorical question is asked because the answer is common to everyone. As a figure of speech, a rhetorical question is a type of question asked for its persuasive effect without expecting a response (Abioye, 2011). Abioye further states that rhetorical questions encourage the listener (reader) to ruminate on the possible answers implied by the question. This is also the role rhetorical questions play in written Igbo poetry. By encouraging the reader to ruminate on the possible answers to the rhetorical question in the poem, the poetic device heightens the poem's thought. In the second stanza of the poem "Gịni bụ ańuri" (What is happiness) (Poem 135) by C. Egbuchulam in *Akpa Uche*, for instance, a rhetorical question is used to promote advanced thought where the poet says:

Ọ dī mfe ịnwe ańuri?	(Is it easy to be happy?)
Ka o siri ike ịnwe ya?	Or is it challenging to have it?
Kedụ otu e si achọta ya?	How is it found?
Kedụ ebe e zoro ańuri?	Where is happiness hidden?)

(Egbuchulam in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 61)

The use of rhetorical questions in the above stanza from poem 135 is quite profound. Its use imports other semantic interpretations to the thought projected by the poem. The use of rhetorical questions, in the above stanza, encourages the reader to ruminate on the possible answers to the questions and, by doing so, provide their

own interpretations to the poem. In the first stanza of his poem “*Ụwa bụ nke onye*” (Who owns the world) (Poem 136) in *Uche bụ Afa* (1989, p. 26), G. O. Onyekaonwu used a rhetorical question to heighten thought in the poem, where he says:

Onye bu n’isi, kpara n’abụ?	(Who carries on his head, and has under his armpit?)
Olee ebe o bukọsị aga?	Where is he carrying them to?
Onye chọrọ ibu ụwa n’isi,	He that wants to carry the world on his head,
Olee ebe ọ chọrọ ibu aga?	Where does he want to carry it to?)

(Onyekaonwu, 1989, p. 26)

Here, the rhetorical questions used in lines 1, 2, and 4 are used by the poet to induce the reader into the poem. The device also prompts the reader to consider possible answers to the questions, which, in turn, puts them in a deep-thinking state as they relate the answers to the poem's title and what is said in the succeeding stanza. For instance, poem 136 is a didactic poem that talks about how greed destroys society. The use of rhetorical questions in the first stanza of poem 136 opens readers' creative imagination to all the things that go wrong when people display the greedy attitudes captured in the questions.

Sometimes, in Igbo poetry, poets employ rhetorical questions to evoke certain feelings in the reader. This is seen in N. Okediadi’s use of a rhetorical question in the last stanza of her elegiac poem for F.C. Ogbalu titled “F.C. Ogbalu! Odezulumba!” (Poem 90), where she writes:

F.C. Ogbalu!	(F.C. Ogbalu!
<u>Uwa ebe ahu i no, o ka nke a mma?</u>	That world where you are, is it better than this one?
Ọ bụrụ na ọ ka biko kwadoro anyị ebe	If it is better, please prepare a place for us
Ma ọ bụrụ na ọ kaghị ebe a mma,	But if it is not better than this one,
Ka ndụ anyị dị dịfọrọ anyị oooo!..	Let the life we are living remain for us oooo!...)

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 69)

The use of a rhetorical question in line 2 of the above stanza from poem 90 forces the reader to think of the world of the dead. The device prompts the reader to

consider what happens to human beings when they die. By impelling the reader to consider a world that transcends the physical, the poet re-echoes the grief and pain engendered by the loss of a colossus who spent his lifetime promoting the Igbo language. In the first stanza of N.R. Ezejesi's poem, "Nne" (Mother) (Poem 137) in *Abụ Uto* (2015, pp. 14-15), we notice another instance of a rhetorical question, where the poet says:

Ugogbe ezinaụlọ	(Mirror of the family
I bụ ndụ m	You are my life
Chi m ka ị bụ	You are my god
<u>Onye dika nne m?</u>	Who is like my mother?
O nweghị onye ọ bụ	No one is)

(Ezejesi, 2015, p. 14)

The role of the rhetorical question, here, is to create imagery. The rhetorical question in line 4 (Poem 137) draws the reader into an imaginative state, prompting them to consider the role the poet's mother plays in his life, as answered in line 5. The question also makes the readers appreciate mothers in general for their role in building up the home.

6.3.1.10 Use of Euphemism (Nkwuma)

Euphemism is a literary device used to express an unpleasant situation, idea or thing mildly and politely (Pan, 2013, p. 2107). It is a way of speaking of unpleasant things in favourable terms. In Igbo society, issues relating to death, poison, sex, and other sensitive issues are not spoken in clear terms but in euphemistic terms (Emenanjo, 1983, p. 14). The formation of euphemism, as seen in written Igbo poetry, has its roots in neologisms. Fortunately, the neologistic terms used to express euphemism in written Igbo poetry are often understood by readers who apply associative semantic or pragmatic interpretation to decode them. To this end, euphemism in written Igbo poetry serves communicative and aesthetic functions.

In addressing or speaking of unpleasant things in their poems, modern Igbo poets employ euphemistic terms in a way that waters down the sensitivity of such things or issues. This feature is observed in some poems written in the second and third decades under study. On the other hand, among the poems written in the first decade, only T. Ubesie uses erotic terms in his poem. As earlier stated, in referring to private parts of the human body, the Igbo express them in euphemistic terms instead of saying them as they are. The reason for this is that the Igbo society is a decent society in which individuals are expected to be decent not only in their appearance but also in their speech. However, due to the poetic licence enjoyed by literary writers, some literary writers prefer not to censor some expressions in their works by describing sensitive issues like parts of the human body and sex the way they appear very erotic. This is not peculiar to the poetic genre; it occurs in Igbo novels as well. Onyekaonwu (1986, p. 416) reports that the novelist, P. Munonye, is well-known for his use of erotic language. In written Igbo poetry, while some modern Igbo poets substitute erotic terms for euphemistic ones, T. Ubesie uses erotic terms and expressions in his works. It is not clear why Ubesie prefers the use of erotic terms in his works in places where euphemistic terms can still serve the same purpose. For instance, in Ubesie's poem "Ndu Nwaanyi" (Life of women) (Poem 138) in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 37-40), the poet throws caution to the wind in his continuous use of erotic terms and expressions in the fourth, sixth, and twelfth stanzas. In the fourth stanza, the poet says:

<u>Ara abuo</u> p̄ta ya n'obi	(Two breasts grow in her chest
O sie ike njide	It becomes hard to hold
Uche ya na-agwa ya	Her mind will be telling her
Na ya etozuola	That she is full-grown
Na ya eruola ihe e ji nwaanyi eme	That she is a mature lady
Wee na-eme n'ụwa	And doing in the world)
(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 38)	

Tony Ubesie’s use of erotic terms in line 1, where he says “Ara abụọ pụta ya n’obi” (Two breasts grow in her chest), is quite erotic. To buttress this point, in the sixth stanza of the same poem “Ndu Nwaanyi”, the poet uses the same erotic term, but this time speaks of it impolitely. In the sixth and the twelfth stanza (poem 138), the poet says:

Nwata nwa agboghọ na-aga ije	(When a lady walks
Ya di ya n’uche	She should bear in mind
<u>N’ara kwu oto, ruo n’ikpeazu</u>	That a breast that stands till the end
O ga-emecha daa	It will later fall
Ya jiri ugbo a na-elepu anya	Let her begin to be on the lookout
Ka ndu ya ga-adị	How her life will be)
(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, p. 39)	

There is no doubt in the fact that Ubesie’s use of the erotic term “Ara” (breast) in stanza six above is used in a literary didactic sense; it should still be noted that a euphemistic portrayal of the same concept would have served the same purpose. Again, the tone of the poet in that stanza reveals the poet’s patriarchal mentality. This is the same thing that plays out in the twelfth stanza, as shown above, where the poet uses the same erotic terms and belittles the female gender.

O biri na-aza nne nwe ulo	(She lives and answers to her mother, who owns
the	home.
Uwe eju ya afọ	She is contented with this world
O wee hu na <u>ara kwu oto</u>	And she sees that the breast that is standing
Emechaala daa.	Have fallen
O cheta ndu ya n’agboghọ	She remembers her life in her young age.)
(Ubesie in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975, pp. 39-40)	

On the flip side, many modern Igbo poets demonstrate their respect for Igbo culture by addressing sensitive issues in their poems, using euphemistic terms. For instance, while Ubesie uses erotic terms to express the sensitive parts of the female body, Obierozie uses euphemistic terms to refer to the same sensitive parts of the female body. In the first stanza of A.K. Obierozie’s poem “Ncheta oge agboghobia

m” (Remembering my youthful days) (Poem 139) in *Ekpe Nna* (1986, pp. 21-22), the poet says:

A dī m afọ iri na atọ	(I am thirteen years old
<u>Ero pue m n’obi</u>	Mushrooms grew on my chest
Orụ daara ndị mụrụ m	The responsibility that faced my parents
Abughị ọkụ igba agada nya	Is not an easy one)
(Obierozie, 1986, p. 21)	

Unlike Ubesie, who does not censor his mention of the sensitive part of the female body, Obierozie does by referring to the female breast in euphemistic terms, as seen in line 2 of poem 139. The use of “Ero” in “Ero pue m n’obi” (mushrooms grew on my chest) refers to the breasts of a lady. It is a euphemistic coding of the term that makes it sound pleasant to the ear. Its use in this context is not offensive to the reader, who can also see it as erotic. In a similar vein, Chukuezi employs euphemism in the fourth stanza of his poem “Nsogbu nwaanyi” (Women problems), when he writes:

<u>Ahụ kwurū nwoke ọtọ</u>	(When a man’s body stands up
Nwaanyi aburū ohu ya	The woman becomes his slave
O cheta na ọ bụ ego ka e ji lụọ ya	He remembers that she was married with money.)
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 73)	

Here, euphemism expression is employed to avoid the use of erotic expressions. The poet here clearly shows that he considers his readers' moral sensibility, hence the euphemistic coding of erotic expression. The expression “Ahụ kwurū nwoke ọtọ” in line 1 above is a euphemistic way of saying “when the man’s penis stands up”. Since this expression is entirely unacceptable in the Igbo socio-cultural setting, the poet censors it by expressing it euphemistically. In the first stanza of the poem, “Onwụ Di” (Death of husband) (Poem 141) in *Ije Uwa* (2003, p. 48), N. Okediadi expresses death in euphemistic terms, when she writes:

...Di bi n’ụlọ <u>ebulala akwukwo</u>	(The husband at home has sent home the book
Ụla akwadoghi akwado	An unprepared return
<u>Nwaanyi na umu nnadi ehurula</u>	The woman is at the disposal of kinsmen.)
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 48)	

Uzochukwu (2001, p. 98) rightly asserts that in the Igbo society, death is often spoken of in euphemistic terms. This assertion is borne out by the excerpt above, where the poet (Okediadi) spoke of death in euphemistic terms. By speaking of death euphemistically, the poet makes the unpleasant phenomenon seem less jarring. By focusing on the pains of losing a husband, poem 141 evokes a feeling of sorrow and pain. Again, there is also a euphemistic use of language in line 3 in the above excerpt from poem 141, where the poet says “Nwaanyị na ụmụ nnadi ehurula” (The woman is at the disposal of kinsmen). The use of euphemism here is another way of saying that the wife of the deceased is at the mercy of the man’s kinsmen. Furthermore, C.C. Anozie also employs euphemism in referring to the female breast and buttocks when he satirizes young people in the fifth stanza of his poem “Ọrịa Mmịnwụ” (Poem 112), where he writes,

Agboghọ yibenu mini	(Spinsters continue wearing mini skirt
Okoro sogharibenu ha ka ijiji na-eso ogiri	Bachelors keep following them like a house fly that follows <i>ogiri</i>
Nwunye ụkwụ n’ezi	Wife with two legs outside
Ndị di ledonu	Husbands keep watch
Adazienu na adaziani anya	On their Up and down
Ọnụ m ghere oghe	My mouth is open)
(Anozie, 2005, p. 74)	

Here, the use of “Adazienu” and “adaziani” refers to breast and buttocks. The euphemistic coding of these two sensitive terms shows that euphemism is a cultural phenomenon in Igbo. “Adazienu” and “adaziani” are both neologisms that have euphemistic implications and, as such, serve both communicative and aesthetic functions in the poem.

6.3.1.11 Use of Apostrophe (Nkwusara)

Abrams and Harpham (2012) define apostrophe as a figure of speech that addresses an abstract entity or explicitly addresses an absent person. An apostrophe arises in literature when the writer stops addressing the reader and directs his or her attention or writing to an absent third party (Sayakhan, 2016). In most cases, the addressee is always a personified inanimate object, an abstract quality, or even a dead person (Sayakhan, 2016). Modern Igbo poets use an apostrophe to create a special effect in the poem. By personifying abstract or inanimate things and addressing them directly in the poem, modern Igbo poets make the reader experience the poem in their own way. The reason they do this is summed up in the view of Sayakhan (2016), who asserts that the use of apostrophe encourages (motivates) the reader to develop his or her own point of view that is clear, fresh, and also creative.

The apostrophe is one of the devices that feature in Igbo poetry, adding aesthetic value to the works of modern Igbo poets. As can be seen in the examples from extant texts used here, the use of the apostrophe in Igbo poetry is marked by the second-person singular pronouns “I”, “I”, “Gi”, “ngi” (you). In the poem “Ogbuniigwe”, in *Utara Nti* (p. 39), Madubuike used apostrophe to bring the reader into an imaginative experience of the Nigerian civil war. He did this by using apostrophes in the poem. It is important to note that the entire poem is apostrophic in nature. However, the apostrophe is more apparent in the second stanza, where the poet addresses an inanimate object (bomb) as if he is speaking to a living being (Poem 3).

I bu egbe mmiri	(You are thunder.
I si n'ikuku eje	You move in the wind
I na-awa ala na-awa oha	You make a path in the ground and in the bush.
I maghi enyi nke i ji ama onye iro	You do not know friend or foe.)

(Madubuike in Emenanjo (ed.) Nd., p. 39)

A look at the above stanza shows that the poet is addressing an inanimate object. The use of the second person singular pronoun “I” or “I” as seen in the beginning of each of the above lines shows that the poet diverts the attention from the reader to a personified inanimate object, “bomb,” which has no life. A reader who comes across this stanza can readily interpret what or whom the “I” refers to in the poem. A more vivid use of apostrophe as a literary device is found in the first stanza of A.B. Chukuezi’s poem, “Ala” (Earth) (Poem 142) in *Akọ bụ Ndu* (pp. 21-22), where the poet addresses the earth as if it is human, by saying:

Ala	(Earth
Gee ntị	Listen
Gee ntị	Listen
Odozi obodo! Nne nwe ụwa!	Town organiser! Mother who owns the world!
Ọ bụ maka gị ka anyị ji eru uju	You are the reason we mourn
Gee anyị ntị	Listen to us
Anyị ga-anọ n’elu gị anwụ...	We are going to die on you...)
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 21)	

A reader who reads this stanza will be amazed at the way apostrophe is deployed in making creative imagery possible. The reader understands that the poet is not addressing him or her but another abstract entity. In the above stanza, the poet seems to be addressing the “earth” directly as if it were a human being that has ears. Special attention is drawn to the repetition in lines 2, 3, and 6, where the poet keeps calling the attention of the personified “Ala” to listen to what he is about to say. The use of an apostrophe here clearly demonstrates that the poet expects the reader to experience and interpret the poem in their own way, drawing on their personal experience of Igbo cultural beliefs. In the poem “Oku Latiriki” (Electricity) (Poem 143) by N. Okediadi in *Ije Uwa*, the poet makes use of an apostrophe while introducing the subject of the poem to the reader. In the first stanza, the poet writes:

Ihe aka mere!	(A man-made thing
I na-enye ihe	You give light

Ma na-eme ka ndụ dị uto
 Mmiri oyi atujuola akpịrị ikpōnku
 Ulo dum juru oyi bu gi.
 (Okediadi, 2003, p. 15)

And also make life sweet
 Cold water has relieved the dry throat
 The whole house is cool if you.

In this stanza, “electricity” is addressed as something that can be seen. The use of the apostrophe here is predicated on the poet’s use of the second-person singular pronoun “I” in the second line and “gi” in the fifth line in addressing the subject of the poem, which has no life. Using an apostrophic device to introduce the poem in this manner makes the reader think of all the possible benefits that are derived from the use of electricity. These benefits are relative as they vary from one reader to another based on their personal life experiences.

Based on our discussion so far on the use of apostrophe by modern Igbo poets, it may seem that the use of apostrophe in written Igbo poetry is restricted to only the first stanzas. The modern Igbo poet brings in this device at any stanza in the poem where he or she (the poet) feels it will better serve the purpose. For instance, in H. Nwamah’s poem “Ahūike” (Health) (Poem 144) in *Akōnauche* (2006, p. 70), apostrophe features in the second stanza, where the poet writes:

Ahūike ndewo!	(Good health, well done!
Chi kere gi birikwa	The God that creates you should keep living
Kwe ka m jide gi,	Let me hold you,
Ka oriri na-aga werewere	So that feasting will be smooth
Njem aburu awaraawara	The journey becomes smooth
Ahūike nonyere m...	Good health, abide with me...)
(Nwamah in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 70)	

The poet here (Poem 144) is addressing an abstract entity “Ahūike” (good health) that cannot be seen or heard. In the first line, for instance, the poet salutes good health as if it were a person that she can see. Again, the use of the second person singular pronoun is also used here to refer to the abstract entity. A reader that comes across this stanza can interpret who the “gi” in lines 2-3 stands for. The use of

apostrophes in the above stanza makes the poem more real, and the reader can easily relate to the lines and give them their own interpretation.

6.3.1.12 Use of Proverbs (Ilu)

Proverbs are described as short, pithy statements that are generally accepted as truth about people's lives. Though proverbs belong to the oral repertoire of the Igbo, modern Igbo poets use them to embellish their works. In Igbo written poetry, proverbs serve didactic functions and promote thought in the poem. They are also employed to make the poem aesthetically pleasing to the reader. There are numerous instances of proverbs in written Igbo poetry; only a few will be cited here. In the poem "Onye Ije" (Traveller) (Poem 145) by Chukwudile, in *Utara Nti* (pp. 22-23), the poet employs a proverb in the sixth stanza, where he writes:

<u>Onye nwee ndidi</u>	(He that is patient
<u>O rie azu ukpoo</u>	Eats fish killed with a fishing hook
Onye nwaa n'aka nri	He that tries in the right hand
Ya nwaa n'aka ekpe	Let him try in the left hand)
(Chukwudile in Emenanjo (ed.), Nd., p. 23)	

The use of a proverb, here (Poem 145), as evident in lines 1-2, heightens thought. Since the poem is a didactic poem, the role of the proverb in the verse above is in concordance with the intention of the poet to teach morals. The proverb in lines 1-2 emphasizes the need for people to cultivate patience as a virtue as they journey through life. In the poem "Okukọ na ụmụ ya" (Hen and her chicks) (Poem 146) by Chukuezi in *Ako bu Ndu* (1988, pp. 74-75), the poet employs a proverb for didactic purposes in the third stanza, when he writes:

...Ma unu ga-akpachara anya mgbe niile	(But you people should be careful at all times
N'ihina onye e bu ebu	Because the one who is carried
Na-echefukari na ụzọ di anya	Usually forgets that the journey is far
Elelikwala nwa ogbenye	Do not look down on the poor

Maka na ọ buru na ọ bu ya nwe gi
Ọ ga-elekota gi ka ehi
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 75)

Because if he is your master
He will take care of you like a cow.)

In the above stanza, the italicised proverb in lines 2-3 adds extra didactic thought to the already didactic verse. The use of the proverb in that context suits the purpose and theme of the poem. It is also important to state that apart from adding didactic effect to the stanza, the proverb and how it is used add to the overall aesthetic value of the poem, showing the poet as a master of language. Furthermore, in his poem “Ekpere” (Prayer) (Poem 147) in E Chezola, C. Ofomata employs a proverb to stimulate thought. In the fifth stanza of the poem, the poet writes:

...Ọ buru na e jidesie gi ike
A na-eji okpa agbawa onu uzo
N’ihi na *nwatakiri cheta*
Na nna ya no n’ogbo
O gbara aka ria elu...

(If someone holds you tight
The door is broken with a leg
Because a child that remembers
That his father is on the stage
He climbs the tree with bare
hands.)

(Ofomata, 2001, p. 3)

The use of proverbs here reemphasises the importance of prayer. The poet employs a proverb here to teach the reader that there is so much to gain when a person prays. In the poem “A sokata eze anya” (Poem 148) by N. Anarado in *Akonnauche* (2006, pp. 27-28), the poet uses a proverb to stimulate thought when in the fifth stanza she writes:

Onye kwuo eziokwu
A si si kputa ya ka e gbuo

(If one speaks the truth
It will be demanded that S/he be brought
to be killed.

Maka na nwata zoba onwe ya

Because when a child starts to defend
himself.

O buru ajo mmadu

He becomes a bad person.)

(Anarado in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 27)

Here, the proverb used in lines 3-4 serves didactic functions. It is used to promote the thought that the world hates the truth, and whoever wants to succeed

should not mind what the opinion of people about him is, provided the person is on the path of truth.

6.3.2 Sound Devices

Sound devices, here, refer to various elements employed by modern Igbo poets to enhance sound effects in their poems. The devices examined in this section constitute sound that promotes imagery in written Igbo poetry. In oral Igbo poetry, devices like word play, repetition, and idiophones constitute sound devices (see Uzochukwu, 2001:105). In Igbo written poetry, devices that promote sound effects include idiophones and repetition.

6.3.2.1 Use of Ideophone (Uduokwu)

Ideophone is a phonetic and linguistic term used to refer to a visual representation of an idea in sound, achieved through onomatopoeia (Crystal, 1997, cited in Badomo, 2006, p. 204). From this definition, it becomes clear that onomatopoeia is a subclass of ideophones. Uzochukwu (2001, p. 107) opines that in many African Languages, ideophones also “include onomatopoeia, in that idea-in-sound is always implied.” It is important to note that not all ideophones imitate sounds as they appear in real life; hence, the pragmatic classification of ideophones in African Languages.

This assertion makes it necessary to understand that the classification of ideophones as they appear in literature falls under the purview of pragmatics because of their pragmatic functions. It is also worthy of note that ideophones cannot be syntactically or semantically classified because, syntactically, ideophones in African languages cannot be modified as “they do not enter into phrase structure constructions

with other words like adjectives to form compound words and phrases (Bodomo, 2006, p. 204). Semantically, ideophones lack hyponyms, such as animals (dog, goat, cattle, rats), and, as such, make their semantic characterisation difficult (Bodomo, 2006). To this end, based on their pragmatic functions, ideophones can be classified into two types: onomatopoeic and phonaesthetic ideophones. Both onomatopoeic and phonaesthetic ideophones feature in written Igbo poetry. In Igbo poetry, ideophones add special sound effects to its aesthetics.

6.3.2.1.1 Onomatopoeic Ideophone (Uduokwu ụda)

Ideophones that imitate sounds as we know them in real life, such as the barking of a dog, drops of rain, and other sounds, are known as onomatopoeic ideophones. Modern Igbo poets also use onomatopoeic ideophones to describe and promote imagery in their works. In the poem “Nganga na Mpako” (Laziness and Pride) (Poem 149) by J. Onwuchekwa in *Akpaala Okwu* (1983, pp. 30-31), an onomatopoeic ideophone is employed for descriptive and imaginative purposes. In the seventh stanza of the poem, it is said that:

...Mpako buru ụzọ,	(Pride goes first
Nganga sowe ya	Pompositivity follows
Ọdịda ya bụ <u>gbim</u>	Its fall is <i>gbim</i> !
Nghọta adighị ọzọ	No more understanding)
(Onwuchekwa, 1983, p. 31)	

Here, the underlined word “gbim” in “Ọdịda ya bụ *gbim*”, line 3, is an imitation of the sound heard when a heavy object falls to the ground. Therefore, it is onomatopoeic. Its use in the stanza serves a descriptive purpose as it gives the reader a mental picture of the shameful or colossal fall of a proud person from the ivory tower of his ego. Another use of onomatopoeic ideophone in written Igbo poetry is

seen in the poem, “Udummiri” (Rainy season) (Poem 150) by A.K. Obieroze in *Ekpe Nna* (1986, p. 20), where the poet, in describing the sound of the rain, writes:

<u>Pata pata pata pata</u>	(<i>Pata pata pata pata</i>
Ka o na-ada na-abia	It sounds as it approaches
Umụ anumanụ kelewenụ chi	Animals thank God
Nụọ mmiri ndụ chi kutere	Drink the water of life God fetches)
(Obieroze, 1986, p. 20)	

The underlined words, *Pata pata pata pata*, in line 1, are an actual imitation of the sound of the rain as it drops on the ground. Therefore, it is onomatopoeic. The use of *Pata pata pata pata* in the above stanza reminds the reader of the sounds of rain when it comes. By imitating the sound of rain in the above stanza, the image of the sound of the rain (both on rooftops and the ground) comes to mind. In the third stanza of “Ekwentị” (Telephone) (Poem 77), the poet describes the sound of the telephone, an indication of an onomatopoeic ideophone. In the third stanza of the poem, the poet says:

<u>Tirim, tirim, tirim</u>	(<i>Tirim, tirim, tirim</i>
Mara na ozi abatala	Know that a message has entered
Onye nwe m ebulie m elu mado m na ntị	My owner picks me up and places me on the ear
Heloo, heloo a na-ada	Hello Hello will be sounding)
(Anozie, 2005, p. 68)	

In this stanza also, the underlined words, *Tirim, tirim, tirim*, in line 1, are an actual imitation of the soundtrack of a telephone when it rings. This is why the words are considered onomatopoeic. Apart from its aesthetic value in the stanza, the onomatopoeic ideophone conjures the image of a ringing telephone, thereby promoting imagery in the poem and helping the reader connect with it. G.I. Nwaozuzu in her poem “Ebewu Naijiria” (Which way Nigeria) (Poem 151) in *Akọnauche* (2006, pp. 85-88) describes the sound of a gun in the seventh stanza of the poem, where she writes:

Naijirĩa	(Nigeria
Nara ji rie	Take yam and eat
Obi amapuna gi	Do not be afraid
A gbaa <u>kpowam</u> !	Any shot <i>kpowam</i>
Umụ gi ka a gbaturu...	It is your children who were shot down.

(Nwaozuzu, 2006, p. 87)

In the above excerpt, the underlined word *kpowam* in “A gbaa kpowam” imitates the sound of a gunshot, hence its onomatopoeic quiddity. The imitation of the actual sound of a gun in the above excerpt helps the poet create, in the mind, an image of destruction and, in doing so, evoke feelings of sorrow and fear.

6.3.2.1.2 Phonaesthetic Ideophones (Uduokwu Myiriūda)

Ideophones that do not imitate sounds as they appear in real life but convey their meaning through their sounds are known as phonaesthetic ideophones (Babalola, 1974, p. 23, cited in Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 107). Modern Igbo poets employ phonaesthetic ideophones to create imagery of the poem's subject in the reader's mind. In Igbo written poetry, phonaesthetic ideophones serve descriptive functions. It helps both the poet and the reader arrive at a place of imaginative convergence, where the poet's mind is opened to the reader by making the reader see through the poet's eyes. Let us instantiate this claim by looking at a stanza from the poem “Adamma” (Poem 152) by C.W.O. Ajaegbu in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 19-20), where the poet writes:

Imi ya dī <u>warara</u>	(Her nose <i>warara</i> (pointed))
Anya ya na-eke <u>riřiri</u>	Her eyes <i>riřiri</i> (bright)
Eze ya na-enwu dī ka <u>ogwa</u>	Her teeth shines like <i>ogwa</i>
Mkpīsi aka ya dī <u>sam</u>	Her fingers are <i>sam</i> (straight or smooth))

(Ajaegbu in Ekechukw (ed.), 1975, p. 19)

Here, the type of ideophones used is phonaesthetic. This is because the words “Warara” in line 1, “riřiri” in line 2, and “sam” in line 4 are not imitating any sound per se; instead, they are ideas represented in sound. The meaning of the sounds cannot

be syntactically or semantically interpreted; its interpretation in the reader's mind instead lies in its pragmatic sense. This is why translations of phonaesthetic terms will vary from one reader to another, depending on the reader's life experiences. "Warara" is used to describe anything narrow, and this is the sense it suggests in the above stanza. "Ririṛi" as used in line two means "bright", that is to say that the eyes of the person, "Adamma", glitter. "Sam" as used in the above stanza can mean "straight" or "smooth". It is important to state that other phonaesthetic-ideophonic terms can still be used in place of the ones used in the above stanza, and they will still convey the same meaning. For instance, in line 2, where the poet says "Anya ya na-eke *riṛiṛi*", the term *riṛiṛi* can be replaced with "zazaza". This is why the classification of ideophones in written Igbo poetry is based on its contextual pragmatic functions. Again, the import of these ideophonic words in the above stanza performs descriptive functions as they are all used in describing the beauty of a lady. Each of the phonaesthetic-ideophonic words contributes to the mental imagery that the poet now shares with the reader.

Let us consider another example of the use of phonaesthetic ideophone in written Igbo poetry by looking at an excerpt from one of Chukuezi's poems, "Ikuku" (Wind) (Poem 153), in *Akọ bụ Ndu* (1988, p. 16), where the poet writes:

Ọ bụ ya ji ndụ	(It holds life
Ọ na-eme ahụ <u>juu</u> mgbe oke anwụ na-acha	It cools the body when the sun is scorching.
Nwayọọ ka o ji agafe ka onye ori	It gently passes as a thief.
Anyahughị ya	Eyes do not see it
Aka ejideghinwu ya	Hands could not catch it)
(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 16)	

Here (poem 153), the phonaesthetic ideophone "juu" used in line 2, where the poet says "Ọ na-eme ahụ juu mgbe oke anwụ na-acha" (It cools the body when the sun is scorching), serves a descriptive purpose as it contributes to the imagery created

in that line. The ideophone is phonaesthetic because “jụjụ” as used there represents “cool (ness)” which does not have any sound in real life. However, in a bid to describe the feeling that arises from the blowing wind in the scorching sun, “jụjụ”, which to the Igbo represents a state of being or feeling cool, serves that descriptive purpose, hence its use in the poem.

Furthermore, in C.C. Anozie’s poem “Akpati Ozu” (Casket) (Poem 154) in *Uche bu Akpa* (2005:118-119), the poet employs phonaesthetic ideophone as a descriptive device, where he writes:

Akwa ọcha na-enwụ <u>zaa</u>	(White cloth that is very bright
Okooko na-acha <u>ritoo</u>	Flower shines as ripped
Azụ friji dị n’ime ya	Ice fish is inside it
Kpọọ nkụ	Is dry
Eji <u>kpii</u>	Very dark

(Anozie, 2005, p. 118)

In the above stanza (poem 154), the use of phonaesthetic ideophone serves a descriptive purpose as it is used to describe a casket displayed, perhaps during a funeral ceremony. Its use in the poem enhances the poem's aesthetic appeal. The image it creates in the reader's mind makes the poem real, thereby evoking emotions. The sound devices “zaa” in line 1, “ritoo” in line 2, and “kpii” in line 5 intensify emotion in the poem. These words are not used to imitate any sound, as the objects they are used to qualify in the stanza do not have any sound. However, the words convey a lot of pragmatic sense. “Zaa”, for instance, connotes brightness. “ritoo” connotes deeply ripped, while “Kpii” is used to refer to utmost darkness or deep black. These are also the interpretations they bring to the poem. When the poet says “Eji kpii” in line 5, he is simply saying that the corpse inside the casket looks very dark.

In the last stanza of the poem “Akwa Nkwụ” (Tears of Palm wine) (Poem 155) in *Abụ Uto* (2015, pp. 36-38) by N. R. Ezejesi, the poet uses the phonaesthetic

ideophone “Tokomtokom” to describe the beat of the throat when a person salivates, when he writes:

Akwa nzuzo gi	(Your secret cry
Aputala ihè	Is in the open
Puta jee wuoro gi ulo	Come out and build a house
Ndi chorọ gi di uba	Many seek you
Akpiri ha na-atu	They salivate
Tokomtokom	<i>Tokomtokom</i>
N’ihi na akwa di uto	Because tears is sweet)

(Ezejesi, 2015, pp. 37-38)

“Tokomtokom,” as used here, is a phonaesthetic ideophone that connotes salivating movement or tickling of the throat when a person salivates for anything that pleases him or her. Its import in this excerpt is to describe how a person longs for a taste of good palm wine. Having shown instances of the use of phonaesthetic ideophones in written Igbo poetry, let us look at the use of onomatopoeic ideophones in written Igbo poetry.

6.3.2.2 Use of Repetition (Kwunkwukwa)

The term ‘repetition’ has many meanings in different fields of learning. In literature, repetition involves the repetition of sounds, words, clauses, or certain expressions in particular succession with a view to providing emphasis (Manjavidze, 2013). Apart from aiding rhythm in poetry, repetition also enhances sound effects in the poem (Uzochukwu, 2001). Manjavidze (2013) argues that repetition conveys the logical emphasis needed to draw the reader’s attention to a key word or phrase in the text. In written Igbo poetry, repetition is used to foreground an idea or motif in a way that forces the reader’s attention to the importance of the term, idea, or motif. Uzochukwu (2001) opines that two types of repetition exist in oral Igbo poetry: immediate and intermittent repetitions—these two types of repetition feature in written Igbo poetry. There are more instances of intermittent repetition in written Igbo

poetry than immediate repetition. We shall examine these two types of repetitions in relation to how they feature in written Igbo poetry.

6.3.2.2.1 Immediate Repetition (Kwunkwukwa anaghị oke)

Unlike intermittent repetition, in immediate repetition, the repeated lines (utterances) follow one another consecutively (Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 110), with no other line intervening. There are several instances of immediate repetition in written Igbo poetry, but the use of immediate repetition is not as common among modern Igbo poets as the intermittent repetition. Modern Igbo poets use immediate repetition for emphatic reasons. In the poem “Abụ”, poem 68, there is immediate repetition in the third stanza as seen below:

Edebeghị m abụ ahụ	(I have not written it
Abu ahụ ga-edogharị ụwa	The poem that will transform the world
A GA-EDE YA	IT WILL BE WRITTEN
A GA-EDE YA	IT WILL BE WRITTEN
A GA-EDE YA	IT WILL BE WRITTEN
N’ihi ntugharị ga-adi.rịrị	Because there must be a change)
(Madubuike in Emenanjo (ed.), Nd., p. 44)	

Looking at the repetition in lines 3-5 in the above stanza from poem 62, it becomes evident that the use of immediate repetition is deliberate and is written to draw the attention of the reader. Again, repeating “A GA-EDE YA” (IT WILL BE WRITTEN) in upper case says so much about the intention of the poet. By writing the line in upper case, the poet intends to draw or force the attention of the reader to the point made in the repeated lines, which hammers on the fact that the best of Igbo poetry is yet to come, hence calling on the readers, perhaps, to become writers in a bid to promote written Igbo poetry. The repeated lines follow one another immediately, with no intervening line, indicating emphasis. In the same vein, there is immediate

repetition of an idea in the second stanza of the poem “Ogbenye” (The Poor) (Poem 156) by A.B. Chukuezi in *Ako bu Ndu* (1988, pp. 23-24), where the poet writes:

Onwu na-eji ike egbu ogbenye, Ndi ka m azogbughi m	(Death kills the poor speedily, If those stronger than me do kill me by stampede
Ugbo ala egburu m togbo Ogbenye ajoka	A car kills me Poverty is bad
<u>Onye na nke ya</u>	Everyman for himself
<u>Onye na nke ya</u>	Everyman for himself
<u>Onye na nke ya</u> , e chezoog ogbenye (forgotten)	Everyman for himself, the poor is

(Chukuezi, 1988, p. 24)

Here, the repeated lines (idea), “Onye na nke ya” (Everyman for himself), in lines five, are repeated in lines 6 -7 for emphasis. By repeating the line, the reader's attention is drawn to its import, which focuses on satirising the capitalist nature of modern Igbo society. In the traditional Igbo society, a communist ideology is largely promoted, in which the rich person in every family is expected to assist their siblings and other family members in growing. This is why the term “Ogbenye” used for the poor interprets as “Ogbe ga-enye” while “Ogaranya” for the rich interprets as “O gaara gi, nye”. With this ideology, people helped each other, and an individual's success meant success for every family member. Unfortunately, this is no longer the case, and the poor have continued to wallow and die in their poverty. This philosophy is foregrounded by the poet (Chukuezi) in the poem, through immediate repetition. As seen in the above excerpt, there is no line break between the repeated lines.

In the poem, “Suturajiki” (Abubuoru) (Strike) (Poem 157) in N. Okediadi's *Ije Uwa* (2003, pp. 56-57), the poet employs immediate repetition in re-emphasising her displeasure to the incessant strike actions by various trade and professional unions in Nigeria. Having highlighted the various socio-economic, and socio-cultural challenges arising from strike actions in Nigeria, in her third stanza, the poet asks:

Olee mgbe i ga-ebi	(When will you end
--------------------	--------------------

O mere ndi okenye oke n'ezi,	It makes the elderly to be rats
ngwere n'ulo	outside
Ndi penshionu ufodu anwuola maka gi	Lizards in the house
	Some pensioners have died because
	of you
Ndi oru aghasara n'ulo	Workers stay at home
<u>Olee mgbe i ga-ebi?</u>	When will you end?
<u>Olee mgbe i ga-ebi?</u>	When will you end?)
(Okediadi, 2003, p. 57)	

The immediate repetition of “Olee mgbe i ga-ebi” (When will you end) draws the attention of the reader to the mind of the poet, which is captured in the repeated lines. The repeated lines follow one another without any intervening line, indicating the seriousness of the questions. The repetition here is used for emphasis. In the poem, “Iheanacho” (What is sought after) (Poem 158), by D. Epuchie in *Akponauche* (pp.76-77), there is immediate repetition in the second stanza, where the poet writes:

Iheanacho	(What-is-sought
<u>Onye ma ebe i di?</u>	Who knows where you are?
<u>Onye ma ebe i di?</u>	Who knows where you are?
Ogaranaya na-achọ gi?	The rich search for you
Ogbenye na-achọ gi...	The poor search for you.)
(Epuchie in Nwadike (ed.), 2006, p. 76)	

Here, the repetition of lines 2-3 “Onye ma ebe i di?” (Who knows where you are) is immediate. There is no line coming between the repeated idea in line 2 and the succeeding repeated line 3. The repetition serves an emphatic purpose in the poem.

6.3.2.2.2 Intermittent Repetition (Kwunkwukwa nara oke)

In this type of repetition, the repeated line(s) are separated from the other by an unspecified number of lines (Uzochukwu, 2001, p. 111). This is the most common form of repetition in written Igbo poetry. Let us draw our first example of an intermittent repetition in written Igbo poetry from the second stanza of the poem “Ijiji” (Housefly) (Poem 159) by K. Amasike in *Akpa Uche* (1975, pp. 10-11), where the poet writes:

Mpi gi di ka ube e ji alu agha	(Your horn is like the spare used in battle
I miri mmiri ojoo,	You suck bad water,
<u>I misa ya n'elu nri mmadu ga-eri</u>	You place it on top of the food that humans will eat
I miri nsi,	You suck feaces
<u>I misa ya n'elu nri mmadu ga-eri</u>	You place it on top of the food that humans will eat
Ihe obula joro njo i butere	Any bad thing you carry
I busa ya mmadu	You spit it on humans)
(Amasike in Ekechukwu (ed.), 1975. p. 11)	

Here, the intermittent repetition reiterates the theme of satire on the housefly as a source of germ dissemination. The repeated line here is separated just by a line (line 4). By repeating “*I misa ya n'elu nri mmadu ga-eri*” (You place it on top of the food that humans will eat) intermittently in lines 3 and 5, the poet emphasizes the dangers of having a housefly around the home or around edible things and the need to maintain a clean environment that will not allow the housefly to thrive. In the poem “*N’ote aka*” (From a distance) (Poem 160), by L.C. Okoro in *Omenka* (2002, p. 20), the last two lines of the three verses in the poem are repeated intermittently. Let us instantiate this point with the second and third stanzas from the poem, where the poet writes:

N’ote aka ka a no nye ya	(He was given it from a distance
Bu ihe nwata ji loo uwa	What a child reincarnated with
Ma o bughị ibu ogbenye	If not to become poor
O buru ibu ogaranya	It will be to become rich
O bughị inwu ka oghanje	If not to die like the <i>ogbanje</i> spirit
O buru ibi ogologo ndu	It will be to live long
Ma nke o bula o bu	But no matter what it is
<u>O dighi nnapu</u>	It cannot be taken away
<u>O dighi nhicha</u>	It cannot be cleaned)

Lee ya bu nwata anya n’ihu	(Look at face of that child
Lee anya n’obo aka ya	Look at his palm
Nwata ga-abu eze	A child who will be king
Malitere ichi eze	Begins his reign
Ubochi mbu izu fere nne ya	The first day his mother missed her period
Ihe onye bu, ya kelee chi ya	Whatsoever a person becomes, he should thank his chi
Maka n’ote aka ka e dere ya	Because it was written long ago

O dighi nnapu

O dighi nhicha

(Ikwubuzo, et.al., 1992, p. 20)

It cannot be taken away

It cannot be cleaned.)

In the two stanzas above, the last two lines were repeated intermittently for emphasis. As discussed in the fourth chapter, the poem focuses on the fatality of human destiny. By foregrounding these two lines in an intermittent, repetitive manner, the poet draws the reader's attention to the key phrase that summarises the poem's message: destiny cannot be changed or taken away. It can also be seen in the above excerpt (poem 37) that the repeated lines were separated from each other by six other lines.

There are many instances of intermittent repetition in N. Okediadi's *Ije Uwa*, which is an indication of the poet's stylistic manner of writing. For instance, in the poem "Ire" (Poem 109), out of the six stanzas in the poem, five of them start with the word "Ire" (tongue) as line. Let us only look at the first and second stanzas of the poem, where the poet says:

Ire!

Mma agha nke anụ ahụ

E bepụ, ogbu adaa.

A hapụ, o kwuru

Mma na njọ bilie

(Tongue

The sword of the flesh

When cut off, dumbness sets in

When left, it speaks

Good and bad as it goes

Ire!

I na-agozi ngozi

I na-ekpe ikpe

I na-enye mmadụ

Nsi nke ime obi

Tongue

You bless

You satirise

You give human

Poison of the mind)

(Okediadi, 2003, p. 4)

The repetition of "Ire" in the two stanzas above and in the other stanzas of the poem is used to re-emphasise the motif of the poem so much so that its import and functions become very clear to the reader. The repeated lines are separated by four other lines. Again, the two verses that make up Okediadi's poem "Politikisi" start with the word "Politikisi" as a line. Furthermore, there are many instances of the use

of intermittent repetition in *Akọnauche* (2006). For instance, all the stanzas in the poem “Ibe mata m” (Relatives know me) (Poem 161) by H. Oleru in *Akọnauche* (p. 21), start with the same line “Metu mara ibe bu aha m” (Touch and know relations is my name). Eight out of the nine stanzas in the poem “Asila m na o di mma” (Do not tell me it is good) (Poem 162) in *Akọnauche* (pp. 53-55) start with “Asila m na o di mma” (Do not tell me that it is good). In the poem “Ugo” (Eagle) (Poem 163), by I.U. Nwadike in *Akọnauche*, the first line *Ugo*, is repeated in all the stanzas intermittently. All the lines started with the word “Ugo”. Let us look at just the first and second of five stanzas that have intermittent repetition, where the poet writes:

<u>Ugo,</u> Eze nnu Anu ufe di ike I di oke onu	(Eagle King of bird Strong flying animal You are priceless
<u>Ugo,</u> I na-efeba n'ime igwe N'ihu nku gi di ike O dighi nnu o bu gi na ya (Nwadike, 2006, p. 227)	Eagle You fly into the sky Because your feathers are strong No bird can compete with you.)

In the above stanzas from poem 144, the word “Ugo” is repeated intermittently as it appears at the beginning of each stanza. The repeated line is separated from the next repeated word by three other lines. The repetition of the word " line " in line 1 places more emphasis on the subject of the poem. The repetition device is also used to keep the reader's attention fixed on the poem's motif.

6.4 Conclusion

In this chapter, we have examined the form of written Igbo poetry, giving special attention to the artistic style of modern Igbo poets in defamiliarising language in their works. The chapter identifies linguistic cohesion and deviation, figures of speech, and sound devices employed by modern Igbo poets in making an art out of the

literal use of language. In the next chapter, we shall conclude this study by showcasing the significant findings.

CHAPTER SEVEN

CONCLUSION

7.1 Summary

This study has shed light on the developmental trend of written Igbo poetry from 1975-2015, as well as on the content and form of some examples of the poems produced during this period. The study begins with an insight into the problems that motivated it, the objectives, the methods employed to elicit the data, and the theoretical perspectives that guided our analysis. The review of relevant literature in the study is divided into two sections: conceptual framework and empirical studies. The study also gives a detailed survey of all the factors that marred or contributed in one way or the other to the development of written Igbo poetry from the period of pure oral poetry to the present state of written form, assessing also the level of progress the written Igbo poetry has made from its debut until 2015. Furthermore, the study examines key topical issues of societal and other human concerns addressed by modern Igbo poetry in the periods studied. The study also established the form of Igbo poetry in writing by highlighting the artistic skills of modern Igbo poets.

7.2 Findings and Contribution to Knowledge

In view of the above summary, the study makes these findings:

On the historical development of written Igbo poetry, the study finds that it underwent distinct stages before arriving at its present form. First is the oral Igbo poetic stage, where the study finds that, contrary to the general opinion that written Igbo poetry did not emerge until 1975, the study finds that written Igbo poetry, as we have it now, developed from the religious Igbo hymns that were written by the Igbo,

as contained in *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo* which was published in 1934 by the Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge and used by the Church Missionary Society (C.M.S.). This text (*Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo*) contains hymns that were translated from the C.M.S. hymns Ancient and Modern and some hymns that were composed by the Igbo and labelled 'Original'. These works were initially written in Union orthography. These original religious texts by the Igbo were later gathered, revised, and republished in 1978 under the group name "Abụ ndị Igbo Cheputaara" (Hymns developed by the Igbo), in the revised Igbo hymn book used today in the Anglican communion, known as *Ekpere na Abụ*. However, since these hymns, though written by the Igbo, were written for Christian religious edification. They do not showcase the sociological life of the Igbo; they are not considered, in this study, the first works on written Igbo poetry; hence, the acceptance of *Akpa Uche* as the first Igbo poetic work, edited by R.M. Ekechukwu and published in 1975. The study also finds that all the poems written in *Akpa Uche* and many other Igbo poems today follow the western poetic style, which was founded by the Igbo hymns (poems) in *Akwukwo Ukwę n'Asusu Ibo*.

On the factors that marred the growth of written Igbo poetry, the study finds that, despite these successes recorded towards the development of written Igbo poetry, there are factors that did and still do militate against its development, as evidenced by the drastic decline in published texts in the fourth decade. The factors identified as militating against the development of written Igbo poetry include self-publishing, apathy towards the Igbo language among the Igbo, government policy on education, a lack of market, which discourages publishers from accepting manuscripts in Igbo, and low or poor student enrolment in the Igbo programme in tertiary institutions.

Furthermore, on the present state of written Igbo poetry, the study finds that since the debut of *Akpa Uche* in 1975, written Igbo poetry has grown both in quantity and quality. For instance, in the decades studied, the study finds that 14 texts were published in the first decade (1975-1985), 12 in the second decade (1986-1995), 19 in the third decade (1996-2005), while seven were published in the fourth decade (2006-2015). This means that the number of published poetic texts fell by 20% in the second decade compared to the first decade, but rose again by 58.3% in the third decade compared to the second decade. Unfortunately, instead of rising, the total number of written Igbo-language publications declined by 65% in the fourth decade compared to the third. The most significant increase in the number of Igbo poetic text publications occurred in the third decade (1996-2000), when it rose by 58.3%. On the other hand, the study of written Igbo poetry has increased, as evidenced by progress being recorded in secondary schools and many higher institutions of learning. It is worthy of note that, today, there are about four Ph.D. theses exclusively carried out on written Igbo poetry in Nigeria. B.A. projects and M.A. dissertations on written Igbo poetry have also been carried out in various institutions of learning. These studies attest to the fact that indeed the study of written Igbo poetry has equally grown, which is a direct response to Ugonna's (1982, p. 20) question, in which he sought to know the extent to which written Igbo poetry has grown within the first decade of its emergence.

Regarding the types of poems produced in the decades under study, the study finds that two types of poems occupy the Igbo written poetic scene. The first is the pseudo verse, which comes in two forms: the pseudo traditional verses and the pseudo modern verses. The second type of poem is standard poetry. Apart from these types of

poems, the study also finds two types of poetic titles that appear in written Igbo poetry. They are literary and non-literary poetic titles.

Regarding societal and other human concerns addressed by modern Igbo poets in the decades studied, the study finds that modern Igbo poets mirrored three major sociological topicalities, grouped into political, cultural, economic, and ecological issues. Among the political issues mirrored by modern Igbo poets in the decades under study, some are poor leadership and corruption in Nigeria. Again, on the cultural issues mirrored by modern Igbo poets, it is found that some of the cultural issues that formed the topic of poetic discourse in the decades studied include the menace of the *ogbanje* phenomenon; representation of destiny as a pre-determined fate, and the portrayal of kola nut culture in written Igbo poetry. On the economic issues mirrored by modern Igbo poets, it is found that some of the key issues where modern Igbo poetic thought converged in the decades studied are on the portrayal of money as an economic tool, the portrayal of economic trees and their importance. In the decades studied, modern Igbo poets mirror ecological issues, including the portrayal of the sun as a source of energy and the representation of the moon in written Igbo poetry.

On the artistic skills of modern poets, the study finds that by defamiliarising the literal language, modern Igbo poets do create poetry whose form is appreciated in two ways: its rhythm and language use. On the rhythm of written Igbo poetry, the study finds that the rhythm of written Igbo poetry is not achieved by meter but by (i) regular recurrence of breath pause, (ii) regular recurrence of equal time duration in consecutive lines, and (iii) regular recurrence of sense balance. On the other hand, the study finds that the defamiliarising skills of modern Igbo poets are more apparent in

the language of written Igbo poetry, which they achieve through stylistic deviation and conformity, figures of speech, and the use of sound devices.

- On stylistic conformity as a defamiliarisation technique in written Igbo poetry, the study finds that, sometimes, modern Igbo poets do not create new language structures but defamiliarise (manipulate) the existing possibilities in the language to create an art. They do this through the process of phonological cohesion, lexical cohesion, and grammatical cohesion.
 - On phonological cohesion in written Igbo poetry, the study finds that phonological cohesion is achieved in written Igbo poetry through alliteration, assonance, and tonal rhyme. The study also finds that phonological cohesion in written Igbo poetry is complemented by repetition or parallelism in consecutive lines. Again, phonological cohesion is used in written Igbo poetry to make the poem aesthetically melodic.
 - Lexical cohesion, on the other hand, is achieved in written Igbo poetry by lexical matching and chronological arrangement of hyponyms.
 - Grammatical cohesion in written Igbo poetry is achieved by reorganizing the known structure of the language through a linguistic process known as end-weight and focusing, where cleft construction and topicalisation are the strategies used by modern Igbo poets in defamiliarising language in written Igbo poetry.
- On stylistic deviation as a defamiliarisation technique in written Igbo poetry, the study finds that modern Igbo poets defamiliarise language in poetry by deviating from the linguistic norm in Igbo language. Stylistic deviation is achieved through lexical deviation, phonological deviation, and graphological deviation. Lexical deviation is achieved in written Igbo poetry through the use of loanwords,

coinages, and dialectal words in the poem. On coined words as a technique for stylistic deviation in written Igbo poetry, the study finds that coinages are used for economy of words and for the poem's aesthetic effects. Loanwords, on the other hand, are used by modern Igbo poets to elevate thought in the poem. Modern Igbo poets employ phonological deviation to create sound effects in their poems. For this reason, the study finds that phonological deviation is achieved in written Igbo poetry by omitting a syllable in a word or by not writing the sentence in full, as suggested by Uzochukwu (2012). The study finds that graphological deviation arises in Igbo written poetry due to typographical errors.

- The study also finds that figures of speech play a considerable role as a tool for defamiliarisation in written Igbo poetry. The figures of speech that feature in written Igbo poetry include simile, metaphor, personification, hyperbole, metonymy, paradox, oxymoron, allusion, rhetorical questions, euphemism, apostrophe, and proverbs. Modern Igbo poets use these figures of speech to embellish their poems.

7.3 The Future of Written Igbo Poetry and Recommendations

The findings of this study have made it clear that written Igbo poetry has indeed grown in both quantity and quality. Its study, both in schools and in learned journals, has grown equally. However, the decline in the number of published poetic texts, as seen in the fourth decade of Igbo written poetry, is indeed worrisome. If this trend continues, it will spell doom for the future growth of written Igbo poetry. If the Igbo should show one-third of the interest shown to English literature (poetry) in written Igbo poetry, there will be a great deal of improvement in the development of written Igbo poetry.

Again, in terms of the quality of written Igbo poetry, as it relates to the use of language and its production, it was observed in this study that the quality of poems produced in the first and second decades is much higher than that of the poems published in the third and fourth decades. This is because most Igbo poets now turn to self-publishing in order to have their works published, following the refusal of publishers to accept works written in the Igbo language. To this end, the further growth of written Igbo poetry depends on the publishers' acceptance to publish Igbo poetic works with a view to improving the quality of those works.

The need for the Igbo to change their negative attitude towards their (Igbo) language cannot be overemphasised, as the Igbo language is also used in written Igbo poetry. Not being able to read and write Igbo is also a leading factor discouraging more people from writing poetry, as it has become an unprofitable venture for those who engage in it. If left unchanged, this will lead to the end of written Igbo poetry in the near future. To this end, the study makes the following recommendations:

- 7.3.1.** There is a need to develop simpler and more interesting ways of teaching written Igbo poetry as a subject in schools. This will eliminate the fear that most students feel about poetry, which they often view as a complex subject.
- 7.3.2.** Students should be encouraged to form poetry clubs in schools where the form and content of written Igbo poetry will be discussed and appreciated.
- 7.3.3.** Teachers, on the other hand, should have an attitudinal change towards written Igbo poetry. Instead of patronizing only the prose and drama genres, they should also encourage students to write poems in Igbo and organise poetry competitions across different institutions.

- 7.3.4.** The role of publishers cannot be ignored if written Igbo poetry is to continue to grow. They must continue to accept and publish manuscripts on Igbo poetry, even when they do not make huge profits. They should consider it as part of their corporate social responsibility, tailored to sustaining the poetic genre.
- 7.3.5.** Finally, to encourage the development of written Igbo poetry, governments at all levels should be involved in promoting and sponsoring Igbo poetic competitions among schools and poets. This will stimulate the interest of many people in writing good Igbo poems, which will, in turn, be used in the teaching and learning of written Igbo poetry in schools.

7.4 Suggestions for Further Studies

This study has provided deep insight into the Igbo written poetry genre in general. However, particular areas were not covered in the present study, which the researcher believes might warrant future studies of written Igbo poetry. For instance, the study did not identify key modern Igbo poets and their stylistic manner of writing. Again, the present study did not include a linguistic analysis of selected Igbo poems.

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APPENDIX

Table 13: TITLES OF POEMS USED IN THE ANALYSIS DONE IN THIS STUDY AND THEIR NUMBERINGS

S/N	POEM NO.	TITLE OF POEM	NAME OF POET	PAGE	POETIC TEXT	Date of Publication
1	Poem 1	Abali (Night)	I. Madubuike	32	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d
2	Poem 2	Ugbo elu ogo (War Airplane)	T. Ubesie	32	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
3	Poem 3	Ogbuniigwe (Bomb)	I. Madubuike	39	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d
4	Poem 4	Agha (War)	J.C. Maduekwe	35	<i>Nka Okwu</i>	1979
5	Poem 5	Afrika enwerela onwe ya (Africa is free)	N. Olebara	66	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
6	Poem 6	Ugbo (Transportation)	I.E. Akoma	48	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
7	Poem 7	Akako (Dwarf)	A.K. Obierozie	31	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
8	Poem 8	Alukwaghi m (Divorce)	C. Ogbulogo	22	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
9	Poem 9	Uguru (Harmattan)	J.C. Maduekwe	41	<i>Nka Okwu</i>	1979
10	Poem 10	Uguru (Harmattan)	A.K. Obierozie	16	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
11	Poem 11	Uguru (Harmattan)	N. Okediadi	13	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
12	Poem 12	Ilulu	M.C. Ogunjiofor	43	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
13	Poem 13	Zere Ohi (Desist from stealing)	M.C. Ogunjiofor	55	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
14	Poem 14	Obodo m (My country)	G.O. Onyekaonwu	13	<i>Uche bu Afa</i>	1989
15	Poem 15	E nwere Mgbe (There was a time)	C. Onyeji	79	<i>Akonauche</i>	2006

16	Poem 16	Ùgwù (Honour)	O. Ifeka	7	<i>O Natara Chi</i>	2009
17	Poem 17	Echi (Tomorrow)	Onyejekwe & Ikeokwu	46	<i>Uche bu Ahia</i>	2009
18	Poem 18	Wachie ubi n'oge (close farm early)	A.B. Chukuezi	17	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
19	Poem 19	Uka (Church)	C.C. Anozie	80	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	1975
20	Poem 20	Ezi agbataobi (Good neighbour)	B.M. Mbah	113	<i>Akonauche</i>	2006
21	Poem 21	Obodo Anyi (Our nation)	R.M. Ekechukwu	70	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
22	Poem 22	Uko n'uju (Lack in plenty)	N. Emenanjo	29	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d.
23	Poem 23	Oria Anyi (Our disease)	I. Ikwubuzo	24	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
24	Poem 24	Dibia adugburuja (Fake doctor)	I. Ikwubuzo	28	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
25	Poem 25	Otanisi	C. Ogbulogo	29	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
26	Poem 26	Naijiria (Nigeria)	N. Okediadi	20	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
27	Poem 27	Ngari (Bribery)	R.N. Ekegbo	29	<i>Uwa Onye na Chi Ya</i>	2004
28	Poem 28	Ochichi (Leadership)	H. Oleru	18	<i>Akonauche</i>	2006
29	Poem 29	Ogbanje (Repeater child)	I. Akoma	8	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
30	Poem 30	Ubochi nwata nwuru (The day the child died)	J.C. Maduekwe	18	<i>Nka Okwu</i>	1979
31	Poem 31	Ogbanje (Repeater child)	J. Onwuchekwa	16	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983
32	Poem 32	Ogbanje (Repeater child)	A.K. Obierozie	5	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
33	Poem 33	Ogbanje (Repeater child)	A.B. Chukuezi	28	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
34	Poem 34	Ogbanje (Repeater child)	J. Onuoha	191	<i>Akonauche</i>	2006
35	Poem 35	Akaraaka (Destiny)	A.K. Obierozie	2	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
36	Poem 36	Akaraaka (Destiny)	G.O. Onyekaonwu	21	<i>Uche bu Afa</i>	1989
37	Poem 37	Akaraaka (Destiny)	D. Epuchie	74-75	<i>Akonauche</i>	2006
38	Poem 38	Akaraaka (Destiny)	Ikeokwu & Onyejekwe	49-50	<i>Uche bu Ahia</i>	2009
39	Poem 39	Oji (Kola nut)	T. Ubesie	40-42	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
40	Poem 40	Oji (Kola nut)	A.K. Obierozie	7	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
41	Poem 41	Oji (Kola nut)	R.N. Ekegbo	23	<i>Uwa Onye na Chi Ya</i>	2004
42	Poem 42	Oji (Kola nut)	F. Mbanugo	150-151	<i>Akonauche</i>	2006
43	Poem 43	Akwukwo oru ego (paper money)	J.C. Obienyem	42	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
44	Poem 44	Naira (Naira)	I. Madubuike	44-46	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d.
45	Poem 45	Ego (Money)	J. Onwuchekwa	36-38	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983

46	Poem 46	Ego (Money)	C.C. Anozie	96-98	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005
47	Poem 47	Ego (Money)	J. Ezeuchegbu	116-117	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
48	Poem 48	Nkwu (Palm tree)	T. Nzeako	16-18	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
49	Poem 49	Nkwu (Palm tree)	T. Ubesie	30-31	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
50	Poem 50	Osisi na-amị ego (Tree that grows money)	J.C. Maduekwe	57	<i>Nkà Okwu</i>	1979
51	Poem 51	Nkwu (Palm tree)	A.B. Chukuezi	4	<i>Akọ bu Ndu</i>	1988
52	Poem 52	Ọnwa na Anyanwu (Moon and Sun)	R.N. Ekegbo	15	<i>Uwa Onye na Chi Ya</i>	2004
53	Poem 53	Anyanwu (Sun)	U. Ndunagum	258	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
54	Poem 54	Anyanwu (Sun)	Ikeokwu and Onyejekwe	40-41	<i>Uche bu Ahia</i>	2009
55	Poem 55	Anyanwu (Sun)	N.R. Ezejesi	16-17	<i>Abu Uto</i>	2015
56	Poem 56	Ọnwa (Moon)	J.C. Obienyem	6-7	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
57	Poem 57	Ọnwa (Moon)	A.K. Obierozie	30	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
58	Poem 58	Ọnwa (Moon)	N. Okediadi	24-25	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
59	Poem 59	Ọnwa (Moon)	Ikeokwu & Onyejekwe	69-70	<i>Uche bu Ahia</i>	2009
60	Poem 60	Ihe Egwu Anyi (Our musical instruments)	J.C. Maduekwe	2-4	<i>Nkà Okwu</i>	1979
61	Poem 61	Akwa Ariri (Tears of sorrow)	A.B. Chukuezi	1-3	<i>Akọ bu Ndu</i>	1988
62	Poem 62	Ihere (Shame)	C.C. Anozie	75-77	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005
63	Poem 63	Ihe Adikwaghị ebe o na-Adi (Things fall apart)	R. Ezeuko	220	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
64	Poem 64	Nwayoọ bu Ije (Slow is movement)	I. Madubuike	40-42	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d.
65	Poem 65	Mmadu bu nnu (Man is salt)	A.B. Chukuezi	27	<i>Akọ bu Ndu</i>	1988
66	Poem 66	Eziokwu (Truth)	N.R. Ezejesi	11	<i>Abu Uto</i>	2015
67	Poem 67	Chukwu ndi Isi Ojii (God of black people)	A.B. Chukuezi	26-28	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d.
68	Poem 68	Abu (Poetry)	I. Madubuike	43-44	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d.
69	Poem 69	Ubochi Dike Lara (The day the hero passed)	I. Ikwubuzo	16	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
70	Poem 70	Ura (Sleep)	I.U. Nwadike	226-227	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
71	Poem 71	Ngwere (Lizard)	T. Ubesie	13-14	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
72	Poem 72	Akwa Nwunye Di M (Cry of my co-wife)	A.B. Chukuezi	79-82	<i>Akọ bu Ndu</i>	1988
73	Poem 73	Chineke bi n'Igwe (God that lives in heaven)	N. Okediadi	32-33	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
74	Poem 74	Udara (Sherry)	N.R. Ezejesi	30	<i>Abu Uto</i>	2015
75	Poem 75	Onyinye Chukwu (God's gift)	J.C. Maduekwe	9	<i>Nkà Okwu</i>	1979
76	Poem 76	Onye Nochiri Anyi Uzo (Who stands in our way)	A.B. Chukuezi	71	<i>Akọ bu Ndu</i>	1988
77	Poem 77	Ekwentị (Telephone)	C.C. Anozie	68-69	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005

78	Poem 78	Eze Kwe M (King agree)	Ikeokwu & Onyejekwe	4-6	<i>Uche bu Ahia</i>	2009
79	Poem 79	Abali di egwu (Night is fearful)	E. Egbuchulam	46-48	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
80	Poem 80	Ngwere (Lizard)	T.U. Ubesie	13-14	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
81	Poem 81	Ura (Sleep)	C.C. Anozie	73	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005
82	Poem 82	Mmuta bu ike (Knowledge is power)	O. Njelita	129	<i>Akponauche</i>	2006
83	Poem 83	Onwu (Death)	C. Ajaegbu	6	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
84	Poem 84	Mgbe m bu Nwata (When I was a child)	G.O. Onyekaonwu	31-32	<i>Uche bu Afa</i>	1989
85	Poem 85	Echi (Tomorrow)	N. Okediadi	23-24	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
86	Poem 86	Ekpere (Prayer)	N.R. Ezejesi	20	<i>Abu Uto</i>	2015
87	Poem 87	Ala ezi	J. Onwuchekwa	22	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983
88	Poem 88	Nne Anyi Afrika (Our Mother Africa)	J.C. Maduekwe	5	<i>Nka Okwu</i>	1979
89	Poem 89	Agbaramiikwu	C. Ogbulogo	50-51	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
90	Poem 90	F.C. Ogbalu Odezulumba	N. Okediadi	66	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
91	Poem 91	Onwu (Death)	J.C. Obienyem	4-6	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
92	Poem 92	Biko ka m Werekwa Onwu (please let me take death)	G.O. Onyekaonwu	31	<i>Uche bu Afa</i>	1989
93	Poem 93	Ehiehiediegwu (Afternoon is Fearful)	Iwu Ikwubuzo	37	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
94	Poem 94	Ule (Examination)	C.C. Anozie	89-90	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005
95	Poem 95	Nwaanyi (Woman)	G.I. Nwaozuzu	92	<i>Akponauche</i>	2006
96	Poem 96	Akuko Nwa Ogbenye (Tales of the poor)	M.C. Ogunjiofor	51	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
97	Poem 97	Onye Poliisi (Police officer)	I. Ikwubuzo	38	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
98	Poem 98	Redio (Radio)	C.C. Anozie	109-113	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005
99	Poem 99	Chaaram ka M Kpara Ego (Out of my way let me make money)	G.I. Nwaozuzu	95	<i>Akponauche</i>	2006
100	Poem 100	Ejula (Snail)	N.R. Ezejesi	34-36	<i>Abu Uto</i>	2015
101	Poem 101	Egwurugwu (Rainbow)	K. Amasike	1	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
102	Poem 102	Ako bu Ndu (wisdom is life)	A.B. Chukuezi	7-8	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
103	Poem 103	Uwa ka Onye Njo (Whose world is the worse)	I. Ofodile	136-137	<i>Akponauche</i>	2006
104	Poem 104	Uwa di ka M si Hu Ya (The world the way I see It)	E. Ugwunkwo	103-104	<i>Akponauche</i>	2006

105	Poem 105	Atìliogwụ (Dance)	C. Emenike	27	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
106	Poem 106	Ndiinyom (Ladies)	J. Onwuchekwa	28-29	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983
107	Poem 107	Nsoala (Taboo)	I. Ikwubuzo	35	<i>Omenkà</i>	1992
108	Poem 108	Ọnwụ (Death)	E. Emenike	45	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
109	Poem 109	Ire (Tongue)	N. Okediadi	5	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
110	Poem 110	Agadi Nwaanyi (Old woman)	N Olebara	23	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
111	Poem 111	Ọnwụ (Death)	A.K. Obierozie	13	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
112	Poem 112	Ọrịa Mmịnwu (Hiv & Aids)	C.C. Anozie	74	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005
113	Poem 113	Otu Ezuola (One is enough)	O. Ifeka	31	<i>Ọ Natara Chi</i>	2009
114	Poem 114	Diokpara (First born male)	A.K. Obierozie	9	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
115	Poem 115	Iduuzi (Prose)	O.C. Kanu	44	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	2006
116	Poem 116	Ngana (Laziness)	T. Nzeako	18-19	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
117	Poem 117	Ndu bu nga (Life is prison)	L.C. Okoro	25	<i>Omenkà</i>	1992
118	Poem 118	Mmiri Ozuzo (Rainfall)	N. Okediadi	42	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
119	Poem 119	Oluku (fool)	I.E. Akoma	50	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
120	Poem 120	Obodo Onicha (City of Onitsha)	N. Okediadi	10	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
121	Poem 121	Ọnwụ (Death)	Ikeokwu & Onyejekwe	16	<i>Uche bu Ahia</i>	2009
122	Poem 122	Ọnwụ (Death)	J.C. Obienyem	3	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
123	Poem 123	Anya Ukwu (Greed)	A.K. Obierozie	24-25	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
124	Poem 124	Idula Mmụọ (Killing)	B. Obodo	58	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	2006
125	Poem 125	Echiche bu Ndu (Thought is life)	J. Onwuchekwa	65	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983
126	Poem 126	Nkita (Dog)	A.B. Chukuezi	13	<i>Akpa bu Ndu</i>	1988
127	Poem 127	Ndidi (Patience)	G.O. Onyekaonwu	30	<i>Uche bu Afa</i>	1989
128	Poem 128	Abu (Poetry)	N. Anarado	24	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	2006
129	Poem 129	Ọnwụ (Death)	T. Nzeako	5	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975

	129					
130	Poem 130	Ji (Yam)	J.C. Maduekwe	20-21	<i>Nkà Okwu</i>	1979
131	Poem 131	Igba Mkpu	J. Onwuchekwa	6-7	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983
132	Poem 132	Naijiria bụ Enyimba (Nigeria is giant nation)	G.O. Onyekaonwu	25	<i>Uche bụ Afa</i>	1989
133	Poem 133	Nwaanyi (Woman)	C.C. Anozie	86	<i>Uche bụ Akpa</i>	1975
134	Poem 134	Ndi Ntorị Mmadu Abiakwa o (Kidnappers have come o)	I.U. Nwadike	245- 247	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
135	Poem 135	Gini bụ Anuri (What is happiness)	E. Egbuchulam	61	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
136	Poem 136	Uwa bụ nke Onye (Who owns the world)	G.O. Onyekaonwu	26	<i>Uche bụ Afa</i>	1989
137	Poem 137	Nne (Mother)	N.R. Ezejesi	14-15	<i>Abụ Uto</i>	2015
138	Poem 138	Ndu Nwaanyi (Life of a woman)	T. Ubesie	38-40	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
139	Poem 139	Ncheta Oge Agboghobia M (Remembering my spinster days)	A.K. Obierozie	21	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
140	Poem 140	Nsogbu Nwaanyi (Female problem)	A.B. Chukuezi	73	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
141	Poem 141	Onwu Di (Death of husband)	N. Okediadi	48	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
142	Poem 142	Ala (Earth)	A.B. Chukuezi	21	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
143	Poem 143	Oku Latriki (Electricity)	N. Okediadi	15	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
144	Poem 144	Ahike (Good health)	H. Nwamah	70	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
145	Poem 145	Onye Ije (Traveller)	Chukwudile	22-23	<i>Utara Nti</i>	N.d.
146	Poem 146	Okuko na Umụ Ya (The fowl and her chicks)	A.B. Chukuezi	75	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
147	Poem 147	Ekpere (Prayer)	C. Ofomata	3	<i>E chezola</i>	2001
148	Poem 148	A Sokata Eze Anya	N. Anarodo	27	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
149	Poem 149	Ngana na Mpako (Laziness and Pride)	J.N. Onwuchekwa	30-31	<i>Akpaala Okwu</i>	1983
150	Poem 150	Udummiri(Rainy Season)	A.K. Obierozie	19-20	<i>Ekpe Nna</i>	1986
151	Poem 151	Ebewu Naijiria (Which way Nigeria)	G.I. Nwaozuzu	85-88	<i>Akọnauche</i>	2006
152	Poem	Adamma	C.W.O. Ajaegbu	19-20	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975

	152					
153	Poem 153	Ikuku (Wind)	A.B. Chukuezi	16	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
154	Poem 154	Akpati Ozu (Coffin)	C.C. Anozie	118	<i>Uche bu Akpa</i>	2005
155	Poem 155	Akwa Nkwu (Palm Wine)	N.R. Ezejesi	36-38	<i>Abu Uto</i>	2015
156	Poem 156	Ogbenye (Poor person)	A.B. Chukuezi	23-24	<i>Ako bu Ndu</i>	1988
157	Poem 157	Suturaiki (Strike)	N. Okediadi	57	<i>Ije Uwa</i>	2003
158	Poem 158	Iheanacho (What everyone needs)	D. Epuchie	76-77	<i>Akonnauche</i>	2006
159	Poem 159	Ijiji (House fly)	K. Amasike	10-11	<i>Akpa Uche</i>	1975
160	Poem 160	N'ote Aka (In a Distance)	L.C. Okoro	20	<i>Omenka</i>	1992
161	Poem 161	Ibe Mata M (Relatives know me)	H. Oleru	21	<i>Akonnauche</i>	2006
162	Poem 162	Asila m na o di mma (Do not tell me that it is good)	B. Obodo	53-55	<i>Akonnauche</i>	2006

Table 14: LIST OF INFORMANTS USED IN THIS STUDY

S/N	NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATE INTERVIEWED	LOCATION
1	Prof. Goddy Onyekaonwu (Rtd.)	Scholar and Poet	17 Dec. 2017	Nnamdi Azikiwe University
2	Prof. I. U. Nwadike (Rtd.)	Scholar and Poet	18 Dec. 2017	University of Nigeria
3	Dr. O. Muojama	Scholar	8 March, 2018	University of Ibadan
4	Dr. U. Onumonu	Scholar	20 January, 2020	University of Ibadan
5	J. C. Maduekwe	Poet	10 August, 2018	Ojoto, Anambra State
6	Chinedum Ofomata	Poet	15 July, 2019	Enugu
7	Asso. Prof. C. B. Nnabuihe	Scholar & Poet	30 March, 2018	University of Lagos

